

Quantum And Gravity

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Abstract

Objective: Find out the relationship between quantum mechanics and space-time, and study quantum certainty.

Methods: Pure strict logic reasoning, tree logic diagram, topological analysis, thought experiment.

Results: The space-time relationship is actually a 4-dimensional flat space-time with 1-dimensional quantum phase. The effect of gravitation is the influence coefficient of phase. Quantum uncertainty is actually phase difference, and quantum is still deterministic..

Limitations: Because of the high accuracy of the designed verification test or the problem of funds, I can not implement it now.

Conclusions: Four-dimensional flat space-time can be quantum mechanically consistent, and quantum is still deterministic.

Keywords: Quantum; Gravity; Space-time; Quantum Certainty; Simultaneity

1. Introduction

This paper attempts to use foxi tree to establish a strict guarantee of physical reasoning system.

In this paper, I select "obvious", "simple", "self-evident" and "widely accepted" conclusions as the physical basis. This makes the system more reliable. I fully abandon the "hypothesis" and "non-self-evident foundations", and try to create self-evident "logical physics".

In spatio-temporal analysis, more rigorous topological analysis is enabled and weak foundations are abandoned. I try to solve the problem of absolute simultaneous and absolute time.

This paper attempts to establish a 4-dimensional flat uniform space-time consistent with quantum mechanics and its mechanical relationship.

The mathematical and physical details of the mathematical formula of uncertainty in quantum mechanics are explored in order to find the actual physical meaning.

2. Literature review

Modern physics is a hodgepodge of many people, lacking strict logical connection with each other. As a result, logical islands are formed, which lack strict guarantee of logical reasoning between them.

The formulas of gravitation force and Coulomb force are so similar. Are they and other forces intrinsically related?

There are some problems with inertia that have not been clarified. Newton's bucket problem has been an outstanding case for more than 300 years.

Relativity theory is based on "the assumption that the speed of light is constant" and "the assumption of relativity". Although theory can not be traced back infinitely. However, different forms of foundation have different degrees of reliability. Among them, "hypothesis" is the lowest. The assumption that the speed of light is constant is neither intuitive nor obvious. But the "relativity hypothesis" is only a shell, and what is really useful needs to be specific.

The uncertainty principle of quantum mechanics gives a mathematical formula. In a hurry to conclude that the microcosmic quantum world is uncertain. There is no in-depth mathematical and physical analysis. However, later there were Ozawa inequalities with different lower bounds. If this is the boundary of natural knowledge, which is the boundary of natural knowledge? In fact, it's just a mathematical inequality, and people can construct many. Its true meaning needs to be excavated concretely.

Quantum mechanics is incompatible with relativistic curved space-time, which is a big problem.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Gezhi Physics Basis

(1) The Ideological System of Gezhi Physics

Traditional physics is basically based on Aristotle's ideological system and focuses on practical observation.

However, as Hume said, it is impossible to establish a real causal relationship from actual observation.

However, Gezhi Physics is causal. Therefore, Gezhi Physics takes Plato's ideological system as its core so as to establish causal logic.

According to plan-yong-axiom, the fundamental task of Gezhi Physics is planning. Therefore, it must conform to the observation results and thus be compatible with Aristotle's ideology.

With Plato's ideological system as the core, we can establish strong logical relationships such as causality.

Compatible with Aristotle's ideological system, it has good reality and operability and avoids boring endless debates.

According to plan-yong-axiom, it must interact with the observable world, so it can certainly be tested by actual observation. Moreover, only those conclusions that can be tested by actual observation can be disputed with others, otherwise they will only be regarded as theoretical matters. (Do not take part in problems such as "needlepoint angel".)

In addition, traditional physics centers on observation. The problem is that it is easy to completely overthrow the previous physical system because of new observations.

Gezhi Physics centers on logic; it does not directly face the observation. In this way, there is a layer of buffer protection, to avoid the direct impact of the new observation. Only need to use a good definition and a good logical structure. The new observation can be included; the whole system does not need major changes.

The key is a good definition and a good structure here.

Let's take a math analogy. Long ago, the square of a number was non-negative. Later, the square of the number may be negative. Then the original number is called real number and the new number is called negative number. Seemingly conflicting knowledge is brought together without conflict.

The structure of Gezhi Physics is concentric circles. The core is inside. The closer to the center, the more stable it is.

From Plato's world, Aristotle's world is like a crude little shack; you will see many things that could not be seen before. They are the important intellectual contents of pure logic. Because it is purely logical, not observational. So it was left out. However, it can determine why the world we observe is what it looks like now. For these things, in Aristotle's world, we know what they are, but we don't know why. Only in Plato's world can we see "that's why". "That's why" is the most precious part of our knowledge and wisdom.

Looking back from Plato's world, Aristotle's world missed many important wisdom of pure logic, tautological structure, meta-symmetry, etc.; this loophole was named **Aristotle-loophole**.

This physics centers on thinking. The outside world can only become a raw material component of this system through perception.

Figure 1 Schematic diagram of Gezhi Physics ideological system

(2) The Task of Gezhi Physics

The fundamental task of Gezhi Physics is planning. Planning refers to planning the implementation process

in advance to achieve the selected results. For example, production planning, operational planning, learning planning, moon landing plan.

For convenience of reference, naming

Plan-yong-axiom: The fundamental task of Gezhi Physics is planning, and Gezhi Physics is planable.

There are 2 **derivative tasks: prediction and description**, as a means of fundamental tasks. Prediction refers to describing the result in advance before the event appears or even occurs, such as, the weather forecasting, forecasting the current year's crop harvest. Description refers to the use of symbols (including language systems) to record important details of events for communication. The "important" here is in the sense of self-consistency. The communication here includes the inter-temporal communication of the same subject, such as the experimental report described yesterday, which will be seen today.

For convenience of reference, naming

Predictability Theorem: Prediction is the task of Gezhi Physics, which is predictable.

Descriptive Theorem: Description is the task of Gezhi Physics, which is describable. Therefore, Gezhi Physics has no secret. Gezhi Physics is not mysticism.

(3) Plane Attained of Physics

The plane attained here corresponds to the "horizon" of knowledge, which refers to the extent of knowledge taken into account in thinking. The size of this range is generally described as levels, gradation, etc.

The horizon of the common people is the market.

Mount Dongshan's horizon is Lu.

The horizon of climbing Mount Tai is the world.

For physics.

Level 0 Plane Attained (Natural Plane Attained): People in the street; the superficial relationship of daily life.

Level 1 Plane Attained: Experimental physics in history; direct and universal relation of physical phenomena.

Level 2 Plane Attained: Intuitive physics in history; the direct universal relationship between a wide range of physical phenomena.

Level 3 Plane Attained: Abstract physics in history; logical models of extensive physical phenomena. It is characterized by modeling, rather than directly facing physical quantities.

Level 4 Plane Attained: Global logical physics. Physics established from the whole (Gezhi) knowledge level. Its characteristic is that there are many basic norms from the whole knowledge, such as "causality norms", "locality norms" and "reality norms". They are the mandatory norms for Gezhi knowledge and are primary. "Certainty" is a mandatory norm for rational knowledge systems such as physics and is primary.

In addition, "the locality of knowledge itself" is also an important item. Its meaning is to limit the influence of things to a local area of knowledge as much as possible, that is, there is an unaffected subset of knowledge.

To the extreme, there is an abstract subset of knowledge that is not affected by any real thing. This is "time and space". "Time and space" itself is not a thing, but a thinking container of things. Its function is to provide a definite and unchangeable communicative thinking background for thinking things. Anyone, at any time and under any conditions, can think through this same "background space-time" to exchange knowledge without barrier. The time everyone said is the same time, the space everyone said is the same space, without any additional explanation. For example, when two people talk about the Pacific Ocean, they do not need to explain much. They are both the same space (the Pacific Ocean).

General relativity is a violation of the "locality of knowledge itself." A yawn will disturb time and space. Once space-time is disturbed, the entire knowledge structure is affected without exception. This makes one's mind uneasy. Some people always hate it. If this is the only option, then it can only be done-something being better than nothing. However, nobody can prevent human beings from exploring the physical knowledge system that does not violate this article.

Theory of absolutivity is such a system of physical knowledge. Its absolute space-time is always uniform and straight, and is not affected by anything.

Similarly, in the interpretation of quantum mechanics, "causal criterion", "locality criterion" and "reality criterion" are actually negotiable. However, it violates these general norms of knowledge, which are primary; it is mandatory for the whole knowledge system.

In Gezhi Physics, these three articles are mandatory.

(4) Form of Gezhi Physics

Traditional physics centers on experiments.

Gezhi Physics takes logic as the center and constructs the physics building purely by logic. However, the experiment and experience are only external embellishments and only fit with the part of the logic building.

If experiment and "experience A" agree with "part B of the logic building", we say B may be used to deal with problems like A.

The combination of experiment and experience is the combination of observation. That is to say, they are required to agree with the observation results.

The logic building was built from self-evidence. Its core can only be built on those self-evident basic knowledge.

The logic building was not built from observation results. It is impossible to sum up a rule from experiments or experiences, as in traditional physics, and then take this rule as the basis of physics. More can't use hypothesis, such as the constant speed of light hypothesis. These are not self-evident.

Figure 2 Gezhi Physical Morphology Diagram

Gezhi Physics faces only knowledge, not reality itself. This is very different from traditional physics.

The logical reasoning and assertion of Gezhi Physics are completely confined to the form of thinking, and do not directly face the reality itself. In this respect, it is very different from traditional physics.

Gezhi Physics, as a whole, faces reality. Logical relationships such as causality are encapsulated and protected within this system. Therefore, it avoids Hume's problem.

(5) Application Forms of Gezhi Physics

The logical reasoning and assertion of Gezhi Physics are completely confined to the form of thinking and do not directly face the reality itself. However, physics must face the reality.

For a person, the observed information is first expressed as a form of thinking. Then it is fed into Gezhi Physics. In Gezhi Physics, logical relations such as cause and effect are used to carry out logical deduction, and to deduce conclusions and assertions. Guide him to work. Assertions can be checked repeatedly. They have also been tested repeatedly.

For him, according to a lot of accumulated experience, the result of this physical theory is highly credible under such circumstances, so this time he still believe that its assertion is credible.

It can be seen from this that the conclusion of **Gezhi Physics does not necessarily fit the reality completely, which cannot be guaranteed at all. Only practical experience tells us that it is relatively credible. This is clearly stated by Gezhi Physics.** This is another characteristic of Gezhi Physics.

Figure 3 Formal sketch of Gezhi Physics application

(6) Yong-axiom

As the basis of other theorems, the basic is named **yong-axiom**.

Reason cannot retreat indefinitely. So there is a self-evident knowledge. There is no need to prove it.

Gezhi Physics is a logical physical system based on **self-evident knowledge** and established by **tautology**.

Yong-axiom itself is based on self-evidentness, or is self-evident knowledge it self, or need simple deduction, or need simple induction. So as to facilitate derivation and use.

Self-evidentness is characterized by simplicity and wide acceptance by society. Simple things are relatively more reliable..

(7) Three Physical Elements Theorem

According to the plan-yong-axiom and descriptive theorem, description is the task of Gezhi Physics and Gezhi Physics is describable.

In order to describe the problem, we need to know some basic elements. Other factors can be calculated from these elements, so these "other factors" are not basic elements.

There are three key elements: What, When and Where. They are the most basic elements; not suitable for indirect description by other elements.

For convenience of reference, naming

Three Physical Elements Theorem: What, When and Where are the three physical key elements.

Three-elements Deterministic Theorem: In a physical theory, as long as the description of the three basic physical elements is deterministic, then it is a deterministic physical theory.

In end-atomic mechanics, Ψ corresponds to "What", in the most basic description of the world. Among them, the description of the three physical key elements are definite and are a definite value. Therefore, end-atomic mechanics is a certainty theory.

(8) Yong-Name-Theorem

According to plan-yong-axiom, the fundamental task of Gezhi Physics is planning. So inevitably, the expected results, the reasons for the corresponding results in the planning, the planning itself, and the source information needed in the planning all need to be accurately exchanged. Accurate communication is accomplished by name. Communication accuracy is based on the accuracy of names. That is to say, in communication, the value of a name must be a pre-determined value; one can no longer expect to explain what the value of a name "changes" into at the moment, in order to avoid falling into an infinite circle. Therefore, in communication, the value of a name must be a pre-determined invariant value.

Yong-name-theorem: The value of a name (within its domain of definition) remains unchanged.

Write as

$$\partial V/\partial q=0$$

or $\partial V=0$

V is the value of the name.

q is a dummy parameter of the associated domain of definition. V does not change with q .

The name "Newton" refers to Newton. Newton is value of the name, and the value remains the same. "Newton's weight at birth" always refers to that fixed value. This value does not change with the position change of the speaker, and the partial derivative to space is 0; also does not change with time, the partial derivative to time is 0.

Note that what is said here is a correctly defined name in knowledge. Properly defined names naturally satisfy this relationship.

Only when this relationship is actually satisfied can the name be correctly defined.

Therefore, names are not defined casually.

In the words of ancient Greece, it is "what it is". The "value of the name" is locked to "what it is."

Although it is universal, for the sake of simple use, only simple things should be used as far as possible.

(9) Tautology theorem and the significance of tautology

According to the rationality of planning, the fundamental task of Geophysics is planning. In order to achieve a complex purpose, logical deduction is necessary.

Therefore, Gezhi Physics is a logical physical system based on self-evident knowledge and established by tautology. So Gezhi Physics is tautological.

For ease of reference, name the **Tautology Theorem: Gezhi Physics is tautological.**

This is the third and last time that human beings have been hit by tautology. This is the last and most thorough time.

In the past, tautology was always a negative role.

Now the tautology is a positive role here.

The tautology is the true wisdom. However, the knowledge acquired from the observation of nature is of nature itself, not created by human beings. Only tautology is pure thinking creation.

Previously, it was believed that the tautological assertion content was zero knowledge.

The content of the assertion actually comes from nature itself and is not created by human beings.

The meaning of tautology lies in structure; structure is knowledge.

According to the structure of tautology, we can reason, predict and plan.

As Hume said, natural knowledge is not available in the law of causation.

Human causality comes from tautological structure.

(10) Self-evidentness Theorem

According to the tautological theorem, Gezhi Physics is tautological.

However, Gezhi Physics is not a "tautology" added entirely by human beings.

The reason is that there are many self-evident things in reality, which are simple and widely accepted by the society. If we can deduce new knowledge from these self-evident things by logic, then this new knowledge is not a "tautology" added artificially.

Therefore, Gezhi Physics needs to be based on self-evident knowledge.

Self-evidentness Theorem: Gezhi Physics needs to be based on self-evident knowledge.

From this level, Gezhi Physics is exploring conclusions hidden behind self-evident.

Note that the logic of Gezhi Physics does not depend on the "evidence of self-evidentness" that this "self-evidentness" may bring. Logic comes from tautology.

They were chosen because of their universal popularization and historical precipitation.

It is also very important that these self-evident knowledge are chosen to ensure that they cannot have logical conflicts.

Of course, this self-evident mechanism can also be classified as tautology.

The self-evident knowledge must also satisfy yong-name-theorem, so the self-evident knowledge must be uniquely determined.

(11) Meta-irrelevance Theorem Meta-symmetry Theorem

According to the yong-name-theorem, the value of name remains unchanged.

On the other hand, the definition and characterization of information cannot be based on information that can only be characterized after definition. Therefore, the definition of a certain dimension cannot depend on the specific information of special starting point, ending point and each point. In other words, the definition of dimensionality has nothing to do with specific points. This kind of irrelevance is named **meta-irrelevance**, also called as **meta-symmetry**.

Meta-irrelevance is formally the independence of each element within a category. From a purely formal point of view, they all belong to translational symmetry, so they are also called meta-symmetry. The category of rotational symmetry is $\{(\varphi, \theta)\}$; the category of mirror symmetry is $\{\text{left, right}\}$. Meta-irrelevance/meta-symmetry, corresponding specific symmetry forms, includes translational symmetry, rotational symmetry, mirror symmetry, etc.

So there are

Meta-irrelevance Theorem: The definition and characterization of information dimensions are independent of specific points and are treated in the same way.

From the perspective of symmetry, it is symmetry. So there are

Meta-symmetry Theorem: Information dimension names have meta-symmetry for their domain.

Names in physics can generally be expressed as information dimension names. For example, temperature itself forms a dimension. Note that it only indicates the internal consistency of temperature. This "1 degree" is equivalent to that "1 degree". This temperature and that temperature refer to the same temperature. It does not mean that the external values of temperatures everywhere are the same.

For example, the definition of space and time, zero-point has no special requirements. Any point can be taken as zero. Any point is treated the same.

There is no special requirement for the starting point of the process of defining end-atom.

In addition, the definition of the mechanical properties of the variation of end-atomic distribution($\partial\Psi$), is for any Ψ , so we use the dimensionless $\partial\Psi/\Psi$.

Meta-independence/meta-symmetry can only be created in the definition of (knowledge) name and cannot be abused.

(12) Fuxi Tree

Meta-symmetry is very important in this physics. Meta-symmetry comes from the yong-name-theorem. The key is the relationship between the definitions of names. Therefore, meta-symmetry depends on the definition.

That is, the meta-symmetric content of a name is closely related to the relative position of the definition of the name.

At the same time, the logical relationship between definitions should satisfy the forest shape relationship. In this way, the circular dependence of names can be avoided. There is no ring in this structure.

The relative positions defined are described by fuxi tree.

Names keep growing up from the roots of trees. You can also add roots down — add dimensions accordingly.

Time is at the root of the tree, so it has the most complete meta symmetry. Time does not change with changes in spatial location, speed, acceleration, etc.

The second name is space. Therefore, it also has very complete meta-symmetry. Space does not change with changes in speed, acceleration, etc. But in the radial direction, it does not have complete symmetry, not complete linear translational symmetry, but ray translational symmetry and semi-symmetry. Accordingly, topological symmetry is required to represent. Topologies can ignore the distance to the vertex of the ray. Therefore, this asymmetry can be bypassed in description.

Fuxi tree and logic diagram:

Figure 4 Fuxi tree and logic diagram

(13) Symmetry and Appearance Asymmetry

Movement is relative. That is, it is symmetrical. However, the knowledge displayed may not necessarily appear symmetrical.

For fuxi tree, there is a difference between the roots and the treetops. It is not symmetrical in itself. Moreover, as a background reference for longitudinal asymmetry, it makes all longitudinal differences asymmetric.

For example, the speed of light and all other speeds should have been equal and symmetrical. However, an spatial tectonic light speed w is specified. Then knowledge expands longitudinally. This makes the speed of light and the other speeds behind different longitudinal positions and thus asymmetric. Specifically, the speed of light does not change, but other general speeds do.

This asymmetry needs to be viewed with wisdom. This asymmetry is only a superficial phenomenon. It is a representation of formal logic. We use formal logic as a tool to express our knowledge, which is bound to be limited by formal logic itself. It is only a by-product.

It is symmetrical in itself. Look at it with wisdom. Can be viewed topologically, etc. It is not necessary to look at the specific speed value. Look at its own topological logic. All speeds are equal and symmetrical. All sports are equal and symmetrical.

Although the movement is relative. However, human thinking logic has a specific structure and a specific direction. As a result, inertial system seems to occupy a special position in physics. This selected position is only a tautological thing.

(14) Absoluteness of Time and Space

1> Meaning of physics and mathematics

A rigid body box with a fixed side length L and a fixed volume V of one cubic meter is filled with apples q .

Now apple q is reduced by half, will the space volume be reduced by half logically? No, not at all.

Mathematical representation

$$\partial V / \partial q = 0$$

If there is only air q in the box.

Now that air q is pumped out by half, will the volume of space be reduced by half logically? No, not at all.

Mathematical representation

$$\partial V/\partial q=0$$

The corresponding space lengths are

$$\partial L/\partial q=0$$

The absoluteness of space is reflected by the partial derivative of space being 0.

The absoluteness of space means that the partial derivative of space is 0.

The characteristic that space logically does not change with the changes of objects and motions is named **spatial absoluteness**.

Similarly, 10,000 people are dancing at a fixed time t . Number of people $q=10000$.

Now the number q is reduced by half, will the time be reduced by half logically? No, not at all. Mathematical representation

$$\partial t/\partial q=0$$

The absoluteness of time is reflected by the partial derivative of time being 0.

The absoluteness of time means that the partial derivative of time is 0.

The characteristic that time logically does not change with the changes of objects and motions therein is named **time absoluteness**.

Some people may say that if the world has no matter or movement at all, is there still time and space for such extreme situations?

This question has no practical significance.

Since "I" is still struggling with this problem; then at least there is a tangled thinking "I". Such unrealistic problems (and therefore unobservable) should not be regarded as physics. It should be excluded from physics.

The absoluteness of time and space is an important attribute obtained through **trend** analysis during movement changes.

2> Pure rational meaning

We use time and space to describe many changing things in the world.

According to the plan-yong-axiom, the fundamental task of Gezhi Physics is planning. Therefore, the meaning of this description should be definite.

However, if time and space change with the change of the described things, and the described things themselves change. Then the certainty of this description cannot be guaranteed in terms of self-consistency.

Therefore, for the sake of this certainty, our wisdom has established a norm, stipulating that space-time S does not change with the change of things q .

$$\partial S/\partial q=0$$

This is the absolute mathematical expression of time and space.

3> Meta-symmetry

The fundamental reason is that in fuxi tree, the name of time and space is at the root and the common things are at the top. According to the meta-symmetry theorem, space-time S has meta-symmetry for general things q . So there are

$$\partial S/\partial q=0$$

Therefore, time and space are absolute to common things.

(15) Two Kinds of Knowledge

Gezhi Physics faces the outside world.

Knowledge about the outside world is basic knowledge. This is a kind of cognition.

Gezhi Physics is a knowledge system of logical system. So naturally, in addition to the above basic knowledge, there is knowledge of the logic system itself. This is a kind of wisdom.

There are two kinds of knowledge in Gezhi Physics.

Only by understanding these two kinds of knowledge can we have a clear understanding of Gezhi Physics.

(16) Two Logics

Gezhi Physics faces the outside world.

Knowledge about the outside world is basic logic. This is a kind of cognition.

Gezhi Physics is a knowledge system of logical system. So naturally, in addition to the above basic knowledge, there is also the logic of this logic system itself. This is a kind of wisdom.

There are two kinds of logic in Gezhi Physics.

Understanding these two kinds of logic can clarify the physics of lattice.

(17) Two Worlds and Consistency Theorem

According to the plan-yong-axiom, the fundamental task of Gezhi Physics is planning.

In addition to the observation results, in order to achieve a complex purpose, people must need logical deduction.

The world that can be observed and measured is named **V-World**. This is a cognitive level.

Its characteristics are based on observation.

According to the plan-yong-axiom, the fundamental task of Gezhi Physics is planning. Therefore, Gezhi Physics must be causal.

The final observable result must have a reason in form.

There is a formal reason logically for an observation result.

In this way, all the observations logically have a formal reason.

Therefore, there is a formal reason logically for the observation results at the end of human observation. They are not observed.

These pure thoughts logically constructed knowledge, and the world they constitute is named **T-World**.

Knowledge of the t-world is not observed. This is the level of wisdom.

The knowledge in the t-world is constructed by the logic of the v-world, the causality of the v-world, and the self-consistency. On the other hand, the v-world and the t-world should also keep in touch.

Therefore, the v-world and the t-world use the same logic.

Consistency Theorem(T-Logical Extension Theorem): The v-world and the t-world use the same logic. This theorem faces complementarity principle.

The t-world is based on the v-world and is compatible with the v-world.

V-limit Theorem: The logic applicable to the whole world is consistent with the logic of our v-world

itself in the t-world.

In short, the final physical rule should converge to the classical physical rule in the limit.

Figure 5 Schematic diagram of two worlds and consistency theorem

In this way, the division of the two worlds does not depend on the limitation of technology. It will not disappear with the progress of technology, but will only move with the progress of technology. It is determined by the topological results of human understanding itself. No matter how technology develops or how the lower limit of human knowledge moves, the lower limit will always extend a little further down, thus there will always be such a structure as the t-world.

In any specific historical period, there is a lower limit to the time and space that human beings can observe. Too small difference can't be distinguished by human beings. Below these lower limits is the t-world.

Therefore, in reality, the v-world and the t-world exist alternately in space and time.

The actual v-world is closely spaced in time and space.

(18) Two-body Theorem

According to plan-yong-axiom, the fundamental task of Gezhi Physics is planning. In order to achieve a complicated goal, logical deduction is necessary.

However, the knowledge of appearance obtained from external observation is only a lonely appearance, which is not logical in itself and cannot be deduced. However, the object knowledge system designed according to internal logic can be deduced by causality because of its causality.

Therefore, Gezhi Physics is centered on internal logic rather than external observation. The source of human cognitive information to the outside world lies in the outside world, and the two are only compatible.

Two-body Theorem: In Gezhi Physics, the same object actually corresponds to two object forms in terms of knowledge form.

One is that the observed cognition corresponds to knowledge form A in knowledge, which is a representation form.

The other is a knowledge form B constructed by physical logic according to logical specifications, which is an entity form.

Object B has more content than object A. Object A cannot break the lower limit of observation. Object B can slightly break through the lower observation limit, thus having a more detailed structure. This more detailed structure is constructed by thinking itself.

In terms of satisfying the relation of entity representation, object B is the entity object of A, and knowledge form A is the representation of B.

In terms of correspondence, the representation of the entity B must correspond to the representation knowledge form A.

B emphasizes the logical source.

A emphasizes information sources.

The two may be very different. Sometimes even in the opposite direction.

(19) Two Kinds of Coordinates

Two kinds of coordinates should be distinguished in Gezhi Physics.

One is the inherent coordinates in logical space-time. This is purely mental. It has nothing to do with the outside world.

The space-time mentioned by Gezhi Physics is the space-time corresponding to this set of coordinates. This space-time is also purely thinking. It has nothing to do with the outside world. It is a thinking container. It is a tool for human beings to know the world. Logically, it is independent of the outside world. It is characterized by conciseness, straightness, uniformity and infinite separability.

This kind of coordinate is depicted by thinking itself.

Relative coordinates can be formed between different points.

The corresponding position coordinates of knowledge forms corresponding to objects in this time and space and the relative coordinates between different parts. The actual application generally involves relative coordinates; here is a reference, which is the **reference-frame**. This coordinate is relative to the coordinate of the reference system.

This coordinate reflects the interaction process between human cognition and things, which is named **cognitive-process**. Cognitive-process is the actual process in the real world, which is bound to be limited by reality and thinking logic. Therefore, the coordinates obtained are bound to be limited by reality and thinking logic. "Infinite separability" may not always be realized. In a specific historical period, there is always a minimum lower limit. In a specific cognitive process, if the parameters of the restriction logic are inconsistent with the corresponding parameters of the description mode, the logic form of the lower limit logic may not directly restrict the coordinates, and the lower limit logic may be a complex inequality named as the **lower-limit-inequality**.

(20) The Change of Invariability and The Invariability of Change

When we perceive things, we actually perceive certain changes. True invariance cannot be perceived.

However, in our knowledge, in the v-world, according to the yong-name-theorem, the attribute of things is unchanged for time and space.

This is because the actual v-worl is closely spaced in time and space.

Therefore, this invariable domain that must be satisfied does not need to cover the whole time and space. It just needs to be satisfied in that fine set.

However, in the fine gap in the middle, it need not remain unchanged.

There are changes in the fine gaps in the middle, which can be sensed.

This kind of logical structure is named as the **change of invariability**.

For a process of change, this kind of change violates the yong-name-theorem of knowledge.

For this kind of situation, the corresponding knowledge is the invariable characteristic value that regulates this change process. This kind of logical structure is named the **invariability of change**. Wrap a changed thing into an unchanging thing.

In any case, in terms of knowledge, all meet the yong-name-theorem.

(21) Compatibility Theorem

Gezhi Physics is self-consistent. Therefore, the whole theory applicable to the whole world is applicable to the t-world, the v-world and the macro world .

However, the knowledge in the t-world is formed by the extension of the knowledge in the v-world, on the premise of self-consistency. Therefore, naturally, it is compatible with the theories of v-world and macro world, including various theoretical parameters.

Compatibility Theorem: The whole theory applicable to the t-world should be compatible with the theories of the v-world and the macro world. This theorem faces complementarity principle. Actually, it is a theory applicable to the whole world. The parameters such as E, period and wavelength, conservation criterion, are the same as those used in the t-world.

(22) Causality Theorem

According to plan-yong-axiom, the fundamental task of Gezhi Physics is planning. Then there must be a desired effect B, named as **result**. At the same time, in order to achieve this result, there must be a personal choice of operation A, named as **reason**. Since it is a plan, the result has not yet started before the cause is implemented, so there must be a delay (Δt) between the result and the cause.

Since it is planning; then the result is man-made. Therefore, the result must be selective in thinking. For this result with thinking selectivity, the corresponding reason must have thinking selectivity.

The following expected effect can be achieved by operating on the basis of prior causes, and this relationship characteristic is named **causality**.

Causality Theorem (Antecedents and Consequences Theorem): There is a positive time difference between two things with cause and effect. In terms of time, cause A occurs first and result B occurs later. Otherwise, A cannot be said to be the cause of B.

Antecedents and consequences is a necessary but not sufficient condition for causality.

Causal norm is the norm of knowledge. The causality defined is the content of knowledge. When defining causality, we must follow the causality criterion.

Note that in Gezhi Physics, the causal theorem regulates knowledge without directly facing objective facts. This is very important. That is, it regulates the logic of knowledge in the mind. That is, it regulates the thinking activities in the mind. It regulates our thinking only in this way.

In Gezhi Physics, the result is the inevitable result of the cause under the space-time expansion Δt .

Cause $\rightarrow(\Delta t)\rightarrow$ Result

This clearly shows the inevitability of "antecedents and consequences".

It is this necessity that, gives physics meaning: According to this causal necessity, carry out logical deduction, and predict the development of things.

The reason for free choice by thinking, the unfolding time (Δt), and the result of free choice by thinking are called the **three elements of event causality**.

Figure 6 Schematic diagram of the three elements of event causality

In order to show that "free choice by thinking" it can be further expanded.

Since it is planning. The result of the optional rule that is expected to be achieved must have a definite observable phase, named the **result phase**. The same optional cause operation must have the definite observable phase, named the **cause phase**.

The reason for free choice by thinking, the corresponding cause phase of free choice by thinking, the unfolding time (Δt), the result of free choice by thinking, and the corresponding result phase of free choice by thinking, are called the **five elements of event causality**.

Figure 7 Schematic diagram of the five elements of event causality

Cause events and result events must be freely chosen for thinking. Only in this way can it be defined as causality. This "free choice by thinking" is verified by the corresponding "free choice of cause phase" and "free choice of result phase". That is, it is observable and selectable.

If thinking cannot be freely chosen, it does not constitute a causality. If there is only one possibility and there is no selectivity, it does not constitute a causality.

If it is not observable, it does not constitute a causality of events.

The "free choice" of results is realized through the "free choice of causes". Thinking can freely choose the result, and then thinking can freely choose the corresponding the cause event to realize it. The reason phase is similar to the result phase.

The free choice of cause can realize the free choice of result, which is the purpose, mystery and root of causality. Prediction and planning are realized through causality.

If the result cannot be selected by reason events, then it cannot be defined as causality.

For example, a pair of gloves is placed in the left and right drawers. Seeing the left-hand sleeve first is called event A, then seeing the right-hand sleeve of the right-hand drawer is called event B. A cannot be the reason for B, because whether you look at the drawer on the left or not, the B event is to see the right hand sleeve, and there is no selectivity.

This kind of "selectivity" must be reflected on the surface of observation. Different choices, observation appearances must be different. If A and B are chosen, but the observation representation cannot show selectivity, then there is not an actual "choice".

The experimental events mentioned by Gezhi Physics are observed by many people on an equal footing and do not include pure conscious activities. They can be convincingly demonstrated in front of the public.

Pure conscious activities are those that cannot be observed by more than one person and can be observed on an equal footing. Only people involved in consciousness activities know the truth themselves. It is not convincing. It can only be objects of psychology; therefore, the persuasion and acceptance of psychology cannot be compared with physics at all.

However, it can be introduced into external experiments, such as external electromagnetic characteristics. At this time, the content of internal consciousness does not participate in the research. At this time, it is not a pure conscious activity experiment, but an ordinary physical experiment. The experimenter has the same logical status as the mouse.

This causality of knowledge is completely constructed by thinking. The actual observation cannot observe causality, only the phenomenon itself can be observed.

(23) Certainty Theorem

According to plan-yong-axiom, the fundamental task of Gezhi Physics is planning. So inevitably, the expected results, the causes corresponding to the results in the planning and the planning itself must be determined in the form of knowledge, and the physical three elements of the results and causes must be determined; this characteristic of the object is named **certainty**. This certainty is expressed in terms of knowledge form.

Therefore, Gezhi Physics must be certain.

Certainty Theorem: Gezhi Physics is certain.

"Certainty" is a mandatory norm for rational knowledge systems such as Gezhi Physics and is primary. Gezhi Physics only includes deterministic knowledge.

Physics either gives a certain answer or says nothing.

Some people may say that thermodynamics in physics thinks that thermal motion is "irregular motion". "Irregularities" here is just an explanation. It is not "uncertain". If it is really "uncertain", it includes all possibilities, but in fact it does rule out many possibilities. This kind of motion has a definite model, and thermodynamics is based on this definite model. Otherwise there would be no thermodynamics. The temperature given by physics is also a specific value or range; however, the answer of "both 3 and 2" will never be given.

Certainty is the cornerstone of rationality.

(24) Locality Theorem

According to plan-yong-axiom, the fundamental task of Gezhi Physics is planning. So inevitably, the expected results, the causes corresponding to the results in the planning, and the planning itself, must be determined in the form of knowledge, and the physical three elements of the results and causes must be logically (time, space and other dimensions) local; that is, it can be properly limited within a certain area (generally not a complete set); this characteristic is named **locality**. This locality is expressed in terms of knowledge form.

Therefore, Gezhi Physics must be localized.

Locality Theorem: Gezhi Physics is localized.

Locality norms stipulate that in our knowledge, things must limit their local scope. Beyond this range is irrelevant. It is true for everyone's body, house, computer and desk.

Locality is the basis for rational understanding of things, distinguishing things from time and space.

Locality criterion is the basis of causality criterion. Without locality, causality is impossible.

(25) Reality Theorem

According to plan-yong-axiom, the fundamental task of Gezhi Physics is planning. Then the expected result, the reason corresponding to the result in the plan, and the content of the plan, must all logically and consistently maintain self-consistency, in the logic of the whole knowledge system; its logical appearance logically does not depend on the human consciousness appearance; its logical appearance logically does not depend on whether it is observed or not; its logical appearance logically does not depend on whom it is observed; and the characteristic of the object is named **reality**. This reality is expressed in terms of knowledge form.

Therefore, Gezhi Physics must be real.

Reality Theorem: Gezhi Physics is real.

The norms of reality stipulates that our knowledge can be divided into reality and non-reality. Logically, things in a fundamental position are defined as reality, otherwise they are non-reality. Reality is consistent in the

logic of the whole knowledge system. Reality logically does not depend on human consciousness; reality logically does not depend on whether it is observed or not. Phenomena are non-reality. The real thing behind the phenomenon is reality. Reality is not allowed to be reality in one case and non-reality in another.

This reality of knowledge is completely constructed by thinking. The actual observation can only observe the phenomenon.

(26) Logic Theorem and Decisive Theorem

According to plan-yong-axiom, the fundamental task of Gezhi Physics is planning. In order to achieve a complicated goal, logical deduction is necessary.

However, the knowledge of appearance obtained from external observation is only a lonely appearance, which is not logical in itself and cannot be deduced. However, the object knowledge system designed according to internal logic can be deduced by causality because of its causality.

The determinable deductibility of the knowledge system itself is named **logicality**.

Therefore, Gezhi Physics is centered on internal logic rather than external observation. The source of human cognitive information to the outside world lies in the outside world, and the two are only compatible.

Gezhi Physics is logical because it is constructed with logical centers.

Logic Theorem: Gezhi Physics is Logical. It refers to the form of knowledge of Gezhi Physics.

Logic theorem guarantees the deductibility and predictability of Gezhi Physics.

Because of deduction and predictability, Gezhi Physics is decisive.

Gezhi Decisiveness Theorem: Gezhi Physics is Decisive. It refers to the form of knowledge of Gezhi Physics.

(27) Exact-judgment Theorem

According to plan-yong-axiom, the fundamental task of Gezhi Physics is planning. In order to achieve a complicated goal, logical deduction is necessary.

If a logical process of thinking can determine the exact state of things; the particle is in a corresponding determined state, because the correct "exact-judgment" knowledge must be based on some definite physical process. This process causes things to irreversibly enter the corresponding definite state. For example, change the entangled party to know its state and deduce the state of the other party. Then in fact the other party is in a state of inference. Among them, the intrinsic mechanism of entanglement plays a key role.

Consciousness is not the key in judgment, the key is the physical process logic behind it. On the contrary, if the logic of this physical process cannot be guaranteed, then the original "exact-judgment" may fail.

Exact-judgment Theorem: If a logical thinking process can "exactly judge" the exact state of a thing, then the thing is in the corresponding definite state determined by the real physical process.

Otherwise, we will not recognize this kind of thinking logic.

Exact-judgment theorem is the core of logic.

(28) Gezhi Physics Economic theorem

According to plan-yong-axiom, the fundamental task of Gezhi Physics is planning. Planning naturally involves economy, which is part of the planning. Therefore, Gezhi Physics is economical.

For the convenience of quoting, naming

Gezhi Physics economic theorem: Gezhi Physics is economic.

Therefore, it can be inferred that "if not necessary, need not be introduced" and "if not necessary, do not add entitie".

This is because the introduction of A increases the cost but reduces the overall economy. On the contrary, removing A reduces the cost and improves the overall economy. So don't introduce A.

(29) Gezhi Physics Absolute Theorem

The world seems to be changing.

However, the yong-name-theorem requires that the name value be constant. Correspondingly, it definitely means "constant" and "stable".

This is contradictory. So that means even a name cannot be decided.

Obviously, there are already many names. Then there are other ways.

On the other hand, we can control the world according to those relatively stable things. In reality, we have a saying that "remain essentially the same despite all apparent changes".

Of all the changes, we can still extract the foundation of invarianc. Reference to the change of invariability.

To control the traces of changes with the foundation of invarianc.

According to the economic theorem of Gezhi Physics, Gezhi Physics should have economy.

Obviously, mastering and memorizing the traces of changes takes more cost than the foundation of invarianc, which violates the economic theorem.

In addition, the complexity cost of the relationship brought about by the changes is a square relationship, and the cost growth is a square growth, which is even more contrary to the economic theorem.

Therefore, we have to choose the "the absolute foundation of invarianc"

At the same time, yong-name-theorem requires the name value is unchanged.

For the convenience of quoting, naming

Gezhi Physics Absolute Theorem: Gezhi Physics is absolute.

The most fundamental point is that physics is not a simple list of information.

(30) Gezhi Physics Observation Judgment Theorem

According to plan-yong-axiom, the fundamental task of Gezhi Physics is planning. Planning must have a planning purpose. It must be possible to observe and judge whether the planning purpose is achieved. Many small plans make up a big plan. Whether the planning purpose of each small plan is achieved or not must be observed and judged. Whether the planning purpose is achieved or not constitutes the key conclusion of Gezhi Physics. Therefore, the key conclusion of Gezhi Physics must be observable and judgmental.

In addition Otherwise, it also violates Gezhi Physics economic theorem and cannot be observed, thus causing disputes to consume more.

For the convenience of reference, naming

Gezhi Physics Observation Judgment Theorem: The key conclusion of Gezhi Physics is observable. Only the conclusion that can be observed and judged is debatable.

There are many unobservable and purely logical conclusions in Gezhi Physics. This is an internal matter of theory, not the key conclusion here, and it is not worth arguing with other theories. Whether they are understood correctly or not only indicates whether the theory itself is grasped correctly.

(31) Completeness Theorem

According to plan-yong-axiom, the fundamental task of Gezhi Physics is planning. Then the expected results, the reasons corresponding to the results in the planning, and the contents of the planning, all must logically and consistently maintain self-consistency, in the logic of the whole knowledge system; its logical appearance logically does not depend on human consciousness appearance, and its logical appearance logically does not depend on whether it is observed or not; entities in the system logically maintain entities consistently and consistently; the basic elements that define an entity cannot logically exclude being measured at the same time, while other attributes can be calculated from them; the system satisfies both causality and locality; this characteristic of the system is named **completeness**. This completeness is expressed in terms of knowledge form and knowledge system.

Therefore, Gezhi Physics must be complete.

Gezhi Completeness theorem: Gezhi Physics is complete.

In end-atomic mechanics, position and momentum can be obtained from the wave function. Therefore, simultaneous measurement of position and momentum is not required. The basic elements of wave function do not logically exclude simultaneous measurement. Therefore, end-atomic mechanics is complete.

(32) Description System

Description system is a logical generalization of reference system which does not emphasize practical operation. For example, how and where to observe.

After logical transformation, the space-time description of a description system looks like a space-time. This is also a description system.

(33) Space-time Representation Theory

Pure mathematical space-time established according to the same logic is named **space-time representation**.

Space-time representation is a logical generalization of the mathematical representation of space-time that emphasizes the same logical system instead of the actual space-time.

The results of the description system are also time-space representations.

Replace certain dimensions in an event information flow that distributes events. It also forms the representation of time and space. For example, use phase instead of time.

It can be used to study non-spatiotemporal information is the first essence.

It can also be a logical combination of different reference frame. For example, for people on two spacecraft, it is stipulated that the length of the object to be measured is relatively static, and the reference frames of the two lengths are different.

Allowing multiple reference frames is the second essence.

Space-time representation, a physical tool, can overcome some limitations and deficiencies of reference-frame.

For different problems, time-space representation with different structures can be adopted. In this way, the meta-symmetry of the problem itself can be used. For example, the space-time representation of dynamical elements. At this time, the expression of gravity can be directly obtained.

Allowing different structures is the third essence.

(34) Superextraction Theorem

The observation process is physically a specific action process A; the specific state of the action effect of this process can be used to describe a certain feature of the measured object; this process A is named **super-extraction process**, and this way of obtaining the determined feature is named **super-extraction**. The feature above is the characteristic value of Gezhi Physics.

Superextraction means that the last thing observed is the result of superextraction, and it is not necessarily such a specific shape before the superextraction process.

According to reality theorem, the physical process must be a real process. Therefore, the superextraction process must be a real process.

For end-atom, after the superextraction process occurs, the end-atom is no longer the original end-atom, so the superextraction process is irreversible.

The superextraction process is irreversible, resulting in the corresponding right-material-cause of the original end-atom is exhausted; the original end-atomic entity does not exist; the entity does not exist, and naturally all other states of the original end-atomic entity will not appear.

Because the real superextraction process is a real physical process. Therefore, the actual super-extraction process must consume more than 0 time.

Superextraction Theorem: The fundamental reason why the end-atom suddenly becomes a certain knowledge form (eigenvalue) is the actual superextraction process; it has nothing to do with consciousness itself.

Observation Superextraction Theorem: The fundamental reason why the end-atom suddenly becomes a certain characteristic value in observation is the actual superextraction process; it has nothing to do with consciousness itself.

This will be the case when conscious living people are replaced by unconscious dead bodies, unconscious instruments and appropriate natural objects. For example, photons hit rocks, mud and asphalt and are absorbed by them, all of which will be the same.

When people observe photons, the interaction between photons and retina is absorbed, and this process is a real superextraction process. This spatio-temporal representation location where the superextraction process takes place is the last perceived spatio-temporal representation location of the photon. The photon finally terminates in the last state. The original photon logic entity no longer exists when the right-material-cause is exhausted. Therefore, the original other state can no longer appear. Therefore, over superextraction occurs to obtain certain characteristics, i.e. specific states.

Similarly, when photons impinge on unconscious corpses, the photons interact with the corpses and are absorbed. This process is a real superextraction process.

Similarly, when people use a geiger counter to observe photons, the photons interact with the geiger counter and are absorbed. This process is a real superextraction process.

Similarly, when a photon hits an unconscious stone, mud or asphalt, the photon interacts with the stone, mud or asphalt and is absorbed. This process is a real super extraction process.

Figure 8 Schematic diagram of super-extraction

(35) Characteristic-value

In Gezhi Physics, the characteristics of an object in physical or logical action are named **characteristic-value**. Formal-cause corresponds to Characteristic-value.

Various features of the so-called objects in traditional physics are named characteristic-values.

Some are not actually observed, but are calculated by some logical expression, for example, the corresponding values of operators in quantum physics are also characteristic-values here.

(36) Definition of Scale Number

$$n = \frac{U + U + U + \dots + U}{U}$$

U represents the characteristic-value scale of 1 unit. In the formula, denominator U can be added.

Under the eigenvalue judgment logic f , the scale value of the characteristic-value corresponding to the simplest accumulated total result of n equivalent U is recorded as n .

For example, if the mass of a standard apple is defined as 1 kilogram, then the mass of n identical apples is n kilograms.

Non-standard form:

$$n(A)=n(B)$$

Under the characteristic-value judgment logic f , if A and B are judged to be equivalent, then the scale-values of the characteristic-values are the same.

For example, under the weighing logic, a gourd is equivalent to n kilograms of apples, so the mass of the gourd is n kilograms.

(37) On Operator

1> Non-numeric operators are not numbers, nor can they be regarded as numbers or symbols. In practice, a function (Ψ) must be taken to carry out the actual operation and the actual value

The operator $\hat{p} = -i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial q}$ cannot be regarded as a number and cannot be given a certain value. $\hat{p}\Psi = -i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial q} \Psi$ can calculate the certain value $-i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial q} \Psi$.

2> No multiplication is defined between operators or between operators and the following functions. Writing together in sequence does not mean multiplication, but a combination. To put it bluntly, it is just written together.

3> Between operators, between operators and the following functions, besides the literal combination relation, a simple distribution law about addition and subtraction is also defined.

4> The multiplication relation is not expressed between the operator and the following functions, but only the combination relation. The actual relationship is determined by the combination of operators.

For example, the operator of derivation actually performs derivation.

5> In $AB\Psi$, AB is not first combined. Ψ side (right side) takes precedence. B and Ψ are combined first. The actual meaning is $(A(B\Psi))$.

$$AB\Psi = (A(B\Psi))$$

$$BA\Psi = (B(A\Psi))$$

Because Ψ is inserted first, the result includes Ψ . Mathematics naturally does not require AB symmetry.

6> The results calculated by non-numerical operators are still non-numerical operators and not numerical

values, even if the results are formally a certain value.

$$[\hat{q}, \hat{p}] = i\hbar$$

Where $i\hbar$ does not represent a value $i\hbar$. Actual meaning:

$$[\hat{q}, \hat{p}]\Psi = i\hbar\Psi$$

$i\hbar\Psi$ is the numerical value.

In $[\hat{q}, \hat{p}]\Psi$, $[\hat{q}, \hat{p}]$ and Ψ are not multiplication relations, so the result of $[\hat{q}, \hat{p}]$ cannot be obtained as value $i\hbar$ according to the inverse operation of numerical multiplication.

$[\hat{q}, \hat{p}] = i\hbar$ simply means that the operator is literally replaced, $[\hat{q}, \hat{p}]\Psi$ is literally replaced by $i\hbar\Psi$, and the result is unchanged.

$$\hat{q}\hat{p}\Psi = q(-i\hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial q})\Psi = -i\hbar q\frac{\partial}{\partial q}\Psi$$

$$\hat{p}\hat{q}\Psi = (-i\hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial q})q\Psi = (-i\hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial q})(q\Psi) = -i\hbar(\frac{\partial}{\partial q}q)\Psi - i\hbar q(\frac{\partial}{\partial q}\Psi) = -i\hbar\Psi - i\hbar q\frac{\partial}{\partial q}\Psi$$

$$\hat{q}\hat{p}\Psi - \hat{p}\hat{q}\Psi = i\hbar\Psi$$

Ψ is an arbitrary function, so there is an equivalent relation in form:

$$\hat{q}\hat{p} - \hat{p}\hat{q} = i\hbar$$

$$[\hat{q}, \hat{p}] = i\hbar$$

7> The physical meaning of $\hat{p}\hat{q}$ itself is not defined. Does not mean "momentum \times position".

Note: $C = \hat{q}\Psi$.

Complete form: $\hat{p}\hat{q}\Psi = \hat{p}(C) = \hat{p}(C)$

We define the physical meaning of $\hat{p}(C)$, but do not define the physical meaning of $\hat{p}(C)$.

(38) Non-commutative Algebra and Ordinary Algebra

Nonreciprocal (multiplication) operator

$$A \text{ op1 } B - B \text{ op1 } A \neq 0$$

(Multiplication) operator op1 is asymmetric. $A \text{ op1 } B \neq B \text{ op1 } A$.

The (multiplication) operator op1, which does not satisfy the commutative law, actually undertakes two functions, symmetrical symmetric (multiplication) operation and position function.

The position function is separated as a single operator, then the (multiplication) operator has only symmetric (multiplication) function, thus satisfying the (multiplication) commutative law.

Use the following format to describe

$$\text{op3}(A) \text{ op2 } B - \text{op3}(B) \text{ op2 } A \neq 0$$

(Multiplication) operator op2 is symmetric. $A \text{ op2 } B = B \text{ op2 } A$.

Operator op3 replaces the position function of the original operand. Because the (multiplication) operator op2 no longer needs to express the operand position relation, is insensitive to the operand position, becomes symmetrical to the operand position, and satisfies the (multiplication) commutation law.

Op3 is named the **set-operator**.

$$\text{op3}(A) \text{ op2 } B \neq \text{op3}(B) \text{ op2 } A$$

Due to the inclusion of another operator op3 in the middle, symmetry between A and B is naturally not required. Op2 itself satisfies the (multiplicative) commutative law.

In this way, asymmetric multiplication can be completely disenchanted and disenchanted by transforming it into symmetric multiplication. Therefore, the problem is not multiplication operator but physics itself.

Non-commutative multiplication can be replaced by an commutative multiplication operator and a set-operator.

Non-commutative algebra can be replaced by a corresponding ordinary operator and a set-operator.

Mathematics has no secrets.

(For physics) **Mathematics is transparent.**

For complex numbers, set-operator is to take the conjugate operator.

Use the following format to express

$$\bar{A} \times B - \bar{B} \times A \neq 0$$

Set-operator is the conjugate operator $\bar{}(A)=\bar{A}$.

$$\bar{A} \times B = \bar{}(A) \times B$$

$$\bar{B} \times A = \bar{}(B) \times A$$

However, $\bar{A} \times B - \bar{B} \times A = \bar{}(A) \times B - \bar{}(B) \times A = \text{im}(\bar{A} \times B) \times 2$.

$\bar{A} \times B - \bar{B} \times A$ equals twice the imaginary part of $\bar{A} \times B$.

Due to the inclusion of the preferred conjugate operator $\bar{}$, naturally, the expression does not require the order of the two parts to be symmetrical.

$$\bar{}(A) \times B \neq \bar{}(B) \times A$$

For matrices.

Asymmetric matrix multiplication can be replaced by symmetric **parallel-multiplication** \otimes , and transpose operator T . $A \otimes B = B \otimes A$. Set-operator is the transpose operator T .

$$A \otimes B = A \times T(B)$$

$$A \times B - B \times A$$

Expressed in the following format ($a=T(A)$, $b=T(B)$)

$$T(a) \otimes b - T(b) \otimes a$$

Due to the inclusion of the precedence transpose operator T , naturally, the expression does not require the two parts to be symmetrical in order.

$$T(a) \otimes b \neq T(b) \otimes a$$

For operators.

1> Non-numeric operators are not numbers, nor can they be regarded as numbers or symbols. In practice, a function (Ψ) must be taken to carry out the actual operation and the actual value.

The operator $\hat{p} = -i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial q}$ cannot be regarded as a number and cannot be given a certain value. $\hat{p}\Psi = -i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial q} \Psi$ can calculate the certain value.

2> No multiplication is defined between operators or between operators and the following functions. Writing together in sequence does not mean multiplication, but a combination. To put it bluntly, it is just written together.

3> The multiplication relation is not expressed between the operator and the following functions, but only the combination relation. The actual relationship is determined by the combination of operators.

For example, the operator of derivation actually performs derivation.

4> In $AB\Psi$, AB is not first combined. Ψ side (right side) takes precedence. B and Ψ are combined first. The actual meaning is $(A(B\Psi))$.

$$AB\Psi = (A(B\Psi))$$

$$BA\Psi = (B(A\Psi))$$

Because Ψ is inserted first, the result includes Ψ . Mathematics naturally does not require AB symmetry.

$$AB\Psi \neq BA\Psi$$

If the operator involves partial derivatives, generally, mathematics does not require symmetry.

The key is to define the priority of derivation and multiplication.

If there is a variable between the sign of the partial derivative and the right Ψ , to multiply Ψ firstly, then the product is first multiplied and then the partial derivative is obtained.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial q} q\Psi = \frac{\partial}{\partial q} (q \times \Psi)$$

If the right side of the partial derivative symbol directly encounters Ψ , then naturally, the partial derivative will be directly calculated for Ψ .

$$q \frac{\partial}{\partial q} \Psi = q \times \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial q} (\Psi) \right)$$

Due to the inclusion of partial derivative operation, naturally, the expression does not require the two parts to be symmetrical in sequence.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial q} q\Psi \neq q \frac{\partial}{\partial q} \Psi$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial q} (q \times \Psi) \neq q \times \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial q} (\Psi) \right)$$

$$\hat{q} \hat{p} \Psi - \hat{p} \hat{q} \Psi = q \left((-i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial q}) \Psi \right) - (-i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial q}) (q\Psi) = i\hbar \Psi$$

Therefore,

$$\hat{q} \hat{p} \Psi \neq \hat{p} \hat{q} \Psi$$

$$\hat{q} \hat{p} \neq \hat{p} \hat{q}$$

(39) Universal Action Theorem

The characteristic value scalar Φ of an object's total external acting ability, is named **flux** (gravitational flux, electric flux, magnetic flux, magnetic field A potential flux, etc.). Charge size is recorded as Q .

In meta-symmetric space-time, Corresponding to yong-name-theorem, it only indicates the external action capability of the source itself and emphasizes the subordinate relation. Therefore, the unit areal density detection charge is used here for detection.

In measurement, at least one separating interface Σ can be found at any point outside the source. The total amount of internal action on the outside (scalar) is Φ .

In meta-symmetric space-time, it can be obtained from yong-name-theorem:

$$\partial\Phi/\partial q=0$$

$$\Phi=const$$

It is still valid for the unit source charge.

$$\Phi/Q = const \quad \Phi = kQ = const$$

Named **Gezhi Universal Action Formula** and **Universal action theorem** .

The external effect of an Q-scale charge object, in the meta-symmetric space, is on a sphere with the object as its center, and the spherical area is S .

Due to meta-symmetry, the action intensity E of each point is spherically symmetric, and the scalar integral on the whole sphere is $\Phi=ES$.

It can be obtained from yong-name-theorem:

$$\partial(ES)/\partial q=0$$

$$\therefore ES = \text{const}$$

It is still valid for the unit source charge.

$$ES/Q = \text{const}$$

Get:

$$ES/Q = \text{const} \quad E = kQ/S$$

Named **Gezhi Universal Strength Formula**. k is constant.

For 3-dimensional space $S = 4\pi r^2$.

For the coulomb force of Q charge, in the distance of its meta-symmetric space r , the electric field intensity E is

$$E = kQ/(4\pi r^2) = k_e Q / r^2$$

$$F = EQ_2 = k_e QQ_2 / r^2$$

This is the formula of **Coulomb's theorem**.

For the universal gravitation of M mass charge, in the distance of its meta-symmetric space r , the gravitational field intensity E is

$$E = km/(4\pi r^2) = Gm / r^2$$

$$F = Em_2 = Gmm_2 / r^2$$

This is the formula of the **universal gravitation theorem**.

According to this, the force that truly satisfies complete symmetry is named the **basic-force**. In a 3-dimensional meta-symmetric space, the inverse square ratio is satisfied.

The apparent force obtained by the distribution and movement of basic force is named **structural-force**, also called **non-basic-force**.

According to this, I think the basic-force is this completely symmetrical force, otherwise it cannot be called the basic-force, but only the structural-force.

It can also be applied to the magnetic field intensity B around the infinitely long guiding line.

Removing the dimension of infinite conductor, space is a 2-dimensional meta-symmetric space, and the 3-dimensional sphere becomes a 2-dimensional sphere, with $S = 2\pi r$.

$$B = kI/S = kI/(2\pi r) = KI/r$$

For the functions of light radiation, heat radiation, A field strength of long solenoid magnetic field, etc. and the functions of end-atom, it all holds; this theorem is **purely logical**, is determined by the logic of name, and does not involve specific physical mechanism. The key is yong-name-theorem and meta-symmetric space-time representation.

Note that, **in Gezhi Physics force does not define speed**. In reality, the speed of force is actually the apparent speed. The reason is the space-time equivalence. Therefore, this apparent speed is equal to the space-time equivalence constant. Just like a person flying by plane, it doesn't mean that this person can run so fast.

The flux is constant and appears as a topological quantity. The flux corresponds to the source charge. Therefore the flux and source charge are the topological quantities.

Topological Charge Theorem: Flux and source charge are topological quantities.

This explains the strange geometric characteristics in the "Aharonov-Bohm effect of the potential of the electromagnetic field". This is because, as long as the topological quantity remains unchanged, no matter how the path changes, the final path integral remains unchanged.

(40)Independent Proof of Universal Action Theorem

Not directly use yong-name-theorem.

In measurement, at least one separating interface Σ can be found at any point outside the source. The total amount of internal action on the outside (scalar) is Φ .

For point charge (universal gravitation, coulomb force, etc.), scalar is the point product of area element action and normal vector.

Similarly, make an interface Σ_2 further outside, and the total effect of the inside on the outside is Φ_2 .

$$\Phi = \Phi_2$$

$$\text{Otherwise, } \Delta\Phi \equiv \Phi_2 - \Phi \neq 0$$

Then it shows that part of the action $\Delta\Phi$ in Φ_2 comes from the space Σ to Σ_2 . However, Σ logically separates the source of action completely. Then this part of the space is not the source of action. Then this part of Φ_2 does not count as the source of action. Contradiction. So $\Phi = \Phi_2$.

Therefore, $\Phi = \text{const}$

The following is omitted.

For complex cases, the meta-symmetric calculation is used first (that's enough), and then the general definition of interface and integration method is deduced in reverse. If necessary, it can be used as an auxiliary vector. For example, if \mathbf{B} around an infinitely long conductor is rotated 90 degrees in the normal direction, it can be directly accumulated.

(41)Gravitational Mass Theorem

The cause of momentum change is called acting force.

Then it is divided into different categories. An important criterion for classification is that forces that rise and fall completely with a certain source charge are classified according to that source charge.

For example, the force that completely increases and decreases with the source electric charge is named **coulomb force**. Therefore, the source charge of Coulomb force is electric charge.

Similarly, the force that increases and decreases completely with source inertial mass is named **universal gravitation**. Therefore, the source charge of universal gravitation is inertial mass.

However, if we use the name of universal gravitation, we may directly name its source charge as the gravitational mass.

Obviously, these two names both point to the source charge of universal gravitation.

\therefore Inertial Mass = Source Charge of Universal Gravitation

Gravitational Mass = Source Charge of Universal Gravitation

\therefore Gravitational Mass = Inertial Mass

Gravitational mass theorem: Gravitational mass is inertial mass.

According to Gezhi Physics economic theorem, these two mass should not be regarded as the "not the same thing".

Under the explanation, the factor brought by the relative speed is not considered here. This is not a

fundamental problem, it only affects the coefficients in the physical relations and does not affect the topological structure of the physical relations.

Some people plausibly say that the two mass represent completely different meanings. Gravitational mass promotes motion speed change, but inertial mass prevents motion speed change. So they are not a mass.

In fact, this is just a matter of different perspectives of the same object. Is actually the same physical object. There is no need for two names in physics.

This is like buying-price and selling-price in a transaction. Their meanings also look completely different. The buying-price indicates how much money I need to pay. The selling-price indicates how much money I can get. This difference is only caused by different perspectives. In fact, it refers to the "transaction-price" of the same real object. From the perspective of the buyer, it is called the buying-price. From the angle of the seller, it is called the selling-price.

\therefore selling-price = transaction-price

buying-price = transaction-price

\therefore selling-price = buying-price

(42) Fuxi-equation and Isovolt Theorem

Fuxi theorem: For the n-dimensional space equation A , if there is a scalar f such that the variation equation $\delta[f]df = 0$ can obtain the equation A , then A can be replaced by $\delta[f]df = 0$ (of course, there are initial conditions).

This is obvious.

This theorem is purely logical.

The variational equation $\delta[f]df = 0$ is named **fuxi-equation**.

Scalar f is named **fuxi-value**, also known as **topological-value**.

What matters in the equation are topological relations and topological values, regardless of the coordinate difference between them.

For example, a coordinate grid is drawn on a transparent rubber film, and a coordinate grid (which can be different) is arranged on the coordinate paper below. Draw a line on the rubber membrane and pull the rubber membrane to deform it. Then spread it on the coordinate paper. It turns out that the coordinate difference between the two points AB on the line on the graph paper coordinate grid can become larger and smaller. However, the coordinate difference of AB in the rubber coordinate grid is always the same.

λ is a corresponding monotonically increasing scalar, $df = Q*d\lambda$, so the fuxi-equation is written as $\delta[(Q*d\lambda)] = 0$.

The representation transformation that keeps the fuxi-value constant is named the **isovolt-transformation**.

Isovolt theorem: Fuxi-equation does not change in isovolt-transformation.

Note that this is purely logical (physics is logical) and naturally applies to physics, but not specifically from the physical theory. This is purely logical and does not need the support of physical mechanism. Its transcendence even goes beyond ordinary numerical mathematics, a pure form of logic. No matter how it changes, the topological line will remain unchanged from the topological point of view.

The problem becomes that we only need to find this isovolt-transformation and the corresponding fuxi-value, and this is a scalar quantity, which is much simpler.

Here, the transformation is equivalent to a scaling coefficient matrix \mathcal{G}_μ , i.e., the basis vector \mathbf{g}_μ , named as the **isovolt-factor**.

The problem is that we just need to find this \mathcal{G}_μ .

Also, here, it is for a set S , not for the whole number. Corresponding to physics, there is no need for the entire universe, the entire galaxy, or the space-time of the entire star. Only the set S involved in the problem is required. For example, for the movement around the center of constancy, the region S that does not include the center of constancy can be selected.

There are special occasions when the central area is needed and the central point brings inconvenience. The central point can be simply "cut off" and the line that needs to cross the central point becomes two open intervals. Both sides are handled separately. Subjectively, the two parts are connected here. If integration is involved, piecewise integration is required and there are different integration constants. Without one (infinitesimal) point, one line, and one surface, in this theory, it does not matter to physical objects.

In some processing, the central point will destroy the topological invariance, and the unconnected points on the radial "parallel lines" will be connected here, thus the points around the center will have an additional connection path, so they need to be "cut off".

However, actually it has no influence on fuxi-equation, and only the topological relation of the actual problem itself is actually considered.

This λ represents a capture of the dynamic process and its uniformity. (Dynamics) λ will never flow backwards and always flows evenly.

This theorem provides the cornerstone for the theory of absolute opposition. This theorem is purely logical. Therefore, the general theory of relativity is in fact purely logical, which is the premise that Mr. Einstein can obtain only by ideological deduction. In this way, the equivalent principle of headache is unnecessary.

Here, with (dynamics) λ (phase) as the basic reference, a dynamics dimension is added. The whole problem becomes a 4+1 dimensional mathematical space problem.

Physics belongs to physics and mathematics to mathematics.

Mathematics is only a method and means for physics and is transparent and does not involve physical essence.

Isovolt-transformation is only a method for physics and has nothing to do with whether there is gravity or not and the essence of gravity.

Similarly, Riemannian geometry is only a method for physics and has nothing to do with whether there is gravity or not and the essence of gravity. **Substituting Riemannian geometry for physical essence is ideological confusion.** Isovolt-transformation will not be the case.

Property 1, Fuxi-value Proportion Invariance Theorem: Fuxi-value multiplied by a non-zero constant k remains equivalent.

$$\delta[d(kf)] = 0$$

Property 2, Fuxi-value Power Invariance theorem: Under the premise of meaningful and unchanged symbols, the fuxi-value remains equivalent by adding a non-zero power n .

$$\delta[df^n] = 0$$

(43) Thinking and Measuring Theorem

Knowledge acquired by pure thinking is named **think-or**.

The knowledge that must be measured is named the **measur-or**.

Think-ors form the world of pure thinking, which is marked as A. The world made up of measur-or that must be measured to be known is marked as B.

For a measur-or b_i , it is completely determined by B and completely independent of A. A cannot determine b_i .

Therefore, measur-or could not be acquired by pure thinking.

For a think-or a_i , it is completely determined by A and completely independent of B.

First of all, a_i is generally a continuous quantity and cannot be measured with absolute accuracy. Then a_i is actually not measurable. For example, the Pythagorean Theorem.

Secondly, a_i is generally an infinite range and cannot be exhaustively measured. Then a_i is actually not measurable. For example, the Pythagorean Theorem.

Thirdly, some think-ors are the rules of complete thinking and measurement is meaningless. Then a_i is actually not measurable.

Therefore, think-ors are not measurable.

Thinking and Measuring Theorem: Think-or could not be acquired by measuring and measur-or could not be acquired by pure thinking.

Meaning: The conclusion of pure thinking cannot be obtained by experimental measurement. The conclusion that needs actual measurement cannot be obtained by pure thinking.

For example, $1+1=2$ is pure thinking and cannot be proved or denied by experimental measurement. In reality, $1+1$ is equal to 2 or not.

For example, the weight of a Newton apple can only be measured actually, and cannot be obtained by pure thinking. For pure thinking, it is possible that the weight and not the weight, and neither violates the basic rules of pure thinking.

An interesting inference:

Pure Thinking Inference: The conclusion of pure thinking is definitely not a conclusion requiring actual measurement.

This is very unexpected. Because some of the previous conclusions that need to actually measure the world often feel unbreakable because they are drawn from pure thinking and believe that the world must be so. However, this inference holds that it must not be an actual conclusion that requires actual measurement of the world, precisely because it is arrived at through pure thinking; actually, it's just spinning in the mind.

For example, the uncertainty principle of quantum mechanics. It is pure thinking. Previously, people thought it was unbreakable and believed that it must be the case in the world where actual measurements are needed. In fact, it must not be a practical conclusion that requires actual measurement of the world. It is only a kind of pure thinking phase difference inequality.

For example, Bell inequality. It is pure thinking. Previously, people felt that it was unbreakable and used to verify the local real causality of quantum mechanics. In EPR experiments, there is no real causal relationship between the two objects. Just spinning in the mind. Therefore, the experiment is invalid.

Isn't there a lot of pure thinking in this article?

First of all, it made it clear from the beginning that this article is tautological.

Second, those conclusions are naturally pure thinking.

Third, some conclusions are only formal. There is another parameter. This parameter must come from actual measurement. This parameter has become the main switch to face the real measuring world. Such as gravity and coulomb force's conclusion.

(44) Cognitive World — End-atomic Mechanics Foundation

1) End-atomic Mechanics Foundation

Precisely, when we measure a mechanical quantity, there is always a period of time. Otherwise, it cannot be measured. For example, if the exposure time of the camera is too short, the correct picture cannot be taken.

Therefore, the measured physical value is not at a certain time. It should be a process.

Therefore, precisely, a process should be used to express a physical process.

Therefore, precisely, we should use a certain cumulative effect S process to express the physical process.

According to plan-yong-axiom, the fundamental task of Gezhi Physics is planning. So naturally, we must first measure the world to obtain the world's cognition.

Observation Process Noun: Observation is a process.

That is to say, we must use "**process thinking**" to study.

According to plan-yong-axiom, the fundamental task of Gezhi Physics is planning. Therefore, it must conform to the observation results.

Since observation is a process, its model is a process. Then the observed knowledge is also process model in the model. Therefore, the knowledge we use to accurately express the physical process itself must also be process model.

Process Lemma 1: Accurate expression of physical processes should be represented by procedures..

The **progress** of the standard process used to describe the process can be specified by a **scalar** phase characteristic value, named **soil-entropy** and denoted as S .

Due to meta-symmetry, the standard process used to describe the observation process has meta-symmetry, so its soil-entropy is constant.

Because of space-time symmetry, each space-time dimension is consistent. All dimensions of space and time should be treated in the same way.

The standard process of constant soil-entropy is used to describe the observation process

The observation process is described by the standard process of constant soil-entropy. This standard process is named **end-atom** and **holo-atom**, this constant is named **Planck constant** h . $h/(2\pi)$ is named as the **reduced Planck constant** \hbar . The world corresponding to end-atom is t-world.

The progress of the standard process describing the process actually uses a **dimensionless scalar** phase $S_p=S/\hbar$.

Process Lemma 2: Accurate representation of physical processes should be represented by a standard process of constant h soil-entropy.

Energy is the most important scalar physical quantity in mechanics. So here we study end-atomic mechanics from the starting perspective of energy; let it correspond to the non-directional basic rate of change $\partial S/\partial t$. The basis is the consistency theorem (the t-logical extension theorem).

Objects have macroscopic energy. According to yong-name-theorem, this value should be unchanged. So E is the microscopic invariant average observation of the end-atomic process. S can be measured from the perspective of E ; that is, E is the average observation of $-\partial S/\partial t$.

Therefore, macroscopically, E is the "average value" of $-\partial S/\partial t$ over the period T .

- ∴ E is the observed value of $-\partial S/\partial t$.
- ∴ $\partial S/\partial t$ has energy dimension.
- ∴ S has the dimension of energy•time, and the unit is joule second.
- ∴ $\partial S/\partial x$ has momentum dimension.
- ∴ $\partial S/\partial \theta$ has the dimension of energy•time, and the unit is joule second.

For the unit process, there is always $S=h$.

For a period T , the macroscopic observation E is regarded as a constant eigenvalue. E is the average value of $\partial S/\partial t$ in period T .

$$ET=S=h$$

$$\therefore E=h/T=h\nu=(h/2\pi)(2\pi\omega)=\hbar\omega$$

∴

$$E = h\nu = \hbar\omega$$

This is the **end-atom energy frequency formula**.

Macroscopically, it is the change of invariability. Microscopically, it is the invariability of change.

For a period T , corresponding to the nominal wavelength λ , and for the macroscopic observation momentum p , it is regarded as a constant eigenvalue. p is the average value of $\partial S/\partial q$ in the period T , that is, wavelength λ .

$$p\lambda=S=h$$

$$p=h/\lambda$$

∴

$$p = h / \lambda$$

This is the **end-atom momentum wavelength formula**.

Macroscopically, it is the change of invariability. Microscopically, it is the invariability of change.

Momentum operator:

$$\hat{p} \equiv -i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial q}$$

Energy operator:

$$\hat{E} \equiv i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t}$$

Based on the intrinsic displacement q , therefore

Displacement operator:

$$\hat{q} = q$$

This way of describing the intrinsic displacement of the basis is named **Schrodinger picture**.

2) Distribution, Character, End-atomic Topological Wave Theorem

Due to the conflict of many symmetries in end-atom mechanics, it is obvious in geometric diffusion. Distribution and characters are used to satisfy these symmetries respectively.

As the most basic model to describe the world, it should have spatial directional meta-symmetry. Its distribution has spatial geometric diffusion.

As the most basic model to describe the world, it should have the logical ability to broadcast itself from near to far to be perceived, and this characteristic is named **adjacent infectivity**.

For material causes, the end-atom has spatial geometric diffusion and complete angular meta-symmetry. The size, energy totality and charge of the object will change in diffusion, translate along the radial direction, become thinner as the volume becomes larger, and change inversely with the volume. Does not satisfy the complete coordinate axis translational symmetry, and volume changes in reverse. These correspond to local formal causes. When space spreads, it spreads out like waves, showing the spread of fluctuations. This kind of inflexibility (elasticity), under the action of adjacent infectivity, is manifested as delaying potential and forming fluctuation.

The basic solution of the end-atom can only be the sinusoidal wave solution that can stably propagate. Generally speaking, it is the same, like a uniform straight line, ensuring stable transmission and satisfying yong-name-theorem. Microscopically, it fluctuates and changes according to sine wave to ensure that the adjacent infectivity is satisfied.

According to the exponential form function $e^{iS/\hbar}$ variation, the characteristic of Planck constant corresponding to each phase period is named as **end-atom-phase-nature**.

The spatial geometric diffusibility, adjacent infectivity, and end-atom-phase-nature of this distribution are named **logical-wave-nature**.

Objects, such as photons, diffuse along the radial direction. According to yong-name-theorem, they should remain unchanged. A photon is still that photon; its property is that property. Therefore, for characters, some character models of objects prohibit spatial geometric diffusion and require translational symmetry. End-atom is the basic model of an object. Some end-atom properties, which are the properties of an object, should naturally prohibit the spatial geometric diffusion and require translational symmetry.

Some end-atom properties prohibit the spatial geometric diffusion, prohibit the complete angle system symmetry, and require translational symmetry. The color, frequency, energy and momentum internality of the end-atom translate along the radial direction and remain unchanged during diffusion. Meet the translational symmetry of the coordinate axis. The system properties remain unchanged after translation. These correspond to global formal causes. When moving in space, like a solid bullet.

Due to the end-atom model, $E=h\nu$, $p=h/\lambda$, E and p remain unchanged in spatial geometric diffusion.

The non-spatial geometric diffusion and translational symmetry of this intrinsic energy, momentum and other attributes are named **logical-particle-nature**. They have nothing to do with the intensity of the wave (it is **topological**), and remain unchanged in space diffusion.

End-atomic Logical Wave-Particle Duality Theorem: End-atom has both logical-wave-nature and logical-particle-nature in logic. This is a kind of internal logic, itself is not a real wave and a real particle.

Let's not talk about whether end-atom and light are waves or particles. This is for itself. The expression pattern is "A is waves, A is particle"; this violates the law of contradiction. There are profound problems in expressing logical forms. The principle of complementarity also has this problem. The principle of complementarity embodies vulgar applicability and cannot be regarded as a physical theory with strict logic. The fundamental reason for this chaotic description mode is that the internal logical relationship is not clarified.

However, it should be said that end-atom and photon have logical-wave-nature and logical-particle-nature. This is for different attributes. Its expression mode is "B is logical-wave-nature, C is logical-particle-nature"; this will not violate the law of contradiction.

This logical-particle-nature is actually a topological property. End-atoms can be called **topological waves** and have **topological volatility**. This is more pleasant to the ear. Its expression mode is "A is a topological wave"; this naturally does not violate the law of contradiction.

End-atomic Topological Wave Theorem: An end-atom is logically a topological wave with topological volatility.

In fact, a better and more accurate understanding of this logic fluctuation is topological diffusion. See end-atom topological diffusion theory.

3) Right-material-cause

The scale of an object reflects the **material-cause** of logic. Ψ in the end-atom right wave equation corresponds to the material-cause, also known as **right-material-cause**, also known as the **right**.

Right-material-cause itself regulates the immortality of matter, that is, the conservation of material-cause; therefore, the right-material-cause does not need any further normalization and normalization is not allowed.

Right-material-cause is also called qi in visual image. Qi also expresses locality, reality and certainty.

To say that the material cause is mainly a matter on the surface of logic, which mainly reflects such a relationship: the number of material causes corresponds to the number of end-atom, and the end-atom is gone without material cause. It is just like how many steamed buns there are corresponding to how many material cause of steamed buns there are; there will be no steamed buns without material cause of steamed buns.

Normalization is not allowed, but the total amount can be equivalently specified as 1 unit.

The end-atomic model describes the form and corresponds to the formal cause.

Ψ describes the material and corresponds to the material cause.

As a form, end-atom has nothing to do with the amount of material cause. No matter how much, even if the amount is infinitesimal, it is still that form. But in physics, once the infinitesimal amount of material is negligible, it is completely ignored.

Figure 9 Schematic diagram of right-material-cause

The end-atom, as a form, has nothing to do with the amount of material-cause. It can be seen that the end-atom in actual physics can also be infinitely separable. All children are divided by right-material-cause.

A certain amount of "modular square of right Ψ " is named as the **right-square**. The right-square is not limited to the unit volume.

4) Measuring the World Theorem

Measurement is actually an affected process. We don't know what the world is like. Only the final influence $\Psi(q',t')$ of the world upon measurement can be known. It includes the influence of all points (q,t) in the world. This effect can be nominally seen as $\Psi(q,t)$ in the influence factor $K(q',t';q,t)$.

The influence factors of different nominal action positions (q,t) on Ψ of points (q',t') in whole space are $K(q',t';q,t)$, the total space accumulation is $\Psi(q',t')$.

So there are

Measuring the World Theorem: All object measured is actually the whole world.

Since the object of measurement is the whole world, the total material quantity is the whole world. So the total material quantity $C \equiv 1$.

The measurement window is $(q',t';f)$. f represents the measurement method and the corresponding type of

action. Because the object is the whole world, only right Ψ can be used to distinguish them.

The whole world is measured from (q',t') in f mode, and the measured right is $\Psi(q',t')$. Measured from (q',t') , but the measured is the total effect of the right $\Psi(q,t)d\tau$ to (q',t') of the volume element $d\tau$ at (q,t) all over the world.

Ψ corresponds to the number of end-atoms. In our thinking, the attributes of matter have nothing to do with their quantity. Therefore, the physical quantity of an end-atom's attribute is independent of the intensity of Ψ ; it is the topological quantity. The variation characteristic physical quantity is represented by a dimensionless $\partial\Psi/\Psi$.

In addition, the definition of, the mechanical properties of the variation of atomic distribution($\partial\Psi$), that is, the mechanical properties of any $\Psi(q,t)$ for $\Psi(q',t')$, is for any Ψ . It has metasymmetry for Ψ . Therefore, it can only contain no dimension of Ψ .

When measuring the mechanical properties of any $\Psi(q,t)$ for $\Psi(q',t')$, logically, $\Psi(q,t)$ is used as the measurement charge. Therefore, the unit measurement charge corresponding quantity should be obtained. So it need to divide by $\Psi(q,t)$. So we use dimensionless $\partial\Psi/\Psi$. Therefore, it can only contain no dimension of Ψ .

Due to space meta-symmetry, the whole space needs to be integrated in the same way.

Due to time meta-symmetry, the temporal evolution rule does not depend on a specific time point, and always evolves according to this rule.

That is, the influence factors from (q,t) to (q',t') are consistent $K(q',t';q,t)$. In this way, the influence right of right element $\Psi(q,t)d\tau$ to (q',t') at (q,t) is $K(q',t';q,t)\Psi(q,t)d\tau$. The accumulated right is $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K(q',t';q,t)\Psi(q,t)d\tau$, which is the measured right $\Psi(q',t')$. $t'=t+dt$.

$$\Psi(q',t+dt) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K(q',t+dt;q,t)\Psi(q,t)d\tau$$

Of course, as a useful measure, $(q',t';f)$ is selected, has a strong locality, logically can be used as something related to the local area, so in practice can be used to represent the role of a local object. As will be seen from the following calculation, only when the deviation η approaches 0 will there be a significant contribution.

Then, on the other hand, from the perspective of measurement, the so-called measured objects are only the local measurement representation of the whole world.

The object corresponding to the locality measurement representation of the whole world is named **right-object**.

World Object Theorem: The measured object is the local measurement representation of the whole world.

That is to say, intellectually, actually and intuitively, the object is the right-object of the right, not the right is the right of the object. Object is subordinate to right, not right to object.

Measurement is a measurement of the whole world and includes all space-time points. Therefore, formally, measurements and objects contain holographic information of the world. However, due to the lack of commitment to its changing relationship, it cannot be predicted. The influence right of each part is also different; also cannot decompose each part influence, is only a confusion final result; therefore, there is no practical significance of holography. This kind of pseudo-holography gives people the feeling of spontaneity in space and chaos in time if they are not careful.

Pseudo-holographic Theorem: Formally measured results and measured objects contain holographic information from all over the world.

This is actually "evolutionary thinking".

Figure 10 Schematic diagram of measuring the world theorem

5) Fundamentals and Verification Methods of End-atom

End-atom is a kind of thinking entity that is constructed reversely according to the logical norm of observing the world with the result of the v-world; on the other hand, we can infer the observation phenomena and evolution of the v-world from the same logical norm and the same causal thinking; so as to complete the fundamental task of physics.

Although it is only a thinking entity. However, it can deduce the result phase that the mind can freely choose, which is observed and tested by us — the method of authenticity verification. The important thing is that it can really help us plan.

6) End-atomic Self-superposition

The substructure is logically consistent with recursion. According to the distribution, the real end-atom can be seen as the distribution of many microscopic end-atoms, which are superimposed according to the superposition logic of end-atoms themselves. This is called **End-atomic self-superposition**.

Therefore, end-atoms in reality are actually self-superposing.

Real end-atoms can be divided into smaller end-atoms.

When the reality of macro objects, divided into end-atoms, it is also self-consistent, and there will be no contradictions.

Only this road needs too much information.

Therefore, the reality is a much simpler way — starting a new stove. Directly from the macro level to describe. Thus, a macro firewall has been formed.

There is no contradiction, but most of them said their own things.

7) Eigenvalue and Its Significance

For operator \hat{A} , if there is a value λ such that,

$$\hat{A}\Psi = \lambda\Psi$$

Then the value λ is named the **eigenvalue** of the operator \hat{A} .

It can be seen that end-atom is a thinking entity constructed according to logic in thinking according to v-world. Therefore, priority must be given to meeting the v-world's observations, that is, the value of mechanical quantity. At the same time, the value of mechanical quantity must be a real number, not a complex number that is not a real number.

So there are,

Eigenvalue Theorem: The value of any mechanical name is the eigenvalue of its corresponding operator.

For non-numeric operators, most values are not real numbers; this is because end-atom is a thinking entity. These values have no real physical meaning. Its indirect physical meaning lies in prediction and planning. That is, by this logic model, we can do these things.

8) End-atomic Topological Operator, End-atomic Topological Quantity

For end-atomic operator \hat{A} , there are the following relations in pure form.

$$\hat{A} = \hat{A}\Psi/\Psi$$

For the linear end-atomic operator \hat{A} , on the right, Ψ appears in both the denominator and the numerator, and the result is independent of the intensity of Ψ . Thus the end-atomic operator \hat{A} is purely topological and is named the **end-atomic topological operator**.

$$\text{momentum operator: } \hat{p} = -i\hbar\nabla\Psi/\Psi = -i\hbar\left(\frac{\partial\Psi/\Psi}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial\Psi/\Psi}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial\Psi/\Psi}{\partial z}\right)$$

$$\text{energy operator: } \hat{E} = i\hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial t}\Psi/\Psi = i\hbar\frac{\partial\Psi/\Psi}{\partial t}$$

The expected value of the end-atomic topological operator \hat{A} is named **end-atomic topological macro quantity** and **end-atomic topological macro property**. Obviously, the end-atomic topological macro quantity is also topological. Such as p and E .

$$p = \overline{\hat{p}}$$

$$E = \overline{\hat{E}}$$

The eigenvalue of the end-atomic topological operator λ is named as **end-atomic topological quantity** and **end-atomic topological property**. The atomic topology quantities are also topological. End-atomic topological macro quantities and atomic topological quantities are real physical quantities.

$$\lambda \equiv \hat{A}\Psi/\Psi$$

According to the consistency theorem (the t-logical extension theorem), there is no substantial difference between the two, and they are merged into end-atomic topological quantities.

9) End-atomic Field

End-atom is not an infinitesimal point. Every end-atom has its space-time distribution. The physical space-time distribution of the real end-atom is named **end-atomic field**. The interaction between end-atoms and the outside world is actually the interaction between the end-atomic field and the outside world. End-atomic fields are topological.

10) End-atomic Multipoint Triggering

The real end-atom is an end-atomic field with space-time distribution. Many points on the end-atomic field can interact with the outside world at the same time, which is called **end-atomic multipoint triggering**.

End-atomic Multipoint Triggering Theorem: Many points on the end-atomic field of the real end-atom can act with the outside world at the same time.

End-atomic multipoint triggering is a characteristic completely absent from point particle model. The multi-point triggering of end-atoms leads to the perception of spontaneity in the particle model, which can be

instantaneously located in distant places. Therefore, there are:

End-atomic Distance Action Theorem: The real end-atom can act on different objects far away in an instant.

11) Pseudo holographic effect Theorem

Because the end-atom based on observation logic is the smallest model to describe the world. And this model has a minimal space-time restriction logic.

Therefore, the model itself is described as a whole and its interior is indistinguishable. Its corresponding space-time is also indistinguishable. That is to say, it is regarded as a point.

But in fact, it has real time and space. Therefore, the actual space-time is projected to a space-time point. It's like a holographic effect. This effect is named **pseudo holographic effect**. So there are,

Pseudo-holographic Effect Theorem: The actual space-time of the end-atom is projected to a space-time point and pseudo-holographic effect occurs.

In terms of time, the process does not take time, that is, the time difference is zero.

In space, it doesn't take time to appear in distant places, and mysteriously appear and disappear.

12) Meta-symmetry of End-atoms

In the meta-symmetry space-time, the meta-symmetry of end-atoms is as follows.

- 1> Meta-symmetry to spatial coordinates.
- 2> Meta-symmetry ($\pm x$) to the direction of spatial coordinates.
- 3> Meta-symmetry to spatial angular direction.
- 4> Meta-symmetry for time coordinates.

13) End-atomic Non-repeatability Theorem

End-atoms face the primitive world and therefore cannot give repeatability. End-atoms are not related to each other at the end of understanding, so it is impossible to judge identity. Even if it is the same, intellectuality cannot be judged as the same.

End-atomic Non-Repeatability Theorem: End-atoms are intellectually unrepeatably.

The real meaning is the lack of knowledge, "people don't know it at all."

14) Macro Repeatability

End-atoms face the primitive world and cannot give repeatability. The macro world obtained by macro redefinition is subjective by macro redefinition. Therefore, the subjective macro world can be endowed with repetitiveness subjectively.

Macroscopic Repeatability Theorem: Macroscopic world can be repeated intellectually.

15) End-atomic No-cloning Theorem

Because of the end-atomic non-repeatability theorem, it is intellectually impossible to clone an end-atom. Even if it is the same, intellectuality cannot be judged as the same.

End-atomic Non-cloning Theorem: End-atoms cannot be cloned intellectually.

This is only for theoretical deduction.

The real meaning is the lack of knowledge, "people don't know it at all." Of course, people cannot confirm that something they do not know has been cloned.

This conclusion has no practical guarantee. To the specific end-atom, "end-atom" is only a name. When people can know it technically, it will not be at the end of cognition, it will not be end-atom and will not be guaranteed by this conclusion.

It is only periodic.

16) Macroscopical Measurability Theorem

End-atoms face the primitive world and cannot give repeatability. The macro world obtained by macro redefinition is subjective by macro redefinition. Therefore, the subjective macro world can be endowed with repeatability. Repeatability leads to accurate measurement of position and momentum (speed) respectively, and it is absolutely accurate measurement.

Macroscopical Measurability Theorem: Repetitive macroscopic measurements are not restricted by simultaneity.

17) Element Group

The most basic information describing a physical system is named **primitive element**. It contains at least three physical elements and generally consists of one or several groups of three elements.

All other quantities in the system can be calculated by primitive element.

The set of primitives is named **primitive element group**.

Naming of **element group**:

1) primitive element group is element group.

2) Variables calculated by the same operator from the same number of primitives belong to the same element group. For example $\{p_x, p_y, p_z\}$.

3) The variables obtained from the partial derivatives of variables of the same element group to primitives (denominator index can be different, excluding the primitive representing "what") belong to the same element group. For example $\{p_x, p_y, p_z, E\}$. Two groups of the same element groups are correspondingly used to obtain partial derivatives.

Such as m or Ψ , q and t .

Element groups are characterized by simultaneous measurement without rejection.

If a quantity is obtained by the difference or averaging or summing of multiple groups of primitives, then there is a **generation difference** between them and the original element group. This relationship can be expressed by **phase**. Difference or derivation **leads**, averaging or integration or summation **lags**. Derivation lead phase by $\pi/2$, and it is multiplied by an $e^{i\pi/2}$, and there is an i indication in the operator.

For example, m or Ψ , q and t are in primitive elements.

speed: $v=(q_2-q_1)/(t_2-t_1)$

2 primitive element group are required. So there is a generation difference.

Therefore, speed v is the difference of q ; relative m or Ψ , q and t have generation difference, and the phase is $\pi/2$ ahead.

momentum: $p=m(q_2-q_1)/(t_2-t_1)$

Therefore, momentum p is the difference of q ; relative m or Ψ , q and t have generation difference, and the

phase is $\pi/2$ ahead.

Momentum operator

$$\hat{p} \Psi = -i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \Psi$$

Energy operator

$$\hat{E} \Psi = i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi$$

Derivation is involved here, so there are generation differences and phase differences between momentum operators and energy operators. The negative sign above corresponds to the delayed potential relation.

18) Phase Problem — Fixed Fallacy of Flying Arrows Without Moving

Zeno asked his students, "Is a shot arrow moving or not?"

"It is needless to say, of course it is moving."

"Indeed, in everyone's eyes it is moving. However, does this arrow have its place in every instant? "

"Yes, teacher."

"At this moment, does it occupy the same space as its volume?" "It has a definite position and occupies the same space as its own volume." "So, in this instant, is this arrow moving or not?"

"Don't move, teacher."

"At this moment is motionless, then other moments?"

"Still, teacher."

"So, the arrow that goes out does not move?"

There is a fundamental mistake here. *"There is a definite position ... in this instant, is this arrow moving or not moving?"*

In the position-based description (q description), the motility-or-immobility can only be presented by comparing the positions of two different instants. That is, two moments, judging the characteristics of this period of history between these two moments. If the same it is not moving; if not the same it is moving. Rather than the characteristics of a moment. Therefore, strictly logically, there is no point in "moving and static" for an instant.

Of course, in reality, on the premise that the requirements are not high and do not lead to erroneous conclusions, it is still possible to say whether a certain moment is moving or not, for the sake of simplicity. This is just for convenience. Strict reasoning cannot be said so. Especially when saying so will lead to wrong conclusions, we must not say so. Static and dynamic properties and positions do not have equal element-group-properties.

Similarly, in the position-based description (q description) mode, the speed and momentum are not the values of a certain moment. Speed and position do not have equal element-group-properties.

Correspondingly, in the momentum-based description (p description) mode, there is no actual definition of position; speed and position do not have equal element-group-properties.

We just construct the corresponding operators.

There is a phase difference between speed and position.

Later, we see the i corresponding to this phase difference. " i " means that when the position is measurable, it is logically not available from a group of observations. They do not have equal element-group-properties.

Moreover, logically, this phase difference can evolve into two-law-antinomy. The motion-or-immobility has been defined by the primitive q . In addition, the independent reference to the motility-or-immobility being-what-it-is, lead to redefinition. The two definitions violated two-law-antinomy.

19) The Root of End-atomic Problem

1>

The root of the end-atomic problem is the conflict of many symmetries. It is obvious in geometric diffusion.

End-atoms should satisfy the translational symmetry of rectangular coordinate system. But also to satisfy the translational symmetry of angular coordinates.

In macro experience, these two symmetries cannot be satisfied at the same time.

Therefore, people always feel wrong when facing end-atom with macro experience.

2>

Perceiving the source knowledge of the external world actually corresponds to a process. The corresponding description model should be a process, that is, a process is used to describe the process. There is a $TE=p\lambda=h$ constraint.

This is very different from the simplified macro common sense.

3>

End-atoms in the v-world and t-world meet the change of invariability.

End-atoms in the t-world meet the invariability of change.

Finally, $(\partial\Psi/\Psi)/\partial q=\text{constant}$. End-atoms are topological.

(45) Fundamental Mechanics of Mechanics Meta-space-time Representation

Redefining a space-time representation in mechanics element. Because it is an independent redefinition, it has meta-symmetry. The biggest characteristic is meta-symmetry.

Only in the mechanics meta-space-time representation can there be a normative and complete mechanics norm.

The scale of the moving object in the dynamic meta-space-time representation is named **meta-inertial-mass** m_0 , also known as **static-mass** m_0 .

In the dynamic meta-space-time representation, the meta-inertial-mass is the basic quantity, which has meta-symmetry and invariance. Therefore, it has nothing to do with changes in speed, acceleration position, latitude, pressure, temperature, etc. $dm_0/dv = 0$, $dm_0/da = 0$.

The scale of the moving object in the common space-time representation is named **inertial-mass** m , also called **dynamic-mass** m . $m = m_0$ in the mechanics meta-spatio-time representation.

The rate of change of object position is named **speed** v . $v = dx/dt$.

The scale of object motion, that is, the product of speed and inertial mass, is named **momentum** p . In the common space-time representation, $p = mv$. In the dynamic meta-space-time representation, $p = mv = m_0v$.

The cause of momentum change named **impulse** I . $I = \Delta p$.

The change rate of impulse is named **force** F . $F = dI/dt$. $I = F\Delta t$.

According to the definition, the amount of momentum a body changes must be defined as the amount of impulse it has.

Momentum theorem: momentum increment is equal to impulse made by external force. $\Delta p = I$. This is derived from the definition of impulse (or force).

∴ According to the definition of impulse, there is $\Delta p = I$.

∴ if $I = 0$.

∴ $\Delta p = I = 0$.

On the other hand, it is understood that if the momentum changes, then according to the definition, a

non-zero impulse should be defined for the object.

Momentum Conservation Theorem: The momentum of a body will remain unchanged when it is not affected by impulse. This is derived from the definition of impulse (or force).

∴ In mechanics meta-spatio-time representation, $\Delta \mathbf{p} = \Delta(m_0 \mathbf{v}) = m_0 \Delta \mathbf{v} = \mathbf{I} = 0$

∴ $\Delta \mathbf{v} = 0$

$\Delta \mathbf{v} = 0$ means that the object moves in a straight line at a constant speed.

On the other hand, it is understood that if the speed changes, the momentum changes, then by definition, a non-zero impulse should be defined for the object.

Mechanics Meta-space-time Inertia Theorem(Newton First Theorem): The object in the mechanics meta-time-space representation keeps uniform linear motion without external impulse (force).

The dot product of impulse and speed is named **work** A . $A = \mathbf{I} \cdot \mathbf{v} = \mathbf{F} \cdot \Delta \mathbf{s}$. Work is equal to the dot product of force and displacement.

Corresponding to work. The dot product of momentum increment and speed is named **kinetic energy** increment ΔT , and the kinetic energy is 0 when the speed is 0. $\Delta T = \Delta \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{v}$.

$$A = \mathbf{I} \cdot \mathbf{v} = \Delta \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{v} = \Delta T$$

Work-Energy theorem: kinetic energy increment is equal to work done by external force. $\Delta T = A$. Here the potential energy is lost from the point of view of force.

if $A = 0$, $\Delta T = A = 0$.

On the other hand, it is understood that if the kinetic energy changes, then by definition, a non-zero work should be given to the object.

Kinetic Energy Conservation Theorem: The kinetic energy of an object will remain unchanged when it is not subjected to external work. $\Delta T = 0$. Here, the potential energy is lost from the point of view of force.

Referring to the work-energy theorem, the inverse number of work of the potential force is named **potential energy** increment ΔE_p . $\Delta E_p = -A = -\mathbf{I} \cdot \mathbf{v} = -\mathbf{F} \cdot \Delta \mathbf{s}$.

Potential energy and kinetic energy are collectively called **mechanical energy** E . $\Delta E = \Delta E_k + \Delta E_p$.

∴ only under the action of potential force,

potential energy: $\Delta E_p = -A$

kinetic energy: $\Delta T = \Delta E_k$

substitution: $A = \Delta T$

∴ $\Delta E = \Delta E_k + \Delta E_p = 0$

Mechanical Energy Conservation theorem: $\Delta E = \Delta E_k + \Delta E_p = 0$

The rate of change of work is named **power** P . $P = dA/dt = (\mathbf{F} \cdot \Delta \mathbf{s})/dt = \mathbf{F} \cdot \mathbf{v}$.

∴ In mechanics meta-space-time representation, $dm_0 = 0$

$\mathbf{F} = d\mathbf{I}/dt = d(m_0 \mathbf{v})/dt = v dm_0/dt + m_0 dv/dt = 0 + m_0 \mathbf{a} = m_0 \mathbf{a} = m \mathbf{a}$

More generally,

$\mathbf{F} = d\mathbf{I}/dt = d(\gamma m_0 \mathbf{v})/dt = \gamma v dm_0/dt + \gamma m_0 dv/dt = 0 + \gamma m_0 \mathbf{a} = m \mathbf{a}$

Variable Speed Theorem(Newton Second Theorem): $\mathbf{F} = m \mathbf{a}$.

The cross product of the vector diameter and momentum of a rotating object is named the **momentum moment L** , also known as **angular momentum**. $L=r \times p$

The ratio of the total moment of momentum of a rigid body to angular speed is named as the **rotational inertia (moment inertia) J** of the rigid body to the axis of rotation. $J=L/\omega$

The cross product of the vector diameter and impulse of a rotating object is named **impulse moment N** . $N=r \times I$

The change rate of impulse moment is named **torque M** . $M=dN/dt=r \times F$

The force and reaction force between the two particles are internal forces $F_1^{(i)}$ 、 $F_2^{(i)}$.

According to our thinking logic, if we look at the whole, the total impulse is the total external impulse, thus, $dI^{(e)}=dp$

\therefore Impulse effect of internal force: $dI^{(i)}=dp-dI^{(e)}=0$

This is because the change of momentum dp is logically attributed to the external force impulse $dI^{(e)}$. The internal force impulse effect can only be 0.

$\therefore dI^{(i)}/dt=0$

$\therefore F_1^{(i)}+F_2^{(i)}=0$

$\therefore F_2^{(i)}=-F_1^{(i)}$

$\therefore F_1^{(i)}$ and $F_2^{(i)}$ parallel to each other, in opposite directions.

According to our thinking logic, if we look at the overall situation, the total impulse moment is the total external force impulse moment, with $dN^{(e)}=dN$.

\therefore Impulse moment effect of internal force: $dN^{(i)}=dN-dN^{(e)}=0$

This is because the change of the moment of momentum dL is logically attributed to the $dN^{(e)}$ of the external impulse moment. The impulse moment of internal force can only be 0.

$\therefore M^{(i)}=dN^{(i)}/dt=0$

$\therefore F_2^{(i)}=-F_1^{(i)}$

$\therefore M^{(i)}=M_1^{(i)}+M_2^{(i)}=r_1 \times F_1^{(i)}+r_2 \times F_2^{(i)}=r_1 \times F_1^{(i)}-r_2 \times F_1^{(i)}=(r_1-r_2) \times F_1^{(i)}=d^{(i)} \times F_1^{(i)}=0$

\therefore Its size: $M^{(i)}=d^{(i)} \times F_1^{(i)}=0$

$\therefore d^{(i)}=0$. The distance $d^{(i)}$ between the lines of action of the two forces is 0. They are in a straight line.

Mechanics Meta-Space-Time Reaction Theorem(Newton Third Theorem): In the mechanics meta-space-time representation, the force and reaction force are equal in magnitude and opposite in direction, acting on a straight line.

Calculation of Momentum Moment :

$$L_o = \sum_{i=1}^n M_o(m_i v_i) = \sum_{i=1}^n (r_i \times m_i v_i)$$

Momentum Moment of a Translational Rigid Body to a Fixed Point:

$$L_o = \sum_{i=1}^n M_o(m_i r_c) \times v_i = r_c \times \sum_{i=1}^n (m_i v_c)$$

Momentum Moment of Fixed Axis Rotating Rigid Body to Fixed Axis:

$$L_z = J_z \omega$$

Momentum Moment of a Translational Rigid Body to a Fixed Point O :

$$\mathbf{L}_o = \mathbf{L}_c + \mathbf{r}_c \times m\mathbf{v}_c$$

$$d(\mathbf{L}(m\mathbf{v}))=d(\mathbf{r} \times m\mathbf{v})=\mathbf{r} \times d(m\mathbf{v})=\mathbf{r} \times d\mathbf{I}=\mathbf{r} \times d(\mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{I})=d\mathbf{N}$$

Momentum Moment Theorem: Momentum moment increment is equal to impulse moment of external force. $d(\mathbf{L}(m\mathbf{v}))=d\mathbf{N}$

$$d(\mathbf{L}_o(m\mathbf{v}))=d(\mathbf{r} \times m\mathbf{v})=\mathbf{r} \times d(m\mathbf{v})=\mathbf{r} \times d(\mathbf{p})=d\mathbf{N}_o(\mathbf{F})$$

$$d(\mathbf{L}_o(m\mathbf{v}))/dt=d\mathbf{N}_o(\mathbf{F})/dt=\mathbf{M}_o(\mathbf{F})$$

According to our thinking logic, if we look at the overall situation, the total impulse moment is the total external force impulse moment, with $d\mathbf{L}_o=d\mathbf{N}_o^{(e)}$, $d\mathbf{L}_o/dt=d\mathbf{M}_o^{(e)}$.

Particle System Momentum Moment Theorem:

$$d\mathbf{L}_o = d\mathbf{N}_o^{(e)}$$

$$d\mathbf{L}_o / dt = \mathbf{M}_o^{(e)}$$

If the impulse moment of the external force is 0, $d\mathbf{N}_o^{(e)}=0$

Then, $d(\mathbf{L}_o(m\mathbf{v}))=d\mathbf{N}_o^{(e)}=0$

Momentum Moment Conservation Theorem: When the impulse moment of external force is 0, the momentum moment is conserved.

Theorem of Momentum Moment of Particle System Relative to Centroid:

$$d\mathbf{L}_c / dt = \mathbf{M}_c^{(e)}$$

$$\mathbf{M}_z(\mathbf{F})=d\mathbf{L}_z/dt=d(\mathbf{J}_z \omega)/dt=\mathbf{J}_z (d\omega/dt)=\mathbf{J}_z \ddot{\varphi}$$

Differential equation of rigid body around fixed axis of rotation:

$$\mathbf{J}_z \ddot{\varphi} = \sum \mathbf{M}_z(\mathbf{F})$$

$$\mathbf{M}_c(\mathbf{F})=d\mathbf{L}_c/dt=d(\mathbf{J}_c \omega)/dt=\mathbf{J}_c (d\omega/dt)=\mathbf{J}_c \ddot{\varphi}$$

Differential Equations of Plane Motion of Rigid Bodies;

$$m_0 \ddot{x}_c = \sum \mathbf{F}_x$$

$$m_0 \ddot{y}_c = \sum \mathbf{F}_y$$

$$\mathbf{J}_c \ddot{\varphi} = \sum \mathbf{M}_c(\mathbf{F})$$

(46) Gezhi Thermodynamics Fundamentals

According to plan-yong-axiom, the fundamental task of Gezhi Physics is planning. Then the logic is that planning must be trying to maintain the state or push the state to get better, otherwise the state will get worse.

If don't work hard, the state will deteriorate or change reversibly. This bad effect is named **disorder**, and its index is named **entropy**, which specifies that the entropy of irreversible transformation is increased. On the contrary, good effectiveness is named **orderliness**.

The world that will deteriorate or reversibly change without hard work is named as the **non-life world**, otherwise it is named as the **life world**.

By definition, the entropy of an isolated system will never automatically decrease in the non-life period.

For the invertible process A, its entropy is constant in the non-life period.

Otherwise, suppose that it is variable, $A \neq 0$, then it can only be increased, $A > 0$.

The entropy of its inverse B is not reduced. That is, $B > 0$.

Thus, $A+B > 0$

The whole process $C=A+B$, back to the starting state. The entropy of C is constant. That is, $C=0$.

Therefore,

$A+B=0$

Contradiction. Q.E.D.

According to the definition, the entropy of irreversible process A increases in the non-life period.

Gezhi Entropy Increase Theorem: In the non-life of the system, the entropy of an isolated system will never automatically decrease, and the entropy will not change in the reversible process but will increase in the irreversible process.

From the above, on the contrary, entropy can be reduced "automatically" in life. The key is that in this equivalent narration, the third person is adopted, and this effort of life is depicted as internalized "automatic". For example, the growth of human beings and bacteria.

Basically, this is only a matter of perspective. This is the result of looking at the world from the specific perspective of "human planning".

The world itself contains all 3 possibilities: entropy increases, entropy is constant, and entropy is reduced.

The world itself does not have this perspective. In short, this describes a filtered world, not the original world. To put it another way, this is actually only a description of "human planning", not a description of the world. This directivity comes from the directivity of "human planning". For the future, there is no need to worry about the sky.

(47) Mathematical Tools

1) Yin-Yang Numbers and Their Physically Meaningful Application Models

"Yin-yang thinking" corresponds to "evolutionary thinking". In "evolutionary thinking", only the state of the subject object is evolving; the subject object A itself is unchanged; A is always A.

"State evolution", in the formal logic, deducted to the extreme, is the evolution of the two "states" of pure form; the two "states" of pure form are named **Yin** and **Yang**.

The progress of the evolution of the two pure "states" (Yin and Yang) can be represented by only one indicator, corresponding to the phase angle θ . It can be seen that yin-yang is the limit of the simplest model of motion change; only one dimension is needed. It greatly simplified the physical model. The physical meaning of Lagrangian and Hamiltonian can also be derived from "evolutionary thinking".

1> Arithmetic Integral Operator $i()$ and Yin-Number

"Evolutionary thinking" corresponds to the idea of integration. The latter state Ψ' can be seen as the previous state Ψ plus the amount of change $\Delta\Psi$: $\Psi'=\Psi+\Delta\Psi$.

Consider circular motion:

$$x=A\cos(\theta)$$

Derivative of x :

$$x'=-A\sin(\theta)$$

When $\theta=\pi/2$, $x=A\cos(\pi/2)=0$, $x'=-A\sin(\pi/2)=-A$.

At this point $x=0$. But it's different from stopping there with $x=0$. At this time, $x'=-A$ means that the trend of x is the largest. The variation trend of x is not 0, and the variation trend is different.

In order to express the complementary relation of unity, x' takes the inverse number $z=-x'=A\sin(\theta)$, $x'=-z$. $z'=A\cos(\theta)$.

In a method of understanding the world, the part x that is displayed and the part that is not yet displayed are treated as a whole, highlighting its yin-yang integrity, yin-yang convertibility, dynamics and overall invariance.

The numerical value corresponding to the part of x that has already appeared is named **yang number**.

This complementary change trend is named **yin number**.

The concept that yin number and yang number are perfectly round unity is named **yin-yang number**.

Here, the positive part corresponds to $A\cos(\theta)$ and the negative part corresponds to $A\sin(\theta)$.

When $A=1$ and $\theta=0$, the yin-yang number is 1. When $\theta=\pi/2$, the yin number part is 0, and there is only the yang number part. The status at this time is recorded as $i(1)$. For convenience, the yin-number corresponding to θ is written as follows:

$$\Psi(z(\theta)) = \Psi(\sin(\theta)) = \Psi(0 + \int_0^\theta z' d\theta) = \Psi(\int_0^\theta z' d\theta)$$

$i(\theta)$ is named **arithmetic integration operator**, and its basic meaning is to re-integrate $\pi/2$. It is the arithmetization of calculus. Physically, it means that the phase advances by $\pi/2$ (1/4 period). **Specify** $i(0)=1$.

According to the arithmetic integral operator calculation is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} i(1) &= i(0) + \int_0^{\pi/2} (x') d\theta + \Psi(\int_0^{\pi/2} (z') d\theta) \\ &= 1 + \int_0^{\pi/2} (-\sin(\theta)) d\theta + \Psi(\int_0^{\pi/2} (\cos(\theta)) d\theta) \\ &= 1 + (-1) + \Psi(\sin(\pi/2)) = \Psi(z(\pi/2)) \\ &= \Psi(\sin(\pi/2)) = \Psi(\int_0^{\pi/2} z' d\theta) \end{aligned}$$

$i(1)$ represents the state 1 where $\theta=0$ is integrated by $\pi/2$. As shown in the figure, the result state is yin-yang number $i(1)$.

$i(i(1))$ indicates that the $i(1)$ state of $\theta=\pi/2$ is integrated $\pi/2$, and the integration area becomes $0\sim\pi$, as shown in the figure, the result state is yin-yang number -1.

So, $i(i(1))=-1$

According to the arithmetic integral operator calculation is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} i(i(1)) &= x = i(1) + \int_{\pi/2}^{\pi} (x') d\theta + \Psi(\int_{\pi/2}^{\pi} (z') d\theta) \\ &= x(0) + \int_0^{\pi/2} x' d\theta + \Psi(\int_0^{\pi/2} z' d\theta) + \int_{\pi/2}^{\pi} x' d\theta + \Psi(\int_{\pi/2}^{\pi} z' d\theta) \\ &= x(0) + \int_0^{\pi} (x') d\theta + \Psi(\int_0^{\pi} (z') d\theta) \\ &= 1 + \int_0^{\pi} (-\sin\theta) d\theta + \Psi(\sin(\pi)) = 1 + (-2) + \Psi(0) = -1 \end{aligned}$$

Define **addition**: $i(a)+i(b) = i(a+b)$

Additive commutative law: $i(a)+i(b)=i(b)+i(a)$, a and b are real numbers.

$i(1)$ can be **abbreviated** as $i, i1, i1$.

$i(n)$ can be **abbreviated** as in, ni . n is real number.

2> Define multiplication and division operations

If the integral nested expressions $i(i(1))$ and $i(a)$ are written as linear pipelined expressions $i*i$ and $a*i$ by using multiplication form, **multiplication** is defined.

Definition: $i*i \equiv i(1)*i(1) \equiv i(i(1)) = -1$

Prescribe: $i*a \equiv a*i \equiv ai \equiv ia \equiv i(a)$, a is real number.

Prescribe number multiplication law: $i(a*n) = i(a)*n$ $i(a)*n = n*i(a) = i(a*n)$

Prescribe the commutative law of multiplication:

$$i(a)*i(b) = i(b)*i(a) = -ab \quad a \text{ and } b \text{ are real numbers.}$$

Prescribe multiplicative associative law:

$$(a+bi)*(c+di) = (c+di)*(a+bi) = (ac-bd) + (ad+bc)i \quad a, b, c \text{ and } d \text{ are real numbers.}$$

Defines division as the inverse of multiplication.

$$1/i = -i$$

At this point, i participate in the four operations in form like an ordinary real number.

3> yin-yang number

Examine multiplicative associative law:

$$(a+bi)*(c+di) = (c+di)*(a+bi) = (ac-bd) + (ad+bc)i$$

In particular,

$$\begin{aligned} (\cos\theta + \sin\theta i) * (\cos\varphi + \sin\varphi i) &= (\cos\theta\cos\varphi - \sin\theta\sin\varphi) + (\cos\theta\sin\varphi + \sin\theta\cos\varphi)i \\ &= \cos(\theta+\varphi) + i\sin(\theta+\varphi) \end{aligned}$$

That is to say, the multiplication of the two combination numbers corresponding to θ and φ corresponds to the addition $\theta+\varphi$ of θ and φ .

More generally,

$$\begin{aligned} (e^p\cos\theta + e^p\sin\theta i) * (e^q\cos\varphi + e^q\sin\varphi i) &= e^{p+q}(\cos\theta\cos\varphi - \sin\theta\sin\varphi) + e^{p+q}(\cos\theta\sin\varphi + \sin\theta\cos\varphi)i \\ &= e^{(p+q)}(\cos(\theta+\varphi) + i\sin(\theta+\varphi)) \end{aligned}$$

That is to say, the multiplication of the two combination numbers corresponding to (p, θ) and (q, φ) corresponds to addition $(p+q, \theta+\varphi)$.

$A = e^p$, the phase is θ , the yang-number corresponding to $A\cos(\theta)$, yin-number corresponding to $z = A\sin(\theta)$, corresponding **yin-yang number** is

$$F(\theta) = A\cos(\theta) + i(A\sin(\theta)) .$$

4> Exponential operation

As mentioned above, the multiplication of the two combination numbers corresponding to (p, θ) and (q, φ) corresponds to addition $(p+q, \theta+\varphi)$.

The exponential operator can transform multiplication into addition.

In addition, we can use derivative to discuss.

$$F(\theta) = A\cos(\theta) + i(A\sin(\theta))$$

$$dF/d\theta = d(A\cos(\theta) + iA\sin(\theta))/d\theta = -A\sin(\theta) + iA\cos(\theta) = i(i(1))A\sin(\theta) + i(1)A\cos(\theta)$$

$i(i(1)) = -1$ can be written as $i(1)*i(1)$

$$dF/d\theta = i(1)i(1)A\sin(\theta) + i(1)A\cos(\theta) = i(1)(A\cos(\theta) + i(1)A\sin(\theta)) = i*(A\cos(\theta) + i(A\sin(\theta))) = i*F(\theta)$$

Formally, the result of $F'(\theta)$ is similar to the derivative of exponential function. $\exp'(k\theta) = k*\exp(\theta)$, so that $k=i$ corresponds to $\exp'(i\theta) = i*\exp(\theta)$. If $\exp(i\theta) = F(\theta)$, $F'(\theta) = \exp'(i\theta) = i*\exp(i\theta) = i*F(\theta)$

(Using the exponential function of real numbers) we can write $e^{p(\cos\theta + i\sin\theta)}$ as $e^{p+i\theta}$; if $p=0$, $\cos\theta + i\sin\theta$ is recorded as $e^{i\theta}$.

Defines the exponential operation of $i()$ and the exponential form of yin-yang numbers

$$e^{i\theta} \equiv \text{yin-yang-number}(\theta) \equiv \cos(\theta) + i(\sin(\theta)) = \cos(\theta) + i\sin(\theta)$$

$$e^{p+i\theta} \equiv \text{yin-yang-number}(p, \theta) \equiv e^p(\cos(\theta) + i(\sin(\theta))) = e^p(\cos(\theta) + i\sin(\theta))$$

Where θ is the real number and θ is the progress index (phase angle).

It is also **stipulated** that the **exponential operation** satisfies the exponential operation of real number.

$$\text{Multiplication to addition: } e^{p+i\theta} e^{q+i\varphi} \equiv e^{(p+q)+i(\theta+\varphi)}$$

$$\text{Division to subtraction: } e^{p+i\theta} / e^{q+i\varphi} \equiv e^{(p-q)+i(\theta-\varphi)}$$

$$e^{i\pi/2} = i(\sin(\pi/2)) + \cos(\pi/2) = i(1) + 0 = i$$

$$e^{i\pi} = i(\sin(\pi)) + \cos(\pi) = i(0) + (-1) = -1$$

$$i(1)i(1) = e^{i\pi/2} e^{i\pi/2} = e^{i\pi/2+i\pi/2} = e^{i\pi} = -1 = i(i(1))$$

$$\text{Meet the above: } i(1)i(1) = i(i(1)) = -1.$$

Therefore, $i(i(1))$ can be **abbreviated** as $i*i$ and i^2 .

$$\text{Its basic form is } i(i(1)) = -1$$

$$i^2 = i*i = i(1)i(1) = \exp(i(\pi)) = i(i(1)) = -1 \quad \text{Its basic form is } i(i(1)) = -1$$

$i(e^{p+i\theta}) = e^{i\pi/2} e^{p+i\theta} = e^{p+i(\theta+\pi/2)}$, that is, the phase angle of $e^{p+i\theta}$ advances by $\pi/2$. The meaning of $i()$ is still valid for $e^{p+i\theta}$.

At this point, it can be **stipulated** that the yin-yang numbers are applicable to all four operation rules and general functions as the real numbers.

In practical terms, **yin-yang numbers and yin numbers can enter physics openly**. The key is that the negative number represents the trend part of the physical state, and the round and integrated relation (the same as the natural unit) represents the phase state of some "moving" process.

Note that $i^2 = -1$ is a shorthand for $i(i(1)) = -1$.

In addition, $e^{i\theta} = \cos\theta + i\sin\theta$ is not a guest rule, but merely $\cos\theta + i\sin\theta$ is artificially recorded as $e^{i\theta}$.

Note that this is based on phase change. It is not based on changes in time. Of course, if we talk about changes in time, there will naturally be a phase change, but changes in time are not necessary.

In physics, there are many quantities of this complementary potential relation. Such as potential energy, kinetic energy, electric field, magnetic field, alternating current.

For example, the reference-space in this paper is the complement of the reference-time, and the reference-space is directly written as ix . The reference-space-time can be regarded as an integral vector as a whole. The phase of the first 0 is positive reference-time, the phase after integrating $\pi/2$ is positive reference-space, and the phase after integrating $\pi/2$ again is negative reference-time. From the phase point of view, it is like the phase state of a rotating vector.

If this pair of complementary potential quantities are used as vectors, then the square of the yin-yang numbers corresponds to the sum of their inner products (or the inner product of the sum). The relationship between "sum" and "complement", is common in energy relations and corresponds to the logical relationship of conservation of energy.

Like a person's wealth, corresponding to the yin-yang number; not only depends on the existing wealth, corresponding to real numbers; it also depends on the daily items, corresponding to the yin number.

Originally, $i()$ is a whole operator, not a number unit. But as a linear expression, coupled with the exchange law, the combination law and the distribution law, become the same as ordinary numbers, as if it were a number unit i . However, with or without parentheses, it is still operator $i()$. $(a+bi)i = i(a+i(b))$.

<1> Basic mode: the yin-number sign $i()$ is only used as a distinguishing sign

$i(n)$ is actually n , and $i()$ is set outside to distinguish the n in the original scene. In this way, it can be expressed that n with 2 different scenes can be used at the same time without confusion. That is to say, there are two physical scenes A and B, and n in A is still represented by n ; n in B is represented by $i(n)$. In this way, the scope of representation is expanded, and the two scopes need not be treated separately but can be treated in a unified way. This can not only improve the efficiency but also find out the regularity from a wider range.

This is like positive n and negative n . In fact $-n$ is also n , which is n in another scene different from n , with a $-$ in front to show the difference, for example, 2 degrees below zero is marked as -2 degrees. Now it's just this kind of thinking again. First, the minus sign separates two symmetrical scenes. $i()$ is used to divide it symmetrically again, and it becomes 4 symmetrical scenes. Positive evolution sequence: $1 \rightarrow i(1) \rightarrow i(i(1)) = -1 \rightarrow i(i(i(1))) = -i(1) \rightarrow i(i(i(i(1)))) = 1$. Reverse evolution sequence: $i(i(i(i(1)))) = 1 \rightarrow i(i(i(1))) = -i(1) \rightarrow i(i(1)) = -1 \rightarrow i(1) \rightarrow 1$.

If positive direction means multiplying by i , the positive evolution sequence $1 \rightarrow i \rightarrow i^2 = -1 \rightarrow i^3 = -i \rightarrow i^4 = 1$. The opposite direction means divided by i , reverse evolution sequence: $1 \rightarrow i^{-1} = -i \rightarrow i^{-2} = -1 \rightarrow i^{-3} = i \rightarrow 1$.

Figure 11 Evolution schematic diagram of 1 in different scenes

<2> $-n^2$ is expressed as $+(i(n))^2$

This will unify the formula.

$x = \pm 1$ meets $1 - x^2 = 0$, i.e. $1 - 1^2 = 0$

$1 - (\pm 1)^2 = 0$ can also be written as $1 + (i(\pm 1))^2 = 0$

Then $x = i(\pm 1)$ satisfies $1 + x^2 = 0$

The solution of $1 + x^2 = 0$ is $x = i(\pm 1) = \pm i$.

Yin number is a convenient mathematical expression tool.

<3> Only take yang number mode

Yin-yang numbers are only used as a mathematical method. In actual retrieval, only the positive part is taken.

The mathematical treatment method of yin-yang numbers is used here, which takes advantage of its superior expression form and calculation method.

This can be formally expressed as an invariant.

The calculation is often simplified.

For example, the amount of AC voltage.

<4> Yin-yang Coexistence Mode

Here are actually two different relations or entities that are equal. In practice, the treatment is exactly the same.

In this way, the two parts of yin-yang are used respectively. The expression is very concise.

In the process, the actual calculation is expanded into two parts.

<5> Yin-yang Division of Labor Model

Here are actually two different relations or entities that are unequal. In practice, the treatment is completely different.

At this point, only the mathematical indexes of the two factors are combined. $e^{k+i\theta}=e^k \times e^{i\theta}=e^k(\cos\theta+i\sin\theta)$.

For example, in the complex phase, the phase only represents the phase angle, and the modulus corresponds to the scale.

In this way, the two parts of yin and yang are used respectively. The expression is very concise.

In the process, the actual calculation is expanded into two parts.

<6> Unified Seamless Docking of Multiple Models

Exponential function process and sinusoidal function process look completely different. But it can be expressed by e^{kx} .

If k is the yang number, it is the exponential function process. If k is the yin number, it is the sine function process.

For example, the end-atomic model in the end-atomic mechanics is two such models.

<7> $i()$ Represents the Phase Relation of the Process

Yin-yang numbers represent a numerical change process. $i()$ represents the current phase relation of the change process.

For example, in alternating current, there is a phase relationship between the voltage and current across the capacitor inductance, which shows that there is an $i()$ sleeve in its impedance.

In end-atomic mechanics, there is a phase relation between "momentum p and energy E " and Ψ , which shows that there is an $i()$ set in the expression.

<8> Yin-yang Number Directly Represents a Change Process

Such as alternating current neutralization quantum mechanics.

Application modes vary; the meaning is also different. Physics can't just be expressed in terms of i . Its physical meaning should be explained; it can be explained by ordinary real numbers.

2) Super Infinity

What is infinite multiplied by 2? What is infinite plus 1?

Definition

$$[a_m, a_{m-1}, a_{m-2}, \dots, a_1, a_0] \equiv \sum_{i=0}^m a_i k_i$$

Where k_i is the weight of a_i , $k_i > 0$, $k_{i+1} > k_i$.

Define addition $A+B=C$, each filed adds up. If the weight is limited, the borrowing can be carried.

Define addition $A-B=C$, and subtract each filed. If the weight is limited, the borrowing can be carried.

The definition number times $A*k=k*A=C$, each filed times k . If the weight is limited, the borrowing can be carried.

Definition comparison, $A-B=C$, if C can be written as filed 0, then $A=B$, $B=A$. If $C > 0$, $A > B$, $B < A$; if C can

be written as non-negative and $C \neq 0$, then $A > B, B < A$; if $C < 0$, $A < B, B > A$.

Specifically define **Superinfinity** as $[a_m, a_{m-1}, a_{m-2}, \dots, a_1, a_0; b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n]$. The weight $k_0=1$ of a_0 , the weight $k_1=k_0 * \infty$ of a_1 , the weight $k_2=k_1 * \infty$ of a_2 Weight $h_1=k_0/\infty$ of b_1 , weight $h_2=h_1/\infty$ of b_2 , weight $h_3=h_2/\infty$ of b_3 Where ∞ represents positive infinity.

$A-B=C$, if and only if fields of C are 0, then $A=B, B=A$. If and only if the highest non-zero field is positive, then $A > B, B < A$. If and only if the highest non-zero field is negative, then $A < B, B > A$. If and only if field of A and B are the same, then $A=B, B=A$.

Infinity can be written as $A=[1,0]$.

Infinite multiplied by 2: $B=A*2=[1,0]*2=[2,0]$.

Infinite plus 1: $B=A+1=[1,0]+1=[1,1]$.

The superinfinity brings about a change of thought.

Superinfinity Theorem: Infinity is not necessarily unreachable.

For example, an infinite amount of time, an infinite amount of energy, an infinite amount of momentum, an infinite amount of steps, an infinite amount of quantities, etc., cannot be arbitrarily regarded as impossible; in particular, it cannot be used as a basis for **disproof**.

How do we understand when it is reachable? If it is only a logic of thinking, then it is not a problem.

For example, philosophical issues in history. The paradox that Achilles can't catch up with the tortoise. It is concluded here that it is impossible to require an infinite number of "steps". At present, the basis of this disproof method is untenable, thus it is not a paradox.

Similarly, the paradox that runners in Zeno cannot reach the finish line. It is concluded here that it is impossible to require an infinite number of "steps". At present, the basis of this disproof method is untenable, thus it is not a paradox.

The limit beyond infinity in thinking logic is named **absolute-infinity**. Absolute-infinity is the real infinity.

3) Matrix Parallel Multiplication

Define the **matrix parallel multiplication** $A \otimes B = AB^T$

It is characterized by row-to-row multiplication (staggered multiplication of rows and columns in matrix multiplication).

Exchange law: $A \otimes B = B \otimes A$

if $A \otimes B = I$, then A and B are named as **parallel reciprocal matrix** of each other; note $B = A^{-1}$, $A = B^{-1}$.

3.2 End-atomic Mechanics

(1) End-atomic Fundamental Equation

Let's discuss it in meta-symmetric space-time.

There is no special statement that q refers to time and space.

As can be seen from the foregoing, the mechanical properties of the end-atomic distribution change have a metasymmetry for Ψ . Does not contain the dimension of Ψ . Expressed by a dimensionless $\partial\Psi/\Psi$.

On the other hand, it can also be seen.

$$\Psi(q', t + dt) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K(q', t + dt; q, t) \Psi(q, t) d\tau$$

The nominal total mass is $C=1$ and remains unchanged.

It can be seen that end-atomic mechanics is topological.

There are Ψ factors on both sides. Therefore, K , which characterizes the most fundamental characteristics of the system, has nothing to do with the strength of Ψ . Therefore, it is necessary to divide $\partial\Psi$ by Ψ when studying the characteristics of change $\partial\Psi$; study the rule of ratio $\partial\Psi/\Psi$.

In this way, the change rate $\partial\Psi/\partial q$ becomes the relative change rate $(\partial\Psi/\Psi)/\partial q$.

Then, the relative rate of change $((\partial\Psi/\Psi)/\partial q)$ of the standard process of accurately expressing physical process, should be unchanged, according to yong-name-theorem.

Process Lemma 3: To accurately express a physical process, a standard process with constant relative rate of change $((\partial\Psi/\Psi)/\partial q)$ should be used to express the process.

Moreover, due to meta-symmetry, it cannot rely on the prior direction cognition of space q . There is meta-symmetry for the direction of q .

Eliminating dimensional influence, under the dimensionless form $\partial\Psi/\Psi$,

$$(\partial\Psi/\Psi)/\partial(\pm q) = \text{const}$$

$$(\partial\Psi/\Psi)/\partial q = (\partial\Psi/\partial q)/\Psi = \pm k$$

Where q is the space-time coordinate.

End-atomic Process Meta-symmetry Theorem: The standard process describing a process satisfies meta-symmetry $(\partial\Psi/\Psi)/\partial\pm q = \text{constant}$.

In the t-world, the end-atomic Ψ is variable, but $(\partial\Psi/\partial q)/\Psi = \text{const}$, which is the invariability of change.

In the v-world, the end-atomic Ψ is constant, but in the t-world, the end-atomic Ψ is variable. This is the change of invariability .

Exchange ik for k

$$(\partial\Psi/\partial q)/\Psi = \pm ik$$

This is an **exponential process**. \pm means positive and opposite two directions. The opposite direction is the reflected wave.

The basic solution of end-atom is

$$\Psi = e^{\pm ikq}$$

In other words, the equation of Ψ is an equation with $\Psi = e^{\pm ikq}$ as its basic solution.

Atomic General Solution Theorem: The general solution of end-atom is

$$\Psi = C1e^{-ikq} + C2e^{ikq}$$

$C1$ and $C2$ are combinations of arbitrary coefficients.

When k is a real number, ik is a negative number, $\Psi = e^{\pm ikq}$ is a sine wave.

When k is yin-number, ik is real, $\Psi = e^{\pm ikq}$ is normal exponential wave.

That is to say,

End-atomic Basic Waveform Theorem: End-atoms have two basic forms of waveforms: sine wave and exponential wave.

Sine wave is the most common waveform. The wave form in tunneling effect is exponential wave.

Let's look at one-dimensional space first, $q=x$

$$\psi = e^{\pm ikx}$$

$\Psi = e^{ikx}$, no matter what wave it is, it can be regarded as sine wave in mathematical form.

Time domain, $q=t$, corresponding k is angular frequency ω :

Write:

$$\Psi = Ae^{-i\omega t}$$

Time domain and space domain merging:

$$\Psi = Ae^{i(kx-\omega t)} = Ae^{i2\pi(x/\lambda-t/T)}$$

$$k = 2\pi/\lambda = 2\pi/(h/p) = 2\pi p/h = p/\hbar$$

$$\therefore E = \hbar\omega$$

$$\therefore \omega = E/\hbar = 2\pi E/h$$

$$\Psi = Ae^{i(kx-\omega t)} = Ae^{i2\pi(x/\lambda-t/T)} = Ae^{i(x2\pi p/h-t2\pi E/h)} = Ae^{i(px-Et)/\hbar}$$

$$\Psi = Ae^{iS/\hbar}$$

Get:

$$\Psi = Ae^{i(p\bullet r - Et)/\hbar}$$

This is the **basic end-atomic equation**.

(2) Linear Superposition Theorem

Ψ is the solution of $(\partial\Psi/\Psi)/\partial q = k$.

$\Psi' = a\Psi$, a is const.

$$\partial\Psi'/\Psi' = \partial(a\Psi)/(a\Psi) = \partial\Psi/\Psi = k$$

Therefore, Ψ' is also its solution.

This is because $\partial\Psi/\Psi$ is a dimensionless topological form, and the result must be linear.

End-atomic Linearity Theorem: End-atoms have linearity.

$\Psi_1, \Psi_2, \dots, \Psi_n$ are all solutions of $(\partial\Psi/\Psi)/\partial(q) = k$.

$\Psi' = a_1\Psi_1 + a_2\Psi_2 + \dots + a_n\Psi_n$, a_i is const.

$$\partial\Psi'/\Psi' = \partial(a_1\Psi_1 + a_2\Psi_2 + \dots + a_n\Psi_n)/(a_1\Psi_1 + a_2\Psi_2 + \dots + a_n\Psi_n) = k$$

Therefore, it is also its solution.

End-atomic Linear Superposition Theorem: End-atoms have linear superposition.

$\Psi_1, \Psi_2, \dots, \Psi_n$ are all their solutions. $\Psi' = a_1\Psi_1 + a_2\Psi_2 + \dots + a_n\Psi_n$ is also the solution.

(3) Norm Superposition Theorem

$\Psi_1, \Psi_2, \dots, \Psi_n$ and their linear combinations in different proportions are named **norm**.

Note that norm is only a formal thing. Ψ is the material level. norm does not include the specific total Ψ value.

Objects contain materials. So norm is not a particle either.

Norm Superposition Theorem: If $\Psi_1, \Psi_2, \dots, \Psi_n$ are norms of the system, then the linear superposition $\Psi = C_1\Psi_1 + C_2\Psi_2 + \dots + C_n\Psi_n$ of these norms is also a norm of the system. C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n are complex constants.

Norm is a logical thing that can be logically superimposed. Corresponds to a form of thinking.

The state is the general appellation of the entity's current existence form. Therefore, there is always and only one entity's current state.

No matter how the patterns overlap, the final state of existence of the object, however complicated, is called a state. Notice that it is a state.

Therefore, **end-atomic mechanics has no superposition state**. Correspondingly, we can say **complex state**.

(4) Right-Material-Cause Density Theorem

Consider unit volume.

Take exactly the same form of end-atomic model, $\Psi(A)$ and $\Psi(B)$, and the number is A and B. Take the complex orthogonal direction. The total result is $\Psi(C)$.

Formally, $A+B \Rightarrow C$

Ψ has the property of complex vector cancellation, so Ψ is added by complex vectors.

$$\vec{\Psi}(A) + \vec{\Psi}(B) = \vec{\Psi}(C)$$

Figure 12 Schematic diagram of complex vector Ψ addition

In numerical terms, there are:

$$\Psi(A)^2 + \Psi(B)^2 = \Psi(C)^2$$

Note: $P(X) = |\vec{\Psi}(X)|^2 = \Psi(X)^2$

$$P(A) + P(B) = P(C) \quad \text{----- (1)}$$

It's a simple addition.

The scale density of matter (ρ) is as follows:

$$\rho(A) + \rho(B) = \rho(C) \quad \text{----- (2)}$$

Same form as (1) above. It shows that $\rho(X)$ and $P(X)$ have the same power relation.

Therefore, there are:

$$\rho(X) = kP(X)$$

$\rho(X)$ and $P(X)$ have the same power relation, but differ from $P(X)$ by one power.

Therefore, the system has two cumulative relationships of momentum p linearity and density ρ square.

$$\rho(X) = kP(X) = k|\Psi(X)|^2$$

Due to the linear relationship of the system, ρ can be directly defined by $|\Psi(X)|^2$ without considering coefficient k .

$$\rho(X) = |\Psi(X)|^2 = \Psi^*(X)\Psi(X)$$

According to the compatibility theorem and the consistency theorem, the ρ definition in the t-world must also satisfy this relation.

In short, ρ is a scalar cumulative relation, and Ψ is a complex vector cumulative relation. The power relation reflected in accumulation is different. This difference is related to space, not time.

Complex orthogonal addition is simple addition. It is like the accumulation of two unrelated parts. So the Ψ in different places also accumulates in this way.

ρ reflects the weight of unit volume's influence on the world. ρ again depends on Ψ . So Ψ and ρ correspond to right.

The scale of the object reflects the material cause. Therefore, Ψ **logically** corresponds to material cause, so this kind of right is also called **right-material-cause**.

Right Density Theorem:

$$\rho = \Psi^* \Psi$$

The wave corresponding to Ψ is named as a **right density wave** and a **right wave**.

Right-material-cause itself regulates the immortality of matter, that is, the conservation of material cause. Therefore, the right-material-cause does not need any further normalization and normalization is not allowed. However, the total amount of one unit can be taken into consideration. Direct use of general conservation relations of matter ($\int \Psi^* \Psi d\tau$).

(5) First End-atomic Right Wave Equation

$$\because \Psi = A e^{i(kx - \omega t)} = A e^{i2\pi(x/\lambda - t/T)} = A e^{i(x2\pi p/h - t2\pi E/h)} = A e^{i(px - Et)/\hbar}$$

\therefore It is obvious that :

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi = -i\omega \Psi = -i \frac{E}{\hbar} \Psi$$

$$E \Psi = i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi$$

$$E^2 \Psi = -\hbar^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \Psi$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \Psi = i k \Psi = i \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \Psi = i \frac{2\pi p}{h} \Psi = i \frac{p}{\hbar} \Psi$$

$$p \Psi = -i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \Psi$$

$$p^2 \Psi = -\hbar^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \Psi$$

$$\hat{p} \Psi = -i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \Psi$$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \Psi - \frac{1}{u^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \Psi = 0$$

For multidimensional space :

$$\nabla^2 \Psi - \frac{1}{u^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \Psi = 0$$

This is the wave equation of the free end-atom. Where u is the wave speed.

$$p \Psi = -i\hbar \nabla \Psi$$

$$p^2 \Psi = -\hbar^2 \nabla^2 \Psi$$

$$p = -i\hbar \nabla$$

$$H\Psi = E\Psi \text{ is substituted into } E \Psi = i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi$$

Get :

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi = H\Psi$$

Or written

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} |\Psi\rangle = \hat{H} |\Psi\rangle$$

Named the **end-atomic fundamental right wave equation**.

The microscopic end-atom \hat{H} is named **dispersion operator**. To emphasize attribute (eigenvalue) relationships, not energy relationships.

Where Ψ is the column vector. When Ψ is a plurality of components, H is an hermite matrix.

The wave speed u is calculated as follows.

It is assumed that the potential $V(r)$ of the terminal is time-independent. Symmetry breakage is not considered. According to the consistency theorem(the t-logical extension theorem), the following macroscopic equation is used:

$$\frac{1}{2m}(\nabla S)^2 + V + \frac{\partial}{\partial t} S = 0$$

Where $S(r,a;t)$ is principal function, and a is the motion constant vector.

Because potential $V(r)$ is explicitly time-free, S can divide the time part into explicitly time-free eigenfunction $W(r,a)$ and explicitly time-dependent Et ; E is the energy eigenvalue.

$$S(r,a;t) = W(r,a) - Et$$

$$\text{Therefore, } \partial S / \partial t = -E$$

Substituting this into the equation above, the calculation results are as follows

$$(\nabla S)^2 = 2m(E-V)$$

The total derivative of S with respect to time t is

$$\frac{d}{dt} S = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} S + \nabla S \cdot \frac{dr}{dt}$$

Take S-equivalent surface Σ motion in space

∴ Σ is the isosurface, that is, the equiphase surface.

$$\therefore dS/dt=0$$

$$\therefore 0 = dS/dt = \partial S / \partial t + \nabla S \cdot dr/dt = -E + \nabla S \cdot dr/dt$$

$$\therefore (dr/dt)^2 = E^2 / (\nabla S)^2$$

The normal speed u of Σ is

$$u^2 = (dr/dt)^2 = (E/\nabla S)^2 = E^2 / (\nabla S)^2 = E^2 / (2m(E-V))$$

u^2 and $E\Psi = i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi$ and $E^2\Psi = -\hbar^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \Psi$ are substituted into the above wave equation, and then

obtained :

$$\nabla^2 \Psi - \frac{2m(E-V)}{E^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \Psi = \nabla^2 \Psi + \frac{2m(E-V)}{\hbar^2} \Psi = \nabla^2 \Psi - \frac{2m}{\hbar^2} V\Psi + i \frac{2m}{\hbar^2} \hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi = 0$$

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \Psi + V\Psi$$

This is named the **first end-atomic right wave equation**, namely the **Schrodinger equation**.

The color arithmetic formula here is $H=E=p^2/2m$, so it is only applicable to low-speed particles with negligible speed break and no spin.

$$E \psi = i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \psi$$

$$p \psi = -i\hbar \nabla \psi$$

In the formulas and equations, i denotes the existence of phase difference. "The energy eigenvalue and momentum eigenvalue" are out of phase with "this moment t and this moment q ".

(6) Second End-atomic Right Wave Equation

Considering the symmetry breaking of speed, the dispersion relation is $H=E=(p^2w^2+m_0^2w^4)^{1/2}$

$$\hat{p}\Psi = -i\hbar \nabla \Psi$$

$$\hat{p}^2\Psi = -\hbar^2 \nabla^2 \Psi$$

$$\hat{E}^2\Psi = -\hbar^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \Psi$$

Substitution into: $E^2\Psi = (p^2w^2 + m_0^2w^4)\Psi$

Get:

$$\frac{1}{w^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \Psi = (\nabla^2 - \frac{m_0^2w^4}{\hbar^2})\Psi$$

This is named the **second end-atomic right wave equation**, namely the **Klein-Gordon equation**.

Covariant form :

$$(\frac{1}{w^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2)\Psi = -\frac{m_0^2w^4}{\hbar^2} \Psi$$

$$(\square^2 + \frac{m_0^2w^4}{\hbar^2})\Psi = 0$$

$$\square^2 = \frac{1}{w^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2$$

(7) Third End-atomic Right Wave Equation

Linearized dispersion relation $H=E=w(p^2+m_0^2w^2)^{1/2}=w\alpha\cdot p+m_0w^2\beta$

$$p\Psi = -i\hbar\nabla\Psi$$

Substituting and adding potential energy term V , $H\Psi=(w\alpha\cdot p+m_0w^2\beta+V)\Psi$

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi(x,t) = (i\hbar w\alpha\cdot\nabla + \beta m_0w^2 + V)\Psi(x,t)$$

This is named the **third end-atomic right wave equation**, namely **Dirac equation**.

Where $\alpha(\alpha_1,\alpha_2,\alpha_3)$ and β are 4×4 Dirac matrices, m_0 is the mass of spin-particle and x and t are the coordinates of space and time respectively. $\Psi(x,t)$ contains 4 components and is called **Lorentz rotation**.

Continuity equation:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \rho + \nabla \cdot \bar{\mathbf{j}} = 0$$

$$\rho = \Psi^*\Psi$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{j}} = w\Psi^*\bar{\mathbf{a}}\Psi$$

(8) The Fourth Approximate End-atomic Right Wave Equation

Dispersion relation $H = E = w(p^2 + m_0^2w^2)^{1/2} = m_0w^2(1 + p^2/(m_0^2w^2))^{1/2} \approx m_0w^2(1 + \frac{1}{2}p^2/(m_0^2w^2))$
 $= p^2/(2m_0) + m_0w^2$

$$p^2\Psi = -\hbar^2\nabla^2\Psi$$

Substituting and adding potential energy term V , $H\Psi = (p^2/(2m_0) + m_0w^2 + V)\Psi$

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi = (m_0w^2 - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_0}\nabla^2 + V)\Psi$$

This is named the **fourth end-atomic right wave equation**.

(9) End-atomic topological diffusion theory

1) Interpretation of Ψ and Wave Functions

The wave function Ψ corresponds to the right-material-cause, and the **modular square ($\Psi^*\Psi$) of the wave**

function is the right-material-cause density; that is, the right-square of the whole microscopic particle's influence on the world through the unit volume at r at time t .

$$\rho = \Psi^* \Psi$$

And "can be super-extracted" is also a kind of effect.

The phenomenological probability of superextraction of particles in unit volume of point q at time t is $p(q)$. The right-square of a single particle that is superextracted corresponds to U .

$$p(q_1) = \rho(q_1)/U$$

$$p(q_2) = \rho(q_2)/U$$

$$p(q_1)/p(q_2) = (\rho(q_1)/U)/(\rho(q_2)/U) = \rho(q_1)/\rho(q_2)$$

$\therefore \rho(q) = \Psi^* \Psi$ is the phenomenological relative probability.

Phenomenological Superextraction Probability Theorem: The phenomenological relative probability of superextracted particle in a unit volume at a certain point is equal to the modular square ($\Psi^* \Psi$) of the wave function.

right-material-cause density determines the **phenomenological relative probability** of microscopic particles being super-extracted in unit volume at time t at r .

That is to say, the relative probability of phenomenology that can surpass-extraction is determined by the scale quantity of right-material-cause.

If the total right-material-cause of a single particle is set at 1, the two are in agreement in calculation.

The key here is the right-square U , which correspond to particles.

Particle Right-Square Theorem: From the perspective of measurement, particles are aliases for the locality of a specific right-square.

Measuring Right-Square Theorem: In fact, we can't measure things, we can only measure right-square.

Superextraction Right-Square Theorem: Superextracted particle is actually locality of superextraction right-square.

Probability Right-Square Theorem: The phenomenological probability ratio of superextracted particle is actually the ratio of right-square.

2) Fundamentals of End-atomic Diffusion Theory

The end-atom has logical fluctuation. Therefore, it has the characteristics of spatial geometric diffusion, adjacent infectivity and end-atom-phase-nature.

The end-atom has spatial geometric diffusion and adjacent infectivity. There is always the characteristic of self-propagation from one point to all directions at all times, except for external constraints. Therefore, the end-atomic process is the process of right diffusion.

This is a process of all-round diffusion of rights Ψ with different functions. This spherical symmetry is determined by meta-symmetry.

Moreover, the end-atom has end-atom-phase-nature, so the end-atom spreads according to the exponential form function $Ce^{iS/\hbar}$.

Ψ wave is the right density wave. Ψ reflects the influence of unit volume on the world.

Figure 13 Schematic diagram of end-atomic meta-symmetric diffusion

There is a propagation function in the diffusion process.

Note that when considering from the point of view of diffusion process, the nominal total material cause is $C=1$, which is always the same. It is only the rights and influence factors that change. This kind of thinking model is to integrate the whole space.

Note that in this model Ψ is expressed as both material cause and right. This is due to the separability of Ψ . When Ψ is divided, it is regarded as material cause. Once divided well, this part is taken as the research object, the total material quantity is $C=1$, which is always the same, and Ψ represents the variable right.

Of course, the part Ψ' obtained after Ψ is divided can also be regarded as another action right Ψ' in the world.

According to the pseudo-holography theorem, formally, the measured results and measured objects contain holographic information from all over the world.

End-atomic Diffusion Theorem and End-atomic Space Integral Theorem:

$$\Psi(q', t + dt) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K(q', t + dt; q, t) \Psi(q, t) d\tau$$

This formula is named the **end-atomic diffusion formula**.

This method is named the **diffusion method** and the **space integral method**.

$K(q', t'; q, t)$ is the **propagation function** and **propagator**.

This is equivalent to the **end-atomic Newton's second equation; the propagator decides the evolution of right wave Ψ** .

The wave function $\Psi(q', t')$ at time t' can be derived from the wave function $\Psi(q, t)$ at time t . Therefore, in terms of logical form, end-atomic mechanics is deterministic.

On the other hand, from the perspective of theoretical form transformation, this can be seen as a purely logical form transformation, which has nothing to do with the specific physical mechanism. The final result depends on the unknown $K(q', t'; q, t)$, which needs to be derived from other theories.

Therefore, it can be regarded as either an independent end-atomic diffusion theory (corresponding to the explanation of the above figure) or just an expression of a theory. This paper is an independent end-atomic diffusion theory.

When considered by right, the nominal total material quantity is actually 1. This is because this right is the function of the whole system (the world), and the total amount is the whole system. In fact, this right is the function of the same "whole world".

Therefore, each part of the system has a parallel transmission effect on the world according to the corresponding rights.

End-atomic Parallel Action Theorem: The rights corresponding to each part of the subspace logically interact with the world in parallel. Even if they are far apart.

This right includes the effect of the whole end-atom. Therefore, any function according to rights is logically the function of the whole end-atom.

End-atomic Integrity Action Theorem: Any action of an end-atom according to its right is logically the action of the whole end-atom.

This right includes the whole effect of the end-atom, which seems to have holographic effect.

There is a very strong interaction mechanism inside, and the logic of "one unit" is maintained. Such a system is named **end-atomic unibody**. For example, one particle and one entangled body.

Pseudo-holographic Right Theorem: The right of any point in an end-atomic unibody is logically the pseudo-holographic effect of the whole particle.

The first is the pseudo holographic effect in space. Secondly, it also involves the pseudo holographic effect in time. But that's just the logic of pure thinking.

Therefore, this right is a pseudo holographic right.

Then look at the pseudo-holographic logic.

$$\Psi(q', t + dt) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K(q', t + dt; q, t) \Psi(q, t) d\tau$$

There is a magic logic in this integral.

For any position q far from Δq , within a very small dt , it can exactly act on this point q' . Δq corresponds to full-space integration, Δq can naturally be very large, and the corresponding speed $\Delta q/dt$ is very, very large. That is to say, almost infinite speed is used for over-distance action.

But this is only the logic of microscopic pure thinking decomposed from thinking. Not visible in practice. What we actually see is the final overall effect. Moreover, the further away, the smaller the proportion of the total effect. Far away places can be ignored. So it is called pseudo.

The superluminal speed here is only the inner thing of the logical model itself, which can't be observed in fact; only the overall effect can be observed.

Atomic Micro Pseudo Superluminal Theorem: The end-atomic microscopic logic has pseudo-superluminal logic.

Let's talk about **end-atomic dispersion**.

Obtain real values that can be observed for the system in some places. Such two points A, B, the time difference is Δt , and the phase difference is an integer multiple of π . That is, an integer number of half cycles. If Δt is divided into integer n half cycles. Then, the phase difference between A and B is $n\pi$. The values at A and B are "real values satisfying observable conditions".

$$nT = 2\Delta t$$

$$T = 2\Delta t/n$$

$$E = h/T = nh/(2\Delta t)$$

The topology energy of the system can only take some discrete values, which can only be increased by integer multiples. Correspondingly, the wavelength is also a discrete change.

It can also be calculated by wavelength or other. $n\lambda = 2\Delta l$, $p = nh/(2\Delta l)$. $L = nh/(2\Delta\theta)$.

For intermediate values, the values at A and B are not "real values that satisfy observable conditions."

For electrons in an atom, the angle scope can only be 2π . This is its natural logical limitation, corresponding

to A-B above.

General end-atoms, macroscopically being observed by people, will bring some observational logical limitation, which is its logical limitation, corresponding to the A-B above.

3) End-atomic Pure Topological Theorem

$$\therefore \mathbf{p}\Psi = -i\hbar\nabla\Psi$$

$$E\Psi = i\hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial t}\Psi$$

$$\therefore \mathbf{p} = -i\hbar(\nabla\Psi)/\Psi$$

$$E = i\hbar\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t}\Psi\right)/\Psi = i\hbar(\partial\Psi/\Psi)/\partial t$$

Ψ is in both numerator and denominator; the result has nothing to do with the intensity change of Ψ . The result is pure topology.

Pure Topological End-atomic Momentum Theorem: End-atomic momentum \mathbf{p} is pure topological and independent of Ψ intensity.

Pure Topological End-atomic Energy Theorem: End-atomic energy E is pure topological and independent of Ψ intensity.

The end-atom is characterized by $\partial\Psi/\Psi$. Ψ is in both numerator and denominator, and the result has nothing to do with the intensity change of Ψ . The result is pure topology. So the end-atomic theory is topological.

End-atomic Pure Topological Theorem: End-atoms are fundamentally pure topological and independent of Ψ intensity.

Frequency ν , period T , wavelength λ are also independent of the intensity of Ψ .

In fact, there are:

$$E = h\nu$$

$$p = h/\lambda$$

They are independent of Ψ intensity. And the result is pure topology.

This explains the instantaneity of photoelectric effect and its independence from intensity change. Because the intensity changes of E and Ψ are independent. No matter how Ψ is diluted, this point E will not change. Whether photoelectric effect occurs depends on E .

4) Right Field Strength

According to the end-atomic wave model, the pure topological **right field strength** is named:

$$\mathbf{B} = \hbar\frac{\nabla\Psi}{\Psi}$$

Obviously \mathbf{B} is purely topological and has nothing to do with the intensity change of Ψ .

$$\therefore \mathbf{p} = -i\hbar\frac{\nabla\Psi}{\Psi}$$

\therefore

$$\mathbf{B} = i\mathbf{p}$$

It can be seen that momentum \mathbf{p} is also purely topological and has nothing to do with the intensity change of Ψ .

Further completeness is $(-\hbar\frac{\partial\Psi/\partial t}{\Psi}, \hbar\frac{\nabla\Psi}{\Psi}) = (iE, i\mathbf{p})$. It can also be (E, \mathbf{p}) .

5) The Relationship between Right and "Being Observed"

When an irreversible reaction occurs in the outside world and the right-material-causes are exhausted, the particle will not appear again, and the particle can no longer be superextracted. "Observed" is such an irreversible reaction process.

During observation, the interaction with measuring equipment is always carried out in the way of the whole end-atom due to the inherent logic of end-atom itself.

If there is not a whole end-atom, in the logical effect, there is a local atom, and the end-atom will interact with the measuring equipment, and then be "observed" instantaneously.

"Being observed" depletes the material cause of an end-atom.

Measuring equipment will also react on the system.

A particle can only be observed in one place. Since the logic is one particle, there is a very strong interaction mechanism in nature, maintaining the logic of "one particle"; not like a handful of sand. This mechanism will transfer the reaction of measuring equipment to the whole system. Superposites and eliminates the original right wave. Just like, octopus has very strong mutual pulling force in its body, maintaining the logic of "one octopus". The internal action of the octopus will transfer this action to the whole octopus from one hole to "be completely grasped", resulting in the "erasure" of half of the octopus in the adjacent hole. Octopus will eventually be "caught whole" in one place.

The same is true for entangled pairs. Since it is logically an entangled pair, there is a very strong interaction mechanism inside nature, maintaining the logic of "one entangled pair". If one party is changed, this mechanism will automatically transfer the external reaction to the other party.

If a process, can break out the exact state of particles; the particle is in a corresponding determined state. This is because the correct "exact-judgment" knowledge must be based on some definite physical process. This process causes the particles to irreversibly enter the corresponding definite state. For example, change the entangled party to know its state and deduce the state of the other party. Then in fact the other party is in a state of inference. Among them, the intrinsic mechanism of entanglement plays a key role.

Consciousness is not the key in exact judgment, the key is the physical process logic behind it. On the contrary, if the logic of this process cannot be guaranteed, then the original "exact-judgment" may fail.

This is the exact-judgment theorem. If a logical thinking process can "exactly judged" the exact state of a particle, the particle is in the corresponding certainty state determined by the real physical process.

6) Right Diffusion Propagator, Spatial Integration Method, Motion Equation and Lagrangian

Variational Equation

Consider $\varepsilon=dt=t'-t$ as infinitesimal. In n dimensional space.

According to the propagator model thinking, it is to integrate the whole space, and the nominal total right-material-cause is $C=1$, which remains unchanged. The derivation is continued by the previous space integral method.

This is actually "evolutionary thinking".

According to "evolutionary thinking", the progress of system evolution can be represented by an index S .

$$\psi = e^{iS/\hbar}$$

Evolution progress index S , like the phase of wave, propagates in space as well as in time. Because of

space-time equivalence, space and time have the opposite effect. Advance in time, lag in space. So have the opposite sign. Therefore, S is the space-time phase difference; this is consistent with the equal phase quantity in the theory of absolutivity.

E corresponds to $-\partial S/\partial t$.

p corresponds to $\partial S/\partial q$.

$$\therefore L(\dot{q}, q, t) \equiv dS/dt = \partial S/\partial t + (\partial S/\partial q) \cdot (dq/dt) = \partial S/\partial t + (\partial S/\partial q) \cdot \dot{q} = -E + p \cdot \dot{q}$$

$L(\dot{q}, q, t)$ is named **right diffusion quantity**.

So we know. Originally, the **physical meaning of Lagrangian** is the total time derivative (variability) of the system evolution phase state (S), and the **physical meaning of Hamiltonian** is the time (negative) partial derivative of the system evolution phase state (S), and " S " is the system evolution phase state.

\therefore The increment of phase S in dt time is $\Delta S = L(\dot{q}, q, t)dt$.

$$\therefore \Psi(q', t+dt) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} A^{-n} e^{i\hbar^{-1}\Delta S} \Psi(q, t) d\tau = A^{-n} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i\hbar^{-1}L(\dot{q}, q, t)dt} \Psi(q, t) d\tau$$

\therefore The propagator of the right diffusion process:

$$K(q', t'; q, t) = b(q, t; dt) A^{-n} = A^{-n} e^{i\hbar^{-1}L(\dot{q}, q, t)dt}$$

Where A^{-n} is the nominal total material factor correction factor.

End-atomic phase evolution theorem and End-atomic phase diffusion theorem and End-atomic Phase Space Integration Theorem:

$$\Psi(q', t+dt) = \Psi(q, t) + dt \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi = A^{-n} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i\hbar^{-1}L(\dot{q}, q, t)dt} \Psi(q, t) d\tau$$

The equation is named the **End-atomic phase evolution equation**, the **phase diffusion equation** and the **phase space integral equation**.

This method is named **phase evolution method** and **phase diffusion method** and **phase space integration method**. The final result depends on the $L(\dot{q}, q, t)$.

This is equivalent to the **end-atomic phase Newton's second equation**; $L(\dot{q}, q, t)$ decides the evolution of **right wave Ψ** .

In addition, the end-atom has end-atomic phase, so the end-atom varies in exponential form function $e^{iS/\hbar}$. Therefore, the right Ψ can be expressed in the form of a complex phase index. $\Psi = e^{iS/\hbar}$

The nominal total material quantity is 1, is always the same, that is, the nominal amplitude is always the same. It is only the phase that changes. The nominal amplitudes of different nominal positions in the whole space are the same, but the phases are different. The sum of the phase propagation effects is the final Ψ .

Note that this is not a summation of the paths, but only a meta-symmetric traversal of the space; there is no path to say.

For distributed end-atoms, we need to determine the total S by Ψ , so we need to analyze Ψ . For non-distributed objects. There is no need to take another step, just use S itself.

If a path P is the actual macroscopic orbit of the end-atom, then the phase S path variation is 0. Only in this way, the adjacent microscopic paths will not cancel each other due to the phase difference, and the accumulated Ψ is the largest when the phase difference is 0. The actual path Ψ is of course the largest.

For macro objects, the above is actually a self-consistency analysis. Since the zero-right non-existence theorem and the macro redefinition theorem, the macroscopic object is only in the macroscopic orbit, and is in other place ($\Psi = 0$).

Variations are actually the differentiation of serialization. δq is not one differential value, but a sequence of differential values. There is a differential value for each point of the process. Actually, it is calculated according to logic of differential/partial derivative.

For the actual macro track from A to B. The process from A to B is a whole.

According to evolutionary thinking, the actual process is dynamic equilibrium. The partial derivative for offset is 0. Otherwise, the non-zero partial derivative will amplify the external disturbance. The system cannot be in this dynamic equilibrium.

In dynamic equilibrium, the actual effect of force, such as the increase of speed, is also considered in the equilibrium state, which is the "total balance of force and effect". The partial derivative is 0, the partial differential is 0, and the variation is 0. $\delta \int_P dS = 0$.

In addition, speak from the practical rational cognition. How do we confirm that the object is just passing the orbit? There are only two limited points at both ends, which can be ensured. But there are countless points in the middle, so it is impossible to guarantee with actual operation. Only logical assurance can be used. Just like "there is only one straight line through two points", it is guaranteed by a logic. Physically, such a logic is also needed to guarantee the orbit in terms of self-consistency. For small offset δq , it is logically guaranteed by the fuxi equation. $\delta \int dS = 0$. This S is used to represent the state of system evolution S . That is to say, from the point of view of self-consistency, "variation equals zero" is the proper meaning of orbit.

Orbital Variational Theorem: The variation of the evolution state S of orbit is 0. $\delta \int_P dS = 0$ is named **orbital variational equation**.

Phase Path Integral Evolution Theorem and Phase Path Integration Theorem: The phase variation of macroscopic orbital path is 0.

$$\delta \int_P dS = \delta \int_{t_0}^{t_1} L(\dot{q}, q, t) dt = 0$$

This method of determining the path is named the **phase path integral method**.

This equation is named as the **phase path integral equation** and the **Lagrangian variational equation**. Further, the Hamiltonian mechanics can be derived.

The **virtual displacement** also has real **physical significance**: the change of external free index dq corresponding to the change of system evolution state dS , that is, the change of free degree.

Therefore, end-atomic mechanics derives **macroscopic Lagrangian mechanics and Hamiltonian mechanics**; they are consistent. They are evolutionary thinking. They are evolutionary equation.

Note that this is different from Feynman's meaning of "historical summation". There is no historical summation, no quantum-state, no probability. Fundamentally speaking, here are the right Ψ of action and the influence coefficient K .

When $\varepsilon = dt \rightarrow 0$,

$$K(q, t; dt) = \left(\frac{2\pi i \hbar dt}{m} \right)^{-n/2} e^{iS(q, t; dt)/\hbar}$$

$$A^{-n} = \left(\frac{2\pi i \hbar dt}{m} \right)^{-n/2}$$

For a finite ε , a path $q \rightarrow q'$, ε is divided into N segments, $\Delta t = \varepsilon/N$.

$$K(q', t+\varepsilon; q, t) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{2\pi i \hbar \Delta t}{m} \right)^{-N/2} \int dq_N dq_{N-1} \dots dq_2 \prod_{k=1}^N e^{iS(k+1, k)/\hbar}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \left(\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{2\pi i \hbar \Delta t}{m} \right)^{-N/2} \int dq_N dq_{N-1} \dots dq_2 \right) \exp \left[i \int_t^{t+\varepsilon} dt L(\dot{y}, y, t) / \hbar \right] \\
&= \left(\int_q^{q'} D(q(t)) \right) \exp \left[i \int_t^{t+\varepsilon} dt L(\dot{y}, y, t) / \hbar \right]
\end{aligned}$$

Named **path integral expression**.

7) Derivation of End-atomic Right Wave Equation

From this, the end-atomic right wave equation can also be derived.

According to the consistency theorem (the t-logic extension theorem), the following macro relationship is utilized.

For low-speed spin-free particles of mass m ,

$$L(\dot{q}, q, t) = \partial S / \partial t + (\partial S / \partial q) \cdot \dot{q} = -E + \mathbf{p} \cdot \dot{q} = -E + 2T = T - V = \frac{m}{2} \dot{x}^2 - V(\mathbf{x}, t)$$

Note: $\eta = y - x$

Substituting L to get:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi &= \varepsilon^{-1} A^{-n} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \varepsilon L(\dot{y}, y, t)} \Psi(y, t) d\tau - \varepsilon^{-1} \Psi(q, t) \\
&= \varepsilon^{-1} A^{-n} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \varepsilon \frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{y-x}{\varepsilon} \right)^2 - \frac{i}{\hbar} \varepsilon V(y, t)} \Psi(y, t) d\tau - \varepsilon^{-1} \Psi(q, t) \\
&= \varepsilon^{-1} A^{-n} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{\frac{im}{2\hbar\varepsilon} \eta^2 - \frac{i}{\hbar} \varepsilon V(y, t)} \Psi(x+\eta, t) d\tau - \varepsilon^{-1} \Psi(q, t) \\
&= \varepsilon^{-1} A^{-n} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{\frac{im}{2\hbar\varepsilon} \eta^2 - \frac{i}{\hbar} \varepsilon V(x+\eta, t)} \Psi(x+\eta, t) d\tau - \varepsilon^{-1} \Psi(q, t)
\end{aligned}$$

When $m\eta^2/\hbar\varepsilon$ is large, if η changes, the function oscillates very rapidly. Therefore, the integral of η is a very small value, most of which cancel each other out (due to the smooth nature of other factors). Therefore, only when η is close to 0 can the integral make a significant contribution. When η is on the order of $(2\hbar\varepsilon/m)^{1/2}$, it contributes most of the integrals; therefore η is also an infinitesimal.

Expand to a power series, preserving the first order of ε and the second order of η .

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi = \varepsilon^{-1} A^{-n} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{\frac{im}{2\hbar\varepsilon} \eta^2} \left[1 - \frac{i}{\hbar} \varepsilon V(x, t) \right] \left[\Psi(x, t) + \eta \nabla \Psi + \frac{1}{2} \eta^2 \nabla^2 \Psi \right] d\tau - \varepsilon^{-1} \Psi(q, t) + \varepsilon^{-1} o(\varepsilon)$$

The coefficient of left and right $\varepsilon^{-1} \Psi(x, t)$ is equal, which is 0.

$$A^{-n} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{\frac{im}{2\hbar\varepsilon} \eta^2} d\tau - 1 = A^{-n} \left(\frac{2\pi i \hbar \varepsilon}{m} \right)^{n/2} - 1 = 0$$

Get:

$$A = \left(\frac{2\pi i \hbar \varepsilon}{m} \right)^{1/2}$$

There is:

$$A^{-n} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{\frac{im}{2\hbar\varepsilon} \eta^2} \eta d\tau = 0$$

$$A^{-n} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{\frac{im}{2\hbar\varepsilon} \eta^2} \eta^2 d\tau = \frac{i\hbar\varepsilon}{m}$$

Get:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi = -\frac{i}{\hbar} V \Psi - \frac{\hbar}{2im} \nabla^2 \Psi + \varepsilon^{-1} o(\varepsilon)$$

Take the limit ($\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$) to obtain the first end-atomic right wave equation:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \Psi + V \Psi$$

Schrodinger Equation of Propagator

Think of $G(2,1)$ as a function of variable 2, because it is a special function, we see that G must also satisfy Schrodinger equation. When ($t_2 > t_1$), for

$$H = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\nabla^2 + V \quad \text{there is}$$

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t_2} G(2,1) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\nabla^2 G(2,1) + V(2)G(2,1)$$

There are generally:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t_2} G(2,1) - H_2 G(2,1) = 0 \quad \text{when } t_2 > t_1.$$

In which the operator H_2 can only act on the variable 2.

8) Zero-right Non-existence Theorem

Right expresses its effect on the world. Therefore, a right of 0 indicates no effect. Therefore, the place with zero right can be regarded as the place where it does not exist, and a fence placed here will not affect it at all.

Zero-right Non-existence Theorem: The place where the right is zero is the place where the right-object does not exist.

The zero-right-nonexistence-theorem greatly reduces the boundary of the object. From permeating the whole world, all of a sudden back to the original shape.

9) Momentum Space (representation) Wave Function

According to Fourier transform, the wave functions can be expressed by r and p , which are transformed into each other.

$$\text{Let: } \Phi_p(\vec{r}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi\hbar)^{3/2}} \exp\left(\frac{i}{\hbar} \vec{p} \cdot \vec{r}\right)$$

$$\Psi(\vec{r}, t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \varphi(\vec{p}, t) \Phi_p(\vec{r}) d\vec{p} = \frac{1}{(2\pi\hbar)^{3/2}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \varphi(\vec{p}, t) \exp\left(\frac{i}{\hbar} \vec{p} \cdot \vec{r}\right) d^3 p$$

$$\varphi(\vec{p}, t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \Phi_p^*(\vec{r}) \Psi(\vec{r}, t) d\vec{r} = \frac{1}{(2\pi\hbar)^{3/2}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \Psi(\vec{r}, t) \exp\left(-\frac{i}{\hbar} \vec{p} \cdot \vec{r}\right) d^3 r$$

$\Psi(\vec{r}, t)$ and $\varphi(\vec{p}, t)$ correspond one to one, which are two different ways of describing the distribution of the same right-material-cause.

From this, the average \bar{p}_x value of momentum \vec{p}_x can be derived.

Take the one-dimensional case as an example:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{p}_x &= \langle p_x \rangle = \int p_x |\varphi(p_x)|^2 dp_x = \int \varphi^*(p_x) p_x \varphi(p_x) dp_x \\ &= \int [(2\pi\hbar)^{-1/2} \int \Psi^*(x) e^{ip_x x/\hbar} dx] p_x \varphi(p_x) dp_x \\ &= ((2\pi\hbar)^{-1/2}) \iint \Psi^*(x) (-i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial x}) e^{ip_x x/\hbar} \varphi(p_x) dx dp_x \\ &= \int dx \Psi^*(x) (-i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial x}) [\int ((2\pi\hbar)^{-1/2}) e^{ip_x x/\hbar} \varphi(p_x) dp_x] \\ &= \int dx \Psi^*(x) (-i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial x}) \Psi(x) \\ &= \int \Psi^*(x) \hat{p}_x \Psi(x) dx \end{aligned}$$

10) Phase Difference Inequality

$$\Delta \hat{A} \equiv \hat{A} - \langle \hat{A} \rangle$$

$$\Delta\hat{B}\equiv\hat{B}-\langle\hat{B}\rangle$$

It is also the Hermit operator.

$$\text{Available: } [\Delta\hat{A}, \Delta\hat{B}] = [\hat{A}, \hat{B}]$$

$$ic \equiv [\hat{A}, \hat{B}] = [\Delta\hat{A}, \Delta\hat{B}]$$

$$\text{Available: } i\bar{c} \equiv [\hat{A}, \hat{B}] = [\Delta\hat{A}, \Delta\hat{B}] = ic$$

Constructing an integral constant inequality for real number ζ :

$$I(\zeta) = \int |\zeta \Delta\hat{A}\Psi - i\Delta\hat{B}\Psi|^2 d\tau \geq 0$$

$$I(\zeta) = \int (\zeta(\Delta\hat{A}\Psi)^* + i(\Delta\hat{B}\Psi)^*)(\zeta\Delta\hat{A}\Psi - i\Delta\hat{B}\Psi) d\tau$$

$$= \zeta^2 \int (\Delta\hat{A}\Psi)^*(\Delta\hat{A}\Psi) d\tau - i\zeta \int (\Delta\hat{A}\Psi)^*(\Delta\hat{B}\Psi) d\tau + i\zeta \int (\Delta\hat{B}\Psi)^*(\Delta\hat{A}\Psi) d\tau + \int (\Delta\hat{B}\Psi)^*(\Delta\hat{B}\Psi) d\tau$$

$\therefore \Delta\hat{A}, \Delta\hat{B}$ are also the Hermit operators.

$$I(\zeta) = \zeta^2 \int \Psi^* \Delta\hat{A}^2 \Psi d\tau - i\zeta \int \Psi^* (\Delta\hat{A}\Delta\hat{B}) \Psi d\tau + i\zeta \int \Psi^* (\Delta\hat{B}\Delta\hat{A}) \Psi d\tau + \int \Psi^* \Delta\hat{B}^2 \Psi d\tau$$

$$= \zeta^2 \int \Psi^* \Delta\hat{A}^2 \Psi d\tau - i\zeta \int \Psi^* (\Delta\hat{A}\Delta\hat{B} - \Delta\hat{B}\Delta\hat{A}) \Psi d\tau + \int \Psi^* \Delta\hat{B}^2 \Psi d\tau$$

$$= \zeta^2 \overline{(\Delta\hat{A})^2} - i\zeta \overline{[\Delta\hat{A}, \Delta\hat{B}]} + \overline{(\Delta\hat{B})^2}$$

$$= \zeta^2 \overline{(\Delta\hat{A})^2} + i\zeta\bar{c} + \overline{(\Delta\hat{B})^2}$$

$$= \overline{(\Delta\hat{A})^2} (\zeta + \bar{c}/(2 \overline{(\Delta\hat{A})^2}))^2 + (4 \overline{(\Delta\hat{A})^2} \overline{(\Delta\hat{B})^2} - \bar{c}^2)/(4 \overline{(\Delta\hat{A})^2}) \geq 0$$

For this constant inequality to hold for any real number ζ , the last term must be non-negative.

$$(4 \overline{(\Delta\hat{A})^2} \overline{(\Delta\hat{B})^2} - \bar{c}^2)/(4 \overline{(\Delta\hat{A})^2}) \geq 0$$

$$\overline{(\Delta\hat{A})^2} \overline{(\Delta\hat{B})^2} \geq \bar{c}^2/4 = (|\overline{[\Delta\hat{A}, \Delta\hat{B}]}/2|)^2 = (|\overline{[\hat{A}, \hat{B}]}|/2)^2 = (|\overline{[\hat{A}, \hat{B}]}|/2)^2$$

$$\sqrt{\overline{(\Delta\hat{A})^2}} \sqrt{\overline{(\Delta\hat{B})^2}} \geq |\overline{[\hat{A}, \hat{B}]}|/2 = |\overline{[\Delta\hat{A}, \Delta\hat{B}]}|/2 = |\overline{[\hat{A}, \hat{B}]}|/2$$

$$\sqrt{\overline{(\Delta\hat{q})^2}} \sqrt{\overline{(\Delta\hat{p})^2}} \geq \hbar/2$$

Named **displacement-momentum phase difference inequality**.

Similarly,

$$\sqrt{\overline{(\Delta\hat{t})^2}} \sqrt{\overline{(\Delta\hat{E})^2}} \geq \hbar/2$$

Named **time-energy phase difference inequality**.

11) The Meaning of Phase Difference Inequality, Not Mean Uncertainty

Ψ , q and t are the three elements of physics and also the basic elements.

In Schrodinger picture, q is a primitive and \hat{p} is not a primitive. q and \hat{p} do not have equal element-group-properties. Correspondingly, Ψ , q and t are all the elements to describe this problem. \hat{p} and \hat{E} are not basic elements. \hat{p} and \hat{E} can be calculated from these three basic elements.

$$\hat{q} = q$$

$$\hat{p}\Psi = -i\hbar\nabla\Psi$$

q is the basic variable. \hat{p} is not a numeric operator.

It can be seen that there is an i factor between \hat{q} and \hat{p} , which indicates that there is a $\pi/2$ difference between \hat{p} and the primitive, thus there is a $\pi/2$ difference between \hat{p} and \hat{q} .

In end-atomic mechanics, the process is represented by a harmonic oscillator model, and there are the following special constraints:

$$p\lambda = ET = 2\pi\hbar$$

These are exactly the reasons why $[q, \hat{p}] = \hbar$ caused.

If there is no difference between \hat{p} and the primitive. If \hat{p} is also a numeric operator p . Participating in the calculation is ordinary numerical calculation.

$$\hat{q}\hat{p}\Psi - \hat{p}\hat{q}\Psi = qp\Psi - pq\Psi = qp\Psi - qp\Psi = 0$$

There is an equivalent relation: $[\hat{q}, \hat{p}] = 0$

\hat{q}, \hat{p} are exchangeable.

$$\text{Result: } \overline{(\Delta\hat{q})^2} \overline{(\Delta\hat{p})^2} \geq (|[\hat{q}, \hat{p}]|/2)^2 = 0$$

But, $\hat{p}\Psi = -i\hbar\nabla\Psi$

For the convenience of taking one-dimensional space q . $\hat{p}\Psi = (-i\hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial q})\Psi$

There is a derivative relation, so there is a difference of $\pi/2$. At the same time, the derivative symbols also leads to non-exchangeability.

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{q}\hat{p}\Psi - \hat{p}\hat{q}\Psi &= qp\Psi - \hat{p}q\Psi = q((-i\hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial q})\Psi) - (-i\hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial q})(q\Psi) = -i\hbar q(\frac{\partial}{\partial q}\Psi) + i\hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial q}(q\Psi) \\ &= -i\hbar q(\frac{\partial}{\partial q}\Psi) + i\hbar(\frac{\partial}{\partial q}q)\Psi + i\hbar q(\frac{\partial}{\partial q}\Psi) \\ &= -i\hbar q(\frac{\partial}{\partial q}\Psi) + i\hbar\Psi + i\hbar q(\frac{\partial}{\partial q}\Psi) \\ &= i\hbar\Psi \end{aligned}$$

It can be seen that it is the derivative symbols corresponding to $\pi/2$ differences that lead to different derivation combinations with different sequences. Furthermore, due to the step-by-step derivation rule, asymmetry is caused. Then $\hat{p}\hat{q}\Psi = (-i\hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial q})p\Psi$ has one more item $-i\hbar(\frac{\partial}{\partial q}q)\Psi = -i\hbar\Psi$.

∴ There is an equivalent relation: $[\hat{q}, \hat{p}] = i\hbar$

\hat{q}, \hat{p} are not exchangeable.

$$\text{Result: } \overline{(\Delta\hat{q})^2} \overline{(\Delta\hat{p})^2} \geq (|[\hat{q}, \hat{p}]|/2)^2 = (\hbar/2)^2$$

For time t and energy \hat{E} , it is similar. $\overline{(\Delta t)^2} \overline{(\Delta\hat{E})^2} \geq (|[t, \hat{E}]|/2)^2 = (\hbar/2)^2$

\hat{p} and \hat{E} are not basic elements.

We say whether a physical theory is certain depends on whether the basic elements that describe physical problems are certain. Here they are Ψ, q, t . It's not about \hat{p} and \hat{E} whether it's certain or not.

Simply speaking from the precise mathematical description: assuming that the total energy of a signal is $h=2\pi\hbar$, the product of the variance of this signal and the variance of its Fourier transform energy is not less than $(h/4\pi)^2$, that is $(\hbar/2)^2$. That is, a signal cannot be concentrated at one point in both the time domain and the frequency domain. This is purely mathematical. It has nothing to do with physics.

Since the three physical elements of end-atomic mechanics are all certain, they do not exclude being measured accurately at the same time, end-atomic mechanics is also a certainty theory, and the physical knowledge described is also certain.

In other words, it is not because of uncertainty, but because of logical phase difference.

In fact, mathematically speaking, it is simply wrong to explain by uncommutative multiplication. Mathematics cannot be used to support it.

If "uncommutative multiplication" is used to explain, then "uncommutative multiplication" must be defined first.

But multiplication based on operators is not the basic operation in mathematics at all. Multiplication of operators is a set of symbolic rules defined by these physicists themselves. Then use this set of symbolic rules to

describe.

Therefore, "noncommutative multiplication" cannot be used to explain.

In fact, it is only to define a symbol system to describe it.

In fact, physically speaking, this formula has no special physical significance. It is not only that an expression is artificially defined, then a lower limit is obtained by pure logic calculation and an inequality is obtained. In fact, people can define different expressions and then get a lower limit by pure logic calculation, and an inequality is obtained. For example, Ozawa defined an expression and got an Ozawa inequality.

Moreover, the knowledge and its model in the t-world are constructed subjectively through self-consistency, and their practical significance is limited, not everything is of practical significance. Correspondingly, the meaning of operators defined on their models is also limited.

In this lower limit $\hbar/2$, from the definition of end-atom. There is a relationship: $p\lambda=ET=2\pi\hbar=h$. According to the end-atomic theory, this h comes from the lower limit of human observation in the current v-world. In the course of history, this lower observation limit is not constant. Therefore, this is only a current restriction.

Therefore, according to this lower observation limit, we can name the era of our technological level **planck era**.

Human beings are visual creatures. At present, the basic information of the world is obtained mainly by visual observation. Due to two-law-antinomy, vision has a submerged effect on other weak perceptions. This lower limit is from $p\lambda=ET=h$ of photons. For us today, **light is the yardstick of the world**. This lower limit comes from our vision, an observation tool.

Due to the phase difference between the two operators. It is inappropriate to require accurate measurement of these two operators at the same time. It's like asking the house to be very close to both the North Pole and the South Pole.

As long as the basic elements of the primitive can be logically measured accurately at the same time, the theoretical model itself is considered certain.

In fact, this difference still exists in the macro world. However, the base number of macro objects is huge and the relative error is negligible. Then it can be redefined macroscopically. Then there is the macro firewall. Then it feels as if there is no such difference on the macro level. Ultimately, there is such a difference in macro level, but it has been ignored.

Logically, there is still such a phase problem in macro world, such as Zeno's "flying arrows without moving" .

In Schrodinger picture, q is the basic element and p is not the basic element. In Heisenberg picture, p is the basic element, q is not the basic element. The two are opposite. Don't mix it up.

In Schrodinger picture, momentum is not an instantaneous value; momentum and position do not have equal element-group-properties. Here, strictly speaking, momentum in a moment is meaningless. We can see " i " corresponding to the phase difference $\pi/2$. " i " means that when the position is measurable, momentum cannot be logically obtained from a set of observations. The phase difference $\pi/2$ corresponding to " i " indicates that, the momentum change and the position change, differ by 1/4 cycle in time distribution, and differ by 1/4 wavelength in space distribution.

Moreover, from a strict logical point of view, in Schrodinger picture, it is not allowed to measure momentum. Momentum has been defined by primitives Ψ and q . Defined by this formula $\hat{p}\Psi = (-i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial q})\Psi$. Measuring momentum is equivalent to redefining momentum. The two definitions violated two-law-antinomy. It is not allowed to measure momentum; naturally, no measurement is required. Violation of two-law-antinomy is a serious problem; and often very concealed. In the "flying arrows without moving" problem, Zeno made a mistake and did not know it.

Obviously, all the influences of history on the future of the world can be obtained by a single huge wave function. The wave function for the next moment is determined by the propagator. Therefore, end-atomic mechanics is deterministic. The premise of determinism is certainty. End-atomic mechanics must be certain.

However, the wave function itself does not need to measure momentum p etc.

The key to phase difference inequality is that there is a phase difference between the two operators. This does not mean that the system is uncertain.

12) Macro Redefinition Theorem — the Moon Is Always There

Let's talk about **end-atomic cancellation**.

Is it true that "when no one looks at the moon, the moon only hangs in the sky with a certain probability; but when someone looks at it, the original uncertain existence of the moon suddenly changes into reality at the moment when people look at it. "

First, analyze the physical basis.

Microscopic effects, fold and cancel each other; it is named **end-atomic cancellation**.

From the perspective of interaction with the outside, the microcosmic actually has a complicated internal structure. The results can be seen as many separate parts. End-atomic cancellation occurs between these parts. This is the end-atomic cancellation seen at the end-atomic level.

End-atomic cancellation at the end-atomic level is one of the physical foundations.

Macroscopic objects are also composed of microscopic particles. The microscopic right-material-cause of a macroscopic object Ψ will undergo drastic microscopic changes due to microscopic motion.

However, the number of particles n is huge, the effect of end-atom cancellation is obvious, and the microscopic effect is macroscopic, and the effect is mutually destructive. This is the End-atomic cancellation at the macro level between many microscopes in a macro object.

Macroscopically scaled end-atomic cancellation is the second of the physical bases.

After the end-atoms cancel, the relative deviation $\Delta A/A$ of its macroscopic characteristic A approaches 0. Attribute A can take a .

Macro Limit Lemma:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\Delta A}{A} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{A - a}{A} = 0 \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a}{A} = 1 \quad A \rightarrow a$$

This kind of limitation is the third basis of physics.

Let's talk about **macro redefinition**.

Therefore, the macroscopic eigenvalues such as mass, position and volume can be viewed macroscopically as an eigenvalue a that is not affected by microscopic motion. It is equivalent to redefining the object on the macro level. Even, the definition of macro object itself is not completely according to the macro material to define. It is defined on the basis of a complex set of history. Macroscopically, things increase or decrease a little, but they are still regarded as the original things. This logic is named **macro redefinition**.

Let's talk about **Sun Wukong's hair problem**.

For example, Sun Wukong's hair problem. From the macro material point of view, his hair is naturally a part of his body A. He went to have his hair cut and cut some of his hair b. The macro material of b accounts for 1% of A. Is b still part of A?

If so, can we say that there is a 1% chance that Sun Wukong is lying on the ground? Naturally, we will not say so.

This is because macro redefinition will occur. Sun Wukong without this part of hair is still redefined as Sun Wukong. Similarly, the ship of Theseus, which replaced several pieces of wood, was redefined as the ship of Theseus.

Similarly, the constant respiration and material exchange with air lead to changes in the body. The new Sun Wukong is still redefined as Sun Wukong.

In fact, the observation of microscopic particles, as far as the results are concerned, belongs to the v-world, and its knowledge form has undergone a macro redefinition. In other words, we give it a certain position or other macro-level eigenvalues, according to the understanding of macroscopic objects.

The microscopic right-material-cause of the moon Ψ will undergo drastic microscopic changes due to microscopic motion. According to end-atomic mechanics, some right-material-cause may be far away from the main body of the moon. We won't say how many probabilities the moon will run away. Instead, find a stable subject space Σ . It happens to contain the vast majority of right-material-cause. We redefine the macro moon macroscopically, which occupies a stable space Σ . Also has the stable quality m , and so on. From the point of view of right-material-cause, it is not consistent with microcosmic, so it is redefined.

Since the moon occupies a stable space Σ , we macroscopically **redefine** a moon that is always hanging there.

As a result of redefinition, the right-material-cause Ψ burrs remaining after microscopic cancellation have been completely ignored, leaving nothing. The macro object after macro redefinition is clean (a definite state) and has no hair (right-material-cause Ψ burr).

So, the moon has been there all the time, and there is not a hair.

It is precisely because of this macro redefinition that there is a slight gap between micro knowledge and macro knowledge. And is always a certain state, no hair (right-material-cause Ψ burr). This slice forms a firewall.

Macro Redefinition Theorem: Macro redefinition exists in macro knowledge. Not only objects, but also things, logic, ideas, judgments, etc.

Macro Hairless Theorem: Macro redefined things are 100% complete and clear. No hair (right-material-cause Ψ burr).

Observation Macro Redefinition Theorem: After observation, things have undergone macro redefinition. End-atom, microscopic particles and macroscopic objects are all applicable. Observation is macro.

As a matter of fact, end-atom cannot be directly observed.

Observation must be a macro process, observation results must be macro results, observation must lead to macro redefinition.

Therefore, due to self-consistency, the v-world boundary is logically the macro world, even for a single microscopic particle.

After macro redefinition, the speed phase difference is generally discarded. Discard the subtle phase difference between speed and time and space. i corresponding to phase difference is not required between speed and space-time.

13) End-atomic Symmetry Breaking

The symmetry that all kinds of end-atomic observation results can be realized symmetrically and freely is called **end-atomic symmetry**.

In this state, the end-atom is in a reversible evolution state. End-atomic symmetry is a condition for reversible evolution.

In a certain physical process, end-atoms enter a certain observation representation and become irreversible, which is named **end-atomic symmetry breaking**.

In a certain physical process, an end-atom irreversibly enters a certain observation representation and is named **end-atom unification**.

End-atomic symmetry breaking is the reason of end-atom unification. This is because the state is irreversible, which depletes the end-atom's corresponding right-material-cause, and there is no more right-material-cause to show other rendering effects.

The corresponding superextraction process of measurement is the end-atomic symmetry breaking process. In some physical experiments, the interaction process between end-atoms and macroscopic instruments is the end-atomic symmetry breaking process, and the nuclear decay is the end-atomic symmetry breaking process. Therefore, end-atomic unification occurs.

For example, when measuring the position of a photon, the photon hits a counter, the photon state is irreversible, the right-material-cause corresponding to the end-atom is exhausted, and no more photon material is used to generate other photon appearances.

The same is true for our eyes. The same is true for animals' eyes. The same is true for some optical recording instruments. The same is true for ordinary light-absorbing objects. They are all equivalent.

What causes end-atomic symmetry breaking is the actual physical process. This has nothing to do with consciousness. For example, photons hit the retina and react with the retina, the photon state is irreversible, the corresponding right-material-cause of end-atoms are exhausted, and there is no more right-material-cause to generate other photon appearances, and photons disappear on the retina.

According to the consistency theorem, the same logic is used in the t-world and the v-world. The end-atomic logic created in thinking according to the observed phenomena in the v-world, must be consistent with the observed phenomena in the v-world. The observational phenomena we used to establish end-atomic logic earlier, are all definite observation appearances. Therefore, the observation phenomenon corresponding to end-atomic logic should be a specific representation.

And there must be some practical physical mechanism to ensure that an end-atom can **only be represented**

as one end-atom representation, otherwise it will not be called an end-atom.

End-atomic Superextraction Unification Theorem: End-atomic superextraction can only enter a certain observation representation.

14) End-atomic Firewall and End-atomic Fence

Our instruments are all specially selected, and our knowledge of the macro world is also specially selected, which ensures that their behavior characteristics can completely ignore the interference of end-atomic effect due to macroscopic redefinition, and corresponding to the macro world, this is called **end-atomic firewall**.

As a result of macro redefinition, there is a slight gap between micro knowledge and macro knowledge. And it is always a definite state without hair (right-material-cause Ψ burr). This slice forms an end-atomic firewall.

It is like a firewall, guarding our knowledge of the macro world. Therefore, in the hybrid system of the macro system and the end-atomic system, end-atoms can generally not be considered at the macro interface. When a macroscopic object interacts with an end-atomic system, it makes the end-atomic symmetry breaking, the end-atomic observation representation irreversible, and the end-atoms are unified on the observation representation. For example, a photon activates a geiger counter. Our chosen geiger counter will inevitably make the photon symmetry breaking irreversible. The photon state stays on the surface, that is, it stops at that place and will never appear at other places.

Note that this is not to say that the two are contradictory. They are still just the same. But at the macro level, we don't talk about the micro set of things. Instead, start a new stove. Each said his own words.

On the other hand, from the end-atomic point of view, the logical fence formed by the end-atomic firewall around the end-atom is named **end-atomic fence**. Therefore, the end-atoms in reality are localized.

15) End-atomic Microscopic Topological Structure

If only the local structures needed at this time are maintained in the actual operation of the system, then the operation of the end-atomic system will not be affected; the sequential topological logic composed of these local structures is named **end-atomic microscopic topological structure**.

End-atomic microscopic topological structure can be the key to end-atomic evolution.

(10) End-atomic Topological Field Theory

It is basically consistent with quantum field theory. Not much more.

However, one thing, the actual end-atoms exist in the form of end-atomic fields. It is not an infinitesimal point. It is actually distributed.

End-atomic fields are topological.

This provides a basic theoretical basis for reforming. It is not infinitesimal, so the divergence problem brought by infinitesimal does not exist.

End-atomic field interacts with vacuum field. In practice, it always exists as a mixed field.

(11) End-atomic Topological Structure Field Theory

The physical basis of end-atomic topological structure field theory is end-atomic topological field theory (quantum field theory). The actual operation is the end-atomic topological field theory. When there is no actual operation, there is no corresponding actual physical field. However, the corresponding topology exists. The

topology of the system in actual operation affects the operation of the system. Because this topological structure depends on the layout of the system and does not have to wait for the actual operation, the world runtime field theory determined by the system topological structure is named **end-atomic topological structure field theory**.

In general simple analysis, there is no need for advanced end-atomic topological field theory, on the contrary, the main concern is only the system topology. End-atomic topological field theory only needs to know simple knowledge points: (1) vacuum is actually a vacuum field; (2) Particles and objects are also fields; (3) the two fields interact to form an action field; (4) Particles and annihilation particles generated by creation operators and annihilation operators in the action field. (5) The action field has fluctuation. (6) Once a particle is superextracted, the original other possibilities will no longer appear.

It is mainly used in some qualitative explanations.

In this way, an electron or photon can be explained by passing through 2 slits and 2 optical fibers at the same time. Because end-atoms are fields. The field interacts with the vacuum field. Finally, the interacting field passes through two separate paths at the same time.

Ultimately, in apparent logic, an end-atom is generated at a certain point in space, which happens to meet the superextraction condition and becomes irreversible. Due to the depletion of the material, there will be no more super-extractable (observable) end-atom. Therefore, an end-atom can only be observed or superextracted in one place.

(12) Explanation

1) Experimental Interpretation of Single Photon Interference

Figure 14 Single photon interference experiment

In the above figure, a partition plate I with two parallel slits is placed between the laser source S and the receiving screen II. Let the light source emit 1 photon at a time. Results interference fringes appeared on the receiving screen II.

Explanation: In a single emission, the photon topological right field uses 2 slit paths at the same time and logically passes through 2 slits at the same time. After that, the two parts logically form two topological coherent wavelets. Two topological coherent wavelets interfere to form interference fringes.

2) Explanation of Single Electron Diffraction Experiment

Figure 15 Single electron diffraction experiment

According to topological field theory, an electron is actually a topological field. And forms an topological action field by interacting with the vacuum field. This field has a wavelength. When the hole is very small, the form of the topological field approximation point of the excitation region behind the small hole. Therefore, it has hemispherical symmetry. It diffuses hemispherically. Finally, a pattern with circular symmetry is formed. Due to its logical fluctuation, a circular symmetrical diffraction ring is displayed on the screen.

3) Explanation of Wheeler's Delay Selection Experiment

Figure 16 Wheeler delay selection experiment

In the above figure, the light emitted by the laser source passes through a semi-silvered mirror A with an angle of 45 degrees; half of the light is reflected, and the other half passes directly through. Two total mirrors B and C follow. After reflection, the two paths of light converge at a 45-degree angle semi-silvered mirror D. ABD and ACD are very long.

Adjusting the path so that interference cancellation occurs in the direction of the receiver F; the light in the direction of receiver E must be enhanced. Receiver F cannot receive light. Only receiver E can receive light.

Let the light source emit one photon at a time. Insert the reflector just before the light reaches D. Receiver F cannot receive light. Only receiver E can receive light.

If the reflector D is removed, both E and F can receive light, but not at the same time.

This is not what wheeler said: "whether to insert a reflector when the light is about to reach D will, in turn, decide afterwards whether the previous light passed through both paths after a or only one of them."

Experiments can confirm this point. Before inserting D, the optical switches K2B and K2C are turned off, which does not affect the experimental results.

No matter whether the upper reflector is inserted or not, the light will travel through 2 paths.

If the delay is inserted into the upper reflector, the light will travel in 2 paths. In F direction interference cancellation; the light in the direction of receiver E must be enhanced. Only receiver E can receive light.

If the reflector D is not inserted at that time, the light will proceed by two paths. Since there is no lens D, light directly passes through, and both E and F can receive light, but not at the same time.

According to the end-atomic topological structure field theory, the photon is topological fields. This topological field interacts with the vacuum field. Finally, the interacting topological field passes through two separate paths at the same time.

Finally, at a certain point in space, it happens to meet the conditions of super-extraction, and super-extraction occurs and becomes irreversible. Right-object, i.e. photon, is observed at this point. Due to the depletion of the right-material-cause corresponding to the photon, there will be no more superextractable (observable) photon. Therefore, a photon can only be observed in one place.

4) Schrodinger's Cat Explanation

Figure 17 Schrodinger's cat experiment

In the above picture, there is a cat C, a radioactive atom U, a device K that can detect atomic decay, and a poison gas releasing device R in a box. After T time, there is a 50% probability that the radioactive substance will decay and release toxic gas to kill the cat, and there is a 50% probability that the radioactive substance will not decay and the cat will survive.

If you don't open the box, is the cat in a dead and not dead state?

No. The reasons are as follows.

1> U decay of a radioactive atom is not end-atomic symmetry, and various states cannot be in reversible evolution state.

Once U decays, it is irreversible. The atom's right-material-cause is exhausted and cannot present other states.

Therefore, U has either not decayed or has decayed, and there is only one choice. It can only be a certain state. Then the result of the following process can only be a certain state. So cat C can only be in a certain state, either

dead or not dead.

2> The detection device K and the release device R are specially selected instruments by human beings. The macro knowledge of cat C is also specially selected. They are all protected by end-atomic firewalls. In the form of knowledge, it can only be a certain state. So cat C can only be in a certain state, either dead or not dead.

(13) Experiment

1) Time Domain Local Single Photon Interference Experiment

In the above figure(Experimental Interpretation of Single Photon Interferenc), a partition plate I with two parallel slits is placed between the laser source S and the receiving screen II. Let the light source emit one photon at a time. Results Interference fringes appeared on the receiving screen II.

Now, it is required that the system be shut down after each emission, and the system be cleaned up by degaussing, etc. It is ensured that each emission is a cold start emission, thus ensuring that photons between each emission have no coherent relation and are independent of each other.

If there is still an interference fringe, then this fringe can only come from the self-interference of the single emission itself. This proves that interference is time-localized. That is to say, it is limited to this emission period and has nothing to do with other long periods of the whole experiment.

There is no interference between multiple emissions. Multiple emissions only present various results of a single emission according to their probability.

Single electron emission self-interference can also be used instead.

The key is to find out the corresponding end-atomic microscopic topological structure.

2) Pallet Space Local Experiment

In the above figure(Explanation of Wheeler's Delay Selection Experiment), the light emitted by the laser source passes through a semi-silver-plated mirror A with an angle of 45 degrees. Half of the light is reflected and the other half passes directly through. Two total mirrors B and C follow. After reflection, the two paths of light converge at a 45-degree angle semi-silvered mirror D. Ki is an optical switch.

Adjusting the path so that interference cancellation occurs in the direction of the receiver F; the light in the direction of receiver E must be enhanced. Receiver F cannot receive light. Only receiver E can receive light.

Let the light source emit one photon at a time. Receiver F cannot receive light. Only receiver E can receive light. This shows that photon materials have passed through two paths and interfere with each other in the F direction.

Ki is disconnected at the beginning and D is removed.

1> Only a period of time before the light reaches this section, close the connection switch Ki or insert D in advance, and disconnect the front switch or remove D after reaching the next section.

If the result is as follows: Just as the switch Ki is always closed and the result is the same, only E receives light.

Correspondingly, the reflector D is always removed and the corresponding switch is turned on or off on time.

If the result is as follows: Just as the switch Ki is always closed and the result is the same, E and F both accept light, but not at the same time.

As the light passes by, the front route is completely disconnected, and is there any connection at the back?

Therefore, it can be considered that light is not in the front and rear parts; therefore, it can be considered that photons are confined to this section, which is like a pallet.

The number of optical switches is not limited, and each segment can be controlled to be small as long as the experimental accuracy allows. Then, we can think of photons within a very short path. That is, the light in the experiment is spatially localized, instead of the whole system being indivisible.

2> Otherwise, adjust the breaking rule. For example, if it is closed, it will not be disconnected, or the disconnected part will not be disconnected, etc.

In any case, the key is to find out the corresponding end-atomic microscopic topological structure through experiments.

Experimental conclusion: Photons in the experiment are spatially localized, instead of the whole system being indivisible as Bohr said.

Theoretical conclusion 1: the end-atom is spatially localized, rather than the whole system is indivisible.

Theoretical conclusion 2: The results depend on the topological structure of the actual microscopic path when the end-atom is running.

This method of gradually narrowing the end-atom in space and time is called the **pallet method**.

3) Corrected EPR Experiment

Fallacy of EPR Experiment

EPR experiments verify the causal logic relationship between the results of entanglement of the two parties (party 1 and party 2). This is simply a fallacy. The result is naturally zero. This is not a causal relationship at all. It is not a cause-and-effect relationship, and naturally no cause-and-effect relationship can be found.

They are "result-result" relations, corresponding to the same reason. Formally, it is a one-cause-multi-result relationship, as shown in the figure.

Figure 18 Causality diagram of EPR experiments

There is no free choice of thinking for the so-called "result". It is not that "if the experimenter chooses a result, the result will appear". The experimenter is just watching a movie and cannot intervene.

There is also no free choice of thinking for the so-called "reasons". It is not that "if the experimenter chooses a reason, the reason will appear". The experimenter is just watching a movie and cannot intervene.

Because it does not meet the **five elements of event causality**, it is not a cause-and-effect relationship.

On the other hand, EPR papers also have defects. Its requirement of reality is unreasonable. Due to the phase difference, position and momentum need not all be physical elements. Other quantities are similar. There is no completeness problem in end-atomic mechanics.

In addition, locality and causality have nothing to do with relativity and should not be bound together.

Corrected EPR experiment

As shown in the above figure, we should take the operation that the thinking can choose as the reason. Then

choose one of the many results appropriately. Measure their corresponding cause phase and result phase, time difference t and distance l .

Only in this way can it be meaningful to test their cause-and-effect relationship.

At the same time, a $t-l$ chart is drawn, and the slope corresponds to a speed, thus quantitative conclusions may be obtained.

3.3 Theory of Absolutivity

(1) Pure Logic

1) Why is it Theory of Absolutivity

We all know that sports are relative.

Why do we propose theory of absolutivity?

1> What does "movement is relative" mean?

It means that the description of movement is relative.

Further, it is said that the description of a movement changes with respect to the change of something.

Further, it is said that the description of a movement changes with respect to the change of the frame of reference.

In short, the "description of a movement" is ever-changing.

However, the yong-name-theorem requires that the name value be constant. Correspondingly, it definitely means "constant" and "stable".

This is contradictory. So that means even a name cannot be decided.

Obviously, there are already many names. Then there are other ways.

On the other hand, we can control the world according to those relatively stable things. In reality, we have a saying that "remain essentially the same despite all apparent changes".

Of all the changes, we can still extract the foundation of invarianc.

To control the traces of changes with the foundation of invarianc.

2> Why do we choose the absolutely unchanging case when compared with the trace of all changes?

According to the economic theorem of Gezhi Physics, Gezhi Physics should have economy.

Obviously, mastering and memorizing the traces of changes takes more cost than the foundation of invarianc, which violates the economic theorem.

In addition, the complexity cost of the relationship brought about by the changes is a square relationship, and the cost growth is a square growth, which is even more contrary to the economic theorem.

Therefore, we have to choose the "the absolute foundation of invarianc"

3> How to Obtain "the absolute foundation of invarianc"?

Use our wisdom to create.

For object length, relativity theory says that the values obtained in different reference systems are different. We should not limit ourselves to the reference system. In addition, create a thinking tool "space-time representation". It does not limit a frame of reference, but only a certain logical norm. It is stipulated that the ruler is relatively stationary and close to the object when the length of the object is obtained. In this way, whether I am

at home or on a spaceship, the measured length values are consistent. The people on the two spacecraft will not argue idly about who is bigger and who is smaller. Similarly, the consistent process time can be measured.

The absolute sequence of events depends only on topological relations. The coordinates of specific events in the frame of reference can be ignored.

2) Exploration of Absoluteness

1> Some Absolute Phenomena in Physics

The most concerned thing is counting. The count is absolute. It has nothing to do with speed, etc. For example, the number of heart beats in Newton's life is absolute.

In fact, there are many more.

Text has nothing to do with speed. The word "good" does not change into "bad" because of speed.

Numbers have nothing to do with speed. "0" will not change to "1" because of speed.

Traffic signals and the like have nothing to do with vehicle speed. If "another man named Einstein" runs a red light and argues that "according to the theory of relativity, when a car is driving at high speed, a red light blue shift and becomes a green light". Then, the transportation department will judge "incidental color blindness and banned driving for life".

Language has nothing to do with speed. The word "like" does not become "dislike" because of speed.

Flag language has nothing to do with speed.

2> Mathematical Model — Pulse

The characteristics of these things can be summarized as pulse information.

Motion counting, motion direction commutation is pulse information.

The stroke and structure of characters are pulse information.

The color conversion of traffic lights is pulse information.

Pulse information is mathematically invariant.

For a conventional transformation matrix K of A to B , the number of diagonals is a non-zero positive finite number, and the number of non-diagonal lines is a finite number.

$$dB = KdA$$

Take B_0 as an example.

$$dB_0 = k_{00}dA_0 + k_{01}dA_1$$

If it is not a pulse, $dA_0 = 0$, $dA_1 = 0$.

$$dB_0 = k_{00} * 0 + k_{01} * dA_1 = k_{01} * dA_1 = 0$$

If it is a pulse, $dA_0 = \infty$, $dA_1 = 0$.

$$dB_0 = k_{00}dA_0 + k_{01} * dA_1 = k_{00} * \infty$$

$\therefore k_{00}$ is a positive finite number.

$\therefore k_{00} * \infty$ and dB_0 are both of the same sign ∞ .

$\therefore dB_0$ is still the same pulse.

To sum up, the pulse passes through the conventional transformation matrix K and remains unchanged.

Therefore, the pulse information in the above information remains unchanged. Therefore, the information expressed therein remains unchanged.

3> Mathematical Model — Partial Derivative is 0

However, the infinity of the ideal pulse is used above. The ideal pulse is difficult to achieve in reality.

In the motion count, if the frame of reference moves too fast. Then all are reverse motions, the commutation information is overwhelmed, and the count is zero.

The conditions can be relaxed appropriately. As long as the external disturbance does not exceed a certain limit, the conclusion is still valid.

For motion counting, as long as the frame of reference does not move too fast, the motion commutation pulse information still exists and the counting remains unchanged.

A word, slightly deformed, can still be read positively. In fact, words are not usually written to the full standard.

This condition, pushed to the extreme mathematically, is the infinitesimal perturbation ∂q . Some measurable words, like correctly written words, always have a limited allowable perturbation range Ω . Then given infinitesimal perturbation ∂q , it must be included in this range Ω .

$$\partial q \in \Omega$$

Therefore, for this infinitesimal disturbance ∂q , the information V remains unchanged, and $\partial V=0$.

This is expressed mathematically as the partial derivative of information V being 0.

$$\partial V/\partial q=0$$

This is **mathematical model of absolutivity** of absolute physical quantity.

The representation of time is also a kind of counting information. We can absolutely express time information.

Therefore, we can extract this absolute information from nature and use this absolute information to represent physics.

4> Topological Model

The above pulse model and partial derivative model can be expressed by topology in complex physics. Topological information is a kind of pulse information. Its partial derivative is 0.

Establish event node topology network, such as, Newton's birth and death.

Directed connections are established according to the sequence of events. The direction is the sequence of events. The nominal number represents the number of times (heartbeat).

Then the information of this topological network is not affected by the speed and acceleration. The direction of the connection will not change, indicating the direction of the process (from birth to death). The number marked on the line will not change, indicating the number of times (Newton's heartbeat in his life).

In this way, an absolute physical information topology network can be established.

Topological theory is the mathematical foundation of theory of absolutivity.

In a word, the space-time here is different from that of Bekele and Mr. Einstein. This is a more profound logic created by wisdom.

3) How to Get Theory of Absolutivity

1> The Problem of Gravitational Field

In the relative theory of $F(S,S')=0$, S always appears through the comparison of S' .

Here we fix to take S' at infinity. Then in the gravitational field, this S' can be taken as a constant.

Since it is a constant, it can be deleted from the parameter table. Become a non-relative theory of $F(S)=0$.

In addition, ds corresponds to phase, not inherent time. The problem becomes a 4-dimensional straight space-time and a 1-dimensional phase problem instead of a 4-dimensional curved space-time problem.

2> The Problem of Breakthrough in Uniform Linear Motion in Inertial System

Uniform linear motion has little practical significance in reality. In reality, it is basically variable speed movement in the end.

Absoluteness is reflected in variable speed movement, for example, Newton's heartbeat in his life.

In fact, relativistic time-alignment logic has been replaced by clock-alignment logic of the theory of absolutivity.

Clock-alignment logic can only be implemented in variable speed motion. In uniform linear motion, after separation, they cannot meet again to complete the clock-alignment. There is no guarantee that topological relations will be established.

Therefore, it is meaningless to compare time and space if the 2 frames of reference moving in a relatively uniform straight line do not map to the same space-time representation. Therefore, don't compare and don't ask at all. There is no point in asking and there is no answer. Moreover, it is precisely because we cannot meet again that we cannot confront each other, so it will not cause two-law-antinomy. So we can first define a logical standard clock, according to other laws.

If we want to compare, we must first define a common space-time representation. In this common space-time representation, the object obtains a comparable value. For example, the length of an object is measured by specifying that the object is relatively stationary.

However, from the perspective of absolute theory. Inertial motions are equivalent to each other and have meta-symmetry. Their still light-clocks are meta-symmetrical. Correspondingly, the still light-clock time difference dt_s can be taken as the most basic source time. According to time-topology-1, dt_s can be directly used to judge the order. So as to form a new space-time representation.

4) Multi-space-time Representation Theory

Space-time representations of different patterns can be established for different purposes.

Using different logics, we can establish the space-time representation of different patterns.

The space-time representation itself is not purely for tourists. There are subjective elements. It is the product of wisdom.

1> General Equivalence Descriptor Space-time Representation — Emphasis on Space-time Equivalence

When measuring the length of an object in a relatively moving vehicle, the ruler is stationary relative to the object to measure the length of the object. Such length representations can be directly compared. The physical quantities of such length values are in the same space-time representation.

The duration of the process is measured by the pangu time corresponding to a relatively stationary standard clock. Such process duration representations can be directly compared. The physical quantities of such process time values are in the same space-time representation.

It is suitable for ordinary people's daily life. The height, the length of dance music and the sequence of time are all the same.

The relatively moving astronauts can finally have a good chat.

2> Space-time Representation of Mechanics — Emphasis on Mechanical Relevance

This is for the study of mechanics. The obtained representation always maintain that internal mechanical correlation. Space, time, speed, acceleration, force, energy, pressure, temperature, etc., their internal correlation remains unchanged.

Applicable to natural philosophy researchers, for example, ancient calendar researchers and modern physicists.

At this time, the above method cannot be used. For the above method, the length of individual objects can be compared and the length of individual objects can be compared. However, once everything is taken together, the original mechanical relationship can no longer be guaranteed. There is two-law-antinomy.

Therefore, we must give priority to the mechanical correlation and reconstruct another space-time representation.

In addition to the original mechanical correlation, it is necessary to artificially introduce certain norms to establish temporal-spatial representation correlation.

Here, the phase of the (light) spatial-tectonic motion is used as the correlation; and the infinite distance of gravitational field is **defined** as 0 reference point. In this way, an **inertial system** with meta-symmetry is formed.

This leads to nuwa equal phase exchange formula.

3> Geodetic space-time representation — considering both cases

Fixed with a frame of reference to get consistent expression. At the same time, low-speed dynamics research can also be carried out.

Because of two-law-antinomy different temporal-spatial representations have different logic laws. The above logic cannot be satisfied at the same time. Only one logic law can be selected for each different space-time representation.

In a word, space-time representation is not unique and has certain subjectivity. It is established according to certain needs. We need at least three space-time representations.

One can be used to visually express the absoluteness and symmetry of motion, facilitating recording and communication. The spatial representation values measured by the same object in the relative motion scene are equal. That is, the length of the object is a definite absolute value. The duration of the same process is also the absolute value. Volume is also a definite absolute value.

One can be used to do accurate mechanical research. The space-time representation always maintains the internal mechanical correlation. The logic of its establishment led to nuwa equal phase exchange formula. At the same time, due to the artificial adoption of special reference system (infinite reference system) and special motion (spatial motion of light) as the reference, logically there is a special reference system — inertial system, and at the same time there is a special absolute speed — light speed c ; these are all brought about by the subjective logic of human beings.

A geodetic spatio-temporal representation considering two situations. Expressed with a fixed frame of reference. At the same time, low-speed dynamics research can also be carried out.

In theory, human beings can also establish other space-time representations to achieve other purposes.

Therefore, the space-time representation of events is not fixed.

On the other hand, the fact that two simultaneous events give different duration values in different frames of reference, that is, different representation values, does not mean that they are not simultaneous. Therefore, we can abandon the "simultaneous relativity" of relativity. "It's not that the same-time becomes different, but that the same-time can present different numerical representations." It is topological logic, and numbers are just

appearances.

The two time topologies are:

(1) **Time-Topology-1: The sequence of the same self-consistent subject is a topological sequence (including simultaneity).** For example, eat breakfast first and then go to work.

(2) **Time-Topology-2: "Co-located simultaneity"** is a kind of topology simultaneity, belonging to the topology sequence. For example, two people meet.

The former is the main part; the latter acts as a link to form a complex topological network.

The former corresponds to the sensory-time representation .

Topological Sequence Lemma: Topological sequence is absolute sequence (including simultaneity).

Topological precedence is absolute precedence (including simultaneity); otherwise, the priority relation cannot be uniquely defined.

Newton lived from birth to death. It is a topological order, an absolute sequence.

"At the same time of topology" corresponds to one node.

If 2 events A and B are not topologically simultaneous, the sequence cannot be uniquely defined.

It is not "relative simultaneity", but simply cannot uniquely define the sequence.

Only under known conditions, it is impossible to judge the topological simultaneous relationship between A and B, so it is impossible to judge the simultaneous relationship uniquely. But it's not that they don't have a definite topological simultaneous relationship.

The reality is always in a complex topological network. If there are enough conditions, the topological simultaneous relation can be determined more and more accurately.

This is the same as detection. Two events in different places A and B. At first, the time sequence cannot be determined. With the increase of information, the relationship between them will be gradually known. Then it was confirmed that some suspects had no time to commit crimes and were excluded.

A and C are absolutely in the same place at the same time. C is definitely ahead of D in other places (the same person makes A first and then makes D in another place). Then A definitely precedes D. If it is really "relative simultaneity and relative time" as the theory of relativity says. Then detection is meaningless. The basis of detection is topology.

The key to the difference between the two is the following. The representation calculated by relativity is a numerical value, and its "relative simultaneity" is based on the comparison of numerical values. However, in topology theory, the specific numerical value is not useful, only the topological relation plays a role. One second is not necessarily earlier than two seconds. Relativistic expansion is only a representation. The topological relation is not affected.

The magnitude of the space-time value of the mechanical space-time representation does not necessarily indicate the time sequence, but only the mechanical correlation; this is due to two-law-antinomy. Through this correlation, some useful conclusions can be calculated for prediction and planning.

Moreover, relativity uses luminous signals to judge the same time and gives a time value. $t_2=t_1+\Delta x/c$. It's just a family statement. And the logic is not strictly demonstrated. It cannot be used as a basis for judgment. If the logic is wrong, then naturally we cannot use it. If it can be proved to be correct by some intuitive self-evident logic A; then we will directly use the intuitive A, also do not need this obscure logic. The most fundamental point violates the logic norm of "time has nothing to do with path" and "absolute topological order", since ancient times.

The most reliable is the topological relation above. Here, only the most basic and reliable time sequence judgment logic of human beings is adopted, and no new logic is added artificially.

4> Using Isochronous Plane to Study the Absolute Time Relationship of Events

A vector of time AB for a subject. Logically, each point on it corresponds to an event. AB is one-way increasing.

There is a isochronous plane C. Suppose $A < C < B$.

Then AB must have a point c_1 equal to C, that is, $c_1 = C$. Since AB is increasing in one direction, this point is unique. In this way, every point on AB corresponds to an isochronous plane.

Now, the specified vertical axis represents time. Equal intervals give a real number. Isochronous planes are all horizontally parallel. They don't intersect.

Now AB is vertically upward, c_1 on AB and isochronous plane C are isochronous. AB is topological and scalable. Scaling makes point c_1 exactly on isochronous plane C.

In this way, every point on AB is on the corresponding isochronous plane.

In this way, every point on the time vector of all subjects is on the corresponding isochronous plane.

In this way, each event uniquely corresponds to an isochronous plane.

Then, will the relationship between them be chaotic? That is, whether the isochronous planes will intersect.

No. This is because the isochronous planes are parallel to each other. It will not intersect.

In this way, each event is on a unique isochronous plane. The only isochronous plane represents its absolute time relation.

There is an absolute chronological relationship between events. Time is absolute.

Time Absoluteness Theorem: There can be absolute time-sequence relation between events.

However, some people will say that only the subject's own events (observation itself) are considered above. No consideration has been given to distant celestial events, such as a black hole merger one billion years ago.

Yes. May not be considered; to be precise, different kinds of events have different logical positions in the knowledge system, with different degrees and different treatment.

The event of the subject itself is named the **basic event**. The basic event directly corresponds to the sensory-time. It can be considered that the basic events come directly from the objective world. Basic events must be dealt with directly.

And distant celestial events, those events are someone's mind. Who came up with it is responsible for its logical self-consistency. And whether it is correct or not is still unknown. Those expanded things are handed over to specific sub-disciplines. For example, geological archaeology has its own private time standard to deal with; whether it is right or wrong, physics is not responsible. Private time standard is adopted. The dimension is increased.

Where is the organ here? In fact, it does not violate the Lorentz transformation of relativity. For two events of the same subject itself, there must be $\Delta x = 0$. Therefore, Δt will never change its sign and its sequence will never change. But we should abandon the numerical value.

In fact, "the order of the same self-consistent subject" here, and the order of normal differential inherent time (dt) in general relativity, are corresponding. However, only its topology is preserved here. Moreover, it is only at the differential level (integration is not possible without numerical support).

Note that at present there are only 2 rules of topological order; according to these two articles and the limited information of human beings, it is not possible to determine the absolute sequence of all events objectively and uniquely. This is the reality. We really don't know the sequence of many things. Of course, most of the time it doesn't matter.

In the actual research, some private norms can be artificially introduced to make the event obtain a private representation. This private specification only maps the role of association. Generally speaking, the private

representation it produces is discarded in the final conclusion. Or indicate the private specifications used.

In fact, this absolutivity is only at the level of "Gezhi Physics absolute theorem".

5) Clock-alignment and Time-alignment

Theory of Relativity uses the **time-alignment logic**. The phase relation of optical signals is used to confirm the simultaneous relation between two different events.

However, the actual relationship thus obtained is not simultaneous, but equiphase. The Lorentz transformation is actually an equal phase exchange. The problem is that the phase occupies the name of time, and the dimension decreases. The decrease in dimension leads to the curved space-time, causing chaos.

This theory of absolutivity uses **clock-alignment logic**. The standard clock is defined by purely logical relations. Then use the standard clock to confirm the simultaneous relationship. In addition, the clock logic is aimed at processes, not events. The standard clock should embody the meta-symmetry of time. For example, it has meta symmetry for space, speed, acceleration, temperature, pressure, etc.

The space-time representation of this theory of absolutivity is purely logical, and the space representation and the time representation are connected by purely logical spatial construction coefficients. In reality, the spatial structure coefficient is definitely confirmed by the spatial structure light phase relation. The resulting relationship is also an explicit equal-phase exchange. However, here, time is time, and phase is phase. There is no other way to occupy a bird's nest, thus there is no dimension reduction, thus there is no curved space-time, thus it is clear and refreshing.

6) Time and Space

According to the meta-symmetry theorem, time has meta-symmetry.

Time has nothing to do with the choice of time base point. That is, there is translational symmetry. Therefore, the time is uniform. Therefore, there are:

Time Uniformity Theorem: Time is uniform and has translational symmetry.

Since time is represented by a number here, the absolute value of the time difference between two points has nothing to do with the direction. Therefore, it can be further inferred that the symmetry of time is also true in the opposite direction, so there are:

Time Mirror Theorem: Time is uniform in both positive and negative directions and has translational symmetry.

In addition, because space has mirror symmetry, space is time. Therefore, in turn, time must also be required to have mirror symmetry.

In fact, time has more complete meta-symmetry. This meta-symmetry is automatically obtained in the later defined dimensions. For example, this meta-symmetry is automatically obtained for space, speed, acceleration, temperature, pressure, etc.

When defining time, there is no space. It is also impossible to talk about its spatiality.

But it is precisely because of the post-definition of space. After the space is defined, time has complete independence of basic point selection for space. That is, it has complete symmetry. Therefore, there are:

Total Symmetry Theorem of Time to Space: Time has Complete Symmetry to Space. Including translation symmetry of coordinate axis, rotational symmetry of angle, mirror symmetry of direction and translation symmetry of radial direction.

This total symmetry is also called independence. Therefore, there are:

Time-space Independence Theorem: Time and space are independent of each other.

According to meta-symmetry theorem, space has meta-symmetry.

The irrelevance of space to the choice of spatial base points. That is, there is translational symmetry. Therefore, the space is uniform. Therefore, there are:

Space Uniformity Theorem and Spatial Translation Symmetry Theorem: Space is uniform, and has translational symmetry (in coordinate axis and radial direction).

The irrelevance of space to the choice of basic point of space angle. That is, there is rotational symmetry. Therefore, there are:

Spatial Rotation Symmetry Theorem: Space has rotational symmetry.

The irrelevance of space to the selection of spatial direction base points. That is, there is mirror symmetry. Therefore, there are:

Space Mirror Symmetry Theorem: Space has mirror symmetry.

In fact, space has more complete meta-symmetry. This meta-symmetry is automatically obtained in the later defined dimensions. For example, this meta-symmetry is automatically obtained for speed, acceleration, temperature, pressure, etc.

Because we use the equation of state in mathematics. Logically, this is an isolated equation. It only describes the state S itself; and does not describe the relationship with neighboring states. For states $S1 \rightarrow S2$. Our equation of state F only says that $F(S1) = 0, F(S2) = 0$. Without specifying the sequence of $S1$ and $S2$. In other words, our equation of state F , from the formal logic, must also include its inversion process $S2 \rightarrow S1$. This is caused by mathematical methods, so it is called "pseudo". Therefore, there are:

Pseudo Time Inversion Theorem: Physical laws have inversion symmetry for time.

Due to the meta-symmetry of time, other factors such as time and space are irrelevant. Therefore, time is independent of path.

In the end, time is just a representation of pure thinking logic; the key is to satisfy the "time topology" and self-consistency. At the same time, we should refer to the history of civilization as much as possible.

Any two objects A and B are separated at time 0 (denoted as C events) and then re-engaged together (denoted as D events).

According to "**Time-Topology-2**", C is an absolute topology for both parties, and D is also.

Regardless of A or B , the time elapsed is the same reality determined by C to D . So things are equal. therefore:

Time Path Independence Theorem: Time is independent of path.

7) Rigid Body Length and Duration of Object Point Process

When the standard ruler is relatively stationary and close to the object, the measured object length is named as the **rigid body length**.

When we talk about the length of an object at ordinary times, we use the object as a rigid body model, for example, the height of the physical examination.

The rigid body length has nothing to do with the frame of reference, because it has locked the frame of

reference, that is, the frame of reference that is still attached to it; at the same time, due to the measurement with the physical ruler, the influence of the gravitational field is shielded.

In the sense of self-consistency, the ideal point-shaped clock which is not affected by the outside world and its state, and is always consistent, is named the **standard clock**. It reflects the logic of time itself. Therefore, its characteristic is that time has nothing to do with path.

Point-like object without rotation is named **object-point**.

When the standard clock and the object-point remain stationary, the increment of the standard clock value is named as the **object-point time** ζ .

Events can be associated with an object-point, so this time is also the time interval of events.

The time that an object experiences has nothing to do with the frame of reference, because it has locked the frame of reference, that is, the frame of reference that remains stationary with it; and at the same time, due to the definition of the standard clock, it shields the influence of the gravitational field.

The time and length defined here are at the entity level of the object. That is, it has nothing to do with observation.

8) Geodetic Time Representation, Geodetic Space Representation, Reference Time representation and Reference Space Representation of Events

The above definition ensures the strictness of logic. In fact, the same is true.

However, there are simplified expressions for specific social applications.

The above definition requires a static fit with the object. Then when you understand this value, you have to "still fit" once. Then you need to know the original motion state of the object. There is no problem with the length of an absolute rigid body, because its definition ensures that it will not change, so just find a system. But the reality is much more complicated. This is very complicated in reality.

The key here is the background frame of reference. In reality, a well-known **standard frame of reference** is defined, such as the earth. First, use the above strict definition to establish a standard timing and positioning system in this coordinate system. The timing and positioning of the event at this point in the standard frame of reference are named **geodetic time representation** and **geodetic space representation** of the event. This is an event.

Geodetic temporal representation and geodetic spatial representation are at the event entity level. That is, it has nothing to do with the observation process. This is due to the existence of a standard reference system, so that this value can be understood consistently across different observers.

Because of its simplicity and high efficiency, the archival system records events with geodetic temporal representation and geodetic spatial representation.

Here, actually speaking from the "earth" side, the time and space of events are recorded from the earth's perspective.

On the contrary. In physics, the timing and positioning of an event in the temporarily selected frame of reference is named the event's **reference time representation** and **reference space representation**. It is based on events. It actually corresponds to the phenomenon of events, that is, the specific phenomenon observed by the observer.

Therefore, the reference time representation and the reference space representation are at the event phenomenon level. That is, it is related to the observation process. This is because this value cannot be understood consistently across different observers.

Theory of relativity expands in time and shrinks in space, contrary to reality. And then endanger the reality of the corresponding things; thus jeopardizing the completeness of the theory.

This also violates the yong-name-theorem.

The fundamental reason is that it violates two-law-antinomy. That is, there are multiple definitions for one reality. Conflicts arise between different definitions. It is defined once in each frame of reference, which is logically not allowed.

The solution here is to define it only once in one frame of reference. Standard clocks are used to define the event intervals of events in a frame of reference that is relatively stationary with respect to objects. The length of an object is defined by a standard ruler in a frame of reference that is relatively stationary with respect to the object.

Mr. Einstein confused two completely different things: the relative motion reference system and the gravitational field. The former is only an observer effect, is transparent, does not involve the objective presence itself.

For the latter, the objective presence is actually affected by the gravitational field, which is also part of guest presence. It affects the actual duration of the ticking.

So he mistakenly equated all τ as the standard of real time. In fact, the actual time of each tick corresponding to τ is different, so τ can not be used as the standard of actual time.

So he inappropriately equated all τ as the standard of actual time. In fact, the actual time of each tick corresponding to τ is different, so τ can not be used as the standard of actual time.

He brought the process of light into the time measurement and made the measurement continuous; it is not appropriate. The result destroyed "the finiteness of absolute deviation and the relative deviation approaching 0"; the result is that the absolute deviation can be infinitely amplified and the relative deviation does not approach 0.

Let's talk about **the length operator and the time operator**.

The standard frame of reference and the general frame of reference face event apparent. Do not face objects and specific processes. Operators are required to face objects and specific processes; geodetic time representation, geodetic space representation, reference time representation and reference space representation are all operators. The rigid body length L and the object-point time ζ are also operators.

9) Force Equivalence Theorem

People cannot see the force. Only the kinematic effect, that is, the change of the object's motion state, can be seen.

All the acting forces are a decomposed correspondence of the change effect of the motion state of the object. It's just a logical argument.

Therefore, all forces and inertial forces are equivalent to each other.

Force Equivalence Theorem: All forces and inertial forces are equivalent to each other.

The Gravitational And Inertial Force Equivalent Theorem: Universal gravitational force and inertial force are equivalent. It faces the principle of equivalence.

10) Inertia and Newton's Bucke

1> General understanding

Inertia is understood as the opposite of force.

The cause of momentum change is named impulse force.

When the state of motion changes, we say it is affected. On the contrary, there is no force, and the corresponding motion becomes **inertial motion**. The kinematic logic of inertial motion is named **inertia**. Based on self-consistency, purely logically, the force corresponding to the extra part of motion change in a specific frame of reference is named **inertial force**.

In fact, inertia and force are named together. Contact each other through self-consistency. They are like a pair of mirror-images.

Generally, force is defined by human initiative. Then inertia is the logic of passive mirroring.

So there are:

$$\text{Inertia} = \text{Mirror image}(\text{of force})$$

Therefore, inertia can only be specifically understood through the definition of force. The definition of function is different, so is the meaning of inertia.

From the perspective of generality, there is only the above formula of pure form. The specific meaning does not exist.

At the same time, the isolated thinking of understanding inertia as an obstacle to movement changes is too narrow.

The gravitational mass and inertial mass are opposed. In fact, the two are mirror images. It's an integrated thing, but with different perspectives.

Inertia and force form a self-consistent tautology about the state of motion.

Finally, the inertia can only be understood from the self-consistency of the motion state. Get the mirror image of the effect.

Fundamentally speaking, it is only a kinematic problem.

Inertial force is a virtual thing that is logically mirrored, so long as it satisfies logical self-consistency. Therefore, **the inertial force does not require an actuator and have not reaction force**.

From the derivation process, the reaction force comes from the internal force logic. Inertia is inherently an external force. Therefore there is no reaction.

The actuator is logically derived from the analysis of the source. The inertial force is not like this, it comes from pure mathematical transformation, so no actuator is created for it.

It is seriously inappropriate to understand inertia as the function of the whole universe. It will turn physics into the story of "needlepoint angel". Physics is an exact quantitative discipline. The whole universe cannot be accurately depicted, quantified, described or tested.

2> Several Mechanical Models

In Newtonian mechanics, force is defined as acting force.

Inertia is understood from the angle of acting force.

In general relativity, gravitational force is defined as curved space-time.
Therefore inertia is also understood from space-time geometry.

In theory of absolutivity, gravity is defined as force.
Inertia is understood from the angle of acting force.

3> Square and Circle — Two Movements

Two kinds of different symmetries are inherently unconquerable, that is, rectangular axis symmetry and rotational symmetry.

Corresponding to two dimensions, rectangular axis dimension and angle dimension.

The dimension of the right-angle coordinate axis can be extended endlessly and repeatedly.

The angle dimension is circular.

Corresponding to two completely different motion states.

Correspondent square and circle problem.

In the bucket problem. This is not an absolute space problem or an absolute motion problem. It has nothing to do with absolute space and absolute motion.

It only reflects the square and circle problems.

Square and circle are two absolutely different logical structures. It corresponds to two completely different movements.

Moreover, linear motion and circular motion are equal in themselves.

It cannot be said that circular motion is absolute motion or linear motion is absolute motion. They are equal.

Therefore, it is inappropriate to regard the bucket problem as an absolute space problem and an absolute motion problem.

It's just two different sports.

4> Square and Circle — Inertia

When we specify a linear motion for the motion form whose state has not changed. This defines force. At the same time, inertia is defined in mirror image.

However, circular motion and linear motion are definitely not the same kind of motion. Their topological logic is different. This assertion does not require any reference system to participate.

Thus, in this definition, circular motion must not be inertial motion.

However, this does not mean that circular motion is absolute motion, nor does it mean that circular motion is relative to absolute spatial motion. It's just one of many sports. But because circular motion and linear motion have completely different topological logic.

5> Looking for Reference System in Newton's Bucket Problem

Because inertia is a mirror image of force. Therefore, in order to understand the inertia problem, one must start from the force. For example, the definition of force and the balance of force.

First consider the equilibrium state of Newton's bucket on earth. At this time, the liquid level is curved. Unlike a calm liquid level.

The bending of the liquid surface is caused by the balance of forces. Specifically, the earth's gravity and inertia.

The key here is the gravity of the earth. The definition of gravity measurement of the earth involves a frame

of reference, the earth.

Therefore, in this problem, there is a frame of reference, namely the earth; the bucket rotates relative to the earth. The key is that the measurement of (gravity) universal gravitation depends on the frame of reference.

6> Reference System in Space Bucket Problem

The equilibrium state of a rotating liquid sphere in space. At this point the sphere becomes ellipsoid. Different from a sphere at rest.

Ellipsoid is caused by the balance of forces. Specifically, internal force and inertia.

The key here is internal force. The definition of specific measure of internal force involves a frame of reference.

Specific from the definition of the internal force logic.

Specifically, find out from the definition logic of the internal force.

If we do not consider gravity, we only consider surface tension. That is electromagnetic force. The measurement of electromagnetic force depends heavily on the frame of reference. The frame of reference used to define the surface tension state of a sphere at rest is the frame of reference to be found. That is, we define the frame of reference for measuring the static surface tension of the sphere.

If it is a gravity ball that only considers universal gravitation. That is gravity. The measure of universal gravitation also depends on the frame of reference. The frame of reference used in the definition of the measure of universal gravitation is the frame of reference to be found. This is the frame of reference that we use to define the static gravity measurement of the sphere.

(2) Perceptual Process Analysis

Look at the tree in front. Do we really see the tree itself?

According to current knowledge, sunlight is reflected to people's eyes by trees. It was thus observed. So, instead of observing the tree, we observe the light reflected by the tree to human eyes.

Not only is the subject and object incorrect.

Moreover, time is not right. According to current knowledge, there is a time difference between the light rays hitting the human eye. What the human eye sees is another thing afterwards. For example, a bee fell from a tree at time t_1 , which is event A. At time t_2 , the light of A hits the human eye, and when people see the incident of A, they record the incident of B. $\Delta t = t_2 - t_1 > 0$. B and A are two completely different things. A is actually not seen by human eyes at all. What the human eye sees is B.

We can still go on. According to current knowledge, the consciousness system cannot look at light either. It needs to be converted into electrical signals, transmitted to the consciousness system, sensed by the consciousness system, and recorded as Event C. The subject and object are not correct. Similarly, propagation results in another time difference Δt_2 . The time is not right either.

The so-called "see the tree" and "the tree see" are only subjective creations in people's thinking consciousness. What people perceive is only some primitive perception.

(3) Pangu Space-time Representation

1) Pangu Time Representation and Sensory-time representation

The continuously increasing sequence of original perception of a single sense source is named **pangu time representation**. The continuously increasing sequence of the original perception of a single sense source is named

the **sensory-time representation**. It and other reference-time representations are collectively called **reference-time representations**.

From any state-A to any state-B, then state-B is a simple increment of state-A,

Record as state-B $>$ state-A, also record as state-A $<$ state-B.

For example, when one ear is listening, it will hear the sound 1, the sound 2, the sound 3, and so on. . . Its corresponding sequence is called the reference time representation. Note that what is said here is sound, not sound with special meaning.

As for eyes, study one eye first. Moreover, it is emphasized here that the original perception everywhere in front of us has no priority. Otherwise, treat it as a compound eye and study the one in the compound eye first. A complete phase is presented directly and completely, just like a traditional photosensitive camera. Note that what is said here is the original phase (photo image) with no meaning, just like the color dot matrix people say today. There are no special shapes like pigs, dogs, cats, trees, circles and triangles.

Of course, some people say that he can get it directly at once, especially those who have received special training, but what I emphasize here is the original feeling of the same sense source. Obviously, those complicated senses are not the direct original feeling of the eyes, are not from a sense source, and are not a sequence (generally speaking, those complicated senses have thinking or nerve intervention, and thus are another sense source).

Pangu Time Representation Irreversibility Theorem: Pangu time representation is Irreversible.

Proof: Otherwise, state-B will return to the previous state-A.

According to the naming of pangu time representation, state-B is added to state-A, state-B $>$ state-A.

And state-B to state-A, this is pangu time representation sequence, so we have:

state-B $<$ state-A.

Contradiction. Q.E.D.

2) Pangu Space-time Representation

Pangu space representation is empty. The pangu events were all piled up on the Pangu time axis.

(4) Nuwa-Reference-Space-time Representation

1) Local-Reference-Time Representation and Common-Reference-Time Representation

Pangu time representation is actually the sensory-time representation. In fact, the common reference-time representation is finally realized in nuwa-reference-space-time, which requires the assistance of the assistant reference-space dimension. Of course, pangu time representation can also be merged simply and directly without the intervention of reference-space representation .

Sensory-time representation is a local reference-time representation. Everyone has his own independent sensory-time representation. Moreover, a person has multiple independent sensory-time representation, one for each source. In addition, in different links of sensory transmission, there are different sensory-time representation.

The question is whether one person has so many sensory-time representations, can they be combined into one reference-time representation, and whether different people's reference-time representations can be combined into one reference-time representation.

The synthesized reference-time representation is named **nuwa reference-time representation**. In which an event can be created subjectively.

The simple and directly combined reference-time representation without the intervention of reference-space

from "sensory-time representation".

2> The merged sequence is subjective, and this "drift" (drifting from one sequence to another) is easily misleading. Only by returning to the original "sensory-time representation" is that objective. People often fail to notice this "drift".

3> So far, the reference-time representation is only an ordinal number, that is, an ordinal number, not a cardinal number.

Some people may say that different sequences may exist in reverse order and cannot be merged.

In series 1, " $A < B$ "; in series 2, " $A > B$ ".

First of all, it should be noted that this is not an ontology. The two series are independent and are not related. Therefore, fundamentally speaking, there is no "reverse order" problem. This is because "reverse order" is premised on correlation. There is no original "identity" of "ontology".

Secondly, besides, in reality, it does appear that people feel opposite about the timing of the 2 events. But this is subjective, that is, people merge different information, resulting in most of the same, local differences.

This problem is a matter for the mind to know itself. Only after this contradiction has been resolved can the merger take place.

The "thing" here is not at the level of "sensory-time representation". There is no such cross-series thing as "thing" in the sensory-time representation. The sequence of the sensory-time representation level is within this series. From this level, the above two series are independent without any contradiction. Of course, there is no "one sequence". These are two independent series.

They were like this: $A1 < B1$

$A2 > B2$

In this way, there is no contradiction.

People may think subjectively that " $A1 = A2 = A$ $B1 = B2 = B$ ".

This is the problem. Resulting in " $A < B$ $A > B$ ".

This is what happened before the reference-time representation. There is no fundamental contradiction with the reference-time representation. It's like some people think " $1 + 1 = 9$ "; it's not related to it.

After people think so subjectively, it is not suitable for the reference-time appearance.

So how to solve this realistic problem?

1> The problem lies in this "subjective view".

2> If there is no such thing as $A1$, $A2$, $B1$, $B2$, there would be no problem.

So there are 2 solutions:

1> The new "subjective view" makes the order not contradictory. The common method is splitting and reordering: changing the order in another series.

For example, $A1$ and $A2$ of A above are no longer one sequence but two sequences. $A2$ is delayed to $A2'$ in sequence 2. There are $A2' = A2 = C$ $B1 = B2 = B$

series1: $A1 < B1$

series2: $B2 < A2'$

merged:

$A1 < B < C$

2> One of them is taken as a slave series, and a new series is regenerated according to certain rules and then

merged. For example, when you move against a sound source, the series you hear is different from that of a watch. At this time, people subjectively try to rearrange, "try to eliminate the differences caused by sports", generate new sequences, and then merge them.

Note that the series heard at this time and the series seen at the watch are independent of each other and have nothing to do with each other. People here "pull" together subjectively.

3> Neglect method. If people think that a certain sequence is not so important, they can discard some or all of these sequences. There is no corresponding sequence in the merged order.

Some people may feel very surprised. Is this still studying?

But what I want to say is that this is a common practice. For example, most of the time sequences in the dream will not be pursued, but simply say "it is just a dream"; it will be written off. There are still those long-term memories, most of which will not be pursued, but simply say "it is just a memory"; it will be written off.

At this point, the reference-time representation applied to the whole society is "created".

Note that, the meaning of standard time in actual use will only be cared about. Beyond the actual use, there is nothing to be done.

The name "reference-time representation" needs to be related. It is to know how a sequence relates to the actual process in life.

For example, when it comes to spring, summer, autumn and winter, one can relate to different phases on the sundial.

For example, when it comes to 1: 00, 2: 00 and 3: 00, you can contact different phases on the hand table. (At present, it is only limited to ordinal function)

The name of reference-time representation is understood by means of contact. It is on this shore. The name of reference-time representation is not "what it is" on the other side of ontology.

The Basic Properties of Ordinal Reference-time Representation:

1> Connectivity

Knowing how a sequence relates to the process of life.

2> Orderliness

The order is certain.

3> Irreversibility

Ordinal reference-time representation is **irreversible**.

4> Infinite separability

Ordinal reference-time representation is infinitely divisible.

It is defined as infinitely separable, because logically, when merging, other events are always allowed to be inserted in the middle, and always so.

The direction in which the reference-time representation sequence extends is named the **future** direction. The opposite direction is named the **past** direction.

The sequence corresponding to the reference-time representation sequence being formed is named **present**. **It stipulates that the present is the dividing line between the past and the future.**

Note: The reference-time representation in this article is on this side.

The above reference-time representation is only ordinal, which is called **ordinal reference-time representation**. You can **only sort and compare the order**. **No four operations** can be performed.

2) Cardinal Reference-time Representation

The following is "creating the cardinal reference-time representation". Can participate in four operations.

Theoretically, the same reference-time representation interval is repeatedly generated by a mechanism; and each time interval is regarded as an equivalent "1"; there is no difference for each "1" here; this reference-time representation is named the **thinking reference-time representation**.

In reality, first of all, it is necessary to select a specific reference-time representation sequence, and adjacent timing difference is defined as no difference, that is, there is no difference in the thinking tool of cardinal reference-time representation. Adjacent timing differences are directly specified as the same, and this timing difference is named as the **reference-time representation of "1" unit**. This reference-time representation is named the **real reference-time representation**. Real reference-time representation is a concrete realization of thinking reference-time representation.

For example, the daily sunrise constitutes a time sequences. In creating the "sunrise" base time, the time span between adjacent time sequences is directly **defined** as the same, and this time is named "1" unit of time. This is the "1" day.

Note that 1 day is equal here. There is only one base time and no other reference, so it is impossible to confirm or deny it.

The equivalent "1" actually corresponds to "one can expect some consistency in life".

This "1" is, in the final analysis, a "1" in life. Each "1" day corresponds to a certain consistency in life, such as arranging the same workload or getting the same harvest.

Note: this "choice" is purely logical, without prior judgment.

On the contrary, if, regardless of day and night, both day and night are treated as a "1" to arrange the same workload, this is another kind.

Some people will say that the earth's rotation period remains unchanged, "originally" is one sunrise a day, with sunrise as "1". why bother?

But this "originally" reveals that this sentence comes from "ontology", not the category of this theory.

This theory is not ontology. There would be no support for the "prescient" belief, and there would be no knowledge of the "originally" of the belief.

So far, this article has no knowledge about the earth.

Note: Due to two-law-antinomy, there can be only one basic unit of reference-time representation in this knowledge. Other units of reference-time representation can only be subordinate to it.

At present, the basic reference-time representation unit is Earth day. Years, months, weeks, hours, minutes and seconds are subordinate to it.

A day is divided into 24 small "1", and each small "1" means "1" hours. One day is exactly divided by 24 consecutive small ones. How to calculate "uniformity", that is, the "selection" of this small "1", is the same as the above process.

Similarly, an hour is divided into 60 small "1" which is "1" minute. The basic unit is minutes.

Similarly, a minute is divided into 60 small "1" which is "1" second. The basic unit is second.

Now, there are new basic units of time, not to mention, the basic selection process is the same.

Let's talk about the **four operations** of the reference-time representation.

Because (it is stipulated that) every "1" is the same, so can be **combined** together to say; many details were abandoned in the combining; only how many "1" are there without difference.

One day plus one day can be combined and said directly for two days. When it comes to 2 days, it doesn't matter which day is before and which day is after, whether it is two consecutive days, specifically which 2 days. In this way, **addition** can be specified.

$$1+1 = 2 \text{ (days)}$$

5 times the "2 days" can be combined to say 10 days. In this way, **multiplication** can be specified.

$$5 \times 2 = 10 \text{ (days)}$$

Subtraction is defined as the inverse of addition. **Division** is defined as the inverse of multiplication.

Thus, four operations can be performed.

Cardinal Reference-time Representation Uniformity Theorem: Cardinal Reference-time representation is Uniform.

Proof: It is stipulated above that the reference-time representation of each "1" unit is the same and there is no difference. Q.E.D.

The Basic Properties of Cardinal Reference-time Representation:

1> Connectivity

Knowing how a sequence relates to the process of life.

There is a realistic foundation for its "mechanism". There is usually a realistic clock.

2> Orderliness

The order is certain.

3> Irreversibility

Reference-time representation is irreversible.

4> Infinite separability

Time representation is infinitely divisible.

5> Uniformity

Reference-time representation is uniform.

6> Operationality

Four operations can be performed.

Note that although concrete real reference-time representation is often used to replace it, the reference-time representation in this knowledge actually refers to the thinking reference-time representation. The clock will stop, but **the thinking reference-time representation will not stop for it.**

Cardinal reference-time representation is a special ordinal reference-time representation constructed artificially in thinking.

Duration Unknown Theorem: How long is "1" unit reference-time representation (the other side) is unknown; furthermore, how long the reference-time representation (the other side) is unknown.

Proof: Because "1" unit reference-time representation is the first reference-time representation length, there is no other reference, so I don't know how long it is ("1" unit reference-time representation is directly stipulated as the same). Since it is not known how long the "1" unit reference-time is, it is not known how long the reference-time representation composed of multiple "1" unit reference-time representations is. Q.E.D.

Some people may worry that this will lead to incomprehensible reference-time representation. This theory is

not ontology; there is no problem; this theory is understood through contact.

The length of the "1" unit reference-time representation is named **pangu reference-time representation unit** and is specified as 1. The pangu reference-time representation unit is a constant of pangu reference-space-time representation.

3) Reference-space Representation

In the merging of different reference-time representation sequences, such phenomena will occur. On the one hand, the two cannot be distinguished in order and actually merge, but on the other hand, they still need to be distinguished in life.

For example, you can see an apple (left) and a pear (right) in front of you. For the sake of simplicity, only two different sensory-time representation sequences are considered.

Now we want to combine these two sensory-time representation sequences. According to the previous regulations, superposition will be found. That is, there is an apple and a pear in the same reference-time representation order.

In order to express this distinction, we need to re-create auxiliary sequences.

Because the sensory-time representation sequences are independent, there is no order relationship between them. So we have to create order relations.

Here we use the order of sensory-time representation to express this relationship.

Here we **borrow** the order of sensory-time representation to express this relationship.

We do a specific action — "move like this" (head moves from "right" to "left"). First, pears enter the eye sensory-time representation sequence, and then apples enter the eye sensory-time representation sequence. In this way, pears and apples have different orders in eye sensory-time representation sequence. This process is named **reference-space representation process**.

This auxiliary order is named **reference-space representation**.

Note: The "left" and "right" above are quoted to indicate that they are fictitious names. Because there is no reference-space representation, naturally there is no left or right side to say. It can be written as "this" and "that" and only expresses the specific meaning. If I really write like this, it is not easy to understand.

At the same time, the **left** and **right** are named according to the extension direction and reverse direction of this sequence. This auxiliary sequence is named **left-right** sequence.

If there are 4 different fruits in front, arrange them in "up and down" 2 rows. At this time, it is still impossible to express this distinction in life.

Similarly, do a specific action — "move like this" (move your head from "up" to "down"). Therefore, there is another sensory-time representation of auxiliary senses. This auxiliary sensory-time representation sequence is also named as a reference-space representation sequence.

At the same time, the **up** and **down** are named according to the extension direction and reverse direction of this sequence. This auxiliary sequence is named **up-down** sequence.

In this way, we have 2 auxiliary reference-space representation sequences.

If there are 8 different fruits in front, arrange them in "up and down" 2 rows and "front and back" 2 rows. This is still unable to fully express this distinction in life.

Similarly, do a specific action — "move like this" (move your feet "forward"). Therefore, different fruits enter the secondary eye sensory-time representation sequence in turn. Therefore, there is another auxiliary

sensory-time representation sequence. This auxiliary sensory-time representation sequence is also named as a reference-space representation sequence.

At the same time, the **front** and **back** are named according to the extension direction and reverse direction of this sequence. This auxiliary sequence is named the **front-back** sequence.

So we have 3 auxiliary reference-space representation sequences.

So we can distinguish 8 fruit sequences by 3 reference-space sequences. In fact, many things can be distinguished.

In this way, depending on 1 reference-time representation sequence and 3 reference-space representation sequences, a total of 4 **reference-space-time representation** sequences can be used to distinguish the different reference-time representation states of eight fruits.

These 4 sequences are named **4 dimensions**. At present, we have created 4 dimensional reference-space-time representation, 1 dimensional reference-time representation and 3 dimensional reference-space representation.

Reference-space representation sequence is created by using reference-time representation sequence.

The sequence of reference-space representation created by using ordinal reference-time representation is named **ordinal reference-space representation**.

The sequence of reference-space representation created by using cardinal reference-time representation is named **cardinal reference-space representation**.

Cardinal reference-space representation involves the measurement of reference-space representation.

Note: The reference-space representation in this knowledge is on this shore.

4) There Are Several Dimensions to Spatial Representation

This is a problem that people are generally concerned about and can not be ignored.

First of all, there is a problem with this problem itself. It seems to imply that there is a space of "being what it is", and let's see how many dimensions it has.

This knowledge does not study noumenon.

The "being what it is" space is invisible. For example, a plane in the sky. Do we see the space outside the plane that is what it is?

No, in this knowledge, we study the original perception we see. What we see is the visual image produced by "eyes", which is not outside the body. So what you see is neither space nor things in space.

Let's look at "the scene on the retina".

In fact, the "eyeball" and "retina" are both created in the later period.

The scene in this learning, starts from the more difficult and abstract "viewpoint", which is named **pangu-space-time-point**. Correspondingly it is reference-spatially called **pangu-point**, also called **"I" point**.

The reference-space in this knowledge is a thinking tool for creation, corresponding to only one sequence.

The question corresponding to this knowledge is: **how many dimensions of space need to be created to be sufficient**.

For simple problems, use fewer dimensions. Complex problems may require more dimensions.

The same problem has more or less dimensions.

For example, seats in cinemas. It can be either 2-dimensional or 1-dimensional.

Let's talk about 2 dimensions first. According to the row and column numbers, the row is 1 dimension and the column is 1 dimension. Number: a row and a column (seat). The advantage is convenient maintenance.

Besides, one dimension, numbering starts from the left of the first row, then the second row, follows the

number on the previous line. In this way, all actions can be represented by a 1-dimensional sequence: a certain seat. The advantage is simplicity.

5) Why is Reference-space Representation 3-dimensional

We say that reference-space representation is three-dimensional. In fact, this is only a general reference-space representation model. This is not the only way.

Why is it three-dimensional? **This is related to our body structure.**

People have a lot of muscles. Muscle can drive body changes.

However, from the perspective of original perception, the effects produced by all muscles can be combined into a combination of 3 independent effects: left and right, up and down, front and back. Correspondingly, 3 reference-space auxiliary dimensions are sufficient.

In this way, the effect function $f(x)$ corresponding to the reference-space representation can be written as $f(x^1, x^2, x^3)$, and the reference-space representation (x) can be written as (x^1, x^2, x^3) .

In this way, our reference-space representation is now 3-dimensional. This is said in a self-consistent sense.

However, in the theory of absolutivity of dynamics, five dimensions are actually needed, namely, 1-dimensional time, 3-dimensional space and 1-dimensional phase.

Some people say that space is therefore 3-dimensional according to the inverse square ratio of gravity and coulomb force. This won't do.

The formula used here is actually $ES=\text{constant}$. This shows no inverse square ratio. The effect of gravity and coulomb force is inversely proportional to the square. But there are also forces that are not inversely square, such as the magnetic field of long straight wires. Some people may say that gravity, coulomb force is the basic force. But this kind of "basic" is only subjective identification.

6) Construction of Cardinal Reference-space Representation

In pangu reference-space representation, there was no space to spread, and everything was "instant arrival" — "**perception is arrival**". These original perceptual information are isolated from each other and have no correlation.

From pangu-point where there is no space to the space where there is a wide extension and a uniform scale, we need to **specify** a constant speed w , **blow** the copy of the original information from the pangu-point "I" to the specified position evenly, and use the information that is uniform in time to form a uniform spatial scale. This movement is named **pangu reference movement**, also known as the **reference nuwa reference movement**. Its movement speed is specified as a fixed "1" unit speed. Note that we cannot measure and check the speed before the space is established, so we can only **specify** the speed of a certain movement as a fixed "1" unit speed.

This fixed speed is named **pangu-speed**, which is recorded as w , also known as the **reference nuwa speed**.

$$dl \equiv w * dt$$

Pangu reference-space representation is empty and has a uniform scale of reference-space representation (the copy is discarded after being blown into the reference-space representation to form a scale). This is different from nuwa reference-space representation. There are events in nuwa reference-space representation, and the copies are in nuwa reference-space representation. Here, the key of pangu reference-space representation is to "create" a reference-space representation that can hold things. As for how the event information is placed in the

reference-space representation, it is very complicated and related to nuwa system.

Pangu-time-scale and pangu-speed w are two structural constants of pangu space-time representation.

The pangu-speed has nothing to do with the movement state of "I" but should follow "I". My walking speed and arm extension speed are all satisfied because they move with me.

It is artificially stipulated that a certain basic perceptual phase state is its **motion initiation state** and a certain basic perceptual phase state is its **motion arrival state**. In the middle is a sequence of basic perceptual phase states named **intermediate process states**. In this way, for original perception, an orderly association has been established artificially: initial state — intermediate process state — arrival state. Some motion arrival states are artificially selected as spatial construction points. Pangu reference-space reference motion, from the initial state of motion at "I" to the arrival state at this spatial structure point, has a reference-time representation interval of dt (or vice versa); then we **specify** that the spatial distance dl from here to "I" is defined as $w*dt$, and the reverse distance dl is also defined as $w*dt$. In this way, the measured spatio-temporal coordinate difference of the spatial construction points is (dt,dl) , where $|dl|=w*dt$. Note that the positive and negative directions are the same here.

Pangu reference-space reference motion, from the initial state of motion at "I" to the arrival state at this spatial structure point, has a reference-time representation interval of dt (or vice versa)

The distance dl from any point in space to "I" (the origin) is defined as:

$$|dl|=w*dt$$

The formula is named **reference-space distance definition**.

After squaring: $dl^2=(w*dt)^2$

An hour's walk from village A to village B. "To Village B" needs spatial definition, otherwise I don't know "where", which is the visual perception phase state for us human beings now. The same is true of "From village A".

About **measuring with a ruler**. Ruler measurement is to measure the other reference-space representation extension with the reference-space representation extension of the ruler.

But if the reference-space representation has not been created, where did the reference-space representation of the ruler come from?

In fact, the pangu-speed was used to create a uniform reference-space representation. Then use this uniform reference-space representation to create the reference-spatial structure of everything such as ruler. This uniform reference-space representation created first provides support for this. Then, the extensiveness of the reference-space representation structure of the ruler is used to measure the extensiveness of the reference-space representation structure of other things. This uniform reference-space representation created first provides support for measuring everything with a ruler.

In other words, after the reference-space representation was created, the units of the space were "changed". For the same w , the proportion is fixed, it doesn't matter.

The referencespace representation corresponding to pangu speed and $1/n$ second is defined as 1 meter. Then $1 \text{ meter} = w * \text{one-second}/n$.

$$w=n \text{ meter/second}$$

But for different environments, such as vacuum, air and water, this n is different for the structure of ruler, $n_1 > n_2 > n_3$. Then the length of the ruler will be different.

However, we subjectively **stipulate** that the length of the ruler is constant, which in turn causes w to vary, $w_1 > w_2 > w_3$.

The advantage of using a ruler is that it can shield the difference of nuwa-speed ω . The measured length thus remains unchanged. It is easy to know that this invariance comes from artificial regulations.

Relationships:

Speed $w \Leftrightarrow$ cardinal space representation \Leftrightarrow object structure \Leftrightarrow ruler \Leftrightarrow

"Confirmed" Ruler Length Invariant \Leftrightarrow Reference-space Representation Length 2 \Leftrightarrow Speed 2

As the basic speed, the pangu-speed is unknown. Furthermore, it is not clear how fast is any speed?

Unknown Speed Theorem: The basic pangu-speed and all speeds are unknown.

Furthermore, it is not clear how long the unit reference-space representation is. Furthermore, it is not clear how long the reference-space representation is.

Unknown Reference-space Theorem: It is not clear how long the unit reference-space representation and the reference-space representation are.

Reference-space is Reference-time Theorem: Ordinal reference-space representation is ordinal reference-time representation; the cardinal reference-space representation is the cardinal reference-time representation. Reference-space representation is reference-time representation.

Proof: reference-space representation is an auxiliary dimension of reference-temporal representation. Since the reference-space representation sequence is expressed by the reference-temporal representation sequence. In this way, it is impossible to fundamentally distinguish between reference-temporal representation and reference-space representation.

One more thing. The reference-space representation had no ordinal number or quantity, but was given by the reference-temporal representation. The number of such reference-space representations actually refers to the number of reference-temporal representations.

For example, it is an hour's walk between the two villages. One hour of reference-time representation here expresses the distance between the two villages.

For example, the two cities are two hours away by car. The two hours of reference-time representation here express the distance between the two cities.

Even the cloth is 3 meters. According to specific specifications, use a meter-ruler to measure the cloth, one reference-time representation sequence at a time. There are 3 reference-time representation sequences. (Note that this knowledge does not know the length of the other side of "what it is.")

We say this is longer than that, and it is also a comparison of the size of the reference-time representation interval.

Q.E.D.

This theorem denies the independence of reference-space representation.

Cardinal Reference-space Representation Uniformity Theorem: Representation of Cardinal reference-space is Uniform.

Proof: Since the cardinal reference-space representation directly borrows the cardinal reference-time

representation and the cardinal reference-time representation is uniform, then the cardinal reference-space representation is uniform, that is, the reference-space representation of each "1" unit is the same and there is no difference.

Q.E.D.

Because the spatial representation is directly borrowed from the temporal representation, there follows.

Basic Characteristics of Ordinal Reference-space Representation:

1> **Connectivity**

In life, we know how this reference-space representation sequence is connected with the life process.

2> **Orderliness**

The order is certain.

3> **Infinite separability**

Infinitely separable.

The Basic Characteristics of Representation in Cardinal Reference-space:

1> **Connectivity**

In life, we know how this reference-space representation sequence is connected with the life process.

2> **Orderliness**

The order is certain.

3> **Infinite separability**

Infinitely separable.

4> **Uniformity**

Uniform.

5> **Operationality**

Four operations can be performed.

7) Reference Frame

Reference Frame : A multi-dimensional sequence starting from a point marked with time and space; each ordinal number is arranged in sequence, thus forming an ordered array [sequence 1, sequence 2, sequence 3, sequence 4]. For convenience, it is stipulated that the starting point is 0. And it stipulates that all our description rules are consistent. This point is named the **origin**. Ordered arrays are used to represent perception and everything.

If only the reference-space representation dimension is included here, the set composed of all these ordered arrays becomes the **reference-space representation**.

If only the reference-time representation is included here, the set of all these ordered arrays becomes the **reference-time representation**.

If there are reference-time representation and reference-space representation dimensions, the set of all these ordered arrays becomes the **reference-space-time representation**.

Starting from the origin, simply change one ordinal number and keep the other ordinals unchanged at 0. Such a set is named the **coordinate axis**.

There are three coordinate axes for the three-dimensional space representation.

For 4-dimensional reference-space-time representation, there is 1 coordinate axis of reference-time representation and 3 coordinate axes of reference-space representation.

The following focuses on the 3-dimensional reference-space representation.

Theorem 1: The points of a reference-space representation or a reference-space-time representation consist of 3 independent reference-space coordinates.

Proof: Otherwise, the name [sequence 1, sequence 2, sequence 3, sequence 4] is violated.

Theorem 2: A sequence of points in a reference-space representation or a reference-time representation corresponds to a unique sequence.

Proof: First of all, there is only one "number", otherwise the name [sequence 1, sequence 2, sequence 3, sequence 4] is violated.

Secondly, this order ("number") can only be unique, otherwise it violates the simple order of reference-time and reference-space dimensions.

Theorem 3: The reference-time representation in the reference-space-time representation is uniform, and the dimension of any reference-space representation is also uniform.

Proof: Otherwise, the uniformity of time series and space series is violated.

Theorem 4: Reference-space representation is uniform.

Proof: Because all the dimensions that make up a reference-space representation are uniform;

Thus, the reference-space representation is made up of several "1" cubes (2-dimensional space is square) with equal sides

Theorem 5: Reference-time representation has only one dimension in reference-space-time representation, and reference-space representation can have multiple dimensions.

Proof: Otherwise, it violates the naming of the reference-space-time representation.

How to understand this theorem 5? Why is the reference-space representation so different from the reference-time representation? According to the naming process of the above reference-space representation, the reference-space representation is subordinate to the reference-temporal representation. Because of its dependency, there can be multiple.

In fact, put it another way. Reference-space representation and reference-time representation are actually the same thing, that is, the ordering of various basic perceptions. First, a primary sequence is created and named as reference-time representation. However, it is not convenient to find it. In this case, several auxiliary sequences are duplicated in turn, thus ensuring that each basic perception to be distinguished can be corresponding to a unique compound sequence. Then the main sequence is named reference-time representation and the auxiliary sequence is named reference-space representation. Of course there is only one main sequence; while there may be multiple auxiliary sequences; that's all.

Coordinate system and coordinate system mathematical space do not represent the irreversibility of reference-time representation. This is because the fundamental function of coordinate system and coordinate system mathematical space is the only corresponding function.

Pangu Relativity Theorem: All the states in the reference-space-time representation have nothing to do with the motion state of "I" and the motion state of the motion source.

Proof: Because everything in pangu space-time representation (at present, the original perception and the reference-space-time representation) has not involved the motion state of "I" and the motion source. Even what is the source of motion is not involved.

And everything is relatively "I" motionless.

Q.E.D.

Inference: Electrostatic field and static magnetic field have nothing to do with "I" and the motion state of field source.

Law Relativity Theorem: Such a law system can be created so that all created laws are equally applicable to all reference systems.

Proof: According to the naming of the reference system. The most basic pangu reference-space-time representation has nothing to do with the specific reference system, and its establishment does not involve the motion state of the reference system itself, so the laws thus described have nothing to do with the specific reference system.

Q.E.D.

How to understand this pangu relativity theorem.

This is because "I am the world", so there is no external reference to judge my state, and I cannot know my movement state.

Figuratively speaking, 1) I am running with the reference-space-time representation behind my back, 2) Of course, I was running with the reference system "based on me".

For convenience and image, this reference system that always follows "I" is named **pangu-material**, also known as **empty-ether** and **pangu-ether**.

Special Relativity Inference: Such a system of laws can be created so that all laws created are equally applicable to all inertial reference systems.

Let's talk about **Surge and Pangu Surg**.

At first, everything in pangu reference-space-time representation was relatively static to "I" and everything was only alive and dead. It was named **the first generation world**.

In contrast, the chaotic state before was named the zero-generation world.

Some birth and death in the same position, merger, named **intensity changes**, including the previous birth and death, the world at this time is named **the second generation of the world**.

Some series of intensity changes merge, that is, the reference-space representation motion of pure scenes is named **surge (wave) motion**, and the world at this time is named **the third generation world**. **Surge** means the **wave of this shore**.

The surge movement relative to "I" is named **pangu surge (wave) movement**.

Taking "I" as a model to subjectively create a medium, it was named pangu-ether, so that pangu surge movement refers to the movement of pangu-ether.

The process involving changes in intensity and pangu surge movement was named as **movement**. In fact, it is change.

Pangu Surge (Wave) Speed Invariant Theorem: Pangu surge speed has nothing to do with "I" and the motion state of the motion source.

Proof 1: Because neither the "I" nor the motion state of the motion source was involved in the process of establishing pangu surge speed. Q.E.D.

Proof 2: This is only a simple merger of the first generation world. Therefore, the original pangu relativity theorem is still valid. Q.E.D.

Pangu surge are logically relative to pangu-material. Therefore, we can say that pangu surge moved in the pangu-material.

8) Nuwa Reference-space-time Representation

The main human perception is vision.

Subjective creation of something as the cause of visual perception and its changes is named **haziness**, that is, the **light of this shore**. It can also be written as **light**.

Haziness-speed Invariance Theorem: Haziness-speed has nothing to do with the motion state of "I" or the motion state of hazy source.

Since the main perception of human beings is vision, other senses are expelled in the construction of the marked space representation because consistency can be obtained. Inconsistency caused by different sensory structures can be avoided.

In this way, our reference-space representation is actually constructed according to vision, i.e. haziness. Therefore, our reference-space representation is named **nuwa reference-space representation**, and our reference-space-time representation is named **nuwa reference-space-time representation**.

Include the merging of reference-space representations between different people.

Thus pangu-surge speed of haziness was preserved, and it was also preserved through the structure of the reference-space representations.

pangu surge speed invariant theorem for haziness, has become the structural feature of our nuwa reference-space-time representation.

Since there is only one reference-space representation, only one speed can participate in the construction of reference-space representation, and this kind of haziness is named **pangu-haziness**.

The constant speed of pangu-haziness is named as the nuwa-hazy-speed (nuwa-speed), which is recorded as ω .

Since our information about space is visual information, this movement is named **pangu-haziness movement**.

Once the apparent reference-space representation is constructed, we use reference-space representation to describe the motion in the reference-space representation.

In fact, in pangu reference-space-time representation there is no reference-space representation extending widely, and the haziness "arrived instantly" — arrival upon seeing. It is artificially stipulated that a certain visual phase is the **light source state** and a certain visual phase is the **arrival state**. Some arrival states are artificially selected as **space construction points**. If the time interval from "I" to this arrival state is dt (or vice versa), then we specify the spatial distance from here to "I" $\omega*dt$; because space is symmetric in both directions, the reverse distance is also $\omega*dt$. The difference between the measured spatio-temporal coordinates of such spatial construction points is (dt, dl) , where $|dl| = \omega*dt$.

From pangu-point, where there is no extensive space, to the space where there is extensive and uniform scale, we need to specify a constant speed to "blow" the original information out evenly and use the time-uniform information to form uniform spatial scale.

In this way, when measuring speed, we actually use this hazy motion as a reference, that is, the hazy speed is **defined** as a "1" unit. The hazy speed becomes the reference unit for all speeds.

On the other hand, when we measure the hazy speed, it is equivalent to measuring itself, and we can only get

a fixed value, that is, the speed value of "I" units. In fact, at this time, the hazy speed is actually artificially determined as a fixed value. $v=dl/dt=1*dt/dt=1$.

Why is the speed value not 1? This is because once the reference-space representation is created, we can measure the defined speed and divide it into smaller units.

For example, the basic unit of the original standard time is "earth day". After it is created, the defined speed can be measured and can be divided into smaller units of hour, hour, minute, second, millisecond and microsecond.

The calculation is as follows.

In the coordinate system of "I", the light source reference-space representation A is at "I" ($x_1=0$), and the light source reference-space representation A event occurs. the "arrival at place B" incident occurs after dt time. According to the regulations of the "I" space, the distance dl from A to B is ωdt , and $dl=\omega dt$. ($x_2=x_1+dl$)

Calculation speed:

$$v = dl/dt = \omega dt/dt = \omega$$

Key points:

1> Locating the light source and reaching the position of light is through the original perception of "visual perception", which is "bound" to the reference system of "I", and the original perception always follows "I". In this way, the original perceived position has nothing to do with my movement state.

2> It is by the change of "visual perception" that the reference-space representation is extended, so that $|dl| = \omega dt$ can be obtained.

3> It is by the change of "visual perception" that the reference-space representation is extended, thus the binding of "visual perception — I" is preserved along with the binding of "visual perception — reference-space representation". Form the binding of "visual perception — 'I' — reference-space representation". In this way, "the position corresponding to visual perception" and "I" form a binding relationship. In this way, the "original perceived position" has nothing to do with my movement state.

4> The speed of pangu movement logically precedes the light source. That is to say, rational logic has the speed of light first, then the light source. So when there is light speed, there is actually no light source. Naturally, logically, the speed of light does not depend on the motion state of the light source, otherwise it is a circular reference.

5> Form the binding of "hazy speed — reference-space representation". However, the motion state of the hazy source is free in reference-space representation, so the hazy speed has nothing to do with the motion state of the hazy source.

6> This is just like, the hazy "pure form of motion" being transferred from the hazy source to the reference system "I". The starting position of hazy is bound in the reference-space representation of "I", and the hazy source can run away.

7> Form the binding of "visual perception — 'I' — reference-space representation". That is, "visual perception — reference-space representation" binding. However, the original "visual perception" has nothing to do with the state of the light source, and this relationship has been preserved, so that the "original perception position (the initial hazy position) has nothing to do with the motion state of the hazy source, and this position is bound in the reference system "I".

Calculation speed:

$$v = dl/dt = \omega dt/dt = \omega$$

Speed is the **fundamental constant ω of nuwa reference-space-time.**

This calculation process has nothing to do with my motion state or the motion state of the hazy source. The result is always the same.

∴ The hazy speed has nothing to do with the "I" motion state, and also has nothing to do with the motion state of the hazy source.

Since the reference frame that can be used as the substitute of "I" is the substitute of "I", the speed of light has nothing to do with the motion state of the reference frame.

At the same time, it can be seen from the process of demonstration that: Only "I" and those reference system that can be used as the substitute of "I", can draw a conclusion.

Here we can see:

- 1> "Haziness-speed Invariance Theorem" is a historical relic: pangu surge speed invariance theorem.
- 2> Why is the speed of light, this is a coincidence. It has something to do with us human beings because we are visual creatures.
- 3> Light is an ancient surge movement.

As the beginning of space-time representation, the sensory-time representation and the pangu time representation are one-dimensional. Therefore, space-time representation are fundamentally one-dimensional.

Space-time 1-dimensional Theorem: Space-time is fundamentally one-dimensional from rationality.

Therefore, there is pangu normalization; it is to return to this one-dimension. Nuwa equal phase exchange is also based on this one-dimension.

(5) The Flat Uniform Independent Reference-space-time Representation and Pangu Geometry

Here's a study of "**straightness**".

Reference-space-time representation is straight, uniform, independent and independent. This is determined by the meta-symmetry of the reference-space-time representation.

In geometry, we do not need to define straight lines. The reason why it is feasible is that everyone understands each other tacitly and what they understand is consistent. Everyone understands that straightness is the same straightness.

(On the level of self-consistent)there is only one kind of straight. Straight has definite consistency, so it can be regarded as self-evident.

On the contrary, there are countless kinds of bending, so it does not have definite consistency and cannot be regarded as self-evident.

With a straight and uniform understanding, we can use the reference-space representation structure to define various bends.

Moreover, the reference-space-time representation is flat. The "straight" here, fundamentally speaking, does not emphasize "straight relative to bending" and cannot be said to be curved until the reference-space-time representation is established. Instead, it emphasizes "a state of unanimity determined by the tacit understanding of each other." It exists in the form of "self-evident".

Can "the shortest straight line between two points" be used to define straight?

I don't think it is appropriate. This is because "shortest" is a more complicated and advanced concept than "straight". The "curve length" is even more complex and advanced concept, which can only be mastered after studying mathematics and learning it well. Distance involves quantity. Quantity itself is a very advanced concept.

The quantity came to mind very late. On the contrary, "straight" is only a simple primitive intuition, which was established very early.

Here's a study of "**uniformity**".

Similarly, (on the level of self-consistent) there is only one uniformity. Uniformity has definite consistency, so it can be regarded as self-evident.

The rules we have laid down are even, and everyone understands them tacitly, and what they understand is consistent. Everyone knows that uniformity is the same uniformity.

On the contrary, there are countless kinds of nonuniformity, so it does not have definite consistency and cannot be regarded as self-evident.

In fact, the reference-space-time representation is uniform. "Uniformity" here, fundamentally speaking, does not emphasize "uniformity as opposed to non-uniformity". It cannot be said to be uniform or non-uniform until the reference-space-time representation is established. Instead, it emphasizes "a state of unanimity determined by the tacit understanding of each other."

When uniformity is stipulated, the infinite extension of reference-space-time representation is stipulated. This can be used to specify the distant reference-space-time representation that has not been reached. Before experiencing it, there was a known uniform reference-space-time representation grid. Full of the whole reference-space-time representation that human beings have not reached.

Here's a study of "**independence and priority**".

We use space-time to study things. Then logically space-time must be prior; therefore, it is not affected by what is being studied.

At the same time, because the most basic meta-symmetry of the reference-space-time representation is located at the root of fuxi tree, reference-space-time representation is independent of all things in the world. And reference-space-time representation **logically** exists first. This is because the reference-space-time representation is a tool to describe all things in the world, so logically it exists first and is independent of all things in the world. If affected by everything in the world, there is logically a problem of **circular dependence**; can't be used to describe things accurately.

Here we say that the straight and uniform space-time is not to emphasize "straight and uniform", but only in the negative sense, *which is only a negation of "curved space-time"*. Needless to say, it exists in our thinking and civilization in a self-evident form. Nor does it depend on such negation (against relativism).

Since Lagrange, physics has embarked on the path of de-geometrization of analytical mechanics, in which flat and uniform space-time takes precedence. Curved space-time gravity theory is against this historical trend.

Therefore, in this study, gravity is the force in the "prior flat and uniform space-time".

This self-evident, straight, uniform, prior and independent geometry is named **pangu geometry** (meaning original geometry), namely **euclidean geometry**.

First Geometry Theorem: Pangu geometry (euclidean geometry) is the first geometry.

∴ Pangu geometry is also called the first geometry. Euclidean geometry is the first geometry.

(6) Nuwa Equal Phase Exchange

1) Nuwa Equal Phase Exchange

(This entry needs to be read twice. For the first time, only inertial system is considered. read the whole entry after 5 paragraphs of the next entry.)

When there are many equivalent "I". A new problem has come.

The original "I" in the reference-space-time representation of that point, may be another "I", now like me also has its own reference-space-time representation. Then how to establish and communicate these reference-space-time representations. This process is named **nuwa reference-space-time representation process**. This reference-space-time representation is named **nuwa reference-space-time representation**. This information exchange is named **nuwa exchange**.

First of all, on the establishment of reference-space-time representation, all "logical people" are identical "replicas" and use identical reference-space-time representation logic. This is guaranteed by the **meta-symmetry of the cognitive subject**.

Fundamentally speaking, each observation behavior is also meta-independent, namely meta-symmetry, named **meta-symmetry of observation**.

Naturally, first of all, all observers are expected to create time and space in a consistent way, and proceed in front of pangu reference-space-time-time representation, and all transformations are consistent.

Naturally, first of all, all observers are expected to create the reference-space-time representation in a consistent way, and perform on the previous pangu reference-space-time-time representation, and all transformations are consistent.

According to the law relativity theorem, the law system can be created in such a way that all created laws are equally applicable to all reference systems. But it needs a certain method to be created.

First, choose a suitable description method to make each frame of reference equal and inherit the meta-symmetry of space-time representation.

The frame of reference actually means to observe there. Moreover, observation has meta-symmetry, then the frame of reference naturally has meta-symmetry.

The description of the dimension of physical laws cannot depend on the starting point, ending point and specific information of each point in a special frame of reference.

Therefore, there are:

Reference System Meta-symmetry Theorem(Relativity Theorem): Physical laws can be meta-symmetric to symmetric reference systems in the domain. This theorem faces the principle of relativity and the principle of generalized relativity.

For example, the physical law equation $F(A,B)$ has $F(S,S')=0$. Then the parameter exchange between S and S' is also satisfied, $F(S',S)=0$. (S,S') and (S',S) are elements in the domain of $F()$. It is the symmetry of (S,S') and (S',S) here; not of S and S' .

However, the symmetry between reference systems does not necessarily lead to the symmetry of physical laws we create for all reference systems. It just provides the conditions. It also depends on the process of creating physical laws; decide domains.

Note that the relativity theorem, relativity principle and generalized relativity principle are only the conclusion of "wise after the event". Can't promise to have a certain rule; it is only said that if there is a certain

rule, it is bound to be so.

In addition, there is no guarantee that physical laws are symmetrical to all reference systems. It is only symmetrical to the frame of reference in its domain.

In fact, its only and true meaning is that physical laws can be expressed in a symmetrical way. That's it.

For different people, the results may not be the same. It is symmetrical to one person and asymmetrical to another. This depends on his cognitive depth, abstract ability and expressive ability. Different factors must be distinguished. We must first select a suitable description to make each reference frame equal.

This conclusion is neither inevitable nor necessary. "It is not inevitable" because, it also depends on the author's ability and input. "It is not necessary" because the expression does not satisfy this symmetry and does not mean that the law is wrong. At the same time, satisfying this symmetry does not mean that it is correct.

Lorentz covariance is a concrete expression of this conclusion.

This conclusion actually comes from the meta-symmetry of space-time itself and the observed meta-symmetry.

The real key is the specific content: which are symmetrical, how symmetrical, and which do not have to be symmetrical.

Otherwise, the general and absolute symmetry is harmful. Mr. Einstein made the movements of any place absolutely symmetrical, and the time corresponding to τ was also symmetrical; this is not true. In the gravitational field, the clock becomes slower and the time of one cycle changes. The τ accumulation corresponds to the period accumulation. Then the τ accumulated value is no longer proportional to time. Different paths have different τ , which leads to the wrong conclusion that "time is related to paths". It also leads to erroneous curved space-time. He also made the motion of light in the vacuum absolutely symmetrical, leading to the wrong conclusion of "the unique speed of vacuum light". In inertial systems, not all light motions are symmetrical; non-stationary emission light is not suitable for judging time sequence — they have not symmetry; it needs stationary emission light to judge time sequence — they have symmetry.

Let's look at "**linearity**".

The following proof shows that the uniformity of reference-space-time representation requires that the transformation of coordinate systems S and S' must be linear. Only consider that the coordinate systems S and S' are invariant.

For convenience, temporarily write the coordinates as $x_a(a=0,1,2,3)$.

Imagine that a standard logic clock is stationary in the S3 system and moves in a uniform straight line in the S system. Its reading is denoted by λ . According to the requirement of uniformity of reference-space-time representation, the corresponding dx_a should be equal at any place as long as $d\lambda$ is equal. That's, $dx_a/d\lambda = \text{constant}$. Then $d^2x_a/d\lambda^2 = 0$. Similarly $d^2x'_a/d\lambda^2 = 0$.

Node transformation relation $x'_a = x'_a(x)$, then

$$\frac{dx'_a}{d\lambda} = \sum_{b=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial x'_a}{\partial x_b} \times \frac{dx_b}{d\lambda} \right)$$

$$\frac{d^2x'_a}{d\lambda^2} = \sum_{b=0}^3 \left(\frac{\partial x'_a}{\partial x_b} \frac{d^2x_b}{d\lambda^2} \right) + \sum_{b,c} \left(\frac{\partial^2 x'_a}{\partial x_b \partial x_c} \left(\frac{dx_b}{d\lambda} \frac{dx_c}{d\lambda} \right) \right) = \sum_{b,c} \left(\frac{\partial^2 x'_a}{\partial x_b \partial x_c} \left(\frac{dx_b}{d\lambda} \frac{dx_c}{d\lambda} \right) \right) \equiv 0$$

$d^2x'_a/d\lambda^2$ must always be 0. And $\frac{dx_b}{d\lambda} \frac{dx_c}{d\lambda}$ is arbitrary, then this requires that each coefficient be constant at 0;

that is to say, $x'_a = x'_a(x)$ is a linear transformation. Similarly $x_a = x_a(x')$ is a linear transformation.

The coordinate system can always be properly selected so that the origin of the coordinates coincide and both sides move on the average x axis. Moreover, this choice does not affect the incremental form of linear transformation.

Figure 19 Relative motion diagram

In order to highlight the complete symmetry, the x axis direction of S' is reversed as the positive direction, and the corresponding coordinate value is marked as x'' , obviously $x''=-x'$, and the corresponding coordinate system is marked as S'' .

As shown in the figure, in the boundless space and time, since S and S'' are meta-symmetric, it is not possible to specify which direction is better (nor can it be said that S must be left), and they are all treated in the same way. S and S'' have mirror symmetry.

Therefore, it is required that the transformation equation $F(A,B)$ from S to S'' also has this meta-symmetry.

S to S'' transformation equation $F(S,S'')=0$. Then the parameters of S and S'' are exchanged, that is, the transformation equation $F(S'',S)=0$ from S'' to S .

This method is named **meta-symmetrical method**.

Since $(0,0)$ corresponds to $(0,0)$, there is no constant term. The calculation is incremental.

Known conditions:

1> According to the structure of pangu space representation.

For the meta-space representation, due to complete meta-independence, there is angular meta-symmetry, including directional meta-symmetry. The reference-space parameter $\omega=w$ is the same in any direction.

For ordinary space-time representation, due to the breaking of gravitational field, there is no complete angular meta-symmetry, but the positive and negative directional meta-symmetry is still not broken. The reference-space parameter ω is the same in both positive and reverse directions.

The S system spatial construction point $(dt,\omega dt)$ corresponds to the S' system spatial construction point $(dt',\omega' dt')$; the S system space construction point $(dt,-\omega dt)$ corresponds to the S' system space construction point $(dt',-\omega' dt')$. ω and ω' are nuwa-space-tectonic-speeds. The spatial distance means that the nuwa-speed ω blows from the origin to here is dt , then the spatial distance is recorded as ωdt . In short, it means that everyone (S and S') still uses the same spatial representation in the sense of identification. The reference-spatial parameters w are the same.

Definition formula of space distance: The distance from any point in the representation of meta-reference-space-time to the origin of "I": $|dl|=w dt$

After squaring: $d l^2=(w dt)^2$

Meta-space-time representation, 3-dimensional reference-space, at this time, the points on the whole sphere have this correspondence. The spatial construction points $(dt,(dx,dy,dz))$ of the S frame of reference correspond to $(dt',(dx',dy',dz'))$ of the S' frame of reference. There are $dx^2+dy^2+dz^2=(w dt)^2$ in the 3-dimensional basic space;

$$dx'^2+dy'^2+dz'^2=(w dt')^2.$$

Requirements for the constructed transformation:

2> The conversion is linear and has no constant term (corresponding to incremental formula due to coincidence of origin points).

And only the points on the x axis are considered first, $dy=dz=dy'=dz'=0$. (or only consider 1-dimensional space)

$$\begin{cases} dt'=a_{11}*dt + a_{12} * dx \\ dx'=a_{21}*dt + a_{22} * dx \end{cases} \quad [1]$$

3> S to S', and then to S, reducing the original form (dt,dx).

Considering the difference of reference systems, a parameter coefficient α , α' is extracted. For the basic description system(inertial system) $\alpha=1$, $\omega=w$.

Next, the difference parameter α of the reference system is considered in the transformation, and the above formula is equivalent to the deformation.

The origin (0,0) of S' moves to (dt,vdt) relative to S, and moves to (dt',0) in S' own view. With transformation:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha'\omega' dt'=a_{11}*\alpha\omega dt + a_{12}*\alpha v dt \\ \alpha'\omega'*0=a_{21}*\alpha\omega dt + a_{22}*\alpha v dt \end{cases} \quad [2]$$

$$\text{Get: } (a_{21}*\alpha\omega+a_{22}*\alpha v)dt=0$$

\therefore dt is an arbitrary differential.

$$\therefore a_{21}*\alpha\omega+a_{22}*\alpha v=0$$

$$\therefore a_{21}=-a_{22}*v/\omega=-a_{22}*\beta$$

$$\beta \equiv v/\omega \quad \beta' \equiv v'/\omega'$$

$$\therefore a_{21}=-a_{22}*\beta \quad [3]$$

According to (1):(dt, ω dt) corresponds to (dt', ω' dt'), and there are transformations:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha'\omega'*dt'=a_{11}*\alpha\omega*dt + a_{12}*\alpha*\omega dt \\ \alpha'\omega'*dt'=-a_{22}\beta*\alpha\omega*dt + a_{22}*\alpha*\omega dt \end{cases}$$

Get:

$$(a_{11}+a_{12})\alpha\omega dt=(-a_{22}\beta+a_{22})\alpha\omega dt$$

\therefore dt is an arbitrary differential. \therefore

$$a_{11}+a_{12}=-a_{22}\beta+a_{22} \quad [4]$$

On the basis of (1):(dt,- ω dt) corresponds to (dt',- ω' dt'), and there are transformations:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha'\omega' dt'=a_{11}*\alpha\omega dt + a_{12}*\alpha(-\omega dt) \\ \alpha'*(-\omega' dt')=-a_{22}\beta*\alpha\omega dt + a_{22}*\alpha(-\omega dt) \end{cases}$$

Similarly, get:

$$-a_{11}+a_{12}=-a_{22}\beta-a_{22} \quad [5]$$

The 2 formulas are added to obtain:

$$2*a_{12}=-2*a_{22}\beta$$

$$\therefore a_{12}=-a_{22}\beta$$

The 2 formulas are Subtracted to obtain:

$$2*a_{11}=2*a_{22}$$

∴ $a_{11}=a_{22}$. Recorded as γ .

Then substitute the above formula to obtain:

$$a_{12}=-a_{22}*\beta$$

There are:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{11}=a_{22}=\gamma \\ a_{21}=a_{12}=-\gamma\beta \end{aligned} \quad [6]$$

When $dx=0, dt'=\gamma dt$. γ is the time scale factor.

Then substitute it into [1], and the transformation is written as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha'\omega'dt'=\gamma*\alpha\omega dt - \gamma\beta*\alpha dx \\ \alpha'dx'=-\gamma\beta*\alpha\omega dt + \gamma*\alpha dx \end{cases} \quad [7]$$

$dx'=-dx''$, substitute, get:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha'\omega't'=\gamma*\alpha\omega dt - \gamma\beta*\alpha dx \\ -\alpha'dx''=(-\gamma\beta)*\alpha\omega dt + \gamma*\alpha dx \end{cases} \quad [7-1]$$

According to (2), the continuous transformation from S to S' and S' to S should change back to itself (dt,dx).

Due to **meta-symmetry**, S' changes back to S, which should be exactly the same as [7-1]; dx and dx'' interchange, dt and dt' interchange, ω and ω' interchange, γ and γ' interchange, α and α' interchange, β and β' interchange:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha*\omega dt=\gamma'\alpha'\omega'dt' - \gamma'\beta'*\alpha'dx'' \\ -\alpha*dx=-\gamma'\beta'\alpha'\omega'dt'+\gamma'\alpha'dx'' \end{cases} \quad [7-2]$$

$dx''=-dx'$; substitute; get:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha\omega dt=\gamma'\alpha'\omega'dt' +\gamma'\beta'*\alpha'dx' \\ \alpha dx=\gamma'\beta'\alpha'\omega'dt' + \gamma'*\alpha'dx' \end{cases} \quad [7-3]$$

Substituting [7] into the first formula of [7-3], obtains:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha\omega t &= \gamma'(\gamma*\alpha\omega dt - \gamma\beta*\alpha dx) + \gamma'\beta'(-\gamma\beta*\alpha\omega dt + \gamma*\alpha dx) \\ &= \gamma\gamma'(1-\beta\beta')\alpha\omega dt + \gamma\gamma'(\beta'-\beta)\alpha dx = 0 \end{aligned}$$

∴ dt and dx can take any differential.

$$\therefore \gamma\gamma'(1-\beta\beta')-1=0 \quad \text{and} \quad \gamma\gamma'(\beta'-\beta)=0$$

$$\begin{cases} \omega dt = \alpha^{-1}\gamma'\alpha'(\omega'dt' + \beta'*dx') \\ dx = \alpha^{-1}\gamma'\alpha'(\beta'\omega'dt' + dx') \end{cases} \quad [7-4]$$

In fact $\Gamma=\alpha^{-1}\gamma'\alpha'$ as a whole is a parameter. Separation is for the purpose of separating the description system of characteristic parameters. α' is the characteristic parameter of S', α is the characteristic parameter of S; the same part γ remains after separation, so $\gamma=\gamma'$. The parameters of S and S' on both sides of the equal sign in formula (7-4) are completely separated as far as possible.

$$\gamma=\gamma' \quad [7-5]$$

$\gamma\gamma'(\beta'-\beta)=0$, get:

$$\beta'=\beta \quad v'/\omega'=v/\omega \quad [8-1]$$

This relation is named **reduction speed (β) invariant theorem**. This is very useful.

And there are:

$$\gamma\gamma'(1-\beta^2)=1 \quad [8-2]$$

$$\therefore \gamma = \gamma' \quad \therefore$$

$$\gamma' = \gamma = \pm(1 - \beta^2)^{-1/2} \quad [8-3]$$

At low speed and weak field, when v takes the limit of 0, $dt > 0$, $dt' > 0$, $dx = 0$, is substituted into $dt' = \gamma dt$, then $\gamma = dt'/dt > 0$.

$$\gamma' = \gamma = (1 - \beta^2)^{-1/2} \quad [8-4]$$

[7] get:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha' \omega dt' = \gamma(\alpha \omega dt - \beta * \alpha dx) \\ \alpha' dx' = \gamma(-\beta * \alpha \omega dt + \alpha dx) \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} \alpha \omega dt = \gamma(\alpha' \omega dt' + \beta * \alpha' dx') \\ \alpha dx = \gamma(-\beta * \alpha' \omega dt' + \alpha' dx') \end{cases}$$

$\alpha' = \alpha \quad \omega' = \omega$, then

$$\begin{cases} dt' = \gamma(dt - (\beta/\omega) * dx) \\ dx' = \gamma(-v * dt + dx) \end{cases}$$

$$dx' = \gamma(-v * dt + u_x dt)$$

$$dt' = \gamma(dt - \beta/\omega * u_x dt)$$

$$u_x' = dx'/dt' = (u_x - v)/(1 - \beta u_x/\omega)$$

$$\alpha' dx' = \gamma(-\beta * \alpha \omega dt + \alpha u_x dt)$$

$$\alpha' \omega dt' = \gamma(\alpha \omega dt - \beta * \alpha u_x dt)$$

$$u_x'/\omega' = dx'/dt' = (u_x - v)/(\omega - \beta u_x)$$

$$u_y'/\omega' = dy'/dt' = u_y/(\gamma(\omega - \beta u_x))$$

$$(\alpha' \omega dt')^2 - (\alpha' dx')^2 = \gamma^2(\alpha \omega dt - \beta * \alpha dx)^2 - (\gamma((-\beta) * \alpha \omega dt + \alpha dx))^2$$

$$= \gamma^2((1 - \beta^2)\alpha^2 \omega^2 dt^2 - (1 - \beta^2) * \alpha^2 dx^2) = (\alpha \omega dt)^2 - (\alpha dx)^2$$

$$(\alpha' \omega dt')^2 - (\alpha' dx')^2 = (\alpha \omega dt)^2 - (\alpha dx)^2$$

The symmetry of α has been well expressed by $x - t$.

Then consider the y transformation when S and S' are symmetrical, $\alpha' = \alpha$, $\omega' = \omega$.

Considering that the space construction point $dt = dt$, $dx = 0$, $dy = \omega dt > 0$, on the y axis of S system, the distance from the corresponding space construction point (dt', dx', dy') to the origin O' is $\omega' dt' > 0$.

$$dt' = \gamma(dt - (\beta/\omega) * 0) = \gamma dt$$

$$dx' = \gamma((-v) * dt + 0) = -\gamma v * dt$$

$$dx'^2 + dy'^2 = (\omega' dt')^2$$

$$\text{Get: } dy' = ((\omega' dt')^2 - dx'^2)^{1/2} = \omega dt * \gamma(1 - \beta^2)^{1/2} = \omega dt = dy$$

Similarly, when $dy = -\omega dt \leq 0$ and $dy' = -\omega dt' \leq 0$, $dy' = dy$ is still available. so finally:

$$dy' = dy$$

The symmetry of α has been well expressed by x and t . No intervention of other spatial dimension is required.

Here α is the whole α , so there should be no α component in the vertical direction. The vertical direction should be the standard spatial representation dimension of $\alpha_y = \alpha_y' = \alpha_z = \alpha_z' = 1$. The vertical direction should have nothing to do with α .

So the above conclusion is still valid.

$$dy'=dy$$

Similarly, other dimensions can be obtained.

so:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha'\omega'dt' = \gamma(\alpha\omega dt - \beta*\alpha dx) \\ \alpha'dx' = \gamma((-\beta)*\alpha\omega dt + \alpha dx) \\ dy' = dy \\ dz' = dz \end{cases} \quad [11]$$

This relation is named **nuwa equal phase exchange theorem**.

This formula is named **nuwa equal phase exchange**.

There is a constant relationship: $(\alpha'\omega'dt')^2 - (\alpha'dx')^2 - dy'^2 - dz'^2 = (\alpha\omega dt)^2 - (\alpha dx)^2 - dy^2 - dz^2$

α is a Vector that characterizes the frame of reference.

α is named as **the coefficient of additive rate field**. α and $\alpha\omega$ reflect the vector characteristics of the additive rate field.

If $\alpha' = \alpha = 1$, $\omega = \omega = w$, this is the inertial frame.

$$\begin{cases} dt' = \gamma(dt - \beta*dx/w) \\ dx' = \gamma((-\beta)*w dt + dx) \\ dy' = dy \\ dz' = dz \end{cases} \quad [11B]$$

If $\beta = 0$, $\gamma = 1$, that is, the static gravitational field

$$\begin{cases} \alpha'\omega'dt' = \alpha\omega dt \\ \alpha'dx' = \alpha dx \\ dy' = dy \\ dz' = dz \end{cases} \quad [11C]$$

Illustratively, it is named nuwa exchange here. It is completely different from Lorentz transformation of relativity. The Lorentz transformation of relativity is based on the assumption that the speed of light is constant.

The nuwa exchange is not based on grand narration, but on pure rationality. What is described is the exchange protocol between many identical organisms and at different times. For us, it basically exists in our thinking. And basically not outside the mind; on this shore, not on the other. In addition, the fundamental basis is also different, not based on the assumption that the speed of light is constant and the relativity assumption.

It can be seen that: $1 - (v/\omega)^2 > 0$

Get:

$$|v| < \omega \quad [12]$$

That is to say, under normal circumstances, it is required that the speed of any frame of reference in the problem set is smaller than nuwa parameter ω .

With the above results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1> The speed ratio of S' origin to S origin is β ; the origin of S also moves at a constant speed for the S' system, with a speed ratio of $-\beta$.

2> All transformations are the same transformation. The system parameters are speed ratio β and reference frame personality α .

- 3> The transformation is reversible.
 4> S to S' inverse transformation is the transformation from S' to S.
 5> Any continuous transformation of 2 times is equal to a transformation of 1 time. Here will be the speed sum.

6> For any point, $(\alpha\omega dt)^2 - (\alpha dx)^2 - dy^2 - dz^2$ remains unchanged before and after the transformation:

$$(\alpha'\omega' dt')^2 - (\alpha' dx')^2 - dy'^2 - dz'^2 = (\alpha\omega dt)^2 - (\alpha dx)^2 - dy^2 - dz^2 .$$

This constant quantity is named **nuwa equal phase quantity**.

"-" indicates that the contribution of time and space to the phase change is reversed.

In this way, L is like a vertical dimension value, but the square value is used for subtraction, so it is expressed by iL. Since the reference-space is the tiller at the reference-time, combined with the yin-number, it can be imagined that the reference-space is the yin-number form $i\alpha L$ at the reference-time. $-(\alpha L)^2 = (i\alpha L)^2$.

$$(\alpha'\omega' dt')^2 + (i\alpha' dx')^2 + (idy')^2 + (idz')^2 = (\alpha\omega dt)^2 + (i\alpha dx)^2 + (idy)^2 + (idz)^2 .$$

The formula of vuwa speed is obtained by direct derivation.

$$\text{Speed ratio: } U_x' \equiv u_x'/\omega' \quad U_y' \equiv u_y'/\omega' \quad U_z' \equiv u_z'/\omega' \quad U_x \equiv u_x/\omega \quad U_y \equiv u_y/\omega \quad U_z \equiv u_z/\omega$$

$$\begin{cases} U_x' = (U_x - \beta)/(1 - \beta U_x) \\ \alpha'^{-1} U_y' = \alpha^{-1} (1 - \beta^2)^{1/2} U_y / (1 - \beta U_x) \\ \alpha'^{-1} U_z' = \alpha^{-1} (1 - \beta^2)^{1/2} U_z / (1 - \beta U_x) \end{cases} \quad [18]$$

$\alpha' = \alpha \quad \omega' = \omega$, then

$$\begin{cases} u_x' = (u_x - v)/(1 - \beta u_x/\omega) \\ u_y' = (1 - \beta^2)^{1/2} u_y / (1 - \beta u_x/\omega) \\ u_z' = (1 - \beta^2)^{1/2} u_z / (1 - \beta u_x/\omega) \end{cases} \quad [18-2]$$

In particular, if horizontal motion is limited, $u_y' = u_z' = 0$.

From this speed formula, we can deduce:

$$\text{Mass-speed relation: } m = m_0 (1 - \beta^2)^{-1/2}$$

Let's look at the **absolute energy momentum formula**.

$$dm = d(m_0 (1 - v^2 w^{-2})^{-1/2}) = m_0 v \cdot dv w^{-2} (1 - v^2 w^{-2})^{-3/2} = m v \cdot dv w (w^2 - v^2)^{-1}$$

$$\therefore m v \cdot dv = (w^2 - v^2) dm$$

$$\therefore dA = \mathbf{I} \cdot \mathbf{v} = d(mv) \cdot v = v^2 dm + m v dv = v^2 dm + (w^2 - v^2) dm = w^2 dm = d(mw^2)$$

$$\therefore T = A = mw^2 - m_0 w^2$$

Absolute kinetic energy $T = mw^2 - m_0 w^2$

mw^2 is named **absolute energy** E . $m_0 w^2$ is named absolute static energy E_0 . $E \equiv mw^2 = T + m_0 w^2 = T + E_0$

$$T = E - E_0$$

$$E^2 - E_0^2 = E^2 - m_0^2 w^4 = m^2 w^4 - m_0^2 w^4 = m^2 w^4 - m^2 w^4 (1 - v^2 w^{-2}) = m^2 v^2 w^2 = p^2 w^2$$

$$\therefore E^2 = p^2 w^2 + m_0^2 w^4$$

This is called **the absolute energy momentum formula**.

If $m_0 = 0$ for a particle, such as a photon, then $E = p w$.

Another: $E = m w^2$

∴ momentum: $p=mw$

Mass-energy relation equation: $E=mw^2$

Under the w unit system: $E=m$

The frequency and direction of propagation of available light are respectively transformed according to the following formula under nuwa equal phase exchange:

$$v' = v(1 - \cos\theta u/w) / (1 - u^2/w^2)^{1/2}$$

$$\cos\theta' = (\cos\theta - u/w) / (1 - \cos\theta u/w)$$

2) The Calculation of Variability Field and Newton Form of Gravity

Take gravitational field as an example. Apart from the characteristic part of the gravitational field, it is universal.

First, a reference description system S' is selected as the reference of $\alpha=1$, that is, S' is selected as the reference intersection of the description system. Then proceed from this reference (intersection) to the target system to determine its eigenvalue parameters.

Here, choose the meta-symmetric space-time description system S' at infinity as the basic description system, namely the inertial system. Reason:

1> The gravitational field at infinity is 0, which can simplify the formula.

2> In reality, infinity, as a common standard, can be easily realized. Logically, there is a common infinity, at which there is a definite cognitive description of "gravitational field is 0" in any reference system.

Based on the infinite meta-symmetric space-time system S' . At first it was relatively still.

In meta-symmetric space-time, the rate of addition and variation around the celestial body M is calculated by the formula of gravitational intensity.

$$a = -\frac{GM}{r^2}$$

Particle P starts from infinity and falls freely under the action of the universal gravitation field to r . (For the previous formula, the r direction is taken as the x direction).

At this point, a frame of reference that is stationary relative to S' is established as S .

At the same time, a meta-symmetric spatio-temporal description system S'' that falls with itself is established at this point. There is no rate of change, and the spatial tectonic speed is the standard speed w .

In S'' , S' gradually goes away, starting from infinity to r .

$$(v_g)^2 = (v_r)^2 = \int_{\infty}^r 2adr = \int_{\infty}^r 2\left(-\frac{GM}{r^2}\right)dr = \frac{2GM}{r} = \frac{2mw^2}{r}$$

Where $m \equiv GM/w^2 = GE/w^4$ is named **reduced energy** and **reduced mass**.

The S'' relative S' speed is named the **additive-rate-field-speed** vector v_g . The corresponding vector $\beta_g = v_g/w$.

The vector β_g is named the **reduction speed of the additive rate field**.

$$\beta_g = v_g/w = (2GM/r)^{1/2} = (2m/r)^{1/2}$$

$$\gamma_g = (1 - \beta_g^2)^{-1/2} = (1 - 2GM/r)^{-1/2} = (1 - 2m/r)^{-1/2}$$

S' and S'' are both meta coordinate systems and are standard description systems. Their spatial tectonic speed is standard spatial tectonic speed $\omega' = \omega'' = w$, $\alpha' = \alpha'' = 1$. The relative speed ratio $\beta = \beta_g$.

S is not a standard system, and its $\alpha \neq 1$.

Event A(measured the standard silent clock time of the S'): (dt'', dr'') corresponds to $(dt', 0)$

$$dt'' = (1 - \beta_g^2)^{-1/2} (dt' - 0) = (1 - \beta_g^2)^{-1/2} dt'$$

Event B(measured static ruler length in S''): $(0, dr'')$ corresponds to (dt', dr')

$$dr' = (1 - \beta_g^2)^{-1/2} (dr'' - 0) = (1 - \beta_g^2)^{-1/2} dr''$$

$$dr'' = (1 - \beta_g^2)^{1/2} dr'$$

S'' is a relatively stationary local inertial frame corresponding to S at this point. Therefore, their coordinates have a simple correspondence, and further determine (the coordinates of) S''.

1> Clock-alignment relationship: For standard static clocks (frame S'), the measured time intervals are consistent. Therefore, in the event A(measured the standard silent clock time of the S' frame), $dt = dt''$.

2> Ruler-alignment relationship: The standard static ruler of S'' frame, has the same measured length (coordinate interval). Therefore, in event B(measured ruler length in S'' frame), $dr = dr''$, $dy = dy''$, $dz = dz''$.

Event B(measured ruler length in S''): (dt', dr') Corresponding to $(0, dr'')$ Corresponding to $(dt', dr = dr'')$

$$\therefore \alpha dr = (0 * \alpha' \omega + \alpha' dr')$$

$$\text{Solve and get: } \alpha = \alpha' dr' / dr = 1 dr' / dr = dr' / ((1 - \beta_g^2)^{1/2} dr') = (1 - \beta_g^2)^{-1/2}$$

Event A(measured the standard silent clock time of the S'): $(dt'', 0)$ Corresponding to (dt', dr'') Corresponding to $(dt = dt'', 0)$

$$\therefore \alpha \omega dt = (\alpha' \omega dt' - 0 * \alpha' dx)$$

$$\text{Get spatial tectonic speed: } \omega = (1 \omega dt') / (\alpha dt) = (\omega dt') / ((1 - \beta_g^2)^{-1/2} (1 - \beta_g^2)^{-1/2} dt') = (1 - \beta_g^2) \omega$$

For S, β_g is the upper β_g , α is the upper α , and "equivalent rest speed" of S is the upper v_g .

$$\begin{aligned} \text{nuwa-equal-phase-quantity } ds^2 &= (\alpha \omega dt)^2 - (\alpha dr)^2 - dy^2 - dz^2 = ((1 - \beta_g^2)^{-1/2} (1 - \beta_g^2) dt)^2 - ((1 - \beta_g^2)^{-1/2} dr)^2 - dy^2 - dz^2 \\ &= (1 - \beta_g^2) (\omega dt)^2 - (1 - \beta_g^2)^{-1} dr^2 - dy^2 - dz^2 \end{aligned}$$

For meta-symmetric S frame of reference, general conclusion:

$$\begin{cases} \beta_g = v_g / w \\ \alpha = (1 - \beta_g^2)^{-1/2} \\ \omega = (1 - \beta_g^2) w \end{cases} \quad [19]$$

$$\text{nuwa-equal-phase-quantity } ds^2 = (1 - \beta_g^2) (\omega dt)^2 - (1 - \beta_g^2)^{-1} dr^2 - dy^2 - dz^2$$

α is named as **the coefficient of additive rate field**, taking the direction of β_g , when it is 1, there is no direction. α and $\alpha \omega$ reflect the vector characteristics of the additive rate field.

Substituting the previous equation, the standard static gravitation field element conclusion is obtained:

Therefore, S(dt, dr) is relative to S'(dt', dr') :

$$\begin{cases} \beta_g = v_g / w & \beta_g = (2m/r)^{1/2} & v_g^2 = -2 \phi \\ \alpha = (1 - \beta_g^2)^{-1/2} = (1 - 2m/r)^{-1/2} \\ \omega = (1 - \beta_g^2) w \\ dt = (1 - \beta_g^2)^{-1/2} dt' \\ dr = (1 - \beta_g^2)^{1/2} dr' \\ dy = dy' \\ dz = dz' \end{cases} \quad [20]$$

$$\text{nuwa-equal-phase-quantity } ds^2 = (1 - 2m/r) (\omega dt)^2 - (1 - 2m/r)^{-1} dr^2 - r^2 d\theta^2 - r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2$$

The vector β_g is named **the gravitational field reduction speed**.

α is named as **the gravitational field coefficient**, taking the direction of β_g , when it is 1, there is no direction.

Equation of motion:

$$\delta \int ds^2 = \delta \int \{ (1-2m/r)(w dt)^2 - (1-2m/r^2)^{-1} dr^2 - r^2 d\theta^2 - r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\varphi^2 \} = 0$$

(7) Quantum Gravitation Theory and End-atomic Gravitation Theory

1) Physical meaning of τ and s , soil-entropy S

The electromagnetic wave frequency (9,192,631,770hz) defining seconds is named the **standard frequency** ν_{st} ; its standard vacuum wavelength is named **standard wavelength** λ_{st} ; the standard vacuum period is named as the **standard period** T_{st} ; Its standard vacuum speed is named **standard speed** c_{st} .

The corresponding frequency, wavelength and period of light in standard vacuum are named as **reference frequency** ν_b , **reference wavelength** λ_b and **reference period** T_b in turn.

Just talk about light tectonic space-time representation.

$$ds^2 = g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu$$

$$d\tau = ds/w = ds/c$$

ds means that the equivalent phase change is converted into the form of photon reference wavelength, named **phase-distance**, also called **phase-optical-distance**.

$d\tau$ means that the equivalent phase change is converted into a photon reference period form, named **phase-time**, also called **phase-optical-time**.

This phase is used as a variational functional. It is the same thing as the soil-entropy S in end-atomic mechanics, both are phase increments, and one end-atomic period corresponds to a Planck constant h . They are all used as variational functional. Note that the actual effect here is on the proportion of soil-entropy S , not soil-entropy S itself. The influence of gravity is the influence on the soil-entropy S , not that there is a gravitational soil-entropy S_g , which appears as the **soil-entropy coefficient**.

This kind of coefficient is perfectly connected with the topology of end-atomic mechanics.

Accordingly, the gauge is not a space-time gauge, but a phase gauge. The singularity is not a space-time singularity, but just a "**phase singularity**".

For light.

$$d\phi = ds/(c/\nu_b) * 2\pi = (2\pi\nu_b/c_{st}) ds = (2\pi/\lambda_b) ds$$

$$ds = (\lambda_b/(2\pi)) d\phi$$

$$d\tau = d\phi/(2\pi\nu_b)$$

$$dS = (d\phi/(2\pi)) h = \hbar d\phi = (h\nu_b/c_{st}) ds = (h/\lambda_b) ds$$

As Yang Zhenning said in the journal nature, "every interaction corresponds to a generalized complex phase"^[1]. This phase corresponds to "evolutionary thinking". In "evolutionary thinking", only the state of the subject object is evolving; the subject object A itself remains unchanged; A is always A. Evolution progress can be expressed by only one index, corresponding to phase angle θ . "Interaction" corresponds to "state evolution", which brings its phase.

Originally, the so-called "intrinsic" curvature is actually a new dimension — phase S . This is not a 4-dimensional curved space-time problem, but a 5-dimensional mathematical space problem in 4-dimensional straight space-time, that is, 4-dimensional space-time representation plus 1-dimensional phase. The general theory of relativity is missing one dimension; forces the 5-dimensional problem into the 4-dimensional space-time representation; as a result, the space-time representation is stretched and distorted.

$$ds^2 = g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu$$

Written in end-atomic mechanics:

$$dS^2 = (h/\lambda_b)^2 g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu$$

The unified equation of motion for end-atomic mechanics is:

$$\delta \int dS = 0$$

For convenience, the ds calculation method is still retained, but it should be noted that it represent phases; ds is named **phase gauge**.

$$ds^2 = g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu$$

Therefore, the following variational equations are the same thing.

$$\delta \int ds = 0$$

$$\delta \int d\tau = 0$$

$$\delta \int dS = 0$$

Note that although end-atomic phase is mentioned here. However, the definition of space and time, the definition of gravity itself does not depend on end-atomic mechanics. They come from macro knowledge. The phase of the light they are associated with is actually a macroscopic phase, that is, the on-off phase. It does not depend on knowledge of end-atomic phase.

Of course, due to the t-logical extension theorem and compatibility theorem, the on-off phase and the end-atomic phase are agreeable. From the perspective of self-consistency, this phase can directly correspond to the end-atomic phase.

Similarly, from the perspective of knowledge and information, gravity theory does not rely on end-atom theory. But as a self-consistent whole theory, according to the habit of thinking that parts form a whole, gravitation theory can be viewed from the end-atomic level.

From the perspective of theory of absolutivity, the private criterion of phase is adopted here. Raise the dimension and become a 5-dimensional mathematical space problem.

2) Independent Proof of Invariance of Nuwa Equal Phase Quantity

It was previously proved that the uniformity of space-time requires that the transformation of coordinate systems S and S' must be linear.

$$\text{Note } \Delta T = \alpha \omega \Delta t, \Delta X = \alpha \Delta x, \Delta Y = \Delta y, \Delta Z = \Delta z, \Delta T' = \alpha' \omega' \Delta t', \Delta X' = \alpha' \Delta x', \Delta Y' = \Delta y', \Delta Z' = \Delta z'$$

General linear transformation transforms $\Delta s^2 = \Delta T^2 - \Delta X^2 - \Delta Y^2 - \Delta Z^2$ into a quadratic polynomial about $\Delta T', \Delta X', \Delta Y', \Delta Z'$, $\Delta s^2 = P(\Delta T', \Delta X', \Delta Y', \Delta Z')$. Considering the space-bound tectonic movement, $\Delta s^2 = 0 = P(\Delta T', \Delta X', \Delta Y', \Delta Z')$, while on the other hand $(\Delta T')^2 = \Delta L^2 = \Delta X'^2 + \Delta Y'^2 + \Delta Z'^2$, and $\Delta s'^2 = \Delta T'^2 - \Delta X'^2 - \Delta Y'^2 - \Delta Z'^2 = 0$ are defined according to the space-bound representation. We mentioned $\Delta T'^2$ above, and $P(\Delta T', \Delta X', \Delta Y', \Delta Z')$ is expressed as follows:

$$P(\Delta T', \Delta X', \Delta Y', \Delta Z') = (\Delta T'^2 - \Delta X'^2 - \Delta Y'^2 - \Delta Z'^2)k + Q(\Delta T', \Delta X', \Delta Y', \Delta Z')$$

Where $Q(\Delta T', \Delta X', \Delta Y', \Delta Z')$ is still a polynomial, but the power of $\Delta T'$ is one at most. For reference-spatial construction points, there are

$$Q(\Delta T', \Delta X', \Delta Y', \Delta Z') \equiv 0$$

Obviously, there is no constant in Q. Secondly, since $\Delta X', \Delta Y', \Delta Z'$ can be positive or negative, it can be seen that Q cannot contain their first power term (here the first power term includes $\Delta X' \Delta T', \Delta X' \Delta Y',$ etc.); otherwise, the positive and negative values cannot be 0 at the same time. Next, consider the case where $\Delta X', \Delta Y', \Delta Z', \Delta T'$ become negative at the same time. this change reflects the same physical process, starting point coordinates minus

ending point coordinates, but it can be seen that Q also does not contain a term of $\Delta T'$; otherwise $\Delta T'$ takes positive and negative and cannot be 0 at the same time. Next, Q can only take this form:

$$Q = a\Delta X'^2 + b\Delta Y'^2 + c\Delta Z'^2 \equiv 0$$

In particular, considering the spatial tectonic motion on the x' axis, $\Delta Y' = \Delta Z' = 0$, and any non-zero value of $\Delta X'$ becomes:

$$Q = a\Delta X'^2 \equiv 0$$

Q is always equal to 0, $\Delta X'$ any non-zero value, then a is 0. Similarly, $b=0$ and $c=0$.

Therefore, we prove that $Q=0$, thus

$$\Delta s^2 = P(\Delta T', \Delta X', \Delta Y', \Delta Z') = k\Delta s'^2$$

Next, according to symmetry. Due to meta-symmetry, the interchange between Δs and $\Delta s'$ still holds, so:

$$\Delta s'^2 = k\Delta s^2$$

So:

$$k^2 = 1$$

In $\Delta s^2 = k\Delta s'^2$, if considered in the real number range, $\Delta s^2 > 0$, $\Delta s'^2 > 0$, then $k = \Delta s^2 / \Delta s'^2 > 0$.

So $k=1$, and there is

$$\Delta s'^2 = \Delta s^2$$

In particular, it is written in differential form:

$$ds'^2 = ds^2$$

That is, nuwa equal phase quantity and nuwa equal phase element are unchanged.

3) Quantum Gravitation and End-atomic Gravitation

The influence of gravity is actually the proportional influence on the soil-entropy S , not the soil-entropy S itself. The influence of gravity is the influence on the soil-entropy S , which appears as the **soil-entropy coefficient** $g_{\mu\nu}$, rather than saying that there is a gravitational soil-entropy S_g .

For example, light motion in gravitational field. If there is no gravity. The photon's phase has a coefficient of 1 in all directions, resulting in linear motion. However, the gravitational field results in the inconsistency of the phase coefficients of photons in all directions, so that photons do not move in a straight line.

There is only one soil-entropy S , which is the soil-entropy S of the photon itself. There is no so-called gravitational soil-entropy S_g . Gravity is only a coefficient that changes the phase of the photon's soil-entropy S .

In addition to being directly used for dS , it is also possible to quote the soil-entropy S coefficient $g_{\mu\nu}$ in other ways. in fact, it is also end-atomic mechanics. Such as electrodynamics.

$$f^{\mu\nu} = g^{\mu\alpha} g^{\nu\beta} f_{\alpha\beta} = A^{\mu,\nu} - A^{\nu,\mu}$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{-g}} (\sqrt{-g} g^{\mu\alpha} g^{\nu\beta} (A_{\alpha\beta} - A_{\beta\alpha}))_{,\nu} = \frac{4\pi}{w} j^\mu$$

It is the application of dynamics here.

Of course, this is the macroscopic form of end-atomic mechanics.

In addition, due to the influence of gravity, the soil-entropy S coefficient appears instead of saying that there is a separate gravity soil-entropy S_g . In this way, if gravity itself is not quantized and can describe the world well, it is also acceptable. This is because although the coefficient itself is continuous, it does not prevent the quantization of gravitational sources and final results. This is an indirect quantization.

On the other hand, from the perspective of end-atomic mechanics, end-atomic mechanics is also actively compatible with theory of absolutivity.

The foundation of theory of absolutivity is topological theory. Its absolute time representation is topological.

The core of end-atomic mechanics is to adopt the dimensionless logic ($\partial\Psi/\Psi$), which is also topology-based. Just adapted to the topological space-time representation of theory of absolutivity.

From a **purely computational** point of view, it is indeed **equivalent to space-time deformation**.

$$dS^2 = (h/\lambda_b)^2 g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu$$

$g_{\mu\nu}$ is regarded as the correlation of dS , and both $g_{\mu\nu}$ and $dx^\mu dx^\nu$ are effects on phase.

It can also be seen equivalently. Originally $dx^\mu dx^\nu$ affected the phase dS , while $g_{\mu\nu}$ affected the effect of $dx^\mu dx^\nu$. In this way, $g_{\mu\nu}$ is regarded as a correlation of $dx^\mu dx^\nu$, that's, space-time deformation.

Therefore, **the original calculation based on space-time deformation is still valid**.

4) Why is Equal-Phase-Quantity of Phase

1> The phase here is absolute in itself and is a topological quantity.

Once they are recorded, they are absolute quantities. The absoluteness of the record is guaranteed.

The simplest phases are periodic signals. When analyzing these recorded periodic signals, the number of periods has nothing to do with human speed, acceleration, etc.

This absoluteness is exactly what the yong-name-theorem requires.

2> But the phase change law of light relative to the observer is not unique. So we can establish the exchange relationship according to the previous absolute phase.

The phase change recorded by the mover himself corresponds to the sensory-time representation. According to "**Time-Topology-1**", it corresponds to the absolute priority relation. Expressed as $d\tau$ and ds .

In different space-time representations, the phase ($d\tau$) must be consistent. it is "the foundation of invariance".

According to this, the exchange of nuwa and others can be established.

5) Nuwa Annulus-flux Tensor $R^p_{\alpha\beta\gamma}$

Named **nuwa annulus-flux tensor**:

$$R^p_{\alpha\beta\gamma} \equiv (g_{\alpha;\beta;\gamma} - g_{\alpha;\gamma;\beta})g^\rho$$

$$\text{Get: } g_{\alpha;\beta;\gamma} - g_{\alpha;\gamma;\beta} = R^p_{\alpha\beta\gamma} g_\rho$$

This is actually a matter of circulation and flux. Thus it is named in this way.

The covariant derivative will temporarily add the base vector to the derivative expression each time. In this way, due to different levels of semicolons, different parts are added one after the other, and the number of times of participation in the calculation is different. This difference in sequence leads to the difference in the order of derivation of exchange covariants, and the results are also different. The difference is not 0.

Figure 20 Schematic diagram of nuwa annulus-flux tensor

Equivalent to parallel movement relative to the curvilinear coordinate system. Take the vector V_α equal to the unit basis vector g_α of this point. As shown in the figure, $dx^\beta dx^\gamma$ is a rectangular panel in the curvilinear coordinate system. When V_α moves in parallel, the increment $d_p V_\alpha = \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^\rho V_\rho dx^\beta$ corresponding to dx^β will be generated due to the reference of coordinate system.

From P_1 to P' , move the increment of dx^β

$$d_{p1} V_\alpha = \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^\rho V_\rho dx^\beta$$

From P' to P_2 , $P'(x+dx^\beta)$ should be taken as the reference, and then the total increment of dx^γ should be moved.

$$\begin{aligned} \delta' V_\alpha &= \Gamma_{\alpha\gamma}^\rho (x+dx^\beta) V_\rho (x+dx^\beta) dx^\gamma + \{\Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^\rho V_\rho dx^\beta\} \\ &= [\Gamma_{\alpha\gamma}^\rho + \Gamma_{\alpha\gamma}^{\rho,\beta} dx^\beta] [V_\rho + \Gamma_{\rho\beta}^\delta V_\delta dx^\beta] dx^\gamma + \{\Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^\rho V_\rho dx^\beta\} \\ &= [\Gamma_{\alpha\gamma}^\rho \Gamma_{\rho\beta}^\delta V_\delta dx^\beta dx^\gamma + \Gamma_{\alpha\gamma}^{\rho,\beta} V_\rho dx^\beta dx^\gamma + \{\Gamma_{\alpha\gamma}^\rho V_\rho dx^\gamma + \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^\rho V_\rho dx^\beta\}] \\ &= [\Gamma_{\alpha\gamma}^\delta \Gamma_{\delta\beta}^\rho V_\rho dx^\beta dx^\gamma + \Gamma_{\alpha\gamma}^{\rho,\beta} V_\rho dx^\beta dx^\gamma + \{\Gamma_{\alpha\gamma}^\rho V_\rho dx^\gamma + \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^\rho V_\rho dx^\beta\}] \\ &= [\Gamma_{\alpha\gamma}^\delta \Gamma_{\delta\beta}^\rho + \Gamma_{\alpha\gamma}^{\rho,\beta}] V_\rho dx^\beta dx^\gamma + \{\Gamma_{\alpha\gamma}^\rho V_\rho dx^\gamma + \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^\rho V_\rho dx^\beta\} \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, from P_1 to P'' , then from P'' to P_2 , the total increment

$$\begin{aligned} \delta'' V_\alpha &= \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^\rho (x+dx^\gamma) V_\rho (x+dx^\gamma) dx^\beta + \Gamma_{\alpha\gamma}^\rho V_\rho dx^\gamma \\ &= [\Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^\delta \Gamma_{\delta\gamma}^\rho + \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\rho,\gamma}] V_\rho dx^\beta dx^\gamma + \{\Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^\rho V_\rho dx^\beta + \Gamma_{\alpha\gamma}^\rho V_\rho dx^\gamma\} \end{aligned}$$

So the total difference of this loop, that is, the integral of the directed loop

$$\delta' V_\alpha - \delta'' V_\alpha = (\Gamma_{\alpha\gamma}^\rho \Gamma_{\rho\beta}^\delta - \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\rho,\gamma} + \Gamma_{\alpha\gamma}^\delta \Gamma_{\delta\beta}^\rho - \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^\delta \Gamma_{\delta\gamma}^\rho) V_\rho dx^\beta dx^\gamma = R_{\alpha\beta\gamma}^\rho V_\rho dx^\beta dx^\gamma$$

This integral is equal to the flux through this area $dx^\beta dx^\gamma$. Divided by the area is the flux density.

$$(\delta' V_\alpha - \delta'' V_\alpha) / (dx^\beta dx^\gamma) = R_{\alpha\beta\gamma}^\rho V_\rho = R_{\alpha\beta\gamma}^\rho g_\rho$$

$R_{\alpha\beta\gamma}^\rho$ is the flux density in the curvilinear coordinate system. Flux density is the flux density of the surface corresponding to the last two indexes $\beta\gamma$.

When $\beta=\gamma$, $R_{\alpha\beta\gamma}^\rho = 0$.

Multiply $g_{\alpha\rho}$ to decrease the index to obtain **the total covariant form of nuwa annulus-flux tensor**:

$$R_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} = g_{\alpha\rho} R_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\rho = (g_{\beta;\gamma;\delta} - g_{\gamma;\delta;\beta}) g_\alpha = g_{\alpha\rho} (\Gamma_{\beta\delta}^{\rho,\gamma} - \Gamma_{\beta\gamma}^{\rho,\delta} + \Gamma_{\beta\delta}^\sigma \Gamma_{\gamma\sigma}^\rho - \Gamma_{\beta\gamma}^\sigma \Gamma_{\delta\sigma}^\rho)$$

While $R_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$ can be expressed as:

$$R_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} = \frac{1}{2} (g_{\alpha\delta;\beta\gamma} + g_{\beta\gamma;\alpha\delta} - g_{\beta\delta;\alpha\gamma} - g_{\alpha\gamma;\beta\delta}) + g_{\rho\sigma} (\Gamma_{\alpha\delta}^{\rho,\sigma} \Gamma_{\beta\gamma}^\sigma - \Gamma_{\alpha\gamma}^{\rho,\sigma} \Gamma_{\beta\delta}^\sigma)$$

Named **nuwa flux density tensor** $R_{\alpha\beta}$

$$R_{\alpha\beta} \equiv R_{\alpha\mu\beta}^\mu = g^{\mu\nu} R_{\mu\alpha\nu\beta} = (g_{\alpha;\beta;\mu} - g_{\alpha;\mu;\beta}) g^\mu$$

$$= \Gamma_{\alpha\beta,\rho}^{\rho} - \Gamma_{\alpha\rho,\beta}^{\rho} + \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\sigma} \Gamma_{\rho\sigma}^{\rho} - \Gamma_{\alpha\rho}^{\sigma} \Gamma_{\beta\sigma}^{\rho}$$

Mixed nuwa flux density tensor $R^{\mu}_{\nu} \equiv g^{\mu\epsilon} R_{\epsilon\nu} = R^{\alpha\mu}_{\alpha\nu}$

Named nuwa divergence R

$$\begin{aligned} R &\equiv R^{\alpha}_{\alpha} = g^{\alpha\beta} R_{\alpha\beta} = g^{\alpha\beta} g^{\mu\nu} R_{\mu\alpha\nu\beta} = (g_{\alpha;\mu;\beta} - g_{\alpha;\beta;\mu}) g^{\mu} g^{\alpha\beta} \\ &= (\Gamma_{\alpha\beta,\rho}^{\rho} - \Gamma_{\alpha\rho,\beta}^{\rho} + \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\sigma} \Gamma_{\rho\sigma}^{\rho} - \Gamma_{\alpha\rho}^{\sigma} \Gamma_{\beta\sigma}^{\rho}) g^{\alpha\beta} \end{aligned}$$

Further analysis of R and R^{β}_{β} :

$$R = \sum_{\beta} R^{\beta}_{\beta} = \sum_{\beta} \sum_{\alpha} R^{\alpha\beta}_{\alpha\beta}, \quad \alpha \neq \beta$$

Since $R^{\alpha\alpha}_{\alpha\alpha} = 0$, there are actually only 12 items. R is the sum of the fluxes of the 12 (α, β) surfaces of the regular tetrahedron.

The sum of fluxes on the surface of a unit volume element is equal to divergence. So it is named nuwa divergence. Because it is a (0-dimensional) tensor, it has nothing to do with the coordinate system. Note that this is the divergence of the four-dimensional world, corresponding invariant volume element $dV = \sqrt{-g} d^4x$.

Diagonal term R^{β}_{β} of R^{μ}_{ν} :

$$R^{\beta}_{\beta} = \sum_{\alpha} R^{\alpha\beta}_{\alpha\beta}, \quad \alpha \neq \beta$$

Correspondingly, the diagonal term R^{β}_{β} of R^{μ}_{ν} is the sum of the fluxes of the 3 α surfaces with β .

6) Scalar Form of Nuwa Equation of Motion

From the above, we know that R is the invariant nuwa divergence.

Using the previous standard solution, calculate the physical meaning of this value; that is, the corresponding relation with other physical quantities.

$$[g_{\mu\nu}] = \text{diag}\{(1-2m/r), -(1-2m/r)^{-1}, -r^2, -r^2 \sin^2\theta\}$$

$$[g^{\mu\nu}] = \text{diag}\{(1-2m/r)^{-1}, -(1-2m/r), -r^{-2}, -r^{-2} \sin^{-2}\theta\}$$

Diagonal array, calculation is not difficult. (6 groups) 12 surface flux densities are as follows.

$$R^{23}_{23} = R^{32}_{32} = -2mr^{-3}$$

$$R^{02}_{02} = R^{20}_{20} = mr^{-3}$$

$$R^{03}_{03} = R^{30}_{30} = mr^{-3}$$

$$R^{12}_{12} = R^{21}_{21} = mr^{-3}$$

$$R^{13}_{13} = R^{31}_{31} = mr^{-3}$$

$$R^{01}_{01} = R^{10}_{10} = 2mr^{-3}$$

Diagonal term of R^{μ}_{ν} , $R^0_0 = R^1_1 = 4mr^{-3}$, $R^2_2 = R^3_3 = 0$.

$$R = 8mr^{-3} = 8\pi G(4/3w^{-4})(Mw^2/(4/3\pi r^3)) = 8\pi Gw^{-4}(4/3)\rho_r$$

$\rho_r = Mw^2/(4/3\pi r^3)$ is the equivalent energy density in r . So R corresponds to the energy density of the physical quantity in 4-dimensional world.

The 4-dimensional invariant divergence R is invariant, so the variational equation can be obtained by integrating it with the invariant volume element.

Invariant volume element

$$dV = \sqrt{-g} d^4x$$

Named Nuwa Divergence Tensor

$$W_v^\mu \equiv g^{\alpha\mu} (\partial(\sqrt{-g}R) / \partial g^{\alpha\nu}) = R_v^\mu - \frac{1}{2} R \delta_v^\mu$$

$$W_{\mu\nu} \equiv g_{\alpha\mu} W_\nu^\alpha = R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} R g_{\mu\nu}$$

$$W^{\mu\nu} \equiv g^{\alpha\nu} W_\alpha^\mu = R^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} R g^{\mu\nu}$$

Each term of $W_{\mu\nu}$ corresponds to the projection of 4-dimensional invariant divergence R corresponding to $g_{\mu\nu}$; $W^{\mu\nu}$ is its absolute expression.

There is: $W = -R$

The 4-dimensional invariant material corresponding to $R/(2\kappa)$ is named **4-dimensional energy density** T_m . $T_m=0$ in vacuum.

Named energy tensor

$$T_v^\mu \equiv g^{\alpha\mu} \frac{2}{\sqrt{-g}} \frac{\partial(\sqrt{-g}T_m)}{\partial g^{\alpha\nu}} = \rho_{00} u^\mu u_\nu$$

$$T_{\mu\nu} = g_{\alpha\mu} T_\nu^\alpha = \rho_{00} u_\mu u_\nu$$

R is projected into 3 dimensions, making it easier to see.

W^0_0 is the 3-dimensional spatial component, that is, the 3-dimensional divergence.

For flux on the upper 23 surface, $Y^{23}_{23} \equiv R^{23}_{23} - \frac{1}{2}R = (-2mr^{-3}) - \frac{1}{2}(8mr^{-3}) = -6mr^{-3}$

In the spherical coordinate system, 23 plane is the only outer surface of a 3-dimensional ball. Its flux is the total flux. It is also its 3-dimensional divergence W^0_0 . $W^0_0 = Y^{23}_{23}$.

$$W^0_0 = Y^{23}_{23} = -6mr^{-3} = -6\pi G(4/3w^{-4})(Mw^2/(4/3\pi r^3)) = -8\pi Gw^{-4}\rho_r = -\kappa\rho_r$$

The three-dimensional divergence W^0_0 is proportional to the 3-dimensional energy density ρ_r , and the correlation coefficient is

$$\kappa \equiv 8\pi Gw^{-4}$$

At the same time, prepare an optional $-2\wedge$, named the **cosmological constant**. Its partial derivative to $g^{\mu\nu}$ is 0. The partial derivative of the cosmological constant to $g^{\mu\nu}$ is 0, so it cannot be obtained from the equation itself and can only be artificially introduced from the boundary conditions.

Note that it corresponds to a 4-dimensional divergence and a 4-dimensional density, not the 3-dimensional divergence and 3-dimensional density we often say.

$$S \equiv \int [(2\kappa)^{-1}(R-2\wedge) - T_m] dV = \int [(2\kappa)^{-1}(R-2\wedge) - T_m] \sqrt{-g} d^4x = \int [(2\kappa)^{-1}\sqrt{-g}(R-2\wedge) - \sqrt{-g}T_m] d^4x$$

Variational equation:

$$\delta S = \int [(2\kappa)^{-1}\sqrt{-g}(R-2\wedge) - T_m] dV = \int [(2\kappa)^{-1}\sqrt{-g}(R-2\wedge) - T_m] \sqrt{-g} d^4x = 0$$

How can the vacuum outside the gravitational field have non-zero 4-dimensional divergence and 4-dimensional density? It can be understood in this way. This is obtained through the time dimension. Matter can be regarded as some kind of influence. Its influence spread from the center through time to the whole universe. Because it is always in time on the model, it is a non-zero value. The specific value varies with distance. Moreover, because time and space act as inverse sign in phase, so 4-dimensional density ($8mr^{-3}$) and 3-dimensional density ($-6mr^{-3}$) inverse sign.

7) Divergence Tensor Form of Nuwa Equation of Motion

For the $g^{\mu\nu}$ variational equation in curvilinear coordinate system, we obtain:

$$\delta S = \int [(2\kappa)^{-1} \partial(\sqrt{-g}(R-2\Lambda)) / \partial g^{\mu\nu} - \partial(\sqrt{-g}T_m) / \partial g^{\mu\nu}] \delta g^{\mu\nu} d^4x = 0$$

For all the variations $\delta g^{\mu\nu}$ are 0, then

$$(2\kappa)^{-1} \partial(\sqrt{-g}(R-2\Lambda)) / \partial g^{\mu\nu} - \partial(\sqrt{-g}T_m) / \partial g^{\mu\nu} = 0$$

$$\partial(\sqrt{-g}(-2\Lambda)) / \partial g^{\mu\nu} = -2\Lambda \partial\sqrt{-g} / \partial g^{\mu\nu} = g_{\mu\nu} \Lambda$$

$$\sqrt{-g}((R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R) + g_{\mu\nu}\Lambda - \kappa T_{\mu\nu}) = 0$$

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu} + g_{\mu\nu}\Lambda = \kappa T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$R^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}R\delta^{\mu\nu} + \delta^{\mu\nu}\Lambda = \kappa T^{\mu\nu}$$

Obtained and named **nuwa divergence tensor equation**:

$$W_{\nu}^{\mu} + \delta_{\nu}^{\mu}\Lambda = R_{\nu}^{\mu} - \frac{1}{2}R\delta_{\nu}^{\mu} + \delta_{\nu}^{\mu}\Lambda = \kappa T_{\nu}^{\mu}$$

$$W_{\mu\nu} + g_{\mu\nu}\Lambda = R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu} + g_{\mu\nu}\Lambda = \kappa T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$W^{\mu\nu} + g^{\mu\nu}\Lambda = R^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}Rg^{\mu\nu} + g^{\mu\nu}\Lambda = \kappa T^{\mu\nu}$$

Scalar form:

$$g^{\alpha\mu} \frac{\partial(\sqrt{-g}R)}{\partial g^{\alpha\nu}} + \delta_{\nu}^{\mu}\Lambda = \kappa\rho_{00}u^{\mu}u_{\nu}$$

$$\frac{\partial(\sqrt{-g}R)}{\partial g^{\mu\nu}} + g_{\mu\nu}\Lambda = \kappa\rho_{00}u_{\mu}u_{\nu}$$

According to the "topological charge theorem", gravitational charge is a topological quantity; divergence is also a topological quantity; the two are exactly consistent. Therefore, this equation is also a topological equation.

Each term of $W_{\mu\nu}$ corresponds to the projection of 4-dimensional invariant divergence R on $g_{\mu\nu}$.

Where, W_{00} corresponds to the projection of 4-dimensional invariant divergence R in space, that's, 3-dimensional spatial divergence, W^0_0 is the invariant divergence of 3-dimensional space.

(Ignore Λ) Contraction and Attainment

$$W = -R = \kappa T$$

So there are:

$$R^{\mu}_{\nu} = \kappa(T^{\mu}_{\nu} - \frac{1}{2}T\delta^{\mu}_{\nu})$$

$$R^{\mu\nu} = \kappa(T^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}Tg^{\mu\nu})$$

$$R/(2\kappa) = -\frac{1}{2}T$$

And $R/(2\kappa)$ corresponds to T_m , so T_m corresponds to $-\frac{1}{2}T$.

$$T_m = -\frac{1}{2}T$$

Speed, displacement and gravitation approach 0, etc., so as not to affect meta-symmetry. Such conditions are called **limit meta-symmetry condition**.

κ can also be derived by using the gravity formula to calculate the limit under the limit meta-symmetry condition.

$$\text{From the gravitation formula in meta-symmetric space-time we can get: } \nabla^2 V = 4\pi G\rho_{00}(x)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{From Lagrange equation we can get: } \ddot{x}^k / \Gamma_{00k} = 1 \\
& 1 = \Gamma_{00k} / (-\frac{1}{2}(\mathcal{G}_{00,k})) = \Gamma_{00k} / (-\frac{1}{2}\partial(1+2w^{-2}V-1)/\partial x^k) = \Gamma_{00k} / (-w^{-2}\partial V/\partial x^k) \\
& 1 = (\frac{1}{2}\nabla^2 \mathcal{G}_{00}) / (\nabla^2 V) = (\frac{1}{2}\nabla^2 \mathcal{G}_{00}) / (4\pi G \rho_{00}) \\
& 1 = T_{00} / w^2 \rho_{00}(x) = T / w^2 \rho_{00} \\
& 1 = (\kappa T_{00}) / (\frac{1}{2}\kappa w^2 \rho_{00}) \\
& 1 = (\kappa(T_{00} - \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{G}_{00}T)) / (\frac{1}{2}\kappa w^2 \rho_{00}) \\
& 1 = R_{00} / (\kappa(T_{00} - \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{G}_{00}T)) = (w^{-2}\nabla^2 V) / (\frac{1}{2}\kappa w^2 \rho_{00}) = (w^{-2}4\pi G \rho_{00}) / (\frac{1}{2}\kappa w^2 \rho_{00}) = (8\pi G w^{-4}) / \kappa \\
& \kappa = 8\pi G w^{-4}
\end{aligned}$$

8) Internal Solution

As for the internal solution, it is quite special because the radial direction destroys the meta-symmetry here and cannot be directly used. Attention should be paid to boundary conditions. Tensor equation is used to solve the problem with continuous equilateral boundary conditions. The internal solution is analyzed below.

Note: the outer diameter is r_b and the inner diameter is r_0 . For solid ball $r_0=0$.

Note: $r_x^2 = (r_b^3 - r_0^3) / r_b$

The 00 component of the basis vector g_μ is denoted as $g_{_00}$. $g_{_00} = g_{00}^{1/2}$.

The above meta-symmetric model is used to analyze this solution. v_g is calculated first.

Note: $A(r) = 8/3 \pi G \rho(r) w^{-2} = 1/3 \kappa \rho(r)$

$$\begin{aligned}
v_g^2 &= -2\phi = 2 \left\{ \int_{r_0}^{r_b} [G\rho * 4\pi r^2 dr / r] + G\rho * 4/3 \pi r^3 / r - G\rho * 4/3 \pi r_0^3 / r \right\} = 8/3 \pi G \rho (3/2 r_b^2 - 1/2 r^2 - 1/2 r_0^3 / r) \\
&= A [3/2 r_x^2 - 1/2 r^2 + (3/2 r_0^3 / r_0 - 1/2 r_0^3 / r)]
\end{aligned}$$

Formally, it is a combination of several standard external solution models.

$W^0_0 = \kappa T^0_0 = \kappa \rho(r) = 3A(r)$. Can get: $d(-r g_{11}^{-1}) = d(r - Ar^3)$

$-r g_{11}^{-1} = r - Ar^3 + C1$

$-g_{11}^{-1} = 1 - Ar^2 + C1/r = 1 - A(r^3 - r_0^3) / r$

C1 is the integral constant. For the internal solution, $C1 = Ar_0^3$. For solid ball, $C1 = 0$. Ar^2 corresponds to the density here; $C1/r$ term corresponds to continuity.

As can be seen,

g_{11} depends on the average density inside the sphere.

The average density naturally has continuity. (if necessary) **the "continuity" of the internal solution g_{11} can be from the inside out.**

For photons, the time coefficient $g_{_00} = g_{00}^{1/2}$ is related to the frequency of the photon. The frequency of photons remains continuous at the boundary and changes can accumulate. Frequency corresponds to energy and the color of light.

$W^1_1 = \kappa T^1_1$ and $W^2_2 = \kappa T^2_2$ get the equation about g_{00} , which is ultimately the equation about $g_{_00}$.

$$d(g_{_00}(1 - Ar^2 + Ar_0^3 r^{-1})^{-1/2}) / dr = 3/2(1 - Ar_x^2) d((1 - Ar^2 + Ar_0^3 r^{-1})^{-1/2}) / dr - (3/4)(1 - Ar_x^2)^{1/2} Ar_0 (r_0 / r)^2 (1 - Ar^2 + Ar_0^3 r^{-1})$$

-3/2

For the ball $r_0 r_b^{-1} \rightarrow 0$, there are

$$g_{_00} = B - C(1 - Ar^2 + Ar_0^3 r^{-1})^{1/2} = 3/2(1 - Ar_x^2) - 1/2(1 - Ar^2 + Ar_0^3 r^{-1})^{1/2}$$

$B = 3/2(1 - Ar_x^2)$, $C = 1/2$ is the integral constant. The latter term of the internal solution $g_{_00}$ depends on the density, and coefficient B and C depend on the "continuity" of the boundary condition.

Formally, solid sphere $g_{_00} = g_{00}^{1/2}$ is linearly combined according to two standard element symmetric outer solution models, namely, two large sphere models. One corresponds to the density here and one corresponds to continuity.

The "continuity" of g_{00} is inherited from the outside to the inside.

The internal solution and nuwa equal phase quantities are obtained:

$$ds^2=(3/2(1-Ar_b^2)^{1/2}-1/2(1-Ar^2)^{1/2})^2(wdt)^2-(1-Ar^2)^{-1}dr^2-r^2d\theta^2-r^2\sin^2\theta d\varphi^2$$

Equation of motion:

$$\delta\int ds^2=\delta\int\{(3/2(1-Ar_b^2)^{1/2}-1/2(1-Ar^2)^{1/2})^2(wdt)^2-(1-Ar^2)^{-1}dr^2-r^2d\theta^2-r^2\sin^2\theta d\varphi^2\}=0$$

9) Vacuum Solution of Spherical Shell and Scalar of Gravitational Field ϕ

The celestial structure of the spherical shell in the universe is named the **sky dome**.

Radius r_0 of inner shell. First, the internal vacuum solution is solved.

$$v_g^2=2\int_{r_0}^{r_b}[G\rho*4\pi r^2 dr/r]=4G\rho\pi(r_b^2-r_0^2)=\text{const}$$

$v_g^2 w^2$ is constant and has nothing to do with coordinate changes.

If the gravitational acceleration is 0, then the object moves in a uniform straight line in xyz coordinate system, and the coefficient ratio of xyz is constant; due to symmetry, this constant coefficient ratio is 1.

$$-g_{11} = 1$$

In fact, before crossing the inner interface, it was already $-g_{11} = 1$.

But the frequency of free-falling photons, the color, will remain continuous. In the internal interface, the previous state remains unchanged. Therefore, the time scale factor remains the same as before.

So g_{00} has been decreasing before and then remains unchanged. g_{00} is constant and $g_{00} < 1$.

It can also be said from other angle. The color and frequency of photons are always the same in the reference frame that falls freely with photons. Across the inner interface and beyond. Before and after crossing the inner interface, they all move in a uniform straight line. Then the internal static system and the dynamic reference system are in uniform linear motion. Therefore, it seems that the color and frequency of photons will remain unchanged beyond the inner interface and beyond. Therefore g_{00} remains unchanged and $g_{00} < 1$.

It can also be said from another angle. Photons fall freely from the vacuum in the distance. Due to the gravitational field, the frequency moves purple all the way to the internal vacuum. The frequency purple shift is equivalent to being still in an ordinary gravitational field. $g_{00} < 1$.

$$g_{00} = k_t^2 < 1$$

$$ds^2=(w(k_t dt))^2-dr^2-r^2d\theta^2-r^2\sin^2\theta d\varphi^2$$

Explanation: The time coefficient g_{00} in the spherical shell is reduced, and the space-time representation is flat. There is no gravitational acceleration field, but there is a gravitational potential field. The spherical shell does not affect the straightness of the space-time representation.

There is no gravitational acceleration field in the spherical shell, but there is a gravitational potential field. The time coefficient g_{00} in the spherical shell is reduced, and the time and space are straight. The spherical shell does not affect the straightness of space and time.

Therefore, it is necessary to distinguish these two different gravitational characteristics. The scalar quantity of gravitational field needs to be established. The gravitational acceleration field is only its gradient.

Taking infinity as 0, the gravitational potential energy of a unit mass object is named **gravitational field scalar ϕ** .

The corresponding field is named **gravitational scalar field**.

$$\vec{a}_g = -\nabla\phi$$

In this way, we can normally deal with the situation that there is no gravitational acceleration field \vec{a}_g in the spherical shell, but the gravitational field is scalar ϕ .

An important conclusion: **there is no singularity in the center of the spherical shell.**

Another interesting conclusion. There is no singularity in the center of the spherical shell. However, actual balls can generally be regarded as shells with small inner diameters but not infinitesimal ones. Then there is no singularity at its center.

10) Sky Dome and Cosmic-constant Λ

Gauges in the Sky Dome: $[g_{\mu\nu}] = \text{diag}(k_t^2, -1, -1, -1)$.

Calculate R , with a contribution of 0. This is because the partial differential to $g_{\mu\nu}$ is 0. This is the same as the constant in the differential equation. It cannot be determined by the differential equation itself, but as a boundary condition. It can be used as an initial value condition for R .

Substituting into the following derivation, since the partial differential of $g_{\mu\nu}$ is 0, the results are merged together like the cosmic-constant Λ . The partial differential of $g_{\mu\nu}$ is 0, which is also the logical requirement of the term of the cosmic-constant Λ . In other words, this term has become the cosmic-constant Λ .

The dome structure became the source of the Λ term of the cosmic-constant.

From the foregoing, it can be seen that this initial condition of R comes from the continuity of photon frequency at the boundary.

Then, this R initial value condition and **the cosmological constant Λ correspond to the historical inheritance of photon frequency change** and are named **cosmological constant frequency theorem**.

There are many ways to change the photon frequency.

Due to the large structure of the sky, the universe outside us is determined by the material and external movement of the world outside us. There is no need to look for the source in the world we observe. In this way, this item can be large or small, and it is not a problem.

The key is that this is derived from the theory of gravity itself and does not need to be artificially introduced.

The corresponding effect of this cosmic-constant Λ is the difference in the speed of light in vacuum. See the next question.

For example, looking at this universe in the outer universe, the equation is

$$ds^2 = k_t^2(1 - 2m/r)(w dt)^2 - (1 - 2m/r^2)^{-1} dr^2 - r^2 d\theta^2 - r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2$$

Where w is the vacuum light speed constant $w_x = w$ of the outer universe. So there is the effect k_t^2 of the cosmological constant Λ .

However, if the internal vacuum speed $w_i = w k_t$ is adopted, the above equation is written in the form of

$$ds^2 = (1 - 2m/r)(w_i dt)^2 - (1 - 2m/r^2)^{-1} dr^2 - r^2 d\theta^2 - r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2$$

It is the standard vacuum solution, does not show the effect of the cosmic-constant Λ , the only thing is the speed of light w_i , which is smaller than the speed of light w_x .

At the same time, it is also said that the internal infinitesimal vacuum is regarded as the external infinitesimal vacuum and can logically operate independently without knowing the independence and stability of the model of the universe and the outside universe.

11) The Speed of Light in Vacuum is Not Unique

There is no gravitational acceleration field in the spherical shell, but the gravitational field is scalar. The space-time representation is straight. The spherical shell does not affect the straightness of the space-time representation.

The universe does not rule out many such celestial structures. Such spherical shells can also be naturally formed or artificially placed.

They have no gravitational acceleration field inside; time and space are straight. In fact, it cannot be ruled out as a vacuum.

However, the gravitational potential field affects g_{00} . The speed of light is lower here.

If one layer covers another, they are so far away that the gravitational acceleration field between layers can approach zero indefinitely. But the speed of light can vary greatly.

Because the speed of light depends on the scalar quantity of the gravitational field, it can accumulate significant results through huge space.

Each layer can have a wide "vacuum zone with acceleration of 0", but the speed of light can vary greatly.

So when we talk about the speed of light in vacuum, which vacuum is strictly speaking the speed of light?

The vacuum of this sub-universe in which we are currently located is named the **standard vacuum**. Its vacuum speed of light is named the **standard vacuum speed**. No special explanation means it.

12) Nuwa Red Shift And Purple Shift And a Form Of Dark Energy

Let's assume that we have a large spherically symmetric celestial body structure on a large scale, named the **celestial sphere**.

Figure 21 Schematic diagram of celestial sphere frequency shift

As shown in the figure. The center is O . More distant places outside, the gravitational field scalar $\phi=0$. A very far equipotential surface in the celestial sphere is $\phi_1 < 0$. A very far equipotential surface $\phi_i < \phi_1 < 0$ including human observer P . Scalar $\phi_p < \phi_i < \phi_1 < 0$ of human gravitational field. $PO=D$.

Observe star A between ϕ_i and ϕ_1 . Its gravitational field scalar $\phi_s > \phi_i > \phi_p$. Therefore, when human eyes see A , the light from A moves purple. Since star A is outside of ϕ_i . No matter in any direction of human beings, it will move purple and shift Δv .

$$v = v_b - \Delta v$$

As long as $PO \ll PA$, the angle θ between AP and AO can be ignored. Then A in any direction of human beings, PA size can be considered unchanged. The frequency shift is constant.

Consider the further star A' , which has a larger frequency shift due to its further distance.

Of course, this frequency shift effect may be submerged by other effects.

The amount of frequency shift Δv depends on the change $\Delta \phi$ of ϕ .

$$\Delta v = \Delta V / h = -k h^{-1} \Delta \phi$$

Frequency shift speed:

$$\Delta v / \Delta l = \Delta V / (h \Delta l) = -k \Delta \phi / (h \Delta l) = -k \nabla \phi \bullet (-\Delta l) / (h \Delta l) = k \nabla \phi \Delta l \cos \theta / (h \Delta l) = k h^{-1} \cos \theta \nabla \phi$$

The frequency shift speed depends on $\cos \theta \nabla \phi$, that is, the gravitational acceleration field is projected on the line.

However, if it is low in the distance and high in the vicinity, then it is red-shifted. It is still the above mathematical relationship.

For example, it carries a lot of charges, and the effect of charge shift is opposite to that of mass. If it exceeds the effect of mass, ϕ is far lower and near higher, and red shift occurs.

$$ds^2 = (1 - 2m/r + kQ^2/(2r^2))(wdt)^2 - (1 - 2m/r + kQ^2/(2r^2))^{-1}dr^2 - r^2d\theta^2 - r^2\sin^2\theta d\phi^2$$

For example, there is a lot of dark energy with the opposite effect of mass shift. If it exceeds the effect of mass shift, ϕ is far lower and near higher, and red shift occurs.

Is there any dark energy for this effect in reality? Normal matter gravity leads to far higher and near lower. Is there a dark energy that causes ϕ to be far lower and near higher? There are.

This is the case with the (celestial body) rotational motion. It has a tendency to throw objects out. The potential ϕ has a tendency of far lower and near higher, and correspondingly has a tendency of far lower and near higher. This kind of movement is common in the universe. If Hubble redshift is related to this, if it is really reached this level, the rotation will lead to the effect that the potential ϕ is far lower and near higher, which indicates that our sub-universe is "disintegrated", gravity cannot pull the rotating matter, and the matter is splashing out.

If we measure stars that are not too far away, we can measure θ , and thus we can measure our position deviating from the center O .

13) The Singularity At The Center Of a Black Hole Is No Longer a Terrible Plague

Since there is no curved space-time, it is 4-dimensional straight space-time plus 1-dimensional phase. The gauge is no longer a space-time gauge, but a phase gauge. Therefore, the infinity rule of the singularity at the center of a black hole is no longer terrible because it no longer represents space-time. Infinite phase gauge, generally may be a phase change, that is, a model change, which is normal. If it is just a single point, line or side, it can be ignored directly. However, it should be noted that it may need to be calculated from this subsection.

14) the Causes of 4-Dimensional Space-Time of Theory of Absolutivity

This is because the absolutist process actually belongs to end-atomic mechanics. The minimum unit of end-atomic mechanics, Planck constant, corresponds to 4-dimensional space-time. End-atomic mechanics has only 4-dimensional space-time and cannot be separated. Therefore, theory of absolutivity is a 4-dimensional space-time and cannot be separated.

Formally, gravity has completely become a branch of end-atomic mechanics.

15) There is a new Understanding of the Interior of the Black Hole Horizon

$dS^2 < 0$ within the horizon of the black hole.

Now there is one more possible understanding.

At this time, dS is yin-number. According to the end-atomic mechanics, the meaning is that the original sine function wave becomes hyperbolic sine function wave, that is, exponential function wave. Quantum tunneling is this mode.

The horizon has a real meaning: The horizon is a phase change surface and the horizon is a zero phase surface. On this surface, the phase change rate is 0 and then becomes yin-number.

16) General Relativity Curved Space-Time Mistakes τ as Real Time

Technically speaking. In fact, τ is only a functional of variational method, which is used to replace differential equation and is not time itself.

Only talk about light tectonic space-time representation. Physically speaking, $d\tau=ds/w=ds/c$. ds is the optical distance difference corresponding to the phase increment. $d\tau$ is the optical time difference corresponding to the phase increment. $d\tau$ and ds represent the phase increment of the corresponding photon motion. This phase increment is used as a variational functional. It is the same thing as S in end-atomic mechanics, both of which are phase increments and are used as variational functional. $\delta\int dS=0$ can be used uniformly.

In the gravitational field, the clock becomes slower and the time of one cycle changes. The actual time corresponding to the phase-time τ is different. τ accumulation corresponds period accumulation. Then the τ accumulated value is no longer proportional to time. Therefore, in the gravitational field, phase-time τ cannot be used to represent the real time. The order of events cannot be judged by the magnitude of phase-time τ .

It can be seen that the inherent time $d\tau$ of general relativity is relatively small in the gravitational field.

The most intuitive is the running time of light. Obviously its time is a positive number. But the calculated τ is always 0. Topological logic is completely different. So τ is not the real time we want.

The period of the atomic clock on the satellite is smaller than that on the earth, and the atomic clock on the satellite is faster. In fact, if we find a violation of the "time path independence theorem", we will think that at least one party has a problem of speed, and then we will automatically adjust the clock. If there is really no way, plus a tuning factor. After such adjustment, the time value measured by the heaven and earth clocks must meet the "time path independence theorem".

17) Changes Of Photon Phase Ruler

In fact, it is only the change of the photon phase ruler itself, and there is no scaling in time and space.

Consider the gravitational field.

Assume that only g_{11} spatial coefficient is not standard and only diagonal non-zero coefficient.

$g_{00}^{1/2}$ is the scaling factor of phase change corresponding to unit time representation of photon time phase ruler; $g_{00}^{1/2}$ is the amplification factor of the frequency of the photon time phase ruler; $g_{00}^{-1/2}$ is the scaling factor of the period of the photon phase ruler.

Reduce $g_{00}^{1/2}$; reduce the scaling factor of phase change corresponding to unit time representation; reduce the frequency of photon phase ruler, that is, increase the period of photon phase ruler, thus reducing the number of measured time ticks and slowing down the required time representation(dt).

$(-g_{11})^{1/2}$ is the scaling factor of phase change corresponding to unit space representation of photon space phase ruler; $(-g_{11})^{-1/2}$ is the scaling coefficient of photon space phase ruler wavelength.

Increase $(-g_{11})^{1/2}$; increase the scaling factor of phase change corresponding to unit space representation; the wavelength of the photon space phase ruler is reduced, thus increasing the measured spatial wave number and reducing the required spatial representation (dx).

Take the following metric as an example

$$ds^2=(1-2m/r)(w dt)^2-(1-2m/r^2)^{-1}dr^2-r^2d\theta^2-r^2\sin^2\theta d\varphi^2$$

$$g_{00}=(1-2m/r) \quad -g_{11}=(1-2m/r^2)^{-1}$$

The scaling factor corresponding to the phase change of the unit time representation of the photon time phase ruler is reduced: $g_{00}^{1/2}=(1-2m/r^2)^{1/2} < 1$

Reduce the frequency of photon time scale: $g_{00}^{1/2}=(1-2m/r^2)^{1/2} < 1$

Increase the period of photon time scale: $g_{00}^{-1/2}=(1-2m/r^2)^{-1/2} > 1$

Thus, need more time representation. Photon clocks are slower.

The phase change coefficient corresponding to the unit space representation of the photon space phase ruler is increased: $(-g_{11})^{1/2}=(1-2m/r^2)^{-1/2} > 1$

Narrowing the Wavelength of Photon Space Phase Ruler: $(-g_{11})^{-1/2}=(1-2m/r^2)^{1/2} < 1$

So that the measured spatial wavenumber is more. Photon phase ruler is small.

The phase period of the atomic clock on the satellite is smaller than that on the earth, and the phase of the atomic clock on the satellite is faster. In this way, the number of ticks will be more in the same time. It is not the time on the satellite that is slow, but the phase of the atomic clock on the satellite is faster. It is not that time is fast on earth, but that atomic clocks on earth are slower in phase.

Then consider the non-gravitational field. In this case, the gravitational field factor can be ignored. Only different observers moving at a relatively uniform speed are considered.

For different observers, the frequency and wavelength elements of light are actually phenomenal. For observers with different velocities, the frequency and wavelength of the same beam of light are different; different frequencies mean different periods.

Different periods mean that the photon time phase rulers are different in size and the number of periods expressed is different, rather than the actual time becomes different.

Different wavelengths mean different lengths of phase ruler in photon space and different wave numbers expressed, rather than actual space becoming different.

18) Physical Interpretation of Nuwa Exchange

The Physical Explanation of nuwa exchange: Information Exchange.

Nuwa exchange solves the information exchange between people in different states in the unified reference-space-time representation.

So how do different reference-space-time representations exchange information?

We are in the atmospheric reference-space-time representation and the space reference-space-time representation. The structural parameters w of the two reference-space-time representations are different. Different space-time can communicate through a common situation (inertial system). In other words, different spatio-temporal representations need to specify an intersection artificially, and the description of the intersection is the same. We can specify the infinity of the gravitational field as the intersection.

19) Grasping the Space-time Equivalent Parameter ω in Reality

The space-time equivalent parameter ω is the key parameter of space-time.

In reality, it corresponds the speed of spatial tectonic movement. For us, it is the speed ω of spatial tectonic light.

However, the speed of light is so fast that human beings could not measure it directly before, even thinking

that light arrived at once.

Therefore, our space-time representation cannot directly depend on this spatial tectonic light speed ω . we need to switch to another logical model.

According to the end-atomic topological wave theorem, atoms are logically topological waves; have topological fluctuations; they are waves with a topology.

Light is made up of photons. Photons have phases. The spatial tectonic light speed ω is related to the phase speed of light.

The phase speed of light, in turn, is related to the direction of light movement and determines whether it moves in a straight line. And people are very sensitive to direction. Moreover, the direction has a geometric amplification effect; a minimal error or deviation results in wide divergence, especially in astronomical observation. The direction can be controlled very accurately. Therefore, the change of phase speed can be grasped very accurately. Therefore, the change of the spatial tectonic light speed ω can be grasped very accurately.

The linear motion of light corresponds to the topology of light. This ensures that the spatially tectonic light can be used to locate and define the space, and the spatial tectonic light speed ω is used as the space-time equivalent parameter ω .

The phase nature of light corresponds to the logical fluctuation nature of light. This kind of logical fluctuation convert the speed problem to a direction problem.

In short, it is highly dependent on the logical fluctuation nature and topology of light.

In addition, it is the reference space-time equivalent parameter w . Corresponds to the meta-space-time representation. Because it is a meta-space-time representation, it has meta-symmetry. It requires that the reference space-time equivalent parameter w keep meta-symmetry, the meta-time representation has meta-symmetry, and the meta-space representation has meta-symmetry in the whole dynamic process. In this way, it can be ensured that the invariance of such meta-symmetry can be used in derivation. The equal phase relation is derived.

20) Weak Light Speed Confinement Theorem

Weak Light Speed Confinement Theorem: It is difficult for human beings to see superluminal phenomena in reality under natural conditions.

This is because, seeing the phenomenon of superluminal, it is difficult to distinguish between the order. Therefore, it is not conducive to the formation of space-time cognition and the establishment of the concept of cause and effect. As a result, decisions against this creature are unfavorable. So that the biological decision effect is unfavorable. Therefore, the survival of the species is unfavorable. This may lead to the extinction of this species. On the contrary, the weak light speed confinement theorem is beneficial to the determination and survival of species.

21) Fuxi Simplification Theorem

Fuxi Simplification Theorem: Without changing the topological relation, a complex problem can be simplified to a relatively simple problem, thus obtaining the core result quickly.

The key here is not to change the topology. The core result is determined by the invariable topological relation. So the core results remain unchanged.

Especially involves some complex abstract concepts. At this time, we can replace it with definite and

concrete concepts to avoid complicated abstract relations and their uncertainties.

For example, the phase of light is used instead of time, thus obtaining the core result quickly.

22) The Speed of Relativistic Light Cone Cannot Limit the Said Speed

The "superluminal prohibition" of relativity in complex environment finally returns to the "superluminal prohibition of relativistic cone speed".

However, the speed of relativistic light cone is not what we call the speed.

It refers to the local tangential speed. The problem lies in this "local area". Locality refers to taking locality as the frame of reference. This frame of reference is constantly changing. This speed has no meaning in the overall situation.

But the speed we are talking about is certainly not local, but global. If the space-time coordinate flow (q,t) of an object-point is obtained with a fixed reference frame, then the derivative of q to t is the global speed.

$$u=dq/dt$$

Using the speed of relativistic light cone to limit what we call the speed is a surreptitious concept.

The price of changing the speed of light to "relativistic cone speed" is "no ability to assert speed".

And the speed of the cone of light is actually just a parameter obtained by the trend analysis of the sub-world we are in (infinity) .

Moreover, according to theory, such parameters are not unique. Then the current value is just a normal value; it is like the ice water temperature is defined as 0, but it is just a normal temperature.

Therefore, the speed of the general relativity light cone cannot limit what we call the speed.

23) Is Tensor Absolutely Independent of reference system?

No.

The "modulus" of tensor is invariant.

But this "module" is also a physical quantity, so which description system is it referring to?

This is because the values of general physical quantities, except the dimensionless constants, are elastic and different under different description systems. If the unit of the description system is doubled, the value will be reduced by half accordingly. There is also the issue of floating reference points.

Therefore, there is actually a description system related to the selected frame of reference behind this "module".

For second-order tensors, the mixed mode becomes invariant, such as R^{μ}_{ν} and T^{μ}_{ν} . They actually have a selected frame of reference.

The invariance of the constant speed of light c and the constant cone speed of light c is also aimed at some special features of the frame of reference.

In addition, they all float in the universe. Why is one said to float in the gravitational field? The other said it was not floating in the gravitational field. This kind of differential treatment is actually unequal.

The relativity theorem only says meta-symmetry. However, it is not prohibited to designate a special situation artificially. In fact, the theory of relativity has quietly designated a special case, namely the infinite vacuum. Constant speed of light c comes from here.

Don't be blindfolded.

More importantly, this kind of invariance is conditional, but it is harmful to be wrongly declared absolute invariance.

Tensor is only a transparent mathematical tool and will not replace the fundamentals of physics.

Tensor is only a complicated mathematical relation that can be expressed conveniently.

24) Light Speed Electromagnetic Wave Speed Gravitational Wave Speed

It can be described as the attribute of the reference-space representation itself. Its "phase speed" is the space construction speed ω , which is a logical speed and a space-time equivalent speed.

Note that this attribute is logically immovable in the reference-space because it is fixed at some point in the reference-space representation. For example, the color, that is, the color of the point, is fixed at the point. Can't move. There are also electric field strength, magnetic field strength and gravitational field properties.

On the contrary, water waves are not. The corresponding attribute is that of water molecules, which can move in space representation. The rope corresponding to the rope wave can also move in space.

However, this attribute value can change. It change on the reference-time axis.

If it changes regularly on the reference-space at the same time. Then for the observer, it feels like the wave propagation in space.

Let's study its apparent speed.

This change can be expressed in phases. In terms of time, reference-time extension can cause phase changes. From the perspective of reference-space, reference-space extension can also cause phase changes. The latter can be equivalent to the former.

The phase delay caused by reference-space advance $\Delta x = \omega \Delta t$ is equivalent to the phase delay caused by reference-time retrogression Δt .

The phase delay caused by reference-space advance $\Delta x = \omega \Delta t$ and the phase delay caused by reference-time advance Δt cancel each other out, $\Delta \theta = 0$.

Then the mixed form of phase factors in the wave equation of phase is:

$$\Delta \theta = k(\omega \Delta t - \Delta x) \quad \theta = k(\omega t - x) + \theta_0$$

$$\Delta \theta = k(\omega t - (x + \Delta x)) - k(\omega t - x) = -k \Delta x \quad \Delta x = -\Delta \theta / k$$

$$\Delta \theta = k(\omega(t + \Delta t) - x) - k(\omega t - x) = k \omega \Delta t \quad \Delta t = \Delta \theta / \omega / k$$

$$\text{Thus, the wave speed is } v = \Delta x / \Delta t = (-\Delta \theta / k) / (\Delta \theta / \omega / k) = -\omega$$

The minus sign indicates that the reference-time reference-space is opposite in increasing the phase.

This speed is called **the first type of speed**. Let's put it this way. Imagination requires a kind of thinking container as contrast to understand sports. The first type of speed directly uses the reference-space-time as a container, so it is called the first type. Water waves, on the other hand, use a mass of water in reference-space-time as a container, so they are not called the first type, but the speed is called the second type.

The reference-space-time equivalent ω has nothing to do with observer and source motion. Therefore, the first type of speed has nothing to do with observer and source motion.

Reference-Space-Time Phase Speed Theorem: The first type of speed is determined by the space-time equivalence itself and is the space-time equivalent value, namely the space-time structural parameter ω ; moreover, it is purely logical, and it is the speed set by pure logic, and does not need any physical mechanism to explain, and has nothing to do with observer and source motion.

Color corresponds to the speed of light. Electromagnetic properties correspond to electromagnetic wave speed. Gravitational wave speed corresponds to gravitational property.

Therefore, there is,

Light Speed Invariance Theorem: The speed of light is independent of observer motion and source motion.

Theorem of Invariant Electromagnetic Wave Speed: Electromagnetic wave speed is independent of observer motion and source motion.

Gravitational wave speed invariance theorem: Gravitational wave speed is independent of observer motion and source motion.

Corresponding to the gravitational field, space-time representation Isophase mapping make the phase change of light zero at the horizon. Therefore, the gravitational field horizon has a blocking effect on the electromagnetic properties of color.

But gravity cannot stop its own fluctuations. Therefore, gravitational waves are not limited by the horizon of the gravitational field.

Logically, the fluctuation distribution properties of color and electromagnetism come from the space-time representation before mapping. In the mapping process, the distance between the isophase surfaces of the information elements can vary proportionally, so the speed calculated by the information elements is affected by the mapping process, so it may vary under the influence of the gravitational field.

Logically, the gravitational wave's corresponding gravitational field fluctuation distribution attribute does not come from the space-time representation before mapping, but from the space-time representation after mapping, so its speed is not affected by the mapping process, so its speed is not affected by the gravitational field.

25) Reference-Time Distance Representation Expansion and Reference-Space Distance

Representation Contraction

Reference-Time Distance Representation

If the difference between the coordinates of $x_1'=x_2'$ and t' is $\Delta t'=t_2'-t_1'$ for two events in one frame of reference S' (at the same position), the difference Δt between the t coordinates of the two events measured in the other frame of reference S operating at speed u relative to each other.

$$\Delta t = ((t_2' - t_1') - (x_2' - x_1')u/c) / (1 - u^2/c^2)^{1/2} = \Delta t' / (1 - u^2/c^2)^{1/2}$$

Δt is always longer than $\Delta t'$. The difference between the two is a factor of $(1 - u^2/c^2)^{1/2}$.

The $t(t')$ coordinate observed by the observer is named "**reference-time representation coordinate**"; the corresponding physical object is "**reference-time representation**", which indicates the reference-time representation coordinate value phenomenon corresponding to the event in the frame of reference. The reference-time representation represents the individual observation phenomena of the observer. Even if Beijing time representation is adopted, the reference-time representation corresponding to different observers may be different, because they are different events at all. The reference-time representation occurs in the frame of reference itself, not the external physical object. Just like the light bulb inside the frame of reference flashed, there was no relative movement with the frame of reference.

The reference-time representation coordinate difference observed by the observer is named "**reference-time distance representation**", which indicates the reference-time representation coordinate difference corresponding to the event in the frame of reference. Corresponds to the individual observation phenomena of the observer.

Therefore, it can be described as: if the reference-time distance representation separated from the two events of the reference-space representation coordinate in one frame of reference S' is $\Delta t'$, the reference-time distance representation Δt measured in the other frame of reference S , which is related to the separation of the two events, is always longer. This effect is called **reference-time-distance representation expansion** of motion. This shows

the distinctiveness of the reference-time distance representation. Note that here are two logical events, not a whole activity or a physical object, that is to say, there is no logical connection between the two events in this statement, and the reference-time representation coordinates of the two events are simply subtracted.

That is to say, if for two events in one frame of reference S' (the same position), the difference between the coordinates of $x_1'=x_2'$ and the difference of coordinates t' is $\Delta t'$, the difference Δt between the t coordinates measured in the other frame of reference S corresponding to the two events is always longer. The difference between the two is a factor of $(1-u^2/c^2)^{1/2}$. The quantity shows the distinctiveness and phenomenon of reference-time representation measurement.

The previous paragraph corresponds to nuwa exchange, which refers to the same movement of a clock, but the two observers see different phenomena. The second paragraph is the author's play, which becomes the comparison of the two clocks.

"The collected works of Einstein", volume 2, 160 pages. A clock moving at a constant speed v with respect to the frame of reference, judged by the frame of reference, moves slower than when the clock is stationary with respect to the frame of reference. It's still the same meaning, but it's only changed into the comparison of two movement states of the same clock.

The previous paragraph corresponds to the time Lorentz transformation, which refers to the same movement A of a clock. Supposedly, since it is the same movement at the same clock, according to the rule of identity,

$$A=A$$

There is no question of speed. Movement A is as fast as movement A .

Movement A is not as fast as movement A . Logically, it doesn't make sense. Therefore, in the later part of the play, it is "described" as a comparison between the two movements A and B . A is slower than B . To avoid the embarrassment of the rule of identity.

This involves the characteristics of modern physics itself. (1) Modern physics is a discipline that studies phenomena. (2) here based on coordinate values to quantitative research. In this way, physics is here to study the "coordinate value phenomenon".

But logic is concept-centered. Concepts and phenomena are not naturally consistent. Such logic is not necessarily consistent with physics. However, physics is also logical, so it is necessary to design physics conceptually separately.

Moreover, many concepts existed long before modern physics, and the logic of these concepts is not phenomenon level.

Especially for a new and complicated theory, the concept should be clearly stated.

From the point of view of civilization, some things are more advanced, more important and higher priority than phenomena and profound things.

From the perspective of civilization, there is such a concept 1 about clock, the speed of movement itself. This concept has existed for a long time. This concept illustrates the characteristics of the clock motion itself, which has nothing to do with the specific observation of a certain behavior, and has nothing to do with the observer. Otherwise, there would be no point: chickens speak with ducks. More profound than the phenomenon observed by different observers. This concept is named "clock speed".

There is also a concept 2, which explains that the observation of the speed and speed of a certain movement of the clock represented by the user's physical coordinates is related to the specific observation of a certain behavior. Concept 2 is "coordinate value phenomenon", named "reference-time appearance speed". The concept corresponding to the coordinate difference $\Delta t'$ of time representation is "reference-time distance representation". Use "reference-time distance representation" to judge "reference-time representation speed".

Take a mirage as an analogy. Whether there is a lake or not is concept 1. Whether the lake was visually observed at that time was concept 2. This can be recorded with a video camera. If you clearly observe and say that you have not observed, you are lying. Concept 1 is deeper than concept 2.

In history, "reference-time distance representation" can be used to judge "reference-time representation speed", thus "reference-time representation speed" can be used to judge "clock speed". Therefore, we only use the concept of "clock speed" instead of creating the concept of "reference-time appearance speed" without any effort or favor.

But now, after the vision is broadened, it is found that the "reference-time appearance speed" and the "clock speed" are not consistent. This is, two different concepts are needed to make the problem clear.

At this time, is "clock speed" used to indicate concept 1 or concept 2? Another concept needs another name.

Here we should respect history and ensure the continuity of names. That is, history takes precedence. In this way, the history of the "clock speed" or the original meaning.

However, in judging history, profound things take precedence. Concept 1 is deeper than concept 2. Use concept 1, the concept of "clock speed". In this way, the name "clock speed" means the concept of "clock speed". Concept 2 needs another name. Let's name it "reference-time representation speed".

With multiple concepts, the problem description becomes clear.

A clock moving at a constant speed v relative to the frame of reference, in which its corresponding "reference-time representation speed" (the speed corresponding to the "reference-time distance") is slower than the corresponding "reference-time representation speed" when the clock is stationary relative to the frame of reference (the reference-time distance is larger). This effect is the reference-time-distance representation expansion of moving clock. It refers to the individual phenomena of observers.

Rather than: its "clock speed" (the movement characteristics of the clock itself) is slower than when the clock is stationary with respect to the frame of reference. "Clock speed" refers to the movement characteristics of the clock itself, which is consistent for different observers.

Go to the store to buy a clock; you need it not to be fast or slow. "Not fast or slow" here refers to the movement characteristics of the clock itself, which is consistent for different observers and is neither slow nor fast. Instead of saying "observer's individual phenomena". If you buy a watch at a watch shop in Bern and slow down on the high-speed subway, resulting in a late bonus being deducted, would you still want this watch?

On the contrary, if the clock itself is "not fast or slow"; although due to personal or environmental reasons, the clock was measured to be slow. We can still think of the clock as "not fast or slow". The "clock speed" here is exactly consistent with the object-point time.

Reference-Space Distance Representation

Similar to the above.

Calculated length formula

$$\Delta L = \Delta L'(1-u^2/c^2)^{1/2} < \Delta L'$$

The (x,y,z) coordinates observed by the observer are named "**reference-space representation coordinates**"; the corresponding physical object is "**reference-space representation**".

The phenomenon of spatial coordinate difference observed by observers is named "**reference-spatial distance representation**". Corresponds to the individual observation phenomena of the observer. Reference-space representation refers to physical objects that occur within the frame of reference itself, not outside. Just like the bulb of a coordinate point in the frame of reference flashed. And the frame of reference do not move relative to each other.

It can be described as: if the reference-spatial distance corresponding the two event in one frame of reference

S' is $\Delta L'$, the corresponding the reference-spatial distance ΔL measured simultaneously in the other frame of reference S is always shorter. This effect is called (longitudinal) **reference-space distance representation shortening**. This shows the distinctiveness of the reference-space distance representation. Note that here are two logical events, not an object, that is to say, there is no logical connection between the two events in this statement, and the reference-spatial coordinates of the two events are simply subtracted.

The concept of the length characteristic of the object itself retains the historical named **length**, which is the **rigid body length**. Length is the characteristic of the object (specific environment and time). It has nothing to do with the observation phenomenon of the observer. Otherwise, there would be no point: chickens speak with ducks.

Different appearances need to be understood and established through connection.

Relativity uses luminous signals to pair this connection, which is a private connection. From the perspective of theory of absolutivity, this is based on equal quantity.

From the perspective of private time norm, this is a private time norm. The private norm of phase is adopted. Raise the dimension and become a 5-dimensional mathematical space problem.

This connection is based on kinematic representation. It focuses on physical computation.

The numerical value calculated by the method can not express the time sequence relation intuitively.

Absolute time is based on topology, while relativity is based on equal quantity.

26) Absolute Separate Simultaneity Theorem — Topological Train Thought Experiment

In the inertial system, a high-speed rail S runs at a constant speed on a straight track S' . In the view of S , the middle point M emits light signals to the head(H) and tail(T). After the head and tail receive light, signals from the rail to the middle point M' at the same time. Do they arrive at the same time?

Unlike Einstein's train, 2 pairs of light signals are used here. So as to obtain mirror symmetry of the head and tail signals. In their respective frames of reference, the two signals are mirror-symmetrical, the signal delays are equal, and simultaneous reception is equal to simultaneous transmission. In addition, the initial simultaneity has experimental correspondence.

1> Inertial frame calculation

The length of the train is $2L$. Head and tail are marked with h and t .

Because of the symmetry, we consider that the signal event (E_h, E_t) received in the S system is simultaneous.

Take the E_t as the origin. For event E_h , $dt_{(ht)}=0$, $ds_{(ht)}^2=g_{\mu\nu}dx_{(ht)}^\mu dx_{(ht)}^\nu$. The relationship between E_h and E_t is **pure space-like relationship**.

Because of the symmetry of S and S' , the distance between (luminescent points) H' , T' , and M' is also HM ; $dx'_{(h't')} \equiv dx_{(ht)}$.

Because of co-located simultaneity, there is $dx'_{(ht)}=dx'_{(h't')}=dx_{(ht)}$.

The transformation between S and S' is equal phase exchange. So ds does not change, $ds'_{(ht)}=ds_{(ht)}$.

$$\therefore g_{\mu\nu}dx'_{(ht)}^\mu dx'_{(ht)}^\nu = g_{\mu\nu}dx_{(ht)}^\mu dx_{(ht)}^\nu$$

$$\therefore dx'_{(ht)}^i = dx_{(ht)}^i$$

\therefore Obviously $dx'_{(ht)}^0 = dx_{(ht)}^0$ satisfies.

$$\therefore dt'_{(ht)} = dt_{(ht)} = 0, t'_{(ht)} = t_{(ht)} = 0.$$

$t'_{(ht)}=0$ means that in S' , E_h and E_t are simultaneous.

Because of co-located simultaneity, in S' , E_h' , E_t' , are also simultaneous.

Then they pass through $\Delta t'_{h'2} = \Delta t'_{t'2} = L/c$, and reach M' at the same time at $t'=L/c$. Because of the symmetry, it proves the simultaneity of E_h' , E_t' in S' .

(No time elapses; pure space-like relationship. \therefore Reference frame has no relative displacement. \therefore Relative speed may not be involved.)

In fact, the absoluteness of simultaneity is an independent premise definition norm. The above reasoning proves its **self-consistency**; thus it can be used as a norm. That is, this paper **defines** a simultaneity different from that of general relativity, which is more in line with the simultaneity of the public mind.

Here, the reference systems S and S' are universal.

Simultaneity of different places is absolute simultaneity.

2> If it is a constant parallel gravitational field perpendicular to the direction of motion.

At this time, symmetry still exists and the conclusion is still valid. (It is better to replace it with two trains S and S' running symmetrically)

3> General conclusion

Probably due to asymmetry, in S, the moment when the head and tail receive the signal is not simultaneous. The experiment is invalid.

At this time, it is necessary to ensure simultaneous reception, but it cannot be launched at the midpoint M.

Therefore, ensuring the simultaneity of receipt is the organ of the problem.

At this time, the moving light is not spatial tectonic light.

In fact, **simultaneity is only a pre-existing logical norm. Without this pre-existing simultaneity, we cannot even think.** In general narrative, this pre-existing simultaneity is needed.

Logically we can define simultaneity based on a standard light clock; the clock is not affected by the gravitational field. Logically, the corresponding situation is that of the inertial frame above. The conclusion has been proved.

The previous inferences about simultaneity are general.

Absolute Simultaneity Theorem: Simultaneity is absolute simultaneity.

Only directional symmetry is available for stationary emissions, and simultaneity can be determined based on this symmetry.

According to the definition of space distance and the meta-symmetry of inertial system, there are:

Inertial system absolute time theorem: In the inertial system, the travel time of the stationary emitted light calculated at the speed of light can be regarded as absolute time representation (ζ). $\zeta=l/w$.

The space definition is $dl=\omega dt$. When defining space, time is prior and absolutely sequential. In the same description system, they are consistent and absolutely sequential. Then in turn $dt=dl/\omega$. This is the prior, consistent, absolutely sequential time; the events that the stationary emitted light reaches after the same delay are absolutely simultaneous.

Visually, dt can be converted into phase $d\phi$. In any frame of reference, both events are on the same equal phase surface.

The shape may be different in different frame of reference. However, the phase topology relationship does not change.

Absolute Simultaneity Judgment Theorem: In a reference frame, absolute simultaneity can be judged by the travel time(t) of the light emitted statically.

This description system contains situations at infinity. The situation at infinity corresponds to the inertial system. This time representation of the inertial system is absolute time representation. So this time representation is absolute time representation. See the foxi tree diagram.

Absolute Time Theorem: In a reference frame, the travel time of a stationary emitted light is the absolute time representation (ζ). $d\zeta=dt=dl/\omega$.

Visually, dt can be converted into wavenumbers dn . The wavenumber dn (and $d\varphi$) is the topological quantity and is an absolute quantity. Logically, in any frame of reference, the wavenumber (and $d\varphi$) corresponding to the light running is constant.

If the emitted light is unified into standard light, the constant absolute time representation can be expressed as

$$d\zeta=T_{st}dn=T_{st}d\varphi/(2\pi)$$

In different frame of reference, the shape may be different and the density of the stripes may vary. However, the phase topology is unchanged, and the corresponding number of stripes does not change.

In complex cases, short standard optical signals are emitted continuously, and the integration of $d\zeta$ is absolute time representation: $\Delta\zeta=\int d\zeta=\int dl/\omega$

In fact, absolute time and absolute simultaneity are just the logic dictated in thinking. The key is self-consistency, and it can be smoothly connected with people's basic cognition.

Absolute time representation is a topological quantity.

(8) Space-time problems

1) Remote Time Measurement

Here, the clock synchronization has been solved first, and then the time synchronization is solved with the synchronized standard clock.

The synchronized standard clock reflects the meta-symmetry of time. Therefore, synchronous standard clocks are not affected by speed and acceleration. This is guaranteed by meta-symmetry.

This can be done for **remote time measurement**. In this stationary system, a fully synchronized digital standard clock is placed everywhere. In this way, the surveyors can read the local digital clock to obtain the time value. At this time, there is no problem of different places. It is absolutely simultaneity of the same place. In this measurement, the time value read is the same regardless of the speed of the measurer. In this way, the world can obtain synchronous and consistent time values regardless of the (speed) state of the tester. To get the same time is to be **in different places at the same time**.

Some people will ask how to ensure the clock synchronization. This is a technical problem. From a rational point of view, there must be some logically pre-existing rules. This kind of stipulation surpasses rationality and cannot be provided by rationality itself. Rationality (including experiments) cannot be confirmed or denied. Clock synchronization is the rule here. If you insist that it is a problem, it is a common problem that cannot be solved. Theory of relativity also had this problem; how does this light consistent with that light? It said that the speed of light is constant. But in rationality, it's just a logical precedent. Besides, general theory of relativity holds that the speed of light in gravitational field changes. The gravitational field is everywhere. How can you be sure that there is no gravitational field in your place? Then there is no guarantee that the light and the light will move at the same speed, so it is purely a rule to use light to set the time. All are just subjective rules and all are equal.

This is solved by the pre-existing standard clock. And, the standard clock is calibrated by "independent of the path of time"; the standard clock can be specified from a negative logic perspective.

The reference-time and the reference-space corresponding to the clock constitute the reference-space-time representation named **nuwa reference-space-time representation**. It is the common reference-space-time representation of a certain knowledge set. Note that it is for a certain set, not all knowledge of the whole universe. In other words, we cannot talk about absolute reference-space-time at the cosmic level, but only the common

reference-space-time representation specified for a specified set.

The the concept of **beijing nuwa reference-space-time representation**, makes simultaneity of different places meaningful, makes large-scale activities based, and enables many complicated event knowledge to be described and understood in the same space-time.

Each of us and every organization can have a proofreading a good clock, which is the substitute of the standard clock sources. This mechanism is the "clock-alignment" logic of theory of absolutivity; rather than relativistic "time-alignment" logic of optical signals. Clock-alignment logic enables each part to have a standard clock source locally; and then with its simultaneity is absolute simultaneity in the same place.

For example, the whole of China corresponds to a beijing nuwa reference-space-time representation. It can be understood that the National Time Service Center of the Chinese Academy of Sciences in Pucheng, Shaanxi Province has a clock, and a flat reference-space-time representation is established with the clock as the center. This reference-space-time representation, is aimed at the knowledge set of production and life in China.

There is a huge and expensive practical system behind beijing nuwa reference-space-time representation. This also shows the importance of nuwa reference-space-time representation, which is by no means a meaningless concept.

Many of these space-time representations around the world are organically connected to form **greenwich nuwa reference-space-time representation**. Note that technically speaking, the clock refers to an interval clock, not a calendar clock. Beijing time and new york time correspond to the same interval clock.

The name of the specified time corresponds to nuwa reference-space-time, and the name of the specified space corresponds to nuwa reference-space; the reference-time and reference-space in physics correspond to the name of reference-time and the name of reference-space respectively.

Bolt, the flying man in the Beijing Olympics, clocked 9.69 seconds in the 100m. What is used here is geodetic space-time representation.

The 100 meters here refers to the runway. The runway is stationary. The starting and ending space coordinates of the runway are x_1, x_2 . Length $\Delta x = x_2 - x_1 = 100 - 0 = 100$ (meters).

9.69 seconds is also the reference-time difference between two events when the runway was run by Bolt.

The starting (Beijing) time $t_1 = (t_0 + 0)$ is also based on the runway. The starting event was bolt's "set start" at x_1 on the runway when the starting gun was fired.

The ending (Beijing) time $t_2 = (t_0 + 9.69)$ is also based on the runway. The end event is when the detector is triggered at the end of the runway.

The runway is stationary. Time $\Delta t = t_2 - t_1 = (t_0 + 9.69) - (t_0 + 0) = 9.69$ (seconds).

Bolt is the driving cause behind the start and end events here. Therefore, it can also be said that Bolt ran 100 meters in 9.69 seconds.

Therefore, according to the Beijing (geodetic) time calculation speed:

$$v = \Delta x / \Delta t = 100 / 9.69$$

On the other hand, if directly considers moving Bolt's (inherent) running time $\Delta t'$, is different.

$$\beta = v/w = (\Delta x / \Delta t) / w$$

$$\Delta t' = \Delta t (1 - \beta^2)^{1/2} = \Delta t (1 - \beta^2)^{1/2} = \Delta t (1 - \Delta t^{-2} \Delta x^2 w^{-2})^{1/2}$$

$\Delta t'$ is a monotonically increasing function of Δt , so the ranking is the same.

The most important thing is that such records need to be archived, which requires a unified across distance

and history reference-space-time representation, otherwise it cannot be interpreted.

2) Age

We (China) calculate age according to the official (Beijing) time. Subtracting the Beijing time when you were born from today's Beijing time is your age. It has nothing to do with your experience after birth. The impact of space travel on Alan is just like the impact of beauty care on Emily. It only affects certain attributes of people. It has nothing to do with the official time and age. The official time and age is actually some kind of social agreement. This is what we often call time. Time is generated by a common time sequence generator. It's public time.

3) Spatial Tectonic Light and Physical Light

The light corresponding to the light movement in the construction space is named **spatial tectonic light**. Natural light is named **physical light**.

The speed of the spatial tectonic light in the inertial system is defined as the absolute speed w . This does not come from physical mechanism, but from pure conscious logic of thinking. Determined by meta-symmetry.

Spatial Tectonic Light Theorem 1: The basic spatial tectonic light speed is absolute.

In theory, only a little spatial tectonic light is needed. Most common physical light in reality can be used as spatially constructed light. However, not all physical light must be spatial tectonic light and must satisfy the characteristics of spatial tectonic light.

As an spatial tectonic light movement, it actually needs very, very little. That is to say, to construct the reference-space representation, only very, very little light motion is needed. The spatial tectonic light movement only provides the foundation pile for constructing the reference-space representation, and most of the reference-space representation is automatically created by thinking logic on this basis.

However, as the basis of spatial structure, spatial tectonic light must also be common, readily available, and cannot be too difficult to see. Otherwise, the space-time system is too difficult to use. Therefore, most common physical light in reality can be used as spatial tectonic light.

However, once the reference-space is established, other unusual physical light will not matter to the spatial structure. They may not be used as spatial tectonic light.

They do not necessarily have a fixed speed; however, it is not necessarily not equal to the absolute speed of light. Just said, does not necessarily equal the absolute speed of light, does not violate, does not contradict. Therefore, the theory has allowed the physical speed of light not equal to or even exceeding the absolute speed of light.

Another point is that space-time cognition comes from macro experience. Therefore, **in general, the spatial tectonic light is macroscopic.**

Spatial Tectonic Light Theorem 2: Physical Light \neq Spatial Tectonic Light

Spatial Tectonic Light Theorem 3: The spatial tectonic light is macroscopic.

Examples are given to illustrate that reality is not physical light of spatial tectonic light.

Physical light in a mirage is not spatial tectonic light; people don't need it to construct the reference-space. Before the mirage appeared, the reference-space knowledge of the place had already been constructed. This is just a scene.

Looking at the world upside down, the relatively moving physical light is not spatial tectonic light. Before

that, the reference-space knowledge of the place had already been constructed.

The physical light moving around the black hole in space is not spatial tectonic light either. Before the black hole reached the place, the reference-space knowledge of the place had already been constructed. Even for a stationary black hole, logically, the reference-space at that place was already constructed before people knew the black hole, and the black hole was not considered. The reference-space is not affected by black holes.

The relative motion of physical light under ordinary optical microscope is not spatial tectonic light. Before that, the reference-space knowledge of the place had already been constructed. This kind of observation is not used to construct the reference-space, but only used to study the object.

The light motion in the non-inertial frame is not the basic spatial tectonic light motion. For example, when we say that light bends under the gravitational field of the sun, when we say so, the reference-space knowledge of the place has already been constructed, and this light movement is excluded from the standard set and the basic spatial tectonic light movement.

This paragraph makes superluminal theoretically less tense through the excavation of two concepts.

4) Pangu Physics and Pangu Exchange

Pangu exchange is an information exchange protocol between different coordinate systems in the same static description system.

Pangu exchange satisfies the **displacement formula**:

$$AC=AB+BC$$

Pangu exchange:

$$x'=vt+x$$

$$t'=t$$

Among them: $AC=O'X=x'$, $AB=O'O=vt$, $BC=OX=x$.

vt here represents only a displacement $O'O$ (origin displacement), that is, only the difference of positions, not the movement of O system relative to O' system. Here O and O' are only a coordinate system, not a frame of reference; it is purely logical, not physical.

This kind of physics is named **pangu physics**. Here there is only one frame of reference, an absolute frame of reference, is a map, only different positions of pure logic, no movement, only pure logic coordinate system, no frame of reference problem (transformation), only position difference (displacement) between pure logic coordinate systems, no relative movement. The logic of coordinate system transformation is pangu exchange.

Galilean transformation actually corresponds to pangu exchange.

Figure 22 Schematic diagram of pangu exchange

The physics of ordinary women, bearded pirates, beggars and even lower animals.

An aunt called and said, "I'm under the big locust tree in the east of the village, please come here." In the logic, here is a map, you can just move to the "big locust tree" on the map. The relative speed of the coordinate system is not involved at all.

Pangu physics is simple and solid. It always works. It does not involve the relative speed of the coordinate system, so it will not be invalid.

In case of failure of complex theories, emergency can be saved.

Pangu physics can also be used when exceeding the spatial tectonic speed w .

5) Motion-Quantity and Gradient of 4-Soil-Entropy

Momentum is defined in three dimensions of space.

But for a pair of opposite momentum, the sum is 0. However, this is different from no movement at all, and momentum pairs of different sizes are also different. In order to characterize this difference, the amount of movement is defined. Momentum will not vector cancel its zero-axis component.

The quantity indicating how much exercise is named **motion-quantity P**, abbreviated as **motion**, 4 components, $P^0 = mw = mw^{(2)}$, which corresponds to reference-time axis t , $P^1 = mv_x$, $P^2 = mv_y$, $P^3 = mv_z$. Respectively corresponding to the reference-space 3 axis.

P^0 is called 0 motion-quantity, also called **motion-scalar-quantity**. The other components are called **spatial-motion-quantity**.

Logically, P^0 excluding the amount of movement of this kind of movement, that is, $v=0$, is named as the **basic-motion-quantity**.

In this way, if P^0 only corresponds to the motion-quantity of one kind of movement, then excluding the motion-quantity of this kind of movement, there is no other motion-quantity, and there is no corresponding substance, that is, the basic-motion-quantity is 0, such movement is named **basic movement**, and such substance is named **basic substance**. For example, the photon movement $P^0 = hv$, there is no P^0 except hv . Photon motion is a pure basic motion. However, when ordinary matter stops macro movement, there are other movements, which are correspondingly called static masses.

The product of each component and the corresponding axis has the same dimension and is $\text{kg}\cdot\text{L}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$.

Motion-quantity can be regarded as the rate of change of a scalar in four dimensions, i.e. gradient. This scalar is named **4-soil-entropy S4** (inversion of entropy). $\mathbf{P} = \text{grad}(S4)$. Dimension is ML^2T^{-1} . $P^0 = E = mw^{(2)} = \partial S4 / \partial t$, $P^1 = imV_x = \partial S4 / \partial x$, $P^2 = imV_y = \partial S4 / \partial y$, $P^3 = imV_z = \partial S4 / \partial z$.

(9) Discussion on Ac-Rate Field

Note that this section is only derived from a purely logical perspective and does not need the support of physical mechanisms.

Even when it comes to gravity-ac-rate. This is only to study a kind of pure logic ac-rate distribution function with specific distribution from the perspective of pure logic. The fuxi-value of its equal-fu transformation is studied.

As for the pure logic ac-rate distribution function of this specific distribution, where did it come from, not the content of this section.

The field here refers to the distribution function of mathematical space. It is Purely logical.

1) Ac-Rate Field

For the set S of n -dimensional mathematical spaces, λ is chosen as the reference, and the derivative of each dimension x^μ to it is named as the **rate** v^μ . The derivative of the rate v^μ to it is named the **ac-rate** a^μ .

$$v^\mu = dx^\mu / d\lambda \quad (\text{Latin letter } i=1\sim n-1, \text{ Greek letter } \mu=0\sim n-1)$$

$$a^\mu = dv^\mu / d\lambda$$

Our goal is to find the "constant fuxi-value" condition required by the isovolt theorem, so that the original

fuxi-equation is still valid here and can be consistently applied.

First of all, there is a fuxi-value f , which is applicable to all constant rate reference systems St , and the isovolt theorem is satisfied between St .

At present, the non-constant rate system S is a constant rate reference system St_0 equi-topological transformation (the connection relation is not changed), and the fuxi-value of "the fuxi-value is not changed" required by the isovolt theorem is found. According to the isovolt theorem, so S is equivalent to St_0 processing.

We need to find an intersection S_0 between S and St_0 . The fuxi-value f of S_0 in St_0 is known. The fuxi-value f of S_0 in s is specified. S_0 forms the thinking bridge between S and St_0 .

In general, the fuxi-value f of S_0 in S is specified as normal, that is, the same as that in St_0 .

2) Nuwa Equal Phase Quantity as Fuxi-value

First of all, nuwa equal phase exchange ensures that nuwa equal phase quantity remain unchanged in all constant rate reference systems St .

Can nuwa equal phase quantity be used as fuxi-value f ?

It is easy to prove that for the reference system St , nuwa equal phase quantity can indeed be taken as fuxi-value f , and L corresponding to motion is determined by equation $\delta f = 0$. It is known that the actual L at this time is a straight line.

$$df^2 = \eta_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu = (dx^0)^2 - (dx^1)^2 - (dx^2)^2 - (dx^3)^2$$

$\delta f = 0$ corresponding to

$$L(\dot{x}^a, x^a) = 1/2((\dot{x}^0)^2 - (\dot{x}^1)^2 - (\dot{x}^2)^2 - (\dot{x}^3)^2)$$

$$\frac{d}{d\sigma} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}^\mu} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial x^\mu} = 0$$

$$"" = d/d\sigma$$

$$\therefore \frac{\partial L}{\partial x^\mu} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}^\mu} = \pm \dot{x}^\mu$$

$$\therefore \frac{d}{d\sigma} (\pm \dot{x}^\mu) = \frac{\partial L}{\partial x^\mu} = 0$$

$$\therefore \dot{x}^\mu = \text{const}$$

$$\therefore v^i = dx^i/dt = (dx^i/d\sigma) / ((wdt/d\sigma)/w)$$

$$= (dx^i/d\sigma) / ((dx^0/d\sigma)/w) = \dot{x}^i / (\dot{x}^0/w) = (\dot{x}^i / \dot{x}^0) w = \text{const}$$

$\therefore L$ corresponds to uniform linear motion.

3) Looking for Fuxi-value of General Variability Field

Generally speaking, the selection of S_0 system ensures that it is relatively static with a constant rate reference system St_0 .

It's to find out the isovolt-transformation from St_0 system to S system. The fuxi-value expression corresponding to St_0 system in S system is also found.

$$df^2 = g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu = \eta_{\mu\nu} dX^\mu dX^\nu = (dX^0)^2 - (dX^1)^2 - (dX^2)^2 - (dX^3)^2$$

The transformation process is like pulling a rubber membrane.

$$df^2 = \eta_{\mu\nu} dX^\mu dX^\nu = (dX^0)^2 - (dX^1)^2 - (dX^2)^2 - (dX^3)^2$$

From the foregoing, it is easy to know that df can be used as fuxi-value of X^μ space-time representation. The equation of motion $\delta f = 0$. At this time, the space representation moves in a uniform straight line, $dX^i/dX^0 = \text{const}$.

Because the x^μ space-time representation and the X^μ space-time representation correspond to the same df ; is an equal df map. Therefore, df can also be used as fuxi-value of x^μ space-time representation. equation of motion

$$\delta\{df\} = 0$$

4) Number of Independent Parameters

For stationary type, 3 independent parameters of 3-dimensions acceleration are sufficient.

If there is still a relative speed that cannot be eliminated, three parameters of 3-dimensions speed are needed. There are 6 independent parameters.

Where are the four components of \mathbf{g} ? Multiply each line of \mathbf{g} by a different fixed positive real number, which is physically equivalent to scaling the units of n dimensions, which is physically meaningless and physically unchanged. So logically, \mathbf{g} has n components that are floating, not actually effective. In fact, these n components are artificially specified in some way.

Such effective components are: $n(n+1)/2 - n = n(n-1)/2 = 4(4-1)/2 = 6$.

In terms of number, that is (excluding) the number of elements in the upper right corner of the diagonal.

(10) Other

1) Gravitational A Vector Field

By solving the equation, it can be seen that the rotating object has dragging effect. Will drag the surrounding objects to rotate together.

For this effect, there is correspondingly a directed loop integral. It is the loop integration along the direction of rotation. Directed loop integration corresponds to an axis vector.

Illustratively, the static gravitational field itself also has loop integrals. But it is also true in the opposite direction. Does not correspond to axis vector. This is not the case here; the integral values in the opposite direction are opposite, indicating that the axis vector is in the opposite direction.

This axis vector can be regarded as the magnetic effect of the gravitational field. That is to say, the gravitational field also has an induced magnetic field.

Therefore, the vector field of gravity \mathbf{A} , and scalar field are introduced to form a complete theory.

Rotating objects will drag the surrounding objects to rotate together.

In fact, it can be regarded as the force of the magnetic field induced by two rotating objects.

Furthermore, this effect can also be regarded as the induced magnetic force of the moving mass charge in this induced magnetic field \mathbf{H} .

This can explain the problem of insufficient gravity at the edge of galaxies in astronomy. Magnetic force is related to speed and increases with it. In these galaxies, the speed of the celestial bodies on the edge is very high, so the magnetic force is very high. On the contrary, the gravity at the edge is very small. Magnetic force supplements the insufficient centripetal force.

2) The Meaning of Coordinate Differentiation

$$ds^2 = g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu$$

The contribution of coordinate differential to end-atomic phase change differential is calculated here. $g_{\mu\nu}$ is

its coefficient.

The influence of gravity on end-atomic phase change is an undifferentiated coefficient. All kinds of different forms of material movements are treated equally. All give a variable scale factor.

Just because they are treated equally, they do not involve specific sports personality characteristics and are only suitable to appear in the form of coefficients. Personality characteristics affect phase reference changes. Multiply it by the coefficient. Then also indirectly taking into account the personality characteristics.

3) Moving At the Speed of Light It is Not Time That Stop But the Logical Phase Representation Does Not Change

In this theory, if it logically moves at the speed of light, then the influence of time walk and space expansion on the phase of the light sphere will cancel each other out. The phase is always the same. The results are always on the same equal-phase plane. $d\phi=0$.

It is an equal-phase motion. Also known as 0-phase motion.

$$ds=(\lambda_b/(2\pi))d\phi=0$$

In turn, in fact, we use the motion of light as 0 reference, that is, $d\phi=0$, to define the amount of space dl . The distance dl transmitted by the same phase value ϕ_1 in dt time is defined as ωdt . $dl=\omega dt$. Because the same phase value ϕ_1 is transmitted to dl . Therefore, phase ϕ_2 transmitted to dl is still ϕ_1 . $\phi_2=\phi_1$. So $d\phi=\phi_2-\phi_1=\phi_1-\phi_1=0$.

Therefore, back again, logically moving at the speed of light, the change of phase representation must be 0, $d\phi=0$.

4) Turn Circle Into Square and Pangu Aormalization

Why are there so many strange logical relationships in space-time representation?

The key is not the physical relationship of the natural world itself.

But the logic of human understanding of the world itself.

When we recognize the world, we use complete meta-independence, that is, complete meta-symmetry. It includes both translational symmetry and angular symmetry.

But normally, these two symmetries are difficult to realize at the same time.

Axis translation symmetry requires that the space-time representation is square, which facilitates the adjacency of space-time. Parallel parts are seamlessly connected and merged. In terms of describing the world, translational symmetry is the best. The space-time representation used in the description is square.

However, when human beings recognize the world, they cannot first specify the special direction and position locally. This is the meta-independence of angle, so they must be angularly meta-symmetric. It is required that the space-time representation is circularly symmetric and the space-time representation element is circular. In terms of recognizing the world, angular symmetry is inevitable. Its space-time representation element is circular. Can use differential space-time representation to temporarily avoid merging problems and temporarily avoid square requirements.

Visually speaking, it is "**square circle**".

It is naturally very complicated for two parallel balls to join seamlessly. We need to turn the circle into a square first, which is figuratively called "**turn circle into square**".

The basic model of force is angularly symmetric.

The dynamic part adopts angular symmetry. Because differential space-time representation is adopted,

adjacency is not involved. But it will eventually merge into our common space-time representation. So it was just delayed. The corresponding effect is the phase scaling in the gravitational field, that is, the phase scaling in nuwa equal phase exchange .

Kinematics recognizes the world with angular symmetry. Kinematics and dynamics are closely related. From this perspective, angular symmetry should also be adopted.

The basic space-time representation element is spherically symmetric with full angular symmetry. $|dl|=wdt$. It is compressed into an ellipsoid in the gravitational field. But it is still symmetrical in the positive and negative directions, $|dl|=wdt$. Using differential space-time representation and isolated space-time representation does not involve adjacency. But it will eventually merge into our common space-time representation. It is nuwa equal phase exchange.

At its core, it is finally back to nuwa equal phase exchange. In nuwa equal phase exchange, only nuwa equal phase quantity remains unchanged.

Nuwa equal phase quantity corresponds to the sensory-time representation, corresponding to pangu time representation. pangu time representation is 1-dimensional.

Therefore, the "turning circle into square" mechanism is to **reduce the dimension**, directly from the 4D space-time to the 1D pangu time representation, which is named **pangu normalization**.

The pangu normalization and nuwa transformation is the opposite process.

Nuwa transformation is to transform 1-dimensional pangu time representation into 4-dimensional nuwa reference-space-time representation.

Pangu normalization is to regard 4-dimensional nuwa reference-space-time representation as 1-dimensional pangu time representation. The basis is "space-time 1-dimensional theorem".

5) Does Celestial Body Collapse Into Infinitesimal Singularities?

I am not denying it. However, for some reasons, this issue should be given priority among related issues.

For example, when discussing the singularity problem caused by singular points, we should first discuss this problem.

There is no "curved space-time" in this theory. Gravity is only a force. It can compress celestial bodies, that's all.

Let's consider the following in the meta-space-time representation of mechanics. This is more convenient. Gravity is inversely proportional to square. And only static spherically symmetric celestial bodies are considered.

If the celestial body is to collapse into an infinitesimal singularity, it also starts with the internal solution.

But there is no singularity in the internal solution. On the contrary, at the center point, the gravitational acceleration is 0 and the gravitational force is 0. And the closer to the center, the smaller the gravity. Therefore, collapse is not so easy.

According to common sense, the more compressed an object is, the harder it is to compress it. Gas that starts to loosen is easy to compress. The further you go, the harder it is to compress.

For a celestial body with a given mass, its gravity is inversely proportional to the square.

As the radius decreases, the gravity increases in inverse proportion to the square.

So long as the celestial body has a kind of resistance, its speed of change exceeds the inverse square ratio. However, a great probability of microscopic force is satisfied. Then it will eventually prevent gravity from continuing to compress. It will not be infinitely compressed to a singularity of zero volume.

This should be the most common and possible thinking process.

6) Vacuum Multi-speed of Light and Gravitational Equation

1> Gravitational Equation Must Be Solved By Segments

Because the gravitational equation is a differential equation. Mathematically, the differential equation can only be solved by segments.

2> Understanding Vacuum Light Speed from Gravitational Equation

Judging from the gravitational equation. The closer to the gravitational field, the smaller the speed of light.

On the contrary, the farther away from the gravitational field, the greater the speed of light. Take the limit, that is, infinity, and you get the speed of light in vacuum.

That is to say, the so-called vacuum speed of light is actually a limit of the variation trend of the speed of light parameters in the gravitational field equation in which we are located.

3> Look at the Equation in Segments of the Outer World

Looking at this equation in segments of the outer world, they will also analyze their limit light w_x .

Then close to our world, it will become w_1 . $w_1 < w_x$.

Here the density suddenly changes to our vacuum and the equation is segmented. Because of the continuity rule. For us inside here, we will be regarded as the infinity of the inner world. Correspondingly, the light speed limit w_i of our world is related to w_1 .

Because of the piecewise nature of the equation, we inside, through trend analysis. Get the maximum limit of the speed of light, which is w_i . In any case, we cannot deduce a larger w_x outside.

The gravitational field outside, to us inside, is just the same term. It is not reflected in the change trend, so trend analysis is invalid for it. Therefore, it cannot be deduced.

It can only be deduced from the outside to the inside. In order to mirror this possibility.

4> Vacuum Multi-speed of Light Does Not Violate Gravitational Equation

Vacuum multi-speed of light does not violate gravitational equation. But also the gravitational equation is deduced in reverse.

Although it violates the starting point of general relativity, it does not violate the final conclusion.

The same thing has already happened. That is Mach's principle.

5> Mach Principle Changed from Starting Point to Final Throwing

Mach principle is also the starting point of general relativity. Mr. Einstein praised it in his early days.

However, in the later period, he found that mach principle was not compatible with the final general theory of relativity. Completely abandon mach principle.

Mach principle changed from starting point to final abandonment.

Therefore, the uniqueness of vacuum light speed changes from the starting point to the final abandonment. It is also understandable.

7) A Kind of Superluminal Calculation

Whether or not there is superluminal speed, we must first give a mathematical calculation method.

Hyperspeed of light will lead to a mathematical phenomenon with negative square.

Under the current expression logic, part of the fact data corresponds to the whole real number space. This results in other possible fact data being indistinguishable still expressed in this real number space. So we have to open another area to represent it.

Non-superluminal is expressed by ordinary real numbers. The superluminal speed is represented by another area. In order to distinguish, $i()$ mark is used to distinguish, that is, yin-number is used to distinguish. In this way, the original mathematical relation can be used to deal with it together.

Faster than the speed of light,

$$\gamma^{-2} = 1 - \beta^2 < 0$$

Take,

$$\gamma = i(\beta^2 - 1)^{-1/2}$$

$$\begin{cases} \alpha \omega dt = \gamma(\alpha' \omega' dt' - \beta \alpha' dx') \\ \alpha dx = \gamma((- \beta) \alpha' \omega' dt' + \alpha' dx') \\ dy = i dy' \\ dz = i dz' \end{cases}$$

In this way, superluminal motion S' is mapped to our common space-time representation, and $i()$ is applied to get the representation of yin-number time dt and yin-number space dx . In this way, ordinary low-speed movements can be distinguished.

For example, $\beta = \sqrt{5}$, $\gamma = i(0.5)$, $dt = i(0.5)$, $dx = i(-0.5\sqrt{5}w)$. The displacement of 0.5 seconds is $-0.5\sqrt{5}w$.

In addition, pangu physics can also be used directly.

(11) Explanation

1) The Logic of Einstein's Train Thought Experiment

When two lightning strikes an east-west rail at the same time, it hits the head and tail of the train traveling from west to east. For the first observer (A) sitting beside the rail in the middle (M) of the two lightning strikes, the two lightning strikes occur simultaneously. However, for the second observer (B) who is sitting in the middle of the train and passing the first observer, the two lightning strikes are not at the same time. This is because the second observer is approaching the lightning (u_1) in the east and away from the lightning (u_2) in the west at a speed. The lightning in the east reaches his eyes earlier than the lightning in the west.

Judging from the logic of normal space-time cognition, there are some problems in the logic derivation in the latter part.

This kind of indirect judgment of priorities is generally based on symmetry.

However, there is not enough symmetry for the observer on the train.

In space, he is directly in the middle of the two lightning bolts and has spatial symmetry.

But the movement is completely asymmetrical. He is close to one lightning and far away from the other.

In this case, it is not possible to indirectly judge whether flashes are emitted at the same time based on whether they are received at the same time.

According to the understanding of theory of absolutivity, he actually added a phase dimension. The motion of light corresponds to an equal-phase plane. He has actually changed the meaning of time. That is to say, the time he said is not what the public said. That is to say, he is saying what he says — although he justify oneself.

Correspondingly, the simultaneity defined by him does not have the ability to assert "the simultaneity of the

public."

According to the understanding of theory of absolutivity, to be exact, he quoted the constant speed of light to deduce time, which has the problem of citation.

In theory of absolutivity, although there is also the speed of light that has nothing to do with the frame of reference. However, this is only at the level of thinking representation, and only the constant quantitative representation has been obtained. The topological time cannot be deduced in reverse. Topological time is at the lower level. This is the fundamental mistake of him.

See Topology Train Experiment.

2) Explanation of Twin Paradox

First of all, the word "young" has no strict definition in physics, its meaning is uncertain and is not suitable for discussion here.

This problem was set up by French physicist Langevin in response to the time dilation of the moving clock of special relativity. Therefore, we will only discuss it from this point of view.

This is the expansion of the reference-time representation. There is a need for "cleaning" to remove the shifting process. At the beginning of time A left the earth at a uniform speed. Then compare the reference-time distance representation.

Let's take a look at it first:

In A's view, the reference-time interval of A seen by A is larger than that of B seen by A.

In B's view, the reference-time interval of B seen by B is larger than that of A seen by B.

In this theory, "in the view of A", the corresponding reference-space-time representation of phenomena in A, including the reference-time-distance thinking pairs of A and B, are recorded as A::A and A::B respectively.

"In B's view", the corresponding phenomenon is the reference-space-time representation B, in which the reference-time-distance representation thinking pairs of A and B are recorded as B::A and B::B respectively.

Reference-space-time representation A and reference-space-time representation B are different and their contents are independent of each other. There are 4 different mental images and 2 external objects A and B here. As shown in the figure:

Figure 23 The relation diagram of space-time representation of twins

Now expressed as:

$$A::A > A::B \quad B::A < B::B$$

This is a comparison of 4 different thinking objects. There is no conflict.

$$A::A \neq B::A \quad A::B \neq B::B$$

Represented by a mathematical model. Looking at y from x, it is expressed by binary operator f(x,y).

$$f(A,A) > f(A,B) \quad f(B,A) < f(B,B)$$

$$f(A,A) \neq f(B,A) \quad f(A,B) \neq f(B,B)$$

The key point is that this is the concept of reference-time distance representation. If we study the concept of time, then no one can compare it with time.

3) Michelson-Morey Experiment

Note that the stripe state corresponds to the phase relation of the optical phenomenon.

The key here is the stripe state of the light received by the instrument. That is, the part of light received by the instrument is the key to the instrument. Therefore, taking the instrument as the frame of reference, what you see is the key. As for other reference systems, it is only necessary to satisfy the self-consistency of mathematical logic.

And it's a spontaneous collection of instruments. But taking the instrument as the frame of reference, all directions are symmetrical. Then the wavelength λ , speed c , frequency ν and path d of light are always the same. One-way time $t=d/c$, wave number $n=d/\lambda$, so there is no phase difference; this leads to zero effect in the experiment.

The speed of light of the part of light actually received is always c .

The speed of light is the speed of light, which is the corresponding image characteristic of the part of light actually received to its actual receiver. The speed of light, frequency and wavelength are the things on the surface characteristic level. It's not a physical thing.

Note: $\beta=u/c$.

For the part of light that the instrument receives.

The observer description representation of horizontal co-directional relative motion.

$$d=L_1(1-\beta)/(1-\beta^2)^{1/2}$$

$$t=t_1(1-\beta)/(1-\beta^2)^{1/2}$$

$$L_1=d(1-\beta)^{-1}(1-\beta^2)^{1/2}=d((1+\beta)/(1-\beta))^{1/2} > d$$

$$t_1=t(1-\beta)^{-1}(1-\beta^2)^{1/2}=t((1+\beta)/(1-\beta))^{1/2} > t$$

$$\text{Wavelength: } \lambda_1=\lambda(1-\beta)^{-1}(1-\beta^2)^{1/2}=\lambda((1+\beta)/(1-\beta))^{1/2} > \lambda$$

$$\text{Frequency: } \nu_1=\nu(1-\beta)(1-\beta^2)^{-1/2}=\nu((1-\beta)/(1+\beta))^{1/2} < \nu$$

The speed of light: $c_1=\lambda_1\nu_1=\lambda(1-\beta)^{-1}(1-\beta^2)^{1/2} \nu(1-\beta)(1-\beta^2)^{-1/2}=\lambda\nu=c$, is unchanged.

Wave number: $n_1=L_1/\lambda_1=(d(1-\beta)^{-1}(1-\beta^2)^{1/2})/(\lambda(1-\beta)^{-1}(1-\beta^2)^{1/2})=d/\lambda=n$, is unchanged.

Although it seems that the distance traveled by light is longer, the wavelength is correspondingly longer, so the wave number is unchanged.

Wave number: $n_1=t_1\nu_1=t(1-\beta)^{-1}(1-\beta^2)^{1/2}\nu(1-\beta)(1-\beta^2)^{-1/2}=t\nu=n$, is unchanged.

Although it seems that the light run-time representation becomes shorter, the frequency representation also increases accordingly, so the wave number does not change.

In short, the wave number is always the same, so the phase is always the same, so no fringe changes can be seen.

The light seen by the eyes of an observer moving horizontally in the same direction.

$$L_1'=d$$

$$t_1'=d/c=t$$

Frequency: $v_1' = v(1-\beta)(1-\beta^2)^{-1/2} = v((1-\beta)/(1+\beta))^{1/2} < v$, decreases.

Wavelength: $\lambda_1' = \lambda(1-\beta)^{-1}(1-\beta^2)^{1/2} = \lambda((1+\beta)/(1-\beta))^{1/2} > \lambda$, becomes longer.

The speed of light: $c_1' = \lambda_1'v_1' = \lambda(1-\beta)^{-1}(1-\beta^2)^{1/2} v(1-\beta)(1-\beta^2)^{-1/2} = \lambda v = c$, is unchanged.

Wave number: $n_1' = L_1'/\lambda_1' = (d)/(\lambda(1-\beta)^{-1}(1-\beta^2)^{1/2}) = (1-\beta)^{-1}(1-\beta^2)^{1/2}d/\lambda = n((1-\beta)/(1+\beta))^{1/2} < n = n_1$, decreases.

Wave number: $n_1' = t_1'v_1' = t v((1-\beta)/(1+\beta))^{1/2} = n((1-\beta)/(1+\beta))^{1/2} < n = n_1$, decreases.

Although it seems that the light travel distance is constant, the wavelength becomes longer and the frequency becomes lower, so the wave number decreases.

It can be seen that $v_1' \neq v$, $\lambda_1' \neq \lambda$, for the same beam of light entering the eye of the instrument and human eye, different optical parameters are obtained respectively.

4) Explanation of Paradox of Rotating Disk

The circumference ratio of a rotating disk is more than π and uneven, and increases with distance. This description is not like a flat disk.

$$ds^2 = (c^2 - \omega^2 r^2) dt^2 - dr^2 - r^2 d\theta^2 - dz^2 - 2\omega r d\theta dt$$

Phase distance in 3-dimensional space:

$$dl^2 = dr^2 + (1 - \omega^2 r^2 c^2)^{-1} r^2 d\theta^2 + dz^2$$

Phase duration:

$$d\tau = (1 - \omega^2 r^2 c^2)^{1/2} dt$$

Circumferential Phase length: $l_p = (1 - \omega^2 r^2 c^2)^{-1/2} r 2\pi$

Diameter phase length: $D_p = 2r$

Circumferential Ratio Calculated by Phase Range $l_p/D_p = \pi(1 - \omega^2 r^2 c^2)^{-1/2} > \pi$

In fact, it is not the expansion of space and the shortening of time.

Only the end-atomic phase characteristics of moving objects have changed.

In the circumferential direction, the phase changes faster, so the actual length of one phase period is reduced to $(1 - \omega^2 r^2 c^2)^{1/2}$ of the original. The circumference has not changed. In this way, when the length is expressed by a shortened photon phase ruler, the obtained phase length value is expanded to $(1 - \omega^2 r^2 c^2)^{-1/2}$ of the original.

In diameter direction, the phase of photon phase ruler is unchanged, and the obtained diameter phase length value is unchanged.

Therefore, the flat disk itself does not change, only the physical phase changes.

This value is not the true circumferential ratio, but is calculated according to the equivalent phase range. Due to the use of different scaling factors in diameter and circumferential direction, the value becomes larger.

In addition, in the dimension of time representation, the phase change of photon phase ruler slows down, and the phase change of a unit time representation is only $(1 - \omega^2 r^2 c^2)^{1/2}$ of the original. The obtained time representation value expands to $(1 - \omega^2 r^2 c^2)^{-1/2}$ of the original.

5) Gravitational Wave Interpretation of Flat Space-Time

Under relativistic curved space-time, gravitational waves are ripples in space-time.

Under flat space-time, there are no ripples in space-time. Gravitational waves are waves of physics, just like

electromagnetic waves. Gravitational waves are the extension (propagation) of non-uniform gravitational field properties in space-time.

Electromagnetic waves are formed by uneven distribution of electromagnetic properties throughout space. Similarly, gravitational waves are formed by uneven distribution of gravitational properties throughout space. Gravitational properties of various places in space fluctuate with time, and from the perspective of space, they also fluctuate with the extension of space.

Instruments in space can be disturbed by passing electromagnetic waves, thus detecting electromagnetic waves. Instruments in space can be disturbed by passing gravitational waves, thus detecting gravitational waves. Gravitational wave detectors have L-shaped arms.

Under the curved space-time theory, gravitational waves cause changes in the length of two arms (time itself changes), but the nominal speed c of light does not change, thus the time difference of light passing through changes and gravitational waves are detected.

Under the flat space-time of this theory of absolutivity, the time space and the length of the two arms remain unchanged all the time, but the gravitational field property changes wherever gravitational waves go, and the change causes the phase change of photon motion, so the phase of laser motion in the two arms changes, forming the phase difference of laser, and detecting the corresponding interference fringe change. The attribute of gravitational field is directional, so its influence on the vertical two-column wave is different, resulting in stripe variation.

Finally, it is emphasized that gravitational waves are only attribute waves, not space-time waves. For the light in it, it is only phase wave, and the phase change of light in different paths is different, resulting in interference fringe change.

Figure 24 Gravitational wave phase schematic diagram

6) Explanation of Grandfather Paradox — Causality

In fact, when a person travels at superluminal speed, it is possible to "see" the image of his deceased grandfather. This is because the light of his grandfather's moving image still travels at the speed of light in the universe. Mathematically, he can catch up with those images at superluminal speed. However, it only saw the image of light and shadow, not his real grandfather himself. Can only see, can't have any interaction. Actually, it's the same thing as watching videos. Of course it cannot kill his dead grandfather in this way.

(12) Experiment

1) Topological Train Experiment

In inertial frame, a long line of high-speed train runs at a constant speed (U) on a straight track. The front and

rear devices (distance L) transmit signals to the ground inspection and testing devices respectively at the same time, and the reception delay is ignored. So does the ground seem to be receiving signals at the same time?

Note, never emit coherent light from the train to be tested with ground interference fringes. The transmission is controlled separately (showing symmetry) with a high-precision clock when it is aligned. Of course, in practice, the optical signals can be statically transmitted from the middle of the two devices to synchronize.

According to special relativity and simultaneous relativity, in the ground reference system, there are

$$\Delta t = t_{head} - t_{tail} = \gamma(\Delta t' + \Delta x' u / c^2) = \gamma(0 + Lu / c^2) = \gamma u L / c^2$$

The signal received by the detection equipment in the front direction is delayed by $\gamma u L / c^2$, and the time difference increases in proportion to $\gamma u L$.

The space-time representation can only operate through "relation".

The above calculation uses kinematic representation. It focuses on complex physical deduction.

According to theory of absolutivity, the above calculation is based on equal phase quantity, something related to phase, rather than time sequence. Equal phase quantity is consistent with things related to equal phases of interference fringes.

The time sequence generally required is a topological relation. The concrete values of appearances are of little use.

Time has the most complete meta-symmetry and is not affected by motion.

For the ground, it can also be launched at the same time.

Regardless of the delay, it is also received at the same time.

2) The Speed of Light In Vacuum is Not Unique Experiment

Uniform large mass spherical shell in vacuum. There is no gravitational acceleration in the spherical shell, it is vacuum. However, the speed of light of the vacuum inside the spherical shell is smaller than that of the vacuum outside. The speed of light in vacuum is not unique.

4. Conclusion

The physical and logical reasoning system with strict guarantee can be established by using foxi tree.

We can select "obvious", "simple", "self-evident" and "widely accepted" conclusions as the physical basis to establish self-evident "logical physics".

There is indeed a common logic and formula for gravitation and Coulomb force to be generalized.

Inertia and force are mirror relations. Newton bucket is independent of absolute motion and absolute space, and has a reference system.

Time is topological. Time is absolute. The concept of absolute time can be established. The speed of vacuum light is not unique.

Four-dimensional flat uniform space-time compatible with quantum mechanics can be established, and one-dimensional quantum phase can be added to the theoretical relationship. The original τ actually corresponds to the quantum phase. The effect of gravity is the effect on quantum phase, which is a set of coefficients $g_{\mu\nu}$.

In fact, the mathematical formula of uncertainty in quantum mechanics is only a difference inequality. Quantum (end-atomic) mechanics is still "definite".

References

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